

Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers¹

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **Selfie Numbers**. There are many ways of representing **Selfie Numbers**, such as, numbers written in digit's order or its reverse. It can also be represented in increasing and/or decreasing order of digits. This is generally obtained by use of **basis operations** along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Triangular numbers**, **Fibonacci sequence**, etc. In this work we have written **Selfie Numbers** using **Fibonacci sequence** values in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**. In some situations, the results are up to 4, 5 or 6 digits numbers. Results by use of **factorial** are also calculated.

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¹This work is combined and revised version of author's previous three works: <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a142.pdf>, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a143.pdf> and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a156.pdf> given respectively in [17], [18] and [19] done in 2016.

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1 Introduction

This introductory sections deals with the explanations of two principal ideas. One is on *selfie numbers* and another on obtaining selfie numbers by use of *Fibonacci sequence* values.

1.1 Selfie Numbers

Numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations are considered as "*Selfie Number*". These numbers are divided in two categories. These two categories are again divided in two each, i.e., one in order of digits appearing in the numbers and their reverse, and the second is in increasing and decreasing order of digits. See below examples in each category:

- **Digit's Order**

$$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6!$$

$$1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6}$$

$$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!)$$

$$12969 := 1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6! + 9$$

- **Reverse Order of Digits**

$$936 := 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)}$$

$$2896 := (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$$

$$20167 := 7 + (6 + 1 + 0)!/2$$

- **Increasing Order of Digits**

$$936 := 3!! + 6^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := (1+2)! \times 6^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$8397 := -3 - 7! + 8!/\sqrt{9}$$

$$241965 := (1 + (2 \times 4)! + 5) \times 6 + 9$$

• **Decreasing Order of Digits**

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 6^3 \\
 1296 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! \times 6)^2 \times 1 \\
 20148 &:= (8! - 4)/2 - 10 \\
 435609 &:= 9 + (6! - 5!/\sqrt{4})^{(3-0!)}
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that in some case, the same number can be represented in more than one or in all the four ways. For more details on **selfie numbers** refer to author’s work [8, 9, 10], [12]-[16]. Also refer [2, 3, 6, 7] for more studies. Few basic examples connecting Fibonacci sequence values can be seen in [1].

Above we have given examples of **selfie numbers** in four different ways. This has been done using the basic operations along with **factorial** and **square-root**. In this work we shall do only two ways, i.e., in digit’s order and reverse order of digits.

1.2 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature [4, 5]. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Initial values of Fibonacci sequence are given by

F(1) :=	F(8) := 21	F(15) := 610	F(22) := 17711
F(2) :=	F(9) := 34	F(16) := 987	F(23) := 28657
F(3) := 2	F(10) := 55	F(17) := 1597	F(24) := 46368
F(4) := 3	F(11) := 89	F(18) := 2584	F(25) := 75025, etc,
F(5) := 5	F(12) := 144	F(19) := 4181	
F(6) := 8	F(13) := 233	F(20) := 6765	
F(7) := 13	F(14) := 377	F(21) := 10946	

Interestingly, natural numbers can be written in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** values. Below are examples:

0 := F(0)	9 := F(2) + F(6)	18 := F(5) + F(7)
1 := F(1) = F(2)	10 := F(3) + F(6)	19 := F(2) + F(5) + F(7)
2 := F(3)	11 := F(4) + F(6)	20 := F(3) + F(5) + F(7)
3 := F(4)	12 := F(2) + F(4) + F(6)	21 := F(8)
4 := F(2) + F(4)	13 := F(7)	22 := F(2) + F(8)
5 := F(5)	14 := F(2) + F(7)	23 := F(3) + F(8) etc,
6 := F(2) + F(5)	15 := F(3) + F(7)	
7 := F(3) + F(5)	16 := F(4) + F(7)	
8 := F(6)	17 := F(2) + F(4) + F(7)	

Based on values of $F(\cdot)$, we can write composition values, such as, $F(F(1))$, $F(F(2))$, etc. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{F(F(0))} &:= 0 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(1))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(2))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(3))} &:= 1 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(4))} &:= 2 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(5))} &:= 5 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(6))} &:= 21 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(7))} &:= 233 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(8))} &:= 10946 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(9))} &:= 5702887 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(10))} &:= 139583862445 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(11))} &:= 1779979416004714189 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(12))} &:= 555565404224292694404015791808 \\
 \mathbf{F(F(13))} &:= 2211236406303914545699412969744873993387956988653, \text{ etc.}
 \end{aligned}$$

The aim of this work is to write **selfie numbers** by using **Fibonacci sequence** values. In some cases **factorial** is also used. This work is combined and revised version of author's previous three works [17, 18, 19].

2 Palindromic Number Representations

This section brings **selfie palindromic numbers** by use of Fibonacci sequence values. The idea of starting the work with palindromic numbers is as they are symmetric in itself, i.e., remains the same by changing the order of digits. Below are **selfie palindromic numbers**:

2.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55} &:= F(5 + 5) & \mathbf{46364} &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 4 \\
 \mathbf{474} &:= (4 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)) & \mathbf{46464} &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times 6 \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{484} &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(8))^{F(F(4))} & \mathbf{46664} &:= 4 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\
 \mathbf{2772} &:= (-2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(7) - F(2)) & \mathbf{46764} &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + F(6)^{F(4)}) \\
 \mathbf{3773} &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 & \mathbf{47374} &:= (F(F(F(4)) \times 7)^{F(3)} - 7) / F(4) \\
 \mathbf{13531} &:= F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 1 & \mathbf{47574} &:= F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + 5^{7 - F(F(F(4)))}) \\
 \mathbf{14641} &:= 1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 & \mathbf{48384} &:= (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84 \\
 \mathbf{15251} &:= F(15) \times 25 + 1 & \mathbf{48384} &:= (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84 \\
 \mathbf{21961} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 & \mathbf{49994} &:= F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + F(F(9) - 9)) / F(4) \\
 \mathbf{23732} &:= (-F(2) + 3 \times F(F(7))) \times F(3^2) & \mathbf{54645} &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(F(6)) + 4) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{28882} &:= F(2 + F(8)) - 8 + F(F(8 - F(2))) & \mathbf{54745} &:= 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) + F(4) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{32823} &:= (-3 - 2 + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(3)) & \mathbf{54845} &:= (5^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{39393} &:= 3^9 \times F(3) + 9 \times 3 & \mathbf{62426} &:= (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26 \\
 \mathbf{44944} &:= ((4 + 49) \times 4)^{F(F(4))} & \mathbf{63936} &:= 6^3 \times (F(9) + 3) \times F(6) \\
 \mathbf{46264} &:= F(4 \times 6) - 26 \times 4 & \mathbf{65556} &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 5 + 5) \times 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66666 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(6 + 6) + F(F(6))) \times 6 \\
 67176 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + 17) \times 6 \\
 68286 &:= (-6 + F(8)^2 + F(F(8))) \times 6 \\
 69696 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(9-6)} \\
 73793 &:= (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(3) \\
 75257 &:= F(F(7)) + F(5^2) - F(-5 + 7) \\
 75457 &:= 7 \times F(F(5 + F(4))) - 5 \times F(F(7)) \\
 75957 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) - 95) \times 7 \\
 76167 &:= (-F(7) \times (6 - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 76367 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3)) - F(F(6)) - F(F(7)) \\
 76467 &:= F(7) + (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times 6) \times 7 \\
 76567 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(-5 + F(6) + 7) \\
 76667 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6) + F(F(6))/7 \\
 76867 &:= (-7 + F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 7 \\
 78487 &:= 7 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4))) + 8 \times F(F(7)) \\
 78987 &:= (F(F(7)) + 8 + 98) \times F(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84284 &:= F(F(8) + 4) - 2 + F(8)^{F(4)} \\
 86368 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - F(F(3) \times 6)) \times 8 \\
 86968 &:= (F(F(8)) - 69 - 6) \times 8 \\
 87878 &:= (F(F(8)) + 7) \times 8 + F(F(7)) + F(8) \\
 88288 &:= (F(F(8)) + 82 + 8) \times 8 \\
 88788 &:= 8 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + F(8 + 8) \\
 98289 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) + F(2) + 8) \times 9 \\
 98389 &:= -98 + (-3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98489 &:= -F(9) + (F(8/4) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98589 &:= 9 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 98789 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + 8 + F(9) \\
 747747 &:= (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 7 \\
 777777 &:= F(7) \times 77 \times 777 \\
 999999 &:= (9 + F(9)) \times 9 \times F(9 + 9) - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned}
 232 &:= -F(2) + F(F(3! + F(2))) \\
 363 &:= (3! + 6!)/F(3) \\
 383 &:= 3! + F(8 + 3!) \\
 444 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(4) \\
 464 &:= -F(F(4))^{F(6)} + F(4)!! \\
 707 &:= (7 - 0!)! - F(7) \\
 727 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 9 = 9 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\
 1441 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 1 \\
 3333 &:= 3! \times 3!! - F(F(3) \times F(3!)) \\
 3443 &:= (3 + 4)! - F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 3663 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3 = \\
 4224 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 22 \times 4! \\
 4334 &:= (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(4)) \\
 4444 &:= (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(4)) \\
 4884 &:= F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 4 \\
 5445 &:= (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 45 \\
 6336 &:= 6^{3!} - (F(3) + 6)! \\
 6776 &:= F(6) \times (7 + 7!/6) \\
 7227 &:= 7! + F(2 + 2)^7 \\
 7447 &:= 7^4 + F(4)! + 7! \\
 14341 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14441 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 41 \\
 18481 &:= 1 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\
 23332 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 2 \\
 26462 &:= (F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 2 \\
 33633 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 33 \\
 36663 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3 \\
 36963 &:= 3 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)! \\
 39693 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 93 \\
 40204 &:= 4 + F((0! + 2)!) - (0! + 4)! \\
 44644 &:= 4 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\
 44944 &:= F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 4 \\
 46464 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 64 \\
 46564 &:= (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 4 \\
 46764 &:= 4 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4)! \\
 47674 &:= 4 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4! \\
 52925 &:= 5 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\
 53535 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 5 \\
 54845 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 5 \\
 54945 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 45 \\
 55455 &:= 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 5 \\
 64446 &:= 6 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$66366 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$93339 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 9$$

$$66966 := 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 6$$

$$75657 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 57$$

3 Symmetric Representations

In this section, we shall give *selfie numbers* in terms of Fibonacci sequence values along with basic operations. These representations are in symmetric way, i.e., all is same except the digits 0 to 9. This happens in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits. In some cases numbers can be written in both the ways. The following subsections give the symmetric numbers three situations. In this section, we have worked up to width 6, i.e., numbers having maximum 6 digits.

3.1 Symmetric Representations in Both Ways

Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order and its reverse:

3.1.1 Basic Operations

$$5490 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 0 = 0 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5491 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 1 = 1 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5492 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 2 = 2 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5493 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 3 = 3 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5494 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 4 = 4 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5495 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 5 = 5 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5496 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 6 = 6 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5497 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 7 = 7 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5498 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 8 = 8 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$5499 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 9 = 9 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$10980 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10981 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10982 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10983 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10984 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10985 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10986 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10987 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10988 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$10989 := 1 \times F(09) + F(F(8)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(8)) + F(9 \times 01)$$

$$13530 := F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 0 = 0 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$13531 := F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 1 = 1 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}13532 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 2 = 2 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13533 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 3 = 3 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13534 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 4 = 4 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13535 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 5 = 5 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13536 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 6 = 6 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13537 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 7 = 7 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13538 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 8 = 8 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1)) \\13539 &:= F((1+3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 9 = 9 + F(3) \times F(5 \times (3+1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14640 &:= 0 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 0 \\14641 &:= 1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 1 \\14642 &:= 2 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 2 \\14643 &:= 3 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 3 \\14644 &:= 4 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 4 \\14645 &:= 5 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 5 \\14646 &:= 6 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 6 \\14647 &:= 7 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 7 \\14648 &:= 8 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 8 \\14649 &:= 9 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 - 1 = -1 + (F(4) + F(6))^4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}25840 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 0 = 0 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25841 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 1 = 1 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25842 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 2 = 2 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25843 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 3 = 3 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25844 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 4 = 4 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25845 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 5 = 5 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25846 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 6 = 6 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2 \\25847 &:= 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 7 = 7 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$25848 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 8 = 8 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$25849 := 2 \times 5 \times F(F(8) - F(4)) + 9 = 9 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times 5 \times 2$$

$$28670 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 0 = 0 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28671 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 1 = 1 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28672 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 2 = 2 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28673 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 3 = 3 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28674 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 4 = 4 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28675 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 5 = 5 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28676 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 6 = 6 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28677 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 7 = 7 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28678 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 8 = 8 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28679 := F(2 + F(8)) + 6 + 7 + 9 = 9 + 7 + 6 + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28890 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28891 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28892 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28893 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28894 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28895 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28896 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28897 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28898 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28899 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(-F(8) + F(9)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$32850 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32851 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32852 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32853 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32854 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32855 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32856 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32857 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32858 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32859 := 3 \times (-F(2) + F(F(8)) + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 3$$

$$32940 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 0 = 0 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3)))$$

$$32941 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 1 = 1 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3)))$$

$$32942 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 2 = 2 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3)))$$

$$32943 := (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 3 = 3 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32944 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 4 = 4 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32945 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 5 = 5 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32946 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 6 = 6 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32947 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 7 = 7 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32948 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 8 = 8 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \\ 32949 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times F(4) + 9 = 9 + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(F(2^3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33490 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 0 = 0 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33491 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 1 = 1 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33492 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 2 = 2 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33493 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 3 = 3 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33494 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 4 = 4 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33495 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 5 = 5 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33496 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 6 = 6 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33497 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 7 = 7 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33498 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 8 = 8 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \\ 33499 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(3)^4)) \times F(9) + 9 = 9 + F(9) \times (F(4^{F(3)}) - F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 0 = 0 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38761 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 1 = 1 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38762 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 2 = 2 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38763 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 3 = 3 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38764 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 4 = 4 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38765 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 5 = 5 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38766 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 6 = 6 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38767 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 7 = 7 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38768 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 8 = 8 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \\ 38769 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) \times (7 + F(6)) + 9 = 9 + (F(6) + 7) \times F(F(8) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39360 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 0 = 0 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39361 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 1 = 1 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39362 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 2 = 2 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39363 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 3 = 3 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39364 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 4 = 4 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39365 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 5 = 5 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39366 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 6 = 6 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\ 39367 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 7 = 7 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$39368 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 8 = 8 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$39369 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 6 + 9 = 9 - 6 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$43640 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 0 = 0 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43641 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 1 = 1 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43642 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 2 = 2 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43643 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 3 = 3 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43644 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 4 = 4 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43645 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 5 = 5 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43646 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 6 = 6 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43647 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 7 = 7 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43648 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 8 = 8 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43649 := -F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + 9 = 9 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(3 \times 4)$$

$$43760 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 0 = 0 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43761 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 1 = 1 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43762 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 2 = 2 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43763 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 3 = 3 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43764 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 4 = 4 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43765 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 5 = 5 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43766 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 6 = 6 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43767 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 7 = 7 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43768 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 8 = 8 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43769 := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 6) + 9 = 9 + (-6 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4$$

$$43780 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43781 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43782 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43783 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43784 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43785 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43786 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43787 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43788 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43789 := 4 \times (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(8 + F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 4$$

$$43860 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4$$

$$43861 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4$$

$$43862 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4$$

$$43863 := 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}43864 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\43865 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\43866 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\43867 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\43868 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4 \\43869 &:= 4 \times (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}43880 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43881 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43882 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43883 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43884 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43885 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43886 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43887 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43888 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4 \\43889 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) + 8 \times 3) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}44360 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44361 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44362 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44363 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44364 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44365 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44366 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44367 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44368 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4 \\44369 &:= 4 \times (F(4 \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(3 \times 4)) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46360 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 0 = 0 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46361 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 1 = 1 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46362 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 2 = 2 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46363 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 3 = 3 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46364 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 4 = 4 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46365 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 5 = 5 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46366 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 6 = 6 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46367 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 7 = 7 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46368 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 8 = 8 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\46369 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 6 + 9 = 9 - 6 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46370 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46371 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46372 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46373 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46374 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46375 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46376 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46377 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46378 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4) \\46379 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(F(-3 + 7)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(7 - 3)) + F(6 \times 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46380 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 0 = 0 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46381 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 1 = 1 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46382 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 2 = 2 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46383 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 3 = 3 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46384 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 4 = 4 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46385 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 5 = 5 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46386 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 6 = 6 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46387 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 7 = 7 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46388 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 8 = 8 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4 \\46389 &:= 4 + F(6) + F(3 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + F(8 \times 3) + F(6) + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46660 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 0 = 0 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46661 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 1 = 1 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46662 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 2 = 2 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46663 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 3 = 3 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46664 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 4 = 4 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46665 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 5 = 5 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46666 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 6 = 6 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46667 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 7 = 7 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46668 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 8 = 8 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4 \\46669 &:= -4 + F(6) + 6^6 + 9 = 9 + 6^6 + F(6) - 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46670 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 0 = 0 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4))) \\46671 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 1 = 1 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4))) \\46672 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 2 = 2 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4))) \\46673 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 3 = 3 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4))) \\46674 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 4 = 4 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4))) \\46675 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 5 = 5 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))\end{aligned}$$

$$46676 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 6 = 6 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46677 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 7 = 7 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46678 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 8 = 8 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46679 := F(F(F(4))) + 6^6 + F(7) + 9 = 9 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$46680 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 0 = 0 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46681 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 1 = 1 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46682 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 2 = 2 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46683 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 3 = 3 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46684 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 4 = 4 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46685 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 5 = 5 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46686 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 6 = 6 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46687 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 7 = 7 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46688 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 8 = 8 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46689 := F(4) + 6^6 + F(8) + 9 = 9 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$54290 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 0 = 0 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54291 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 1 = 1 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54292 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 2 = 2 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54293 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 3 = 3 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54294 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 4 = 4 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54295 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 5 = 5 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54296 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 6 = 6 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54297 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 7 = 7 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54298 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 8 = 8 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54299 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(2 + 9) + 9 = 9 + F(9 + 2) \times F(F(4) \times 5)$$

$$54560 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54561 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54562 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54563 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54564 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54565 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54566 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54567 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54568 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54569 := 5 \times (-F(4 + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + 4)) \times 5$$

$$54670 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54671 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54672 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54673 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54674 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54675 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54676 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54677 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54678 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54679 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54680 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54681 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54682 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54683 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54684 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54685 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54686 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54687 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54688 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \\ 54689 &:= 5 \times (-4 - 6 + F(F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) - 6 - 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54690 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 0 = 0 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54691 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 1 = 1 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54692 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 2 = 2 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54693 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 3 = 3 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54694 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 4 = 4 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54695 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 5 = 5 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54696 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 6 = 6 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54697 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 7 = 7 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54698 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 8 = 8 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 54699 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) + 9 = 9 + (-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54710 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54711 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54712 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54713 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54714 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54715 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54716 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ 54717 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7+1))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(1+7)) - 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$54718 := 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(1 + 7)) - 4) \times 5$$

$$54719 := 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7 + 1))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(1 + 7)) - 4) \times 5$$

$$54720 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 0 = 0 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54721 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 1 = 1 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54722 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 2 = 2 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54723 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 3 = 3 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54724 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 4 = 4 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54725 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 5 = 5 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54726 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 6 = 6 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54727 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 7 = 7 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54728 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 8 = 8 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54729 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) - 2) + 9 = 9 + (-2 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54730 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54731 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54732 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54733 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54734 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54735 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54736 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54737 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54738 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54739 := 5 \times F(F(4) \times 7) \times F(F(3)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(3)) \times F(7 \times F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54740 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54741 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54742 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54743 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54744 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54745 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54746 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54747 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54748 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54749 := 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + F(F(4))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(4)) + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54750 := 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54751 := 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54752 := 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$54753 := 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54754 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \\ 54755 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \\ 54756 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \\ 54757 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \\ 54758 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \\ 54759 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(F(F(7) - 5))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(-5 + F(7))) + 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54760 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 0 = 0 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54761 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 1 = 1 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54762 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 2 = 2 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54763 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 3 = 3 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54764 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 4 = 4 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54765 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 5 = 5 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54766 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 6 = 6 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54767 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 7 = 7 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54768 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 8 = 8 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54769 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4) \times 7) + 6) + 9 = 9 + (6 + F(7 \times F(4))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54780 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54781 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54782 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54783 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54784 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54785 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54786 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54787 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54788 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54789 &:= 5 \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(4)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54890 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 0 = 0 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54891 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 1 = 1 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54892 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 2 = 2 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54893 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 3 = 3 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54894 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 4 = 4 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54895 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 5 = 5 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54896 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 6 = 6 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54897 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 7 = 7 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54898 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 8 = 8 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 54899 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + F(9)) + 9 = 9 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55870 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55871 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55872 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55873 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55874 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55875 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55876 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55877 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55878 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \\ 55879 &:= 5 \times (-5 + F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) - 5) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65660 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65661 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65662 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65663 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65664 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65665 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65666 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65667 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65668 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \\ 65669 &:= -F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 + 5 - F(F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76720 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 0 = 0 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76721 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 1 = 1 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76722 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 2 = 2 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76723 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 3 = 3 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76724 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 4 = 4 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76725 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 5 = 5 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76726 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 6 = 6 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76727 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 7 = 7 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76728 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 8 = 8 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ 76729 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times 2) + 9 = 9 + (2 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76860 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76861 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76862 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76863 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76864 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76865 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \\ 76866 &:= F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$76867 := F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7)$$

$$76868 := F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7)$$

$$76869 := F(7 + F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(F(6) + 7)$$

$$76890 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 0 = 0 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76891 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 1 = 1 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76892 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 2 = 2 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76893 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 3 = 3 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76894 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 4 = 4 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76895 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 5 = 5 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76896 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 6 = 6 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76897 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 7 = 7 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76898 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 8 = 8 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$76899 := F(F(7)) \times 6 \times (F(8) + F(9)) + 9 = 9 + (F(9) + F(8)) \times 6 \times F(F(7))$$

$$7920 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 0 = 0 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7921 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 1 = 1 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7922 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 2 = 2 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7923 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 3 = 3 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7924 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 4 = 4 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7925 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 5 = 5 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7926 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 6 = 6 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7927 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 7 = 7 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7928 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 8 = 8 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7929 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 9 = 9 - 2 + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$83620 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 0 = 0 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83621 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 1 = 1 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83622 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 2 = 2 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83623 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 3 = 3 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83624 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 4 = 4 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83625 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 5 = 5 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83626 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 6 = 6 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83627 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 7 = 7 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83628 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 8 = 8 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$83629 := F(F(8) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2)) + 9 = 9 + F(-2 + F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)) + F(8))$$

$$86880 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86881 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86882 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86883 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86884 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86885 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86886 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86887 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86888 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$86889 := (-86 + F(F(8))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) - 86) \times 8$$

$$87360 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87361 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87362 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87363 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87364 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87365 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87366 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87367 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87368 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87369 := (F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(7) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87480 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87481 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87482 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87483 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87484 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87485 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87486 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87487 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87488 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87489 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) - 4 - 7) \times 8$$

$$87560 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87561 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87562 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87563 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87564 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87565 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87566 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87567 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87568 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$87569 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 - 5)) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 - F(6) + (-5 + F(7)) \times F(F(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned}87640 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 0 = 0 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87641 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 1 = 1 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87642 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 2 = 2 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87643 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 3 = 3 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87644 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 4 = 4 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87645 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 5 = 5 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87646 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 6 = 6 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87647 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 7 = 7 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87648 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 8 = 8 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8 \\87649 &:= 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) + 9 = 9 + (-4 + F(F(F(6))) + F(7)) \times 8\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87680 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87681 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87682 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87683 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87684 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87685 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87686 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87687 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87688 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8 \\87689 &:= (F(F(8)) - 7 + F(F(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)) - 7) \times 8\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87840 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 0 = 0 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87841 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 1 = 1 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87842 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 2 = 2 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87843 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 3 = 3 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87844 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 4 = 4 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87845 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 5 = 5 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87846 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 6 = 6 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87847 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 7 = 7 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87848 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 8 = 8 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8) \\87849 &:= F(8 + 7) \times F(8 + 4) + 9 = 9 + F(4 + 8) \times F(7 + 8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88450 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88451 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88452 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88453 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88454 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88455 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88456 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88457 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88458 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8)) \\88459 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) - F(8))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88720 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 0 = 0 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88721 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 1 = 1 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88722 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 2 = 2 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88723 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 3 = 3 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88724 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 4 = 4 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88725 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 5 = 5 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88726 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 6 = 6 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88727 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 7 = 7 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88728 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 8 = 8 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\88729 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - F(2))) + 9 = 9 + (F(-F(2) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 8\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}89670 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 0 = 0 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89671 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 1 = 1 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89672 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 2 = 2 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89673 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 3 = 3 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89674 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 4 = 4 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89675 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 5 = 5 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89676 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 6 = 6 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89677 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 7 = 7 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89678 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 8 = 8 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8) \\89679 &:= F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 7 + 9 = 9 + 7 \times F(6 + 9) \times F(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98370 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98371 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98372 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98373 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98374 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98375 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98376 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98377 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98378 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98379 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3 - F(7)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(7) - 3 + F(F(8))) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98460 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\98461 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98462 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98463 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98464 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98465 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98466 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98467 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98468 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98469 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) - F(6)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(6) + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98510 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 0 = 0 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98511 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 1 = 1 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98512 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 2 = 2 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98513 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 3 = 3 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98514 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 4 = 4 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98515 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 5 = 5 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98516 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 6 = 6 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98517 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 7 = 7 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98518 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 8 = 8 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \\ 98519 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) - 5 + 1 + 9 = 9 + 1 - 5 + F(F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98580 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 0 = 0 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98581 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 1 = 1 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98582 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 2 = 2 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98583 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 3 = 3 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98584 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 4 = 4 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98585 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 5 = 5 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98586 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 6 = 6 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98587 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 7 = 7 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98588 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 8 = 8 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98589 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5) + F(8) + 9 = 9 + F(8) + (5 + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98820 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98821 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98822 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98823 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98824 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98825 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98826 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98827 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98828 &:= (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$98829 := (F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(2) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$121390 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 0 = 0 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121391 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 1 = 1 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121392 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 2 = 2 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121393 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 3 = 3 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121394 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 4 = 4 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121395 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 5 = 5 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121396 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 6 = 6 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121397 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 7 = 7 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121398 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 8 = 8 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$121399 := -1 - 2 + F(-1 + 3 \times 9) + 9 = 9 + F(9 \times 3 - 1) - 2 - 1$$

$$159390 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 0 = 0 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159391 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 1 = 1 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159392 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 2 = 2 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159393 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 3 = 3 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159394 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 4 = 4 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159395 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 5 = 5 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159396 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 6 = 6 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159397 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 7 = 7 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159398 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 8 = 8 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$159399 := (-1 + F(-5 + 9 \times 3)) \times 9 + 9 = 9 + 9 \times (F(3 \times 9 - 5) - 1)$$

$$196390 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 0 = 0 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196391 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 1 = 1 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196392 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 2 = 2 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196393 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 3 = 3 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196394 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 4 = 4 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196395 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 5 = 5 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196396 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 6 = 6 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196397 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 7 = 7 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196398 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 8 = 8 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$196399 := -1 \times F(9) + 6 + F(3 \times 9) + 9 = 9 + F(9 \times 3) + 6 - F(9) \times 1$$

$$202890 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 0 = 0 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202891 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 1 = 1 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202892 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 2 = 2 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202893 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 3 = 3 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202894 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 4 = 4 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202895 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 5 = 5 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202896 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 6 = 6 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202897 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 7 = 7 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202898 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 8 = 8 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202899 := (F(20) - 2) \times (F(8) + 9) + 9 = 9 + (9 + F(8)) \times (F(20) - 2)$$

$$202980 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202981 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202982 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202983 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202984 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202985 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202986 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202987 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202988 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$202989 := (F(20) + F(2)) \times (9 + F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(8) + 9) \times (F(20) + F(2))$$

$$229780 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 0 = 0 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229781 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 1 = 1 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229782 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 2 = 2 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229783 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 3 = 3 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229784 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 4 = 4 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229785 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 5 = 5 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229786 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 6 = 6 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229787 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 7 = 7 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229788 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 8 = 8 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$229789 := (F(22) - F(9)) \times F(7) - F(8) + 9 = 9 - F(8) + F(7) \times (-F(9) + F(22))$$

$$231850 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231851 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231852 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231853 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231854 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231855 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231856 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231857 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231858 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$231859 := (2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times (F(8 \times 1 \times 3) + 2)$$

$$243540 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 0 = 0 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243541 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 1 = 1 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243542 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 2 = 2 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243543 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 3 = 3 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243544 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 4 = 4 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243545 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 5 = 5 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243546 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 6 = 6 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243547 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 7 = 7 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243548 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 8 = 8 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$243549 := (2 + 4)^{F(3)} \times F(5 \times 4) + 9 = 9 + F(4 \times 5) \times (34 + 2)$$

$$269280 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 0 = 0 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269281 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 1 = 1 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269282 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 2 = 2 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269283 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 3 = 3 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269284 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 4 = 4 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269285 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 5 = 5 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269286 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 6 = 6 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269287 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 7 = 7 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269288 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 8 = 8 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$269289 := F(2 \times 6) \times F(9) \times F(2 + 8) + 9 = 9 + F(8 + 2) \times F(9) \times F(6 \times 2)$$

$$286570 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 0 = 0 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286571 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 1 = 1 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286572 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 2 = 2 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286573 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 3 = 3 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286574 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 4 = 4 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286575 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 5 = 5 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286576 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 6 = 6 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286577 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 7 = 7 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286578 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 8 = 8 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$286579 := (2 + 8) \times F(6 \times 5 - 7) + 9 = 9 + F(-7 + 5 \times 6) \times (8 + 2)$$

$$317790 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 0 = 0 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317791 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 1 = 1 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317792 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 2 = 2 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317793 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 3 = 3 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317794 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 4 = 4 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317795 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 5 = 5 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317796 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 6 = 6 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317797 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 7 = 7 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317798 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 8 = 8 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317799 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(7) - F(9) + 9 = 9 - F(9) + F(7) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317830 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 0 = 0 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317831 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 1 = 1 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317832 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 2 = 2 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317833 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 3 = 3 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317834 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 4 = 4 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317835 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 5 = 5 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317836 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 6 = 6 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317837 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 7 = 7 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317838 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 8 = 8 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$317839 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + F(8) - F(3) + 9 = 9 - F(3) + F(8) + F(7 \times (1 + 3))$$

$$368360 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368361 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368362 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368363 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368364 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368365 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368366 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368367 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368368 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$368369 := -F(3 \times 6) + F(8 \times 3) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times F(3 \times 8) - F(6 \times 3)$$

$$372020 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372021 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372022 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372023 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372024 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372025 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372026 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372027 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372028 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$372029 := F(3 + 7) \times (F(20) - F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(20) - F(2)) \times F(7 + 3)$$

$$392780 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 0 = 0 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392781 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 1 = 1 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392782 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 2 = 2 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392783 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 3 = 3 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392784 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 4 = 4 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392785 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 5 = 5 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392786 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 6 = 6 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392787 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 7 = 7 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392788 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 8 = 8 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392789 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392820 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 0 = 0 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392821 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 1 = 1 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392822 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 2 = 2 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392823 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 3 = 3 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392824 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 4 = 4 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392825 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 5 = 5 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392826 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 6 = 6 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392827 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 7 = 7 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392828 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 8 = 8 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392829 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 \times 2 + 9 = 9 - 2 \times 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392830 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 0 = 0 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392831 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 1 = 1 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392832 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 2 = 2 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392833 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 3 = 3 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392834 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 4 = 4 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392835 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 5 = 5 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392836 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 6 = 6 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392837 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 7 = 7 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392838 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 8 = 8 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392839 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 8 + F(3) + 9 = 9 + F(3) - 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392840 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 0 = 0 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392841 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 1 = 1 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392842 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 2 = 2 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392843 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 3 = 3 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392844 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 4 = 4 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392845 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 5 = 5 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392846 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 6 = 6 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392847 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 7 = 7 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392848 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 8 = 8 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392849 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + 8 - 4 + 9 = 9 - 4 + 8 + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392870 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 0 = 0 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392871 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 1 = 1 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392872 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 2 = 2 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392873 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 3 = 3 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392874 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 4 = 4 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392875 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 5 = 5 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392876 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 6 = 6 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392877 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 7 = 7 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392878 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 8 = 8 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$392879 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 + F(8) + F(7) + 9 = 9 + F(7) + F(8) + 2 \times F(9 \times 3)$$

$$393590 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 0 = 0 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393591 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 1 = 1 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393592 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 2 = 2 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393593 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 3 = 3 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393594 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 4 = 4 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393595 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 5 = 5 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393596 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 6 = 6 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393597 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 7 = 7 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393598 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 8 = 8 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$393599 := F(3) \times (F(9 \times 3) + F(5 + 9)) + 9 = 9 + (F(9 + 5) + F(3 \times 9)) \times F(3)$$

$$437960 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 0 = 0 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437961 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 1 = 1 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437962 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 2 = 2 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437963 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 3 = 3 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437964 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 4 = 4 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437965 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 5 = 5 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437966 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 6 = 6 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437967 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 7 = 7 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437968 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 8 = 8 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$437969 := (F(4) + F(3 \times 7)) \times (F(9) + 6) + 9 = 9 + (6 + F(9)) \times (F(7 \times 3) + F(4))$$

$$444690 := (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6 + 9) + 0 = 0 + F(9 + 6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}$$

$$444691 := (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6 + 9) + 1 = 1 + F(9 + 6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}$$

$$444692 := (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6 + 9) + 2 = 2 + F(9 + 6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}$$

$$444693 := (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6 + 9) + 3 = 3 + F(9 + 6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}$$

$$444694 := (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6 + 9) + 4 = 4 + F(9 + 6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}444695 &:= (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6+9) + 5 = 5 + F(9+6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \\444696 &:= (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6+9) + 6 = 6 + F(9+6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \\444697 &:= (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6+9) + 7 = 7 + F(9+6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \\444698 &:= (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6+9) + 8 = 8 + F(9+6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \\444699 &:= (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)} \times F(6+9) + 9 = 9 + F(9+6) \times (F(4) \times F(4))^{F(4)}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}463650 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463651 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463652 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463653 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463654 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463655 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463656 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463657 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463658 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4)) \\463659 &:= (F(4 \times 6) \times F(3) - 6) \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times (-6 + F(3) \times F(6 \times 4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}463680 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 0 = 0 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463681 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 1 = 1 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463682 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 2 = 2 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463683 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 3 = 3 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463684 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 4 = 4 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463685 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 5 = 5 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463686 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 6 = 6 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463687 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 7 = 7 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463688 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 8 = 8 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4) \\463689 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times (3 \times 6 - 8) + 9 = 9 + (8 + 6/3) \times F(6 \times 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}466530 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 0 = 0 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466531 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 1 = 1 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466532 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 2 = 2 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466533 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 3 = 3 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466534 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 4 = 4 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466535 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 5 = 5 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466536 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 6 = 6 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466537 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 7 = 7 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466538 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 8 = 8 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4)) \\466539 &:= (-F(4) + 6^6) \times 5 \times F(3) + 9 = 9 + F(3) \times 5 \times (6^6 - F(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$525170 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 0 = 0 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525171 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 1 = 1 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525172 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 2 = 2 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525173 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 3 = 3 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525174 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 4 = 4 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525175 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 5 = 5 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525176 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 6 = 6 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525177 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 7 = 7 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525178 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 8 = 8 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525179 := -5 + F(25) \times 1 \times 7 + 9 = 9 + 7 \times 1 \times F(5^2) - 5$$

$$525180 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 0 = 0 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525181 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 1 = 1 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525182 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 2 = 2 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525183 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 3 = 3 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525184 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 4 = 4 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525185 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 5 = 5 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525186 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 6 = 6 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525187 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 7 = 7 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525188 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 8 = 8 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$525189 := 5 + F(25) \times (-1 + 8) + 9 = 9 + (8 - 1) \times F(5^2) + 5$$

$$606970 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 0 = 0 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606971 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 1 = 1 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606972 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 2 = 2 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606973 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 3 = 3 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606974 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 4 = 4 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606975 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 5 = 5 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606976 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 6 = 6 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606977 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 7 = 7 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606978 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 8 = 8 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$606979 := (6^{06} + F(9)) \times F(7) + 9 = 9 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 6^{06})$$

$$689640 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 0 = 0 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689641 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 1 = 1 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689642 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 2 = 2 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689643 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 3 = 3 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689644 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 4 = 4 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689645 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 5 = 5 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689646 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 6 = 6 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689647 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 7 = 7 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689648 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 8 = 8 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$689649 := F(6) \times F(8) \times (9 + F(6)^4) + 9 = 9 + (4^6 + 9) \times F(8) \times F(6)$$

$$823540 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 0 = 0 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823541 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 1 = 1 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823542 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 2 = 2 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823543 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 3 = 3 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823544 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 4 = 4 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823545 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 5 = 5 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823546 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 6 = 6 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823547 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 7 = 7 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823548 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 8 = 8 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$823549 := (8 - F(2))^{F(3)+5} - F(4) + 9 = 9 - F(4) + (5 + F(3))^{-F(2)+8}$$

$$832040 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 0 = 0 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832041 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 1 = 1 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832042 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 2 = 2 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832043 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 3 = 3 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832044 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 4 = 4 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832045 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 5 = 5 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832046 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 6 = 6 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832047 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 7 = 7 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832048 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 8 = 8 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$832049 := F(8 \times 3 + 2 + 04) + 9 = 9 + F(40 \times 2 \times 3/8)$$

$$834570 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 0 = 0 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834571 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 1 = 1 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834572 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 2 = 2 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834573 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 3 = 3 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834574 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 4 = 4 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834575 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 5 = 5 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834576 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 6 = 6 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834577 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 7 = 7 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834578 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 8 = 8 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834579 := (F(8 \times 3) - F(4)) \times (5 + F(7)) + 9 = 9 + (F(7) + 5) \times (-F(4) + F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834660 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834661 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834662 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834663 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834664 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834665 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834666 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834667 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834668 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834669 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$922740 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 0 = 0 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922741 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 1 = 1 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922742 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 2 = 2 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922743 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 3 = 3 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922744 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 4 = 4 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922745 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 5 = 5 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922746 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 6 = 6 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922747 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 7 = 7 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922748 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 8 = 8 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$922749 := (F(9) + F(22)) \times F(7) \times 4 + 9 = 9 + 4 \times F(7) \times (F(22) + F(9))$$

$$973830 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 0 = 0 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973831 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 1 = 1 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973832 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 2 = 2 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973833 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 3 = 3 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973834 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 4 = 4 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973835 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 5 = 5 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973836 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 6 = 6 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973837 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 7 = 7 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973838 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 8 = 8 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$973839 := (F(9) + 7 \times F(3 \times 8)) \times 3 + 9 = 9 + 3 \times (7 \times F(8 \times 3) + F(9))$$

$$974440 := F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 0 = 0 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)$$

$$974441 := F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 1 = 1 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)$$

$$974442 := F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 2 = 2 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)$$

$$974443 := F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 3 = 3 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)$$

$$974444 := F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 4 = 4 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}974445 &:= F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 5 = 5 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9) \\974446 &:= F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 6 = 6 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9) \\974447 &:= F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 7 = 7 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9) \\974448 &:= F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 8 = 8 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9) \\974449 &:= F(9) \times (F(7 + 4 \times 4) + F(4)) + 9 = 9 + (F(4) + F(4 \times 4 + 7)) \times F(9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}974610 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 0 = 0 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974611 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 1 = 1 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974612 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 2 = 2 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974613 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 3 = 3 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974614 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 4 = 4 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974615 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 5 = 5 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974616 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 6 = 6 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974617 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 7 = 7 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974618 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 8 = 8 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9) \\974619 &:= F(9) \times 7 \times (4^6 - 1) + 9 = 9 + (-1 + F(6)^4) \times 7 \times F(9)\end{aligned}$$

3.1.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned}720 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 0 = 0 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\721 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 1 = 1 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\722 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 2 = 2 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\723 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 3 = 3 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\724 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 4 = 4 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\725 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 5 = 5 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\726 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 6 = 6 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\727 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 7 = 7 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\728 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 8 = 8 + (-F(2) + 7)! \\729 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 9 = 9 + (-F(2) + 7)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1440 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1441 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1442 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1443 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1444 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1445 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1446 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1447 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! \\1448 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$1449 := (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4))!! + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!!$$

$$3360 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 0 = 0 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3361 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 1 = 1 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3362 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 2 = 2 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3363 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 3 = 3 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3364 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 4 = 4 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3365 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 5 = 5 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3366 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 6 = 6 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3367 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 7 = 7 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3368 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 8 = 8 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3369 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 9 = 9 + F(6)! / (F(3) \times 3!)$$

$$3660 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 0 = 0 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3661 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 1 = 1 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3662 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 2 = 2 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3663 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3 = 3 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3664 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 4 = 4 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3665 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 5 = 5 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3666 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 6 = 6 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3667 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 7 = 7 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3668 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 8 = 8 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3669 := 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 9 = 9 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!)$$

$$3840 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3841 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3842 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3843 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3844 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3845 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3846 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3847 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3848 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$3849 := (F(3!))! / F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)) \times 8! / F(F(3!))$$

$$4320 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 0 = 0 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4321 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 1 = 1 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4322 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 2 = 2 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4323 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 3 = 3 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4324 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 4 = 4 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4325 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 5 = 5 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4326 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 6 = 6 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4327 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 7 = 7 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4328 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 8 = 8 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4329 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 9 = 9 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4)$$

$$4350 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4351 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4352 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4353 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4354 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4355 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4356 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4357 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4358 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4359 := F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!$$

$$4480 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 0 = 0 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4481 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 1 = 1 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4482 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 2 = 2 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4483 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 3 = 3 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4484 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 4 = 4 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4485 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 5 = 5 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4486 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 6 = 6 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4487 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 7 = 7 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4488 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 8 = 8 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4489 := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 9 = 9 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$4880 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4881 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4882 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4883 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4884 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4885 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4886 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4887 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4888 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4889 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$5040 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 0 = 0 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}5041 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 1 = 1 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5042 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 2 = 2 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5043 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 3 = 3 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5044 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 4 = 4 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5045 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 5 = 5 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5046 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 6 = 6 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5047 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 7 = 7 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5048 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 8 = 8 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! \\5049 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 9 = 9 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5640 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 0 = 0 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5641 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 1 = 1 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5642 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 2 = 2 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5643 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 3 = 3 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5644 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 4 = 4 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5645 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 5 = 5 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5646 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 6 = 6 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5647 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 7 = 7 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5648 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 8 = 8 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\5649 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 9 = 9 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5760 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5761 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5762 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5763 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5764 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5765 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5766 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5767 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5768 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) \\5769 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6480 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 0 = 0 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6481 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 1 = 1 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6482 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 2 = 2 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6483 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 3 = 3 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6484 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 4 = 4 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6485 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 5 = 5 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6486 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 6 = 6 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6487 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 7 = 7 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! \\6488 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 8 = 8 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$6489 := 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 9 = 9 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6!$$

$$6720 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6721 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6722 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6723 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6724 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6725 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6726 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6727 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6728 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6729 := F(6)! / (7 - F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6$$

$$6840 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 0 = 0 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6841 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 1 = 1 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6842 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 2 = 2 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6843 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 3 = 3 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6844 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 4 = 4 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6845 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 5 = 5 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6846 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 6 = 6 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6847 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 7 = 7 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6848 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 8 = 8 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$6849 := (6! + 8!) / F(4)! + 9 = 9 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6$$

$$7560 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7561 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7562 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7563 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7564 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7565 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7566 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7567 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7568 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7569 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7930 := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 0 = 0 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)$$

$$7931 := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 1 = 1 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)$$

$$7932 := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 2 = 2 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)$$

$$7933 := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 3 = 3 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)$$

$$7934 := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 4 = 4 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}7935 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 5 = 5 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\7936 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 6 = 6 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\7937 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 7 = 7 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\7938 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 8 = 8 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\7939 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 9 = 9 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9360 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9361 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9362 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9363 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9364 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9365 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9366 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9367 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9368 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\9369 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times F(-F(3) + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11480 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11481 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11482 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11483 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11484 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11485 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11486 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11487 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11488 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11) \\11489 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(8)) + F(4)! \times F(11)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12670 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 0 = 0 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12671 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 1 = 1 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12672 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 2 = 2 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12673 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 3 = 3 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12674 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 4 = 4 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12675 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 5 = 5 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12676 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 6 = 6 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12677 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 7 = 7 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12678 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 8 = 8 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1 \\12679 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 9 = 9 - 7! + F(F(F(6)) + F(2)) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$13520 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 0 = 0 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13521 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 1 = 1 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13522 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 2 = 2 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13523 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 3 = 3 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13524 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 4 = 4 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13525 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 5 = 5 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13526 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 6 = 6 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13527 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 7 = 7 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13528 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 8 = 8 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13529 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 9 = 9 + 2 \times (-5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13540 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13541 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13542 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13543 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13544 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13545 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13546 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13547 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13548 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$13549 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)) \times (5 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1))$$

$$14340 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14341 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14342 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14343 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14344 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14345 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14346 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14347 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14348 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14349 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14360 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 0 = 0 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14361 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 1 = 1 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14362 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 2 = 2 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14363 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 3 = 3 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14364 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 4 = 4 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14365 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 5 = 5 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14366 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 6 = 6 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14367 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 7 = 7 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14368 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 8 = 8 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14369 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 9 = 9 + (6! - F(3)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14380 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14381 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14382 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14383 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14384 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14385 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14386 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14387 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14388 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14389 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(8) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)! - 1)$$

$$14420 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 20 = 0 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14421 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 21 = 1 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14422 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 22 = 2 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14423 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 23 = 3 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14424 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 24 = 4 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14425 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 25 = 5 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14426 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 26 = 6 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14427 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 27 = 7 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14428 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 28 = 8 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14429 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 29 = 9 + (-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (F(4)! + 1)$$

$$14460 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 60 = 0 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14461 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 61 = 1 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14462 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 62 = 2 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14463 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 63 = 3 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14464 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 64 = 4 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14465 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 65 = 5 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14466 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 66 = 6 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14467 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 67 = 7 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14468 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 68 = 8 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14469 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 69 = 9 + (6! + F(4)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$14520 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14521 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14522 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14523 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14524 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14525 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14526 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14527 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14528 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14529 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(2) + 5!) \times (4 + 1)!$$

$$14680 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 0 = 0 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14681 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 1 = 1 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14682 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 2 = 2 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14683 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 3 = 3 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14684 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 4 = 4 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14685 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 5 = 5 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14686 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 6 = 6 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14687 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 7 = 7 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14688 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 8 = 8 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$14689 := 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 9 = 9 + F(8) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) + 1$$

$$15840 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 0 = 0 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15841 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 1 = 1 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15842 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 2 = 2 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15843 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 3 = 3 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15844 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 4 = 4 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15845 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 5 = 5 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15846 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 6 = 6 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15847 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 = 7 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15848 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 8 = 8 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$15849 := (1 + 5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 9 = 9 + F(4)!! + F(8) \times (5 + 1)!$$

$$18440 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 0 = 0 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18441 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 1 = 1 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18442 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 2 = 2 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18443 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 3 = 3 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18444 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 4 = 4 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18445 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 5 = 5 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18446 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 6 = 6 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18447 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 7 = 7 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18448 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 8 = 8 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$18449 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 9 = 9 + F(4)^{F(4)!} + F(F(8) + 1)$$

$$19440 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 0 = 0 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19441 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 1 = 1 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19442 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 2 = 2 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19443 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 3 = 3 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19444 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 4 = 4 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19445 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 5 = 5 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19446 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 6 = 6 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19447 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 7 = 7 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19448 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 8 = 8 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$19449 := 1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 9 = 9 + F(4) \times F(4)!! \times 9 \times 1$$

$$20880 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20881 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20882 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20883 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20884 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20885 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20886 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20887 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20888 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$20889 := (2 + 0)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (8 + F(8)) \times (0! + 2)!!$$

$$21650 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 0 = 0 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21651 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 1 = 1 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21652 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 2 = 2 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21653 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 3 = 3 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21654 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 4 = 4 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21655 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 5 = 5 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21656 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 6 = 6 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21657 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 7 = 7 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21658 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 8 = 8 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21659 := 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 9 = 9 + (-5! + F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 2$$

$$21940 := 2 \times (F(F(-1 + 9)) + 4!) + 0 = 0 + (4! + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 2$$

$$21941 := 2 \times (F(F(-1 + 9)) + 4!) + 1 = 1 + (4! + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 2$$

$$21942 := 2 \times (F(F(-1 + 9)) + 4!) + 2 = 2 + (4! + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}21943 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 3 = 3 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21944 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 4 = 4 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21945 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 5 = 5 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21946 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 6 = 6 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21947 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 7 = 7 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21948 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 8 = 8 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2 \\21949 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 9 = 9 + (4! + F(F(9-1))) \times 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22610 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 0 = 0 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22611 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 1 = 1 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22612 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 2 = 2 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22613 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 3 = 3 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22614 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 4 = 4 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22615 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 5 = 5 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22616 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 6 = 6 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22617 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 7 = 7 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22618 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 8 = 8 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22) \\22619 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 9 = 9 + 1 + F(6)! - F(22)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22630 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 0 = 0 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22631 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 1 = 1 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22632 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 2 = 2 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22633 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 3 = 3 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22634 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 4 = 4 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22635 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 5 = 5 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22636 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 6 = 6 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22637 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 7 = 7 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22638 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 8 = 8 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22) \\22639 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 9 = 9 + F(3)! + F(F(6)) - F(22)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22730 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 0 = 0 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22731 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 1 = 1 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22732 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 2 = 2 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22733 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 3 = 3 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22734 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 4 = 4 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22735 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 5 = 5 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22736 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 6 = 6 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22737 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 7 = 7 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22738 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 8 = 8 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22) \\22739 &:= F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 9 = 9 - F(F(3!)) + 7! + F(22)\end{aligned}$$

$$23040 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 0 = 0 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23041 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 1 = 1 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23042 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 2 = 2 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23043 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 3 = 3 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23044 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 4 = 4 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23045 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 5 = 5 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23046 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 6 = 6 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23047 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 7 = 7 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23048 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 8 = 8 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23049 := (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 9 = 9 + F(4)!! \times 032$$

$$23640 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 0 = 0 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23641 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 1 = 1 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23642 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 2 = 2 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23643 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 3 = 3 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23644 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 4 = 4 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23645 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 5 = 5 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23646 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 6 = 6 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23647 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 7 = 7 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23648 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 8 = 8 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23649 := (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 9 = 9 + 4! \times (F(F(6) \times F(3)) - 2)$$

$$23760 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23761 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23762 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23763 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23764 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23765 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23766 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23767 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23768 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$23769 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times (F(7 + F(3)) - F(2))$$

$$24490 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 0 = 0 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24491 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 1 = 1 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24492 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 2 = 2 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24493 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 3 = 3 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24494 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 4 = 4 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24495 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 5 = 5 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24496 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 6 = 6 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24497 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 7 = 7 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24498 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 8 = 8 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24499 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 9 = 9 + F(9) \times F(4)!! + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$24650 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24651 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24652 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24653 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24654 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24655 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24656 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24657 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24658 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$24659 := F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 6!) \times F(F(4)^2)$$

$$25920 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 0 = 0 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25921 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 1 = 1 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25922 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 2 = 2 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25923 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 3 = 3 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25924 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 4 = 4 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25925 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 5 = 5 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25926 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 6 = 6 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25927 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 7 = 7 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25928 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 8 = 8 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$25929 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 9 = 9 + (2 + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2))!$$

$$27330 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 0 = 0 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27331 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 1 = 1 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27332 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 2 = 2 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27333 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 3 = 3 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27334 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 4 = 4 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27335 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 5 = 5 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27336 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 6 = 6 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27337 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 7 = 7 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27338 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 8 = 8 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27339 := (2^7)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 9 = 9 + F(F(F(3!))) + F(3)^{7 \times 2}$$

$$27360 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27361 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27362 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27363 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27364 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27365 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27366 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27367 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27368 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27369 := 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times (3! + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$27720 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 0 = 0 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27721 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 1 = 1 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27722 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 2 = 2 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27723 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 3 = 3 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27724 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 4 = 4 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27725 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 5 = 5 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27726 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 6 = 6 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27727 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 7 = 7 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27728 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 8 = 8 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27729 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 9 = 9 + (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2$$

$$27840 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 0 = 0 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27841 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 1 = 1 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27842 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 2 = 2 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27843 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 3 = 3 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27844 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 4 = 4 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27845 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 5 = 5 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27846 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 6 = 6 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27847 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 7 = 7 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27848 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 8 = 8 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27849 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 9 = 9 + (-F(4) + 8)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$27960 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 0 = 0 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27961 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 1 = 1 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27962 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 2 = 2 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27963 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 3 = 3 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27964 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 4 = 4 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27965 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 5 = 5 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27966 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 6 = 6 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27967 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 7 = 7 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27968 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 8 = 8 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$27969 := (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 9 = 9 + F(-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 2)!$$

$$28540 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 0 = 0 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28541 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 1 = 1 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28542 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 2 = 2 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28543 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 3 = 3 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28544 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 4 = 4 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28545 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 5 = 5 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28546 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 6 = 6 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28547 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 7 = 7 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28548 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 8 = 8 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28549 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 9 = 9 + F(4) - 5! + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28560 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 0 = 0 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28561 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 1 = 1 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28562 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 2 = 2 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28563 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 3 = 3 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28564 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 4 = 4 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28565 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 5 = 5 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28566 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 6 = 6 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28567 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 = 7 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28568 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 8 = 8 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28569 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 9 = 9 + (6! + 5!) \times F(8 + F(2))$$

$$28630 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 0 = 0 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28631 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 1 = 1 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28632 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 2 = 2 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28633 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 3 = 3 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28634 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 4 = 4 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28635 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 5 = 5 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28636 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 6 = 6 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28637 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 7 = 7 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28638 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 8 = 8 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28639 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 9 = 9 - 3! - F(F(6)) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$29380 := (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 0 = 0 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))!$$

$$29381 := (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 1 = 1 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))!$$

$$29382 := (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 2 = 2 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29383 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 3 = 3 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29384 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 4 = 4 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29385 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 5 = 5 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29386 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 6 = 6 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29387 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 7 = 7 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29388 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 8 = 8 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \\ 29389 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 9 = 9 - F(F(8)) + 3! + (9 - F(2))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30960 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 0 = 0 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30961 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 1 = 1 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30962 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 2 = 2 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30963 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 3 = 3 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30964 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 4 = 4 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30965 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 5 = 5 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30966 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 6 = 6 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30967 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 7 = 7 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30968 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 8 = 8 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \\ 30969 &:= 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 9 = 9 + (F(6) + F(9) + 0!) \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31940 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 0 = 0 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31941 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 1 = 1 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31942 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 2 = 2 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31943 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 3 = 3 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31944 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 4 = 4 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31945 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 5 = 5 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31946 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 6 = 6 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31947 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 7 = 7 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31948 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 8 = 8 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \\ 31949 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + 9 = 9 + F(F(F(4)! + 9) \times (-1 + F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32880 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32881 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32882 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32883 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32884 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32885 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32886 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32887 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32888 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 32889 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(8)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$33070 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33071 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33072 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33073 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33074 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33075 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33076 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33077 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33078 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33079 := 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(7)) - 0! + 3 \times F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$33270 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33271 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33272 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33273 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33274 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33275 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33276 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33277 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33278 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33279 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33280 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33281 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33282 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33283 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33284 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33285 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33286 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33287 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33288 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33289 := F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8) - 2) - F(F(3!))) \times F(3!)$$

$$33440 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$33441 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$33442 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$33443 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$33444 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$33445 := -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33446 &:= -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!) \\ 33447 &:= -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!) \\ 33448 &:= -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!) \\ 33449 &:= -F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) - F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33450 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 0 = 0 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33451 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 1 = 1 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33452 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 2 = 2 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33453 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 3 = 3 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33454 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 4 = 4 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33455 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 5 = 5 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33456 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 6 = 6 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33457 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 7 = 7 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33458 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 8 = 8 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \\ 33459 &:= F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 9 = 9 + F(-5 + 4!) \times F(3!) + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33600 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 00 = 0 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33601 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 01 = 1 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33602 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 02 = 2 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33603 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 03 = 3 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33604 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 04 = 4 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33605 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 05 = 5 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33606 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 06 = 6 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33607 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 07 = 7 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33608 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 08 = 8 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \\ 33609 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 09 = 9 - F(06)!/3! + F(3!)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33640 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 40 = 0 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33641 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 41 = 1 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33642 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 42 = 2 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33643 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 43 = 3 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33644 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 44 = 4 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33645 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 45 = 5 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33646 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 46 = 6 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33647 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 47 = 7 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33648 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 48 = 8 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \\ 33649 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 49 = 9 + (4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33670 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 70 = 0 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!) \\ 33671 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6!) + 71 = 1 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$33672 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 72 = 2 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33673 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 73 = 3 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33674 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 74 = 4 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33675 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 75 = 5 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33676 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 76 = 6 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33677 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 77 = 7 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33678 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 78 = 8 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33679 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 79 = 9 + F(7) \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3!)$$

$$33770 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33771 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33772 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33773 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33774 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33775 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33776 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33777 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33778 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33779 := 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(7)) + (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3$$

$$33840 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 0 = 0 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33841 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 1 = 1 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33842 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 2 = 2 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33843 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 3 = 3 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33844 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 4 = 4 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33845 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 5 = 5 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33846 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 6 = 6 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33847 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 7 = 7 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33848 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 8 = 8 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$33849 := 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 9 = 9 + (4! + F(8) + F(3)) \times 3!!$$

$$34280 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34281 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34282 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34283 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34284 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34285 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34286 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34287 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34288 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34289 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! \times 2 - F(4!) + F(3!)$$

$$34530 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 0 = 0 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34531 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 1 = 1 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34532 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 2 = 2 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34533 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 3 = 3 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34534 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 4 = 4 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34535 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 5 = 5 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34536 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 6 = 6 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34537 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 7 = 7 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34538 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 8 = 8 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34539 := (F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 9 = 9 + 3! \times (5 + F(4)!! \times F(3!))$$

$$34670 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 0 = 0 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34671 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 1 = 1 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34672 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 2 = 2 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34673 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 3 = 3 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34674 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 4 = 4 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34675 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 5 = 5 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34676 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 6 = 6 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34677 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 7 = 7 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34678 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 8 = 8 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34679 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 9 = 9 - 7! - F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34730 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 0 = 0 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34731 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 1 = 1 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34732 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 2 = 2 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34733 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 3 = 3 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34734 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 4 = 4 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34735 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 5 = 5 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34736 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 6 = 6 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34737 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 7 = 7 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34738 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 8 = 8 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$34739 := F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 9 = 9 + F(3)! - F(F(7)) \times 4! + F(3)$$

$$35160 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 0 = 0 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35161 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 1 = 1 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35162 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 2 = 2 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35163 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 3 = 3 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35164 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 4 = 4 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35165 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 5 = 5 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35166 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 6 = 6 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35167 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 7 = 7 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35168 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 8 = 8 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35169 := F(3)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 9 = 9 - (6 + 1)! - 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35400 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 0 = 0 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35401 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 1 = 1 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35402 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 2 = 2 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35403 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 3 = 3 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35404 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 4 = 4 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35405 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 5 = 5 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35406 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 6 = 6 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35407 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 7 = 7 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35408 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 8 = 8 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35409 := F(3)! + 5! - (F(4)! + 0!)! + 9 = 9 - (0! + F(4)!)! + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35430 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 0 = 0 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35431 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 1 = 1 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35432 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 2 = 2 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35433 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 3 = 3 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35434 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 4 = 4 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35435 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 5 = 5 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35436 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 6 = 6 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35437 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 7 = 7 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35438 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 8 = 8 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35439 := -F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 9 = 9 + F(3!) + F(4!) - F(F(5 + 3))$$

$$35440 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35441 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35442 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35443 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35444 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 = 4 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35445 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 = 5 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35446 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 = 6 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35447 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 = 7 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35448 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 = 8 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$35449 := F(3)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 = 9 - F(F(4)!) \times F(F(4) \times 5) + F(3)!$$

$$36660 := F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 0 = 0 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36661 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 1 = 1 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36662 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 2 = 2 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36663 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3 = 3 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36664 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 4 = 4 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36665 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 5 = 5 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36666 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 6 = 6 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36667 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 7 = 7 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36668 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 8 = 8 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \\ 36669 &:= F(3)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 9 = 9 - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + F(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36720 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 0 = 0 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36721 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 1 = 1 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36722 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 2 = 2 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36723 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 3 = 3 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36724 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 4 = 4 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36725 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 5 = 5 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36726 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 6 = 6 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36727 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 7 = 7 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36728 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 8 = 8 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \\ 36729 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 9 = 9 + (2 - 7) \times 6! + F(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37280 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37281 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37282 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37283 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37284 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37285 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37286 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37287 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37288 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 37289 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38761 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38762 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38763 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38764 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38765 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38766 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \\ 38767 &:= -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$38768 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)!$$

$$38769 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! - F(7) \times (8 - 3)!$$

$$39240 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 0 = 0 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39241 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 1 = 1 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39242 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 2 = 2 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39243 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 3 = 3 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39244 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 4 = 4 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39245 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 5 = 5 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39246 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 6 = 6 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39247 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 7 = 7 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39248 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 8 = 8 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39249 := F(3)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 9 = 9 - (F(4) + 2)! \times 9 + (F(3))!$$

$$39550 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 0 = 0 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39551 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 1 = 1 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39552 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 2 = 2 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39553 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 3 = 3 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39554 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 4 = 4 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39555 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 5 = 5 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39556 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 6 = 6 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39557 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 7 = 7 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39558 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 8 = 8 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39559 := F(3)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 9 = 9 - 5 \times (5! + F(9)) + F(3)!$$

$$39600 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 00 = 0 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39601 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 01 = 1 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39602 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 02 = 2 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39603 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 03 = 3 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39604 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 04 = 4 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39605 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 05 = 5 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39606 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 06 = 6 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39607 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 07 = 7 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39608 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 08 = 8 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39609 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 09 = 9 + F(06)! - (9 - 3)!$$

$$39640 := -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 0 = 0 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!!$$

$$39641 := -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 1 = 1 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!!$$

$$39642 := -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 2 = 2 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!!$$

$$39643 := -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 3 = 3 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39644 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 4 = 4 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \\ 39645 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 5 = 5 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \\ 39646 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 6 = 6 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \\ 39647 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 7 = 7 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \\ 39648 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 8 = 8 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \\ 39649 &:= -3!! + F(9) + F(6)! + F(4)! + 9 = 9 + F(4)! + F(6)! + F(9) - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39710 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 0 = 0 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39711 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 1 = 1 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39712 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 2 = 2 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39713 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 3 = 3 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39714 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 4 = 4 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39715 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 5 = 5 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39716 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 6 = 6 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39717 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 7 = 7 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39718 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 8 = 8 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \\ 39719 &:= -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 9 = 9 + (1 + 7)! - F(9 + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39880 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39881 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39882 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39883 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39884 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39885 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39886 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39887 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39888 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \\ 39889 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39960 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39961 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39962 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39963 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39964 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39965 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39966 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39967 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39968 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \\ 39969 &:= -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! - 9 \times (F(9) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39980 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39981 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39982 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39983 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39984 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39985 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39986 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39987 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39988 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \\ 39989 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - F(9) \times (9 + F(F(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40200 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 0 = 0 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40201 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 1 = 1 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40202 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 2 = 2 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40203 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 3 = 3 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40204 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 4 = 4 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40205 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 5 = 5 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40206 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 6 = 6 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40207 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 7 = 7 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40208 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 8 = 8 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \\ 40209 &:= -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 9 = 9 + F((0! + 2)!)! - (0! + 4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40240 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40241 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40242 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40243 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40244 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40245 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40246 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40247 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40248 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \\ 40249 &:= -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)!)! - 20 \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40280 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40281 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40282 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40283 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40284 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40285 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40286 &:= -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$40287 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4))$$

$$40288 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4))$$

$$40289 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - 20 \times F(F(4))$$

$$40330 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 0 = 0 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40331 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 1 = 1 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40332 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 2 = 2 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40333 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 3 = 3 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40334 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 4 = 4 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40335 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 5 = 5 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40336 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 6 = 6 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40337 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 7 = 7 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40338 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 8 = 8 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40339 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 9 = 9 + F(3!)! + 3! + 04$$

$$40360 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40361 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40362 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40363 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40364 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40365 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40366 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40367 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40368 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40369 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! + F(3!) \times (0! + 4)$$

$$40490 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 0 = 0 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40491 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 1 = 1 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40492 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 2 = 2 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40493 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 3 = 3 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40494 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 4 = 4 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40495 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 5 = 5 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40496 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 6 = 6 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40497 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 7 = 7 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40498 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 8 = 8 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40499 := F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 9 = 9 + F(9) \times (4 + 0!) + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40560 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40561 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40562 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40563 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40564 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40565 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40566 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40567 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40568 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40569 := -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! - 5! \times (0! - F(4))$$

$$40680 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40681 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40682 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40683 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40684 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40685 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40686 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40687 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40688 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40689 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! + 6! / (-0! + F(4))$$

$$40930 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 0 = 0 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40931 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 1 = 1 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40932 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 2 = 2 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40933 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 3 = 3 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40934 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 4 = 4 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40935 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 5 = 5 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40936 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 6 = 6 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40937 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 7 = 7 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40938 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 8 = 8 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$40939 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 9 = 9 + F(3!)! + F(-9 + 04!)$$

$$41760 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41761 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41762 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41763 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41764 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41765 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41766 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41767 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41768 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$41769 := F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! + (7 - 1)! \times F(F(4))$$

$$42480 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42481 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42482 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42483 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42484 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42485 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42486 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42487 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42488 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42489 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! + F(4) \times (2 + 4)!$$

$$42760 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 0 = 0 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42761 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 1 = 1 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42762 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 2 = 2 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42763 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 3 = 3 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42764 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 4 = 4 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42765 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 5 = 5 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42766 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 6 = 6 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42767 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 7 = 7 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42768 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 8 = 8 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$42769 := 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 9 = 9 + F(6)! + F(F(7) + 2) \times 4$$

$$43060 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 0 = 0 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43061 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 1 = 1 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43062 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 2 = 2 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43063 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 3 = 3 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43064 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 4 = 4 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43065 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 5 = 5 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43066 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 6 = 6 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43067 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 7 = 7 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43068 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 8 = 8 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43069 := 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 9 = 9 - 6! - (0! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4$$

$$43200 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 0 = 0 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43201 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 1 = 1 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43202 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 2 = 2 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43203 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 3 = 3 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43204 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 4 = 4 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43205 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 5 = 5 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43206 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 6 = 6 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43207 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 7 = 7 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43208 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 8 = 8 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43209 := 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 9 = 9 + F((0! + 2)!) + 3!! \times 4$$

$$43480 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 0 = 0 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43481 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 1 = 1 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43482 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 2 = 2 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43483 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 3 = 3 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43484 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 4 = 4 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43485 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 5 = 5 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43486 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 6 = 6 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43487 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 7 = 7 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43488 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 8 = 8 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43489 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 9 = 9 - 8 - 4 \times 3!! + F(4!)$$

$$43560 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 0 = 0 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43561 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 1 = 1 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43562 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 2 = 2 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43563 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 3 = 3 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43564 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 4 = 4 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43565 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 5 = 5 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43566 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 6 = 6 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43567 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 7 = 7 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43568 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 8 = 8 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43569 := (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6!) + 9 = 9 + F(6!) + 5! \times (3 + 4!)$$

$$43700 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43701 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43702 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43703 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43704 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43705 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43706 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43707 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43708 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43709 := 4 \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(F(3!))) \times 4$$

$$43800 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 0 = 0 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43801 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 1 = 1 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43802 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 2 = 2 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43803 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 3 = 3 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43804 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 4 = 4 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43805 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 5 = 5 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43806 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 6 = 6 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43807 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 7 = 7 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43808 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 8 = 8 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43809 := 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 9 = 9 + (0! + F(F(8)) + 3) \times 4$$

$$43820 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43821 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43822 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43823 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43824 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43825 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43826 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43827 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43828 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43829 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43840 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 0 = 0 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43841 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 1 = 1 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43842 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 2 = 2 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43843 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 3 = 3 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43844 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 4 = 4 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43845 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 5 = 5 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43846 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 6 = 6 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43847 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 7 = 7 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43848 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 8 = 8 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43849 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 9 = 9 + (F(4!) + F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 4$$

$$43920 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43921 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43922 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43923 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43924 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43925 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43926 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43927 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43928 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43929 := F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(2) + 9) + 3!) \times F(4)!!$$

$$43980 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43981 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43982 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43983 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43984 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43985 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43986 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43987 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43988 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$43989 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! + F(9 + 3!) \times F(4)!$$

$$44480 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44481 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44482 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44483 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44484 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44485 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44486 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44487 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44488 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44489 := F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) - F(4)!) \times 4 + F(4)!!$$

$$44720 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 0 = 0 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44721 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 1 = 1 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44722 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 2 = 2 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44723 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 3 = 3 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44724 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 4 = 4 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44725 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 5 = 5 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44726 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 6 = 6 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44727 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 7 = 7 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44728 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 8 = 8 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44729 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 9 = 9 + (-2 + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$44860 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 0 = 0 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44861 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 1 = 1 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44862 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 2 = 2 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44863 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 3 = 3 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44864 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 4 = 4 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44865 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 5 = 5 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44866 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 6 = 6 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44867 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 7 = 7 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44868 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 8 = 8 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44869 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 9 = 9 - F(6 + 8) \times 4 + F(4!)$$

$$44940 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 0 = 0 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44941 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 1 = 1 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44942 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 2 = 2 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44943 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 3 = 3 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44944 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 4 = 4 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44945 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 5 = 5 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44946 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 6 = 6 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44947 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 7 = 7 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44948 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 8 = 8 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44949 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 9 = 9 - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44970 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44971 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44972 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44973 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44974 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44975 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44976 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44977 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44978 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$44979 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(4)) + F(4!)$$

$$45360 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45361 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45362 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45363 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45364 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45365 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45366 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45367 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45368 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45369 := F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times F(3 + 5) \times F(4)$$

$$45440 := F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!)$$

$$45441 := F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45442 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45443 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45444 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45445 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45446 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45447 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45448 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \\ 45449 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)!) \times (4 - 5!) + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45640 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 0 = 0 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45641 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 1 = 1 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45642 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 2 = 2 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45643 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 3 = 3 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45644 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 4 = 4 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45645 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 5 = 5 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45646 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 6 = 6 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45647 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 7 = 7 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45648 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 8 = 8 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \\ 45649 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 9 = 9 + F(4!) - 6! - 5 - F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45970 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 0 = 0 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45971 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 1 = 1 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45972 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 2 = 2 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45973 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 3 = 3 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45974 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 4 = 4 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45975 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 5 = 5 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45976 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 6 = 6 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45977 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 7 = 7 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45978 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 8 = 8 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \\ 45979 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 9 = 9 + 7! \times 9 + F(5 \times F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46200 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 0 = 0 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46201 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 1 = 1 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46202 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 2 = 2 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46203 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 3 = 3 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46204 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 4 = 4 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46205 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 5 = 5 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46206 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 6 = 6 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46207 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 7 = 7 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 46208 &:= F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 8 = 8 - F((0! + 2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$46209 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2+0)!) + 9 = 9 - F((0+2)!) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46250 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 0 = 0 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46251 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 1 = 1 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46252 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 2 = 2 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46253 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 3 = 3 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46254 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 4 = 4 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46255 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 5 = 5 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46256 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 6 = 6 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46257 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 7 = 7 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46258 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 8 = 8 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46259 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 9 = 9 - 5! + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46290 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 0 = 0 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46291 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 1 = 1 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46292 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 2 = 2 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46293 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 3 = 3 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46294 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 4 = 4 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46295 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 5 = 5 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46296 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 6 = 6 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46297 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 7 = 7 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46298 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 8 = 8 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46299 := F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2+9) + 9 = 9 - F(9-2) \times 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46400 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 00 = 0 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46401 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 01 = 1 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46402 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 02 = 2 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46403 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 03 = 3 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46404 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 04 = 4 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46405 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 05 = 5 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46406 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 06 = 6 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46407 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 07 = 7 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46408 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 08 = 8 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46409 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 09 = 9 + F(04!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46440 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 0 = 0 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46441 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 1 = 1 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46442 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 2 = 2 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46443 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 3 = 3 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46444 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 4 = 4 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46445 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 5 = 5 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46446 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 6 = 6 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46447 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 7 = 7 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46448 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 8 = 8 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46449 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 4! + 9 = 9 + 4! \times F(4) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46480 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 0 = 0 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46481 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 1 = 1 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46482 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 2 = 2 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46483 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 3 = 3 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46484 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 4 = 4 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46485 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 5 = 5 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46486 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 6 = 6 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46487 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 7 = 7 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46488 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 8 = 8 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46489 := (-F(4) + F(6))! + F(4!) - 8 + 9 = 9 - 8 + F(4!) + (F(6) - F(4))!$$

$$46560 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 0 = 0 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46561 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 1 = 1 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46562 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 2 = 2 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46563 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 3 = 3 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46564 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 4 = 4 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46565 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 5 = 5 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46566 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 6 = 6 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46567 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 7 = 7 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46568 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 8 = 8 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46569 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 9 = 9 - F(6)! + 5! \times (6! + 4)$$

$$46580 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 0 = 0 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46581 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 1 = 1 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46582 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 2 = 2 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46583 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 3 = 3 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46584 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 4 = 4 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46585 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 5 = 5 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46586 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 6 = 6 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46587 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 7 = 7 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46588 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 8 = 8 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46589 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 9 = 9 - F(8) + F(5 + F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46620 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 0 = 0 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46621 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 1 = 1 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46622 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 2 = 2 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46623 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 3 = 3 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46624 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 4 = 4 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46625 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 5 = 5 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46626 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 6 = 6 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46627 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 7 = 7 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46628 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 8 = 8 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46629 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 9 = 9 + 2 \times 6 \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46800 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 0 = 0 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46801 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 1 = 1 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46802 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 2 = 2 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46803 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 3 = 3 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46804 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 4 = 4 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46805 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 5 = 5 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46806 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 6 = 6 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46807 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 7 = 7 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46808 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 8 = 8 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46809 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 9 = 9 + (0! + 8 \times F(6)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$46810 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 0 = 0 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46811 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 1 = 1 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46812 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 2 = 2 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46813 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 3 = 3 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46814 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 4 = 4 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46815 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 5 = 5 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46816 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 6 = 6 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46817 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 7 = 7 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46818 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 8 = 8 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46819 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 9 = 9 + 1 + F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4!)$$

$$46880 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46881 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46882 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46883 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46884 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46885 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46886 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46887 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46888 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$46889 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 8 \times F(6) + F(4!)$$

$$47080 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 0 = 0 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47081 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 1 = 1 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47082 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 2 = 2 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47083 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 3 = 3 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47084 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 4 = 4 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47085 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 5 = 5 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47086 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 6 = 6 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47087 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 7 = 7 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47088 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 8 = 8 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47089 := F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 9 = 9 - 8 + (-0! + 7)! + F(4!)$$

$$47240 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 0$$

$$47241 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 1$$

$$47242 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$47243 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 3$$

$$47244 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 4$$

$$47245 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 5$$

$$47246 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 6$$

$$47247 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 7$$

$$47248 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 8$$

$$47249 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(2) - 7!) \times F(F(4)!) + 9$$

$$47300 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 0 = 0 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47301 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 1 = 1 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47302 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 2 = 2 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47303 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 3 = 3 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47304 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 4 = 4 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47305 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 5 = 5 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47306 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 6 = 6 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47307 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 7 = 7 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47308 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 8 = 8 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47309 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 9 = 9 + (0! + 3) \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47350 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 0 = 0 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47351 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 1 = 1 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47352 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 2 = 2 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47353 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 3 = 3 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47354 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 4 = 4 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47355 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 5 = 5 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47356 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 6 = 6 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47357 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 7 = 7 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47358 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 8 = 8 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47359 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 9 = 9 - 5 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47440 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47441 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47442 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47443 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47444 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47445 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47446 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47447 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47448 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47449 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 4! - 7!) \times F(F(4)!$$

$$47460 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47461 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47462 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47463 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47464 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47465 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47466 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47467 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47468 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47469 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(6)) \times 4 \times F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47520 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47521 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47522 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47523 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47524 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47525 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47526 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47527 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47528 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$47529 := F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (F(2) + 5 \times F(7)) \times F(4)!!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47640 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 0 = 0 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47641 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 1 = 1 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47642 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 2 = 2 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47643 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 3 = 3 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47644 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 4 = 4 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47645 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 5 = 5 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47646 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 6 = 6 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47647 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 7 = 7 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47648 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 8 = 8 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\ 47649 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 9 = 9 + F(4!) - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47960 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47961 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47962 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47963 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47964 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47965 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47966 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47967 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47968 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \\ 47969 &:= F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48360 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48361 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48362 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48363 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48364 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48365 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48366 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48367 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48368 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \\ 48369 &:= (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times (-3 - 8! + F(4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48630 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 0 = 0 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48631 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 1 = 1 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48632 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 2 = 2 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48633 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 3 = 3 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48634 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 4 = 4 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48635 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 5 = 5 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \\ 48636 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 6 = 6 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$48637 := F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 7 = 7 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!)$$

$$48638 := F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 8 = 8 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!)$$

$$48639 := F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 9 = 9 + 3! \times F(6 + 8) + F(4!)$$

$$48790 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 0 = 0 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48791 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 1 = 1 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48792 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 2 = 2 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48793 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 3 = 3 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48794 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 4 = 4 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48795 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 5 = 5 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48796 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 6 = 6 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48797 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 7 = 7 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48798 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 8 = 8 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$48799 := 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 9 = 9 - F(9) + 7! + F(F(8)) \times 4$$

$$52680 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 0 = 0 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52681 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 1 = 1 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52682 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 2 = 2 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52683 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 3 = 3 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52684 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 4 = 4 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52685 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 5 = 5 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52686 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 6 = 6 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52687 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 7 = 7 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52688 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 8 = 8 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$52689 := 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 9 = 9 + (F(8) \times F(F(6)) - 2) \times 5!$$

$$53160 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53161 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53162 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53163 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53164 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53165 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53166 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53167 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53168 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53169 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 5!$$

$$53530 := 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 0 = 0 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5$$

$$53531 := 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 1 = 1 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5$$

$$53532 := 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 2 = 2 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}53533 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 3 = 3 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53534 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 4 = 4 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53535 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 5 = 5 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53536 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 6 = 6 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53537 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 7 = 7 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53538 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 8 = 8 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\53539 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 9 = 9 - (F(3) \times 5! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53670 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 0 = 0 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53671 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 1 = 1 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53672 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 2 = 2 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53673 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 3 = 3 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53674 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 4 = 4 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53675 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 5 = 5 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53676 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 6 = 6 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53677 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 7 = 7 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53678 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 8 = 8 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\53679 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 9 = 9 - (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53760 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53761 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53762 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53763 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53764 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53765 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53766 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53767 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53768 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5! \\53769 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times 7 \times F(3!) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54080 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54081 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54082 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54083 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54084 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54085 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54086 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54087 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54088 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5) \\54089 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4!))) - 0!)) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (F(-0! + F(F(F(4!)))) - 5)\end{aligned}$$

$$54120 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 0 = 0 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54121 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 1 = 1 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54122 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 2 = 2 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54123 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 3 = 3 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54124 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 4 = 4 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54125 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 5 = 5 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54126 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 6 = 6 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54127 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 7 = 7 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54128 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 8 = 8 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54129 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1+2)!) + 9 = 9 + F((2+1)!) \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54130 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54131 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54132 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54133 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54134 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54135 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54136 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54137 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54138 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54139 := 5 \times (-(4+1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(3!))) - (1+4)!) \times 5$$

$$54160 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 0 = 0 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54161 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 1 = 1 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54162 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 2 = 2 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54163 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 3 = 3 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54164 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 4 = 4 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54165 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 5 = 5 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54166 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 6 = 6 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54167 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 7 = 7 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54168 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 8 = 8 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54169 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 9 = 9 + F(6) \times (F(-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5)$$

$$54240 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54241 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54242 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54243 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54244 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54245 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54246 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54247 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54248 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54249 := 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)!) \times F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!$$

$$54390 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54391 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54392 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54393 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54394 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54395 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54396 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54397 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54398 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54399 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(9) \times F(3) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54470 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54471 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54472 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54473 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54474 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54475 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54476 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54477 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54478 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54479 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(7) \times 4 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54610 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54611 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54612 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54613 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54614 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54615 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54616 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54617 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54618 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54619 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54620 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 0 = 0 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54621 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 1 = 1 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54622 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 2 = 2 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54623 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 3 = 3 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54624 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 4 = 4 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54625 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 5 = 5 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54626 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 6 = 6 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54627 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 7 = 7 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54628 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 8 = 8 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54629 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 9 = 9 + (2 + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) \times 5$$

$$54630 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 0 = 0 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54631 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 1 = 1 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54632 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 2 = 2 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54633 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 3 = 3 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54634 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 4 = 4 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54635 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 5 = 5 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54636 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 6 = 6 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54637 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 7 = 7 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54638 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 8 = 8 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54639 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 9 = 9 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54640 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 0 = 0 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54641 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 1 = 1 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54642 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 2 = 2 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54643 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 3 = 3 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54644 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 4 = 4 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54645 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 5 = 5 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54646 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 6 = 6 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54647 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 7 = 7 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54648 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 8 = 8 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54649 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 9 = 9 + (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54650 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 0 = 0 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54651 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 1 = 1 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54652 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 2 = 2 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54653 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 3 = 3 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54654 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 4 = 4 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54655 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 5 = 5 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54656 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 6 = 6 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54657 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 7 = 7 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54658 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 8 = 8 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54659 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 9 = 9 - 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54660 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54661 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54662 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54663 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54664 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54665 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54666 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54667 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54668 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54669 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) - F(6) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54700 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54701 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54702 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54703 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54704 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54705 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54706 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54707 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54708 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54709 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(0! + 7)) - F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$54770 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54771 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54772 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54773 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54774 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54775 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54776 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54777 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54778 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54779 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$54830 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54831 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54832 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54833 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54834 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54835 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54836 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54837 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54838 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54839 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$54840 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 0 = 0 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54841 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 1 = 1 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54842 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 2 = 2 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54843 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 3 = 3 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54844 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 4 = 4 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54845 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 5 = 5 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54846 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 6 = 6 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54847 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 7 = 7 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54848 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 8 = 8 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54849 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 9 = 9 + (4! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$54850 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54851 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54852 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54853 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54854 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54855 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54856 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54857 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54858 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54859 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times F(F(8)) + 4! \times 5$$

$$54870 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 0 = 0 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54871 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 1 = 1 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54872 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 2 = 2 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54873 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 3 = 3 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54874 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 4 = 4 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54875 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 5 = 5 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54876 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 6 = 6 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54877 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 7 = 7 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54878 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 8 = 8 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54879 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 9 = 9 + (7 + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5$$

$$54900 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 00 = 0 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54901 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 01 = 1 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54902 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 02 = 2 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54903 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 03 = 3 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54904 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 04 = 4 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54905 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 05 = 5 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54906 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 06 = 6 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54907 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 07 = 7 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54908 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 08 = 8 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \\ 54909 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 09 = 9 + (F(09) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54930 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54931 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54932 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54933 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54934 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54935 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54936 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54937 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54938 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \\ 54939 &:= 5 \times (F(4)! + F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) + F(4!)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54940 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54941 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54942 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54943 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54944 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54945 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54946 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54947 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54948 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 54949 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55320 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 0 = 0 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55321 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 1 = 1 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55322 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 2 = 2 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55323 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 3 = 3 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55324 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 4 = 4 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55325 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 5 = 5 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55326 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 6 = 6 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \\ 55327 &:= 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 7 = 7 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$55328 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 8 = 8 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55329 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 9 = 9 + (-2 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55330 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55331 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55332 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55333 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55334 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55335 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55336 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55337 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55338 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55339 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(3 + 3))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55340 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55341 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55342 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55343 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55344 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55345 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55346 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55347 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55348 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55349 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(4)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55360 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55361 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55362 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55363 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55364 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55365 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55366 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55367 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55368 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55369 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + 3! + 5!) \times 5$$

$$55440 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)!) + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55441 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)!) + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55442 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)!) + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55443 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)!) + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55444 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55445 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55446 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55447 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55448 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55449 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)!)! + (F(4)! + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55450 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 0 = 0 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55451 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 1 = 1 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55452 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 2 = 2 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55453 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 3 = 3 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55454 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 4 = 4 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55455 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 5 = 5 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55456 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 6 = 6 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55457 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 7 = 7 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55458 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 8 = 8 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55459 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 9 = 9 + (5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5 + 5!$$

$$55680 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55681 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55682 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55683 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55684 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55685 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55686 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55687 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55688 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55689 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! + (F(6) + 5!) \times 5!$$

$$55920 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55921 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55922 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55923 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55924 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55925 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55926 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55927 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55928 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$55929 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(-2 + 9)) \times (5! + 5!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}56530 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 0 = 0 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56531 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 1 = 1 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56532 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 2 = 2 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56533 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 3 = 3 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56534 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 4 = 4 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56535 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 5 = 5 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56536 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 6 = 6 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56537 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 7 = 7 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56538 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 8 = 8 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\56539 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 9 = 9 + (3 \times 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57480 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 0 = 0 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57481 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 1 = 1 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57482 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 2 = 2 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57483 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 3 = 3 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57484 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 4 = 4 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57485 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 5 = 5 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57486 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 6 = 6 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57487 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 7 = 7 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57488 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 8 = 8 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57489 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 9 = 9 + (-8 + F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57840 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57841 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57842 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57843 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57844 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57845 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57846 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57847 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57848 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5! \\57849 &:= 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)) \times (8 + F(F(7))) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}58320 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 0 = 0 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58321 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 1 = 1 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58322 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 2 = 2 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58323 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 3 = 3 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58324 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 4 = 4 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58325 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 5 = 5 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\58326 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 6 = 6 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$58327 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 7 = 7 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58328 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 8 = 8 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58329 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 9 = 9 + (-2 + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58330 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 0 = 0 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58331 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 1 = 1 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58332 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 2 = 2 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58333 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 3 = 3 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58334 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 4 = 4 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58335 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 5 = 5 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58336 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 6 = 6 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58337 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 7 = 7 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58338 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 8 = 8 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58339 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 9 = 9 + ((3 + 3)! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58340 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58341 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58342 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58343 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58344 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58345 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58346 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58347 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58348 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58349 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(4)) + 3!! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58360 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 0 = 0 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58361 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 1 = 1 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58362 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 2 = 2 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58363 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 3 = 3 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58364 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 4 = 4 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58365 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 5 = 5 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58366 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 6 = 6 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58367 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 7 = 7 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58368 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 8 = 8 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58369 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 9 = 9 + (6! + 3! + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$58440 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) + 0 = 0 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5!$$

$$58441 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) + 1 = 1 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5!$$

$$58442 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) + 2 = 2 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58443 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58444 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58445 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58446 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58447 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58448 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \\ 58449 &:= 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + (F(4)!! - F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8))) \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58450 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 0 = 0 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58451 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 1 = 1 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58452 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 2 = 2 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58453 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 3 = 3 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58454 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 4 = 4 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58455 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 5 = 5 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58456 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 6 = 6 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58457 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 7 = 7 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58458 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 8 = 8 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 58459 &:= 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 9 = 9 + 5! + (F(4)!! + F(F(8))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59770 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 0 = 0 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59771 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 1 = 1 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59772 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 2 = 2 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59773 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 3 = 3 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59774 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 4 = 4 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59775 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 5 = 5 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59776 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 6 = 6 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59777 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 7 = 7 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59778 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 8 = 8 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59779 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 9 = 9 + 7! + (F(-F(7) + F(9))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 60480 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 0 = 0 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60481 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 1 = 1 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60482 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 2 = 2 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60483 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 3 = 3 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60484 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 4 = 4 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60485 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 5 = 5 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60486 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 6 = 6 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60487 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 7 = 7 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60488 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 8 = 8 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \\ 60489 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 9 = 9 + F(8) \times 4 \times 06! \end{aligned}$$

$$62640 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62641 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62642 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62643 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62644 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62645 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62646 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62647 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62648 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$62649 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(4) + F(6)) - 2) \times 6!$$

$$63360 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63361 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63362 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63363 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63364 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63365 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63366 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63367 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63368 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$63369 := (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times F(3!) \times (3 + F(6))$$

$$64080 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 0 = 0 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64081 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 1 = 1 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64082 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 2 = 2 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64083 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 3 = 3 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64084 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 4 = 4 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64085 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 5 = 5 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64086 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 6 = 6 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64087 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 7 = 7 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64088 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 8 = 8 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64089 := 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 9 = 9 + F(8 + F(04)) \times 6!$$

$$64800 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 0 = 0 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64801 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 1 = 1 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64802 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 2 = 2 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64803 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 3 = 3 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64804 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 4 = 4 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64805 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 5 = 5 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64806 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 6 = 6 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64807 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 7 = 7 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64808 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 8 = 8 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64809 := 6! \times (F(F(4) + 8) + 0!) + 9 = 9 + (0! + F(8 + F(4))) \times 6!$$

$$64830 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 0 = 0 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64831 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 1 = 1 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64832 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 2 = 2 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64833 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 3 = 3 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64834 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 4 = 4 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64835 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 5 = 5 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64836 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 6 = 6 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64837 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 7 = 7 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64838 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 8 = 8 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$64839 := -6! - F(4)! \times (-F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 9 = 9 - (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)! - 6!$$

$$65520 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 0 = 0 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65521 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 1 = 1 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65522 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 2 = 2 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65523 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 3 = 3 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65524 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 4 = 4 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65525 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 5 = 5 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65526 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 6 = 6 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65527 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 7 = 7 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65528 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 8 = 8 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65529 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 9 = 9 + (2 + 5)! \times (5 + F(6))$$

$$65760 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 0 = 0 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65761 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 1 = 1 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65762 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 2 = 2 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65763 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 3 = 3 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65764 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 4 = 4 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65765 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 5 = 5 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65766 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 6 = 6 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65767 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 7 = 7 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65768 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 8 = 8 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$65769 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 9 = 9 - (F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times 5! + F(6)!$$

$$66360 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6!$$

$$66361 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66362 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66363 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66364 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66365 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66366 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66367 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66368 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \\ 66369 &:= 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 6 + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66390 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 0 = 0 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66391 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 1 = 1 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66392 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 2 = 2 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66393 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 3 = 3 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66394 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 4 = 4 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66395 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 5 = 5 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66396 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 6 = 6 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66397 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 7 = 7 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66398 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 8 = 8 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \\ 66399 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 9 = 9 + F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66540 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 0 = 0 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66541 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 1 = 1 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66542 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 2 = 2 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66543 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 3 = 3 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66544 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 4 = 4 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66545 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 5 = 5 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66546 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 6 = 6 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66547 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 7 = 7 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66548 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 8 = 8 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\ 66549 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 9 = 9 + (4! + 5! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66960 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66961 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66962 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66963 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66964 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66965 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66966 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66967 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \\ 66968 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$66969 := 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(6)) + 9 \times F(6)) \times 6!$$

$$67080 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67081 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67082 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67083 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67084 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67085 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67086 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67087 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67088 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67089 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) + 0! + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$67560 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 0 = 0 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67561 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 1 = 1 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67562 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 2 = 2 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67563 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 3 = 3 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67564 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 4 = 4 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67565 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 5 = 5 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67566 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 6 = 6 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67567 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 7 = 7 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67568 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 8 = 8 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$67569 := F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 9 = 9 - 6! + 5! \times F(F(7)) + F(6)!$$

$$68260 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 0 = 0 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68261 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 1 = 1 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68262 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 2 = 2 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68263 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 3 = 3 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68264 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 4 = 4 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68265 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 5 = 5 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68266 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 6 = 6 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68267 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 7 = 7 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68268 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 8 = 8 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$68269 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2+6)!) + 9 = 9 + F((6-2)!) + F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$69140 := F(F(F(6))) \times (9+1) - F(F(4)!) + 0 = 0 - F(F(4)!) + (1+9) \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$69141 := F(F(F(6))) \times (9+1) - F(F(4)!) + 1 = 1 - F(F(4)!) + (1+9) \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$69142 := F(F(F(6))) \times (9+1) - F(F(4)!) + 2 = 2 - F(F(4)!) + (1+9) \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$69143 := F(F(F(6))) \times (9+1) - F(F(4)!) + 3 = 3 - F(F(4)!) + (1+9) \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$69144 := F(F(F(6))) \times (9+1) - F(F(4)!) + 4 = 4 - F(F(4)!) + (1+9) \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}69145 &:= F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + 1) - F(F(4)!) + 5 = 5 - F(F(4)!) + (1 + 9) \times F(F(F(6))) \\69146 &:= F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + 1) - F(F(4)!) + 6 = 6 - F(F(4)!) + (1 + 9) \times F(F(F(6))) \\69147 &:= F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + 1) - F(F(4)!) + 7 = 7 - F(F(4)!) + (1 + 9) \times F(F(F(6))) \\69148 &:= F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + 1) - F(F(4)!) + 8 = 8 - F(F(4)!) + (1 + 9) \times F(F(F(6))) \\69149 &:= F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + 1) - F(F(4)!) + 9 = 9 - F(F(4)!) + (1 + 9) \times F(F(F(6)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69540 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 0 = 0 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69541 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 1 = 1 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69542 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 2 = 2 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69543 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 3 = 3 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69544 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 4 = 4 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69545 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 5 = 5 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69546 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 6 = 6 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69547 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 7 = 7 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69548 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 8 = 8 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6) \\69549 &:= F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 9 = 9 - (F(4)! - 5!) \times F(9 + 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69660 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 0 = 0 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69661 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 1 = 1 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69662 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 2 = 2 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69663 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 3 = 3 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69664 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 4 = 4 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69665 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 5 = 5 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69666 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 6 = 6 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69667 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 7 = 7 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69668 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 8 = 8 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! \\69669 &:= F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 9 = 9 - F(F(F(6))) + F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69840 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 0 = 0 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69841 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 1 = 1 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69842 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 2 = 2 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69843 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 3 = 3 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69844 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 4 = 4 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69845 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 5 = 5 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69846 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 6 = 6 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69847 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 7 = 7 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69848 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 8 = 8 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6! \\69849 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 9 = 9 + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$70560 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 0 = 0 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70561 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 1 = 1 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70562 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 2 = 2 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70563 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 3 = 3 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70564 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 4 = 4 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70565 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 5 = 5 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70566 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 6 = 6 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70567 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 7 = 7 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70568 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 8 = 8 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70569 := 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 9 = 9 + (F(6) + 5 + 0!) \times 7!$$

$$70830 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 0 = 0 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70831 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 1 = 1 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70832 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 2 = 2 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70833 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 3 = 3 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70834 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 4 = 4 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70835 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 5 = 5 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70836 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 6 = 6 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70837 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 7 = 7 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70838 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 8 = 8 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$70839 := (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 9 = 9 + 3! \times (F(F(8) - 0!) + 7!)$$

$$73440 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 0 = 0 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73441 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 1 = 1 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73442 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 2 = 2 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73443 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 3 = 3 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73444 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 4 = 4 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73445 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 5 = 5 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73446 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 6 = 6 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73447 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 7 = 7 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73448 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 8 = 8 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$73449 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 9 = 9 + F(4)! \times (4! \times 3!! - 7!)$$

$$75480 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75481 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75482 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75483 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75484 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75485 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75486 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75487 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75488 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75489 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! \times F(F(4)) - 5! - 7!$$

$$75600 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 0 = 0 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75601 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 1 = 1 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75602 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 2 = 2 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75603 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 3 = 3 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75604 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 4 = 4 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75605 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 5 = 5 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75606 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 6 = 6 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75607 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 7 = 7 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75608 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 8 = 8 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75609 := 7! \times (-5 + F(F(6)) - 0!) + 9 = 9 + (-0! + F(F(6)) - 5) \times 7!$$

$$75840 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75841 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75842 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75843 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75844 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75845 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75846 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75847 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75848 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$75849 := -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4)) \times (8! + 5!) - 7!$$

$$76320 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 0 = 0 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76321 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 1 = 1 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76322 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 2 = 2 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76323 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 3 = 3 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76324 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 4 = 4 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76325 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 5 = 5 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76326 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 6 = 6 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76327 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 7 = 7 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76328 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 8 = 8 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76329 := -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 9 = 9 + 2 \times F(3)! + 6! - 7!$$

$$76440 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 0 = 0 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76441 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 1 = 1 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76442 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 2 = 2 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76443 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 3 = 3 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76444 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 4 = 4 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$\begin{aligned}76445 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 5 = 5 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76446 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 6 = 6 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76447 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 7 = 7 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76448 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 8 = 8 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76449 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 9 = 9 + (-4! - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76580 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76581 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76582 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76583 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76584 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76585 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76586 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76587 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76588 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7 \\76589 &:= 7 \times (-(F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76630 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 0 = 0 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76631 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 1 = 1 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76632 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 2 = 2 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76633 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 3 = 3 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76634 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 4 = 4 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76635 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 5 = 5 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76636 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 6 = 6 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76637 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 7 = 7 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76638 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 8 = 8 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7)) \\76639 &:= (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 9 = 9 + F(3!) + F(F(F(6))) \times (-6 + F(7))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76790 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 0 = 0 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76791 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 1 = 1 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76792 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 2 = 2 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76793 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 3 = 3 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76794 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 4 = 4 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76795 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 5 = 5 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76796 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 6 = 6 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76797 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 7 = 7 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76798 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 8 = 8 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\76799 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 9 = 9 + ((-9 + F(7))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7\end{aligned}$$

$$78340 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 0 = 0 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78341 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 1 = 1 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78342 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 2 = 2 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78343 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 3 = 3 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78344 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 4 = 4 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78345 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 5 = 5 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78346 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 6 = 6 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78347 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 7 = 7 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78348 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 8 = 8 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$78349 := (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 9 = 9 + F(4!) + F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + 7!)$$

$$80630 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 0 = 0 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80631 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 1 = 1 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80632 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 2 = 2 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80633 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 3 = 3 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80634 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 4 = 4 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80635 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 5 = 5 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80636 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 6 = 6 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80637 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 7 = 7 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80638 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 8 = 8 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$80639 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 9 = 9 - F(3) \times (6 - 0! - 8!)$$

$$81360 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81361 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81362 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81363 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81364 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81365 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81366 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81367 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81368 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$81369 := 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! + F(3 \times 1) \times 8!$$

$$84960 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84961 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84962 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84963 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84964 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84965 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84966 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84967 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84968 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$84969 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times (F(9) + 4 \times F(8))$$

$$85440 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85441 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85442 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85443 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85444 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85445 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85446 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85447 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85448 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$85449 := 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5! \times 8$$

$$86640 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 0 = 0 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86641 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 1 = 1 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86642 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 2 = 2 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86643 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 3 = 3 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86644 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 4 = 4 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86645 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 5 = 5 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86646 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 6 = 6 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86647 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 7 = 7 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86648 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 8 = 8 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86649 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 9 = 9 + F(4!) - F(6) \times 6 + 8!$$

$$86840 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 0 = 0 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86841 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 1 = 1 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86842 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 2 = 2 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86843 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 3 = 3 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86844 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 4 = 4 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86845 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 5 = 5 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86846 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 6 = 6 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86847 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 7 = 7 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86848 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 8 = 8 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86849 := -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 9 = 9 - F(4)!! + F(F(8)) \times F(6) - 8$$

$$86940 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 0 = 0 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86941 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 1 = 1 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86942 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 2 = 2 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86943 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 3 = 3 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86944 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 4 = 4 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86945 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 5 = 5 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86946 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 6 = 6 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86947 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 7 = 7 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86948 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 8 = 8 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$86949 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 9 = 9 + F(4!) \times (9 + 6)/8$$

$$87360 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 0 = 0 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87361 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 1 = 1 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87362 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 2 = 2 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87363 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 3 = 3 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87364 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 4 = 4 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87365 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 5 = 5 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87366 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 6 = 6 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87367 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 7 = 7 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87368 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 8 = 8 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$87369 := (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 9 = 9 + (6! + F(3!)) \times (F(7) - 8)!$$

$$88520 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 0 = 0 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88521 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 1 = 1 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88522 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 2 = 2 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88523 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 3 = 3 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88524 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 4 = 4 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88525 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 5 = 5 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88526 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 6 = 6 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88527 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 7 = 7 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88528 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 8 = 8 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$88529 := 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 9 = 9 + (-F(2) + 5! + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$90440 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90441 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90442 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90443 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90444 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90445 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90446 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90447 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90448 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$90449 := (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9))$$

$$93330 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 0 = 0 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93331 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 1 = 1 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93332 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 2 = 2 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93333 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 3 = 3 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93334 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 4 = 4 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93335 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 5 = 5 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93336 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 6 = 6 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93337 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 7 = 7 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93338 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 8 = 8 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$93339 := (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 9 = 9 + F(3) \times (3!^{3!} + 9)$$

$$96480 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96481 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96482 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96483 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96484 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96485 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96486 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96487 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96488 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$96489 := -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! \times F(4) - 6! \times F(9)$$

$$98640 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 0 = 0 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98641 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 1 = 1 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98642 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 2 = 2 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98643 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 3 = 3 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98644 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 4 = 4 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98645 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 5 = 5 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98646 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 6 = 6 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98647 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 7 = 7 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98648 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 8 = 8 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98649 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 9 = 9 + (F(4)! + F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98730 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 0 = 0 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98731 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 1 = 1 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98732 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 2 = 2 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98733 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 3 = 3 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98734 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 4 = 4 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98735 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 5 = 5 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98736 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 6 = 6 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98737 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 7 = 7 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98738 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 8 = 8 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98739 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 9 = 9 + ((-3 + 7)! + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99560 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99561 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99562 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99563 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99564 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99565 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99566 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99567 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99568 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \\ 99569 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!) \times 9 - F(9) \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Symmetric Representations in Digit's Order

Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order:

3.2.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned} 15250 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 0 & 16428 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 8 \\ 15251 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 1 & 16429 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 9 \\ 15252 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 2 & & \\ 15253 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 3 & 26470 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 0 \\ 15254 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 4 & 26471 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 1 \\ 15255 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 5 & 26472 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 2 \\ 15256 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 6 & 26473 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 3 \\ 15257 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 7 & 26474 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 4 \\ 15258 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 8 & 26475 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 5 \\ 15259 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 9 & 26476 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 6 \\ & & 26477 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 7 \\ 16420 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 0 & 26478 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 8 \\ 16421 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 1 & 26479 &:= F(2 + F(F(6))) - F(4)^7 + 9 \\ 16422 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 2 & & \\ 16423 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 3 & & \\ 16424 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 4 & 27450 &:= F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 0 \\ 16425 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 5 & 27451 &:= F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 1 \\ 16426 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 6 & 27452 &:= F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 2 \\ 16427 &:= 1 + F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)/2 + 7 & 27453 &:= F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$27454 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 4$$

$$27455 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 5$$

$$27456 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 6$$

$$27457 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 7$$

$$27458 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 8$$

$$27459 := F(2 + F(7)) \times 45 + 9$$

$$28730 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 0$$

$$28731 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 1$$

$$28732 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 2$$

$$28733 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 3$$

$$28734 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 4$$

$$28735 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 5$$

$$28736 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 6$$

$$28737 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 7$$

$$28738 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 8$$

$$28739 := F(2 + F(8)) + 73 + 9$$

$$32760 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 0$$

$$32761 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 1$$

$$32762 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 2$$

$$32763 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 3$$

$$32764 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 4$$

$$32765 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 5$$

$$32766 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 6$$

$$32767 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 7$$

$$32768 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 8$$

$$32769 := F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(6) + 9$$

$$43460 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$43461 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$43462 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$43463 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$43464 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$43465 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$43466 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$43467 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$43468 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$43469 := 4 \times (-3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$45750 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 0$$

$$45751 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 1$$

$$45752 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 2$$

$$45753 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 3$$

$$45754 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 4$$

$$45755 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 5$$

$$45756 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 6$$

$$45757 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 7$$

$$45758 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 8$$

$$45759 := F(F(4) \times 5) \times 75 + 9$$

$$54900 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 0$$

$$54901 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 1$$

$$54902 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 2$$

$$54903 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 3$$

$$54904 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 4$$

$$54905 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 5$$

$$54906 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 6$$

$$54907 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 7$$

$$54908 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 8$$

$$54909 := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 90 + 9$$

$$59320 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 0$$

$$59321 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 1$$

$$59322 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 2$$

$$59323 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 3$$

$$59324 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 4$$

$$59325 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 5$$

$$59326 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 6$$

$$59327 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 7$$

$$59328 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 8$$

$$59329 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(2) + 9$$

$$86920 := 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 0$$

$$86921 := 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 1$$

$$86922 := 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 2$$

$$86923 := 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86924 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 4 \\ 86925 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 5 \\ 86926 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 6 \\ 86927 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 7 \\ 86928 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 8 \\ 86929 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9^2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 109370 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 0 \\ 109371 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 1 \\ 109372 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 2 \\ 109373 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 3 \\ 109374 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 4 \\ 109375 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 5 \\ 109376 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 6 \\ 109377 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 7 \\ 109378 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 8 \\ 109379 &:= 10 \times (-9 + F(3 \times 7)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 142130 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 0 \\ 142131 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 1 \\ 142132 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 2 \\ 142133 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 3 \\ 142134 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 4 \\ 142135 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 5 \\ 142136 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 6 \\ 142137 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 7 \\ 142138 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 8 \\ 142139 &:= F(14)^2 + 1^3 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 152500 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 0 \\ 152501 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 1 \\ 152502 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 2 \\ 152503 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 3 \\ 152504 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 4 \\ 152505 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 5 \\ 152506 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 6 \\ 152507 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 7 \\ 152508 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 8 \\ 152509 &:= F(15) \times 250 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 156260 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 0 \\ 156261 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 1 \\ 156262 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 2 \\ 156263 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 3 \\ 156264 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 4 \\ 156265 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 5 \\ 156266 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 6 \\ 156267 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 7 \\ 156268 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 8 \\ 156269 &:= (1 + 5^6) \times (2 + F(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 163850 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 0 \\ 163851 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 1 \\ 163852 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 2 \\ 163853 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 3 \\ 163854 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 4 \\ 163855 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 5 \\ 163856 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 6 \\ 163857 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 7 \\ 163858 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 8 \\ 163859 &:= (-1 + 6) \times (F(3) + 8^5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168920 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 0 \\ 168921 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 1 \\ 168922 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 2 \\ 168923 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 3 \\ 168924 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 4 \\ 168925 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 5 \\ 168926 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 6 \\ 168927 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 7 \\ 168928 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 8 \\ 168929 &:= -1 + (F(6 + 8) + F(9))^2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 175630 &:= 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 0 \\ 175631 &:= 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 1 \\ 175632 &:= 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$175633 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 3$$

$$175634 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 4$$

$$175635 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 5$$

$$175636 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 6$$

$$175637 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 7$$

$$175638 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 8$$

$$175639 := 1 + F(7) + 56^3 + 9$$

$$194470 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 0$$

$$194471 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 1$$

$$194472 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 2$$

$$194473 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 3$$

$$194474 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 4$$

$$194475 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 5$$

$$194476 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 6$$

$$194477 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 7$$

$$194478 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 8$$

$$194479 := F(-1 + 9)^4 - 4 - 7 + 9$$

$$196560 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 0$$

$$196561 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 1$$

$$196562 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 2$$

$$196563 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 3$$

$$196564 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 4$$

$$196565 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 5$$

$$196566 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 6$$

$$196567 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 7$$

$$196568 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 8$$

$$196569 := (1 - 9 + F(6)^5) \times 6 + 9$$

$$196830 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 0$$

$$196831 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 1$$

$$196832 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 2$$

$$196833 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 3$$

$$196834 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$196835 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 5$$

$$196836 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 6$$

$$196837 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 7$$

$$196838 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 8$$

$$196839 := (1 + 9) \times (6 + F(8))^3 + 9$$

$$202950 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 0$$

$$202951 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 1$$

$$202952 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 2$$

$$202953 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 3$$

$$202954 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 4$$

$$202955 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 5$$

$$202956 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 6$$

$$202957 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 7$$

$$202958 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 8$$

$$202959 := F(20) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - 5 + 9$$

$$231840 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 0$$

$$231841 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 1$$

$$231842 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 2$$

$$231843 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 3$$

$$231844 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 4$$

$$231845 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 5$$

$$231846 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 6$$

$$231847 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 7$$

$$231848 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 8$$

$$231849 := F(23 + 1) \times (8 - F(4)) + 9$$

$$233490 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 0$$

$$233491 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 1$$

$$233492 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 2$$

$$233493 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 3$$

$$233494 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 4$$

$$233495 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 5$$

$$233496 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 6$$

$$233497 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 7$$

$$233498 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 8$$

$$233499 := -F(23) + 3 + 4^9 + 9$$

$$278290 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 0$$

$$278291 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 1$$

$$278292 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 2$$

$$278293 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$278294 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$278295 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$278296 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$278297 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$278298 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$278299 := (2^{F(7)} - 8 + F(2)) \times F(9) + 9$$

$$238330 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 0$$

$$238331 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 1$$

$$238332 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 2$$

$$238333 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 3$$

$$238334 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 4$$

$$238335 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 5$$

$$238336 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 6$$

$$238337 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 7$$

$$238338 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 8$$

$$238339 := (-F(2) + 3 \times F(8))^3 + F(3) + 9$$

$$279840 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 0$$

$$279841 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 1$$

$$279842 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 2$$

$$279843 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 3$$

$$279844 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 4$$

$$279845 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 5$$

$$279846 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 6$$

$$279847 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 7$$

$$279848 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 8$$

$$279849 := -F(2) + (-7 + 9 + F(8))^4 + 9$$

$$279990 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 0$$

$$279991 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 1$$

$$279992 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 2$$

$$279993 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$279994 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$279995 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$279996 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$279997 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$279998 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$279999 := (2^{F(7)} + 9 + F(9)) \times F(9) + 9$$

$$295240 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 0$$

$$295241 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 1$$

$$295242 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 2$$

$$295243 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 3$$

$$295244 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 4$$

$$295245 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 5$$

$$295246 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 6$$

$$295247 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 7$$

$$295248 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 8$$

$$295249 := (-F(2) + 9^5) \times (2 + F(4)) + 9$$

$$295250 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 0$$

$$295251 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 1$$

$$295252 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 2$$

$$295253 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 3$$

$$295254 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 4$$

$$295255 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 5$$

$$295256 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 6$$

$$295257 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 7$$

$$295258 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 8$$

$$295259 := (-F(2) + 9^5 + 2) \times 5 + 9$$

$$327560 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 0$$

$$327561 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 1$$

$$327562 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 2$$

$$327563 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 3$$

$$327564 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 4$$

$$327565 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 5$$

$$327566 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 6$$

$$327567 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 7$$

$$327568 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 8$$

$$327569 := (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 5 \times F(6) + 9$$

$$365470 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 0$$

$$365471 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 1$$

$$365472 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 2$$

$$365473 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 3$$

$$365474 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 4$$

$$365475 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 5$$

$$365476 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 6$$

$$365477 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 7$$

$$365478 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 8$$

$$365479 := -F(3) + 6^5 \times 47 + 9$$

$$372190 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 0$$

$$372191 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 1$$

$$372192 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 2$$

$$372193 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$372194 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$372195 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$372196 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$372197 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$372198 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$372199 := F(3) \times F(7) + F(21) \times F(9) + 9$$

$$372370 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 0$$

$$372371 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 1$$

$$372372 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 2$$

$$372373 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 3$$

$$372374 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 4$$

$$372375 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 5$$

$$372376 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 6$$

$$372377 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 7$$

$$372378 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 8$$

$$372379 := -F(3) + (-F(7) + F(23)) \times F(7) + 9$$

$$392760 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 0$$

$$392761 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 1$$

$$392762 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 2$$

$$392763 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 3$$

$$392764 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 4$$

$$392765 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 5$$

$$392766 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 6$$

$$392767 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 7$$

$$392768 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 8$$

$$392769 := F(3 \times 9) \times 2 - 76 + 9$$

$$393660 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 0$$

$$393661 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 1$$

$$393662 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 2$$

$$393663 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 3$$

$$393664 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 4$$

$$393665 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 5$$

$$393666 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 6$$

$$393667 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 7$$

$$393668 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 8$$

$$393669 := 3^9 \times (F(3) \times 6 + F(6)) + 9$$

$$416020 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 0$$

$$416021 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 1$$

$$416022 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 2$$

$$416023 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 3$$

$$416024 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 4$$

$$416025 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 5$$

$$416026 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 6$$

$$416027 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 7$$

$$416028 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 8$$

$$416029 := F((4 + 1) \times 6) / 02 + 9$$

$$470680 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 0$$

$$470681 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 1$$

$$470682 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 2$$

$$470683 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 3$$

$$470684 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 4$$

$$470685 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 5$$

$$470686 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 6$$

$$470687 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 7$$

$$470688 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 8$$

$$470689 := 4 \times (7^{06} + F(8)) + 9$$

$$524880 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 0$$

$$524881 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 1$$

$$524882 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 2$$

$$524883 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 3$$

$$524884 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 4$$

$$524885 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 5$$

$$524886 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 6$$

$$524887 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 7$$

$$524888 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 8$$

$$524889 := 5 \times 2 \times F(4)^8 \times 8 + 9$$

$$557370 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 0$$

$$557371 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 1$$

$$557372 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 2$$

$$557373 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 3$$

$$557374 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 4$$

$$557375 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 5$$

$$557376 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 6$$

$$557377 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 7$$

$$557378 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 8$$

$$557379 := -5 + (5 \times 7)^3 \times F(7) + 9$$

$$589440 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 0$$

$$589441 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 1$$

$$589442 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 2$$

$$589443 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 3$$

$$589444 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 4$$

$$589445 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 5$$

$$589446 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 6$$

$$589447 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 7$$

$$589448 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 8$$

$$589449 := 5 \times (-8 + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times F(4) + 9$$

$$593190 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 0$$

$$593191 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 1$$

$$593192 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 2$$

$$593193 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 3$$

$$593194 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 4$$

$$593195 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 5$$

$$593196 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 6$$

$$593197 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 7$$

$$593198 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 8$$

$$593199 := (5 + F(9))^3 \times (1 + 9) + 9$$

$$638640 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 0$$

$$638641 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 1$$

$$638642 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 2$$

$$638643 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 3$$

$$638644 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 4$$

$$638645 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 5$$

$$638646 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 6$$

$$638647 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 7$$

$$638648 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 8$$

$$638649 := F(6 \times 3) + 86^{F(4)} + 9$$

$$655360 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 0$$

$$655361 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 1$$

$$655362 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 2$$

$$655363 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 3$$

$$655364 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 4$$

$$655365 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 5$$

$$655366 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$655367 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$655368 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$655369 := F(6)^5 \times 5/F(3) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$747740 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 0$$

$$747741 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 1$$

$$747742 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 2$$

$$747743 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 3$$

$$747744 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 4$$

$$747745 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 5$$

$$747746 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 6$$

$$747747 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 7$$

$$747748 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 8$$

$$747749 := (-7 + F(4)^7) \times 7^{F(4)} + 9$$

$$786410 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 0$$

$$786411 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 1$$

$$786412 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 2$$

$$786413 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 3$$

$$786414 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 4$$

$$786415 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 5$$

$$786416 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 6$$

$$786417 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 7$$

$$786418 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 8$$

$$786419 := (-7 + 8^6) \times F(4) - 1 + 9$$

$$786450 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 0$$

$$786451 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 1$$

$$786452 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 2$$

$$786453 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 3$$

$$786454 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 4$$

$$786455 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 5$$

$$786456 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 6$$

$$786457 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 7$$

$$786458 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 8$$

$$786459 := F(7) + 8^6 \times F(4) + 5 + 9$$

$$833490 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 0$$

$$833491 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 1$$

$$833492 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 2$$

$$833493 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 3$$

$$833494 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 4$$

$$833495 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 5$$

$$833496 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 6$$

$$833497 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 7$$

$$833498 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 8$$

$$833499 := F(8)^3 \times (3^4 + 9) + 9$$

$$841300 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 0$$

$$841301 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 1$$

$$841302 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 2$$

$$841303 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 3$$

$$841304 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 4$$

$$841305 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 5$$

$$841306 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 6$$

$$841307 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 7$$

$$841308 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 8$$

$$841309 := F(8)^{F(4)} - 1 + F(30) + 9$$

$$896700 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 0$$

$$896701 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 1$$

$$896702 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 2$$

$$896703 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 3$$

$$896704 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 4$$

$$896705 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 5$$

$$896706 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 6$$

$$896707 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 7$$

$$896708 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 8$$

$$896709 := F(8) \times F(9 + 6) \times 70 + 9$$

$$920040 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 0$$

$$920041 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 1$$

$$920042 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 2$$

$$920043 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 3$$

$$920044 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 4$$

$$920045 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 5$$

$$920046 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 6$$

$$920047 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 7$$

$$920048 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 8$$

$$920049 := F(9) \times F(20) \times 04 + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 943280 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 0 \\ 943281 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 1 \\ 943282 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 2 \\ 943283 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 3 \\ 943284 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 4 \\ 943285 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 5 \\ 943286 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 6 \\ 943287 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 7 \\ 943288 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 8 \\ 943289 &:= (F(9)^{F(4)} \times 3 - 2) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972740 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 0 \\ 972741 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 1 \\ 972742 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 2 \\ 972743 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 3 \\ 972744 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 4 \\ 972745 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972746 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 6 \\ 972747 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 7 \\ 972748 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 8 \\ 972749 &:= F(9) \times (7^2 + F(7)^4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 973980 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 0 \\ 973981 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 1 \\ 973982 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 2 \\ 973983 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 3 \\ 973984 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 4 \\ 973985 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 5 \\ 973986 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 6 \\ 973987 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 7 \\ 973988 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 8 \\ 973989 &:= F(9 + 7)^{F(3)} - 9 \times F(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

3.2.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned} 11880 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 0 \\ 11881 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 1 \\ 11882 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 2 \\ 11883 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 3 \\ 11884 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 4 \\ 11885 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 5 \\ 11886 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 6 \\ 11887 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 7 \\ 11888 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 8 \\ 11889 &:= (-1 + F(-1 + 8))!/8! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13440 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 0 \\ 13441 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 1 \\ 13442 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 2 \\ 13443 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 3 \\ 13444 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 4 \\ 13445 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 5 \\ 13446 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 6 \\ 13447 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13448 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 8 \\ 13449 &:= (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13460 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 0 \\ 13461 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 1 \\ 13462 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 2 \\ 13463 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 3 \\ 13464 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 4 \\ 13465 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 5 \\ 13466 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 6 \\ 13467 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 7 \\ 13468 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 8 \\ 13469 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/F(4) + F(F(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14330 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 0 \\ 14331 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 1 \\ 14332 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 2 \\ 14333 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 3 \\ 14334 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14335 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 5 \\14336 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 6 \\14337 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 7 \\14338 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 8 \\14339 &:= (F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14400 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 00 \\14401 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 01 \\14402 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 02 \\14403 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 03 \\14404 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 04 \\14405 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 05 \\14406 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 06 \\14407 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 07 \\14408 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 08 \\14409 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 09 \\14410 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 10 \\14411 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 11 \\14412 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 12 \\14413 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 13 \\14414 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 14 \\14415 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 15 \\14416 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 16 \\14417 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 17 \\14418 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 18 \\14419 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 19 \\14420 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 20 \\14421 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 21 \\14422 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 22 \\14423 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 23 \\14424 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 24 \\14425 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 25 \\14426 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 26 \\14427 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 27 \\14428 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 28 \\14429 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 29\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14430 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 30 \\14431 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 31 \\14432 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 32 \\14433 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 33 \\14434 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 34 \\14435 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 35 \\14436 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 36 \\14437 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 37 \\14438 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 38 \\14439 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 39 \\14440 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 40 \\14441 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 41 \\14442 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 42 \\14443 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 43 \\14444 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 44 \\14445 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 45 \\14446 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 46 \\14447 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 47 \\14448 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 48 \\14449 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 49 \\14450 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 50 \\14451 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 51 \\14452 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 52 \\14453 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 53 \\14454 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 54 \\14455 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 55 \\14456 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 56 \\14457 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 57 \\14458 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 58 \\14459 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 59 \\14460 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 60 \\14461 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 61 \\14462 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 62 \\14463 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 63 \\14464 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 64\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14465 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 65 \\ 14466 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 66 \\ 14467 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 67 \\ 14468 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 68 \\ 14469 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 69 \\ 14470 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 70 \\ 14471 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 71 \\ 14472 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 72 \\ 14473 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 73 \\ 14474 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 74 \\ 14475 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 75 \\ 14476 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 76 \\ 14477 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 77 \\ 14478 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 78 \\ 14479 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 79 \\ 14480 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 80 \\ 14481 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 81 \\ 14482 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 82 \\ 14483 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 83 \\ 14484 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 84 \\ 14485 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 85 \\ 14486 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 86 \\ 14487 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 87 \\ 14488 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 88 \\ 14489 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 89 \\ 14490 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 90 \\ 14491 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 91 \\ 14492 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 92 \\ 14493 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 93 \\ 14494 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 94 \\ 14495 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 95 \\ 14496 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 96 \\ 14497 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 97 \\ 14498 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 98 \\ 14499 &:= (1+4)!^{F(F(4))} + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14930 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 0 \\ 14931 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 1 \\ 14932 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\ 14933 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 3 \\ 14934 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 4 \\ 14935 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 5 \\ 14936 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 6 \\ 14937 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 7 \\ 14938 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 8 \\ 14939 &:= -1 + ((F(4)!)! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15120 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 0 \\ 15121 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 1 \\ 15122 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 2 \\ 15123 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 3 \\ 15124 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 4 \\ 15125 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 5 \\ 15126 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 6 \\ 15127 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 7 \\ 15128 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 8 \\ 15129 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times (1+2)!! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15360 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 0 \\ 15361 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 1 \\ 15362 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 2 \\ 15363 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 3 \\ 15364 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 4 \\ 15365 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 5 \\ 15366 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 6 \\ 15367 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 7 \\ 15368 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 8 \\ 15369 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!) / F(F(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15730 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 0 \\ 15731 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 1 \\ 15732 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 2 \\ 15733 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 3 \\ 15734 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 4 \\ 15735 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15736 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 6 \\15737 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 7 \\15738 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 8 \\15739 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17160 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 0 \\17161 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 1 \\17162 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 2 \\17163 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 3 \\17164 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 4 \\17165 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 5 \\17166 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 6 \\17167 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 7 \\17168 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 8 \\17169 &:= 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17280 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 0 \\17281 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 1 \\17282 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 2 \\17283 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 3 \\17284 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 4 \\17285 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 5 \\17286 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 6 \\17287 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 7 \\17288 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 8 \\17289 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2)! / F(8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21930 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 0 \\21931 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 1 \\21932 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 2 \\21933 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 3 \\21934 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4 \\21935 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5 \\21936 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 6 \\21937 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 7 \\21938 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 8 \\21939 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23330 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 0 \\23331 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23332 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 2 \\23333 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 3 \\23334 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 4 \\23335 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 5 \\23336 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 6 \\23337 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 7 \\23338 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 8 \\23339 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!} / F(3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23440 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 0 \\23441 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 1 \\23442 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 2 \\23443 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 3 \\23444 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 4 \\23445 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 5 \\23446 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 6 \\23447 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 7 \\23448 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 8 \\23449 &:= 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!) / F(F(4)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}26460 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 0 \\26461 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 1 \\26462 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 2 \\26463 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 3 \\26464 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 4 \\26465 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 5 \\26466 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 6 \\26467 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 7 \\26468 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 8 \\26469 &:= (F(2) + 6)! / 4 \times F(F(6)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}26640 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 0 \\26641 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 1 \\26642 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 2 \\26643 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 3 \\26644 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 4 \\26645 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 5 \\26646 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}26647 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 7 \\26648 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 8 \\26649 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28350 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 0 \\28351 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 1 \\28352 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 2 \\28353 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 3 \\28354 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 4 \\28355 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 5 \\28356 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 6 \\28357 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 7 \\28358 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 8 \\28359 &:= (2 + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}29470 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 0 \\29471 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 1 \\29472 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 2 \\29473 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 3 \\29474 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 4 \\29475 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 5 \\29476 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 6 \\29477 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 7 \\29478 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 8 \\29479 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33600 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 00 \\33601 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 01 \\33602 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 02 \\33603 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 03 \\33604 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 04 \\33605 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 05 \\33606 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 06 \\33607 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 07 \\33608 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 08 \\33609 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 09\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33610 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 10 \\33611 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 11 \\33612 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 12\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33613 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 13 \\33614 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 14 \\33615 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 15 \\33616 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 16 \\33617 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 17 \\33618 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 18 \\33619 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 19\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33620 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 20 \\33621 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 21 \\33622 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 22 \\33623 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 23 \\33624 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 24 \\33625 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 25 \\33626 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 26 \\33627 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 27 \\33628 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 28 \\33629 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 29\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33630 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 30 \\33631 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 31 \\33632 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 32 \\33633 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 33 \\33634 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 34 \\33635 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 35 \\33636 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 36 \\33637 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 37 \\33638 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 38 \\33639 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 39\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}33640 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 40 \\33641 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 41 \\33642 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 42 \\33643 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 43 \\33644 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 44 \\33645 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 45 \\33646 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 46 \\33647 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 47 \\33648 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 48 \\33649 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 49\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33650 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 50 \\ 33651 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 51 \\ 33652 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 52 \\ 33653 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 53 \\ 33654 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 54 \\ 33655 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 55 \\ 33656 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 56 \\ 33657 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 57 \\ 33658 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 58 \\ 33659 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 59 \\ 33660 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 60 \\ 33661 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 61 \\ 33662 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 62 \\ 33663 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 63 \\ 33664 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 64 \\ 33665 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 65 \\ 33666 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 66 \\ 33667 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 67 \\ 33668 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 68 \\ 33669 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 69 \\ \\ 33670 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 70 \\ 33671 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 71 \\ 33672 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 72 \\ 33673 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 73 \\ 33674 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 74 \\ 33675 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 75 \\ 33676 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 76 \\ 33677 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 77 \\ 33678 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 78 \\ 33679 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 79 \\ \\ 33680 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 80 \\ 33681 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 81 \\ 33682 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 82 \\ 33683 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 83 \\ 33684 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 84 \\ 33685 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 85 \\ 33686 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 86 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33687 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 87 \\ 33688 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 88 \\ 33689 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 89 \\ \\ 33690 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 90 \\ 33691 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 91 \\ 33692 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 92 \\ 33693 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 93 \\ 33694 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 94 \\ 33695 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 95 \\ 33696 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 96 \\ 33697 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 97 \\ 33698 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 98 \\ 33699 &:= -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 99 \\ \\ 33920 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 0 \\ 33921 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 1 \\ 33922 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 2 \\ 33923 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 3 \\ 33924 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 4 \\ 33925 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 5 \\ 33926 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 6 \\ 33927 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 7 \\ 33928 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 8 \\ 33929 &:= F(3)! - (3!/9)^2 + 9 \\ \\ 34130 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 0 \\ 34131 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 1 \\ 34132 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 2 \\ 34133 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 3 \\ 34134 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 4 \\ 34135 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 5 \\ 34136 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 6 \\ 34137 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 7 \\ 34138 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 8 \\ 34139 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/F(1 \times 3) + 9 \\ \\ 38640 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 0 \\ 38641 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38642 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 2 \\ 38643 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 3 \\ 38644 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 4 \\ 38645 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 5 \\ 38646 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 6 \\ 38647 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 7 \\ 38648 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 8 \\ 38649 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39560 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 0 \\ 39561 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 1 \\ 39562 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 2 \\ 39563 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 3 \\ 39564 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 4 \\ 39565 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 5 \\ 39566 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 6 \\ 39567 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 7 \\ 39568 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 8 \\ 39569 &:= -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39600 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 00 \\ 39601 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 01 \\ 39602 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 02 \\ 39603 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 03 \\ 39604 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 04 \\ 39605 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 05 \\ 39606 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 06 \\ 39607 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 07 \\ 39608 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 08 \\ 39609 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 09 \\ 39610 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 10 \\ 39611 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 11 \\ 39612 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 12 \\ 39613 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 13 \\ 39614 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 14 \\ 39615 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 15 \\ 39616 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 16 \\ 39617 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 17 \\ 39618 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 18 \\ 39619 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 19 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39620 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 20 \\ 39621 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 21 \\ 39622 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 22 \\ 39623 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 23 \\ 39624 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 24 \\ 39625 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 25 \\ 39626 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 26 \\ 39627 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 27 \\ 39628 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 28 \\ 39629 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 29 \\ 39630 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 30 \\ 39631 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 31 \\ 39632 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 32 \\ 39633 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 33 \\ 39634 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 34 \\ 39635 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 35 \\ 39636 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 36 \\ 39637 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 37 \\ 39638 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 38 \\ 39639 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 39 \\ 39640 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 40 \\ 39641 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 41 \\ 39642 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 42 \\ 39643 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 43 \\ 39644 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 44 \\ 39645 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 45 \\ 39646 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 46 \\ 39647 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 47 \\ 39648 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 48 \\ 39649 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 49 \\ 39650 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 50 \\ 39651 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 51 \\ 39652 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 52 \\ 39653 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 53 \\ 39654 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 54 \\ 39655 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 55 \\ 39656 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 56 \\ 39657 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 57 \\ 39658 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 58 \\ 39659 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6!) + 59 \end{aligned}$$

39660 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 60$
39661 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 61$
39662 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 62$
39663 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 63$
39664 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 64$
39665 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 65$
39666 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 66$
39667 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 67$
39668 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 68$
39669 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 69$
39670 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 70$
39671 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 71$
39672 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 72$
39673 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 73$
39674 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 74$
39675 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 75$
39676 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 76$
39677 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 77$
39678 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 78$
39679 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 79$
39680 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 80$
39681 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 81$
39682 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 82$
39683 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 83$
39684 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 84$
39685 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 85$
39686 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 86$
39687 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 87$
39688 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 88$
39689 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 89$
39690 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 90$
39691 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 91$
39692 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 92$
39693 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 93$
39694 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 94$
39695 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 95$
39696 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 96$
39697 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 97$
39698 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 98$
39699 := $-(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 99$

39760 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 0$
39761 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 1$
39762 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 2$
39763 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 3$
39764 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 4$
39765 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 5$
39766 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 6$
39767 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 7$
39768 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 8$
39769 := $-3!!/9 \times 7 + F(6)! + 9$

39780 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 0$
39781 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 1$
39782 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 2$
39783 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 6$
39784 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 3$
39785 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 7$
39786 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 4$
39787 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 8$
39788 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 5$
39789 := $3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 9$

40260 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 0$
40261 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 1$
40262 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 2$
40263 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 3$
40264 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 4$
40265 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 5$
40266 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 6$
40267 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 7$
40268 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 8$
40269 := $-(4 + 0)!/2 + F(6)! + 9$

41030 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 0$
41031 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 1$
41032 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 2$
41033 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 3$
41034 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 4$
41035 := $F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 5$

$$\begin{aligned}41036 &:= F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)!! + 6 \\41037 &:= F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)!! + 7 \\41038 &:= F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)!! + 8 \\41039 &:= F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)!! + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46080 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 0 \\46081 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 1 \\46082 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 2 \\46083 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 3 \\46084 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 4 \\46085 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 5 \\46086 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 6 \\46087 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 7 \\46088 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 8 \\46089 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46230 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 0 \\46231 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 1 \\46232 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 2 \\46233 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 3 \\46234 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 4 \\46235 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 5 \\46236 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 6 \\46237 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 7 \\46238 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 8 \\46239 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46400 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 00 \\46401 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 01 \\46402 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 02 \\46403 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 03 \\46404 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 04 \\46405 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 05 \\46406 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 06 \\46407 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 07 \\46408 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 08 \\46409 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 09 \\46410 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 10 \\46411 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 11 \\46412 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 12\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46413 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 13 \\46414 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 14 \\46415 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 15 \\46416 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 16 \\46417 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 17 \\46418 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 18 \\46419 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 19 \\46420 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 20 \\46421 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 21 \\46422 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 22 \\46423 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 23 \\46424 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 24 \\46425 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 25 \\46426 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 26 \\46427 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 27 \\46428 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 28 \\46429 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 29 \\46430 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 30 \\46431 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 31 \\46432 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 32 \\46433 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 33 \\46434 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 34 \\46435 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 35 \\46436 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 36 \\46437 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 37 \\46438 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 38 \\46439 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 39 \\46440 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 40 \\46441 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 41 \\46442 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 42 \\46443 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 43 \\46444 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 44 \\46445 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 45 \\46446 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 46 \\46447 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 47 \\46448 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 48 \\46449 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 49 \\46450 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 50 \\46451 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 51 \\46452 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 52\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46453 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 53 \\ 46454 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 54 \\ 46455 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 55 \\ 46456 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 56 \\ 46457 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 57 \\ 46458 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 58 \\ 46459 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 59 \\ 46460 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 60 \\ 46461 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 61 \\ 46462 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 62 \\ 46463 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 63 \\ 46464 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 64 \\ 46465 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 65 \\ 46466 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 66 \\ 46467 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 67 \\ 46468 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 68 \\ 46469 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 69 \\ 46470 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 70 \\ 46471 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 71 \\ 46472 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 72 \\ 46473 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 73 \\ 46474 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 74 \\ 46475 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 75 \\ 46476 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 76 \\ 46477 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 77 \\ 46478 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 78 \\ 46479 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 79 \\ 46480 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 80 \\ 46481 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 81 \\ 46482 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 82 \\ 46483 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 83 \\ 46484 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 84 \\ 46485 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 85 \\ 46486 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 86 \\ 46487 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 87 \\ 46488 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 88 \\ 46489 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 89 \\ 46490 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 90 \\ 46491 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 91 \\ 46492 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 92 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46493 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 93 \\ 46494 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 94 \\ 46495 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 95 \\ 46496 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 96 \\ 46497 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 97 \\ 46498 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 98 \\ 46499 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 99 \\ \\ 46890 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 0 \\ 46891 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 1 \\ 46892 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 2 \\ 46893 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 3 \\ 46894 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 4 \\ 46895 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 5 \\ 46896 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 6 \\ 46897 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 7 \\ 46898 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 8 \\ 46899 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 9 \\ \\ 46920 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 0 \\ 46921 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 1 \\ 46922 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 2 \\ 46923 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 3 \\ 46924 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 4 \\ 46925 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 5 \\ 46926 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 6 \\ 46927 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 7 \\ 46928 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 8 \\ 46929 &:= F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 9 \\ \\ 47580 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 0 \\ 47581 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 1 \\ 47582 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 2 \\ 47583 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 3 \\ 47584 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 4 \\ 47585 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 5 \\ 47586 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 6 \\ 47587 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 7 \\ 47588 &:= F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$47589 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 9$$

$$53640 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 0$$

$$53641 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 1$$

$$53642 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 2$$

$$53643 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 3$$

$$53644 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 4$$

$$53645 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 5$$

$$53646 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 6$$

$$53647 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 7$$

$$53648 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 8$$

$$53649 := -5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!/F(4)! + 9$$

$$54730 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 0$$

$$54731 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 1$$

$$54732 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 2$$

$$54733 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 3$$

$$54734 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 4$$

$$54735 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 5$$

$$54736 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 6$$

$$54737 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 7$$

$$54738 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 8$$

$$54739 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 9$$

$$54900 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 00$$

$$54901 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 01$$

$$54902 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 02$$

$$54903 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 03$$

$$54904 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 04$$

$$54905 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 05$$

$$54906 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 06$$

$$54907 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 07$$

$$54908 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 08$$

$$54909 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 09$$

$$54910 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 10$$

$$54911 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 11$$

$$54912 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 12$$

$$54913 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 13$$

$$54914 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 14$$

$$54915 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 15$$

$$54916 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 16$$

$$54917 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 17$$

$$54918 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 18$$

$$54919 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 19$$

$$54920 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 20$$

$$54921 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 21$$

$$54922 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 22$$

$$54923 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 23$$

$$54924 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 24$$

$$54925 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 25$$

$$54926 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 26$$

$$54927 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 27$$

$$54928 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 28$$

$$54929 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 29$$

$$54930 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 30$$

$$54931 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 31$$

$$54932 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 32$$

$$54933 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 33$$

$$54934 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 34$$

$$54935 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 35$$

$$54936 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 36$$

$$54937 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 37$$

$$54938 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 38$$

$$54939 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 39$$

$$54940 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 40$$

$$54941 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 41$$

$$54942 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 42$$

$$54943 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 43$$

$$54944 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 44$$

$$54945 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 45$$

$$54946 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 46$$

$$54947 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 47$$

$$54948 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 48$$

$$54949 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 49$$

$$54950 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 50$$

$$54951 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 51$$

$$54952 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 52$$

$$54953 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 53$$

$$54954 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 54$$

$$54955 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 55$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54956 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 56 \\ 54957 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 57 \\ 54958 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 58 \\ 54959 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 59 \\ 54960 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 60 \\ 54961 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 61 \\ 54962 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 62 \\ 54963 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 63 \\ 54964 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 64 \\ 54965 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 65 \\ 54966 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 66 \\ 54967 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 67 \\ 54968 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 68 \\ 54969 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 69 \\ 54970 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 70 \\ 54971 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 71 \\ 54972 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 72 \\ 54973 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 73 \\ 54974 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 74 \\ 54975 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 75 \\ 54976 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 76 \\ 54977 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 77 \\ 54978 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 78 \\ 54979 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 79 \\ 54980 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 80 \\ 54981 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 81 \\ 54982 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 82 \\ 54983 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 83 \\ 54984 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 84 \\ 54985 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 85 \\ 54986 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 86 \\ 54987 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 87 \\ 54988 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 88 \\ 54989 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 89 \\ 54990 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 90 \\ 54991 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 91 \\ 54992 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 92 \\ 54993 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 93 \\ 54994 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 94 \\ 54995 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 95 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54996 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 96 \\ 54997 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 97 \\ 54998 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 98 \\ 54999 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 99 \\ \\ 59640 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 0 \\ 59641 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 1 \\ 59642 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 2 \\ 59643 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 3 \\ 59644 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 4 \\ 59645 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 5 \\ 59646 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 6 \\ 59647 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 7 \\ 59648 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 8 \\ 59649 &:= -5! + 9!/6 - F(4)!! + 9 \\ \\ 63840 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 0 \\ 63841 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 1 \\ 63842 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 2 \\ 63843 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 3 \\ 63844 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 4 \\ 63845 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 5 \\ 63846 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 6 \\ 63847 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 7 \\ 63848 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 8 \\ 63849 &:= F(6)! \times 38/4! + 9 \\ \\ 75600 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 00 \\ 75601 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 01 \\ 75602 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 02 \\ 75603 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 03 \\ 75604 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 04 \\ 75605 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 05 \\ 75606 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 06 \\ 75607 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 07 \\ 75608 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 08 \\ 75609 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 09 \\ 75610 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 10 \\ 75611 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 11 \\ 75612 &:= 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 12 \end{aligned}$$

75613 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 13
75614 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 14
75615 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 15
75616 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 16
75617 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 17
75618 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 18
75619 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 19
75620 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 20
75621 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 21
75622 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 22
75623 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 23
75624 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 24
75625 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 25
75626 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 26
75627 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 27
75628 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 28
75629 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 29
75630 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 30
75631 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 31
75632 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 32
75633 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 33
75634 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 34
75635 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 35
75636 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 36
75637 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 37
75638 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 38
75639 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 39
75640 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 40
75641 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 41
75642 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 42
75643 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 43
75644 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 44
75645 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 45
75646 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 46
75647 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 47
75648 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 48
75649 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 49
75650 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 50
75651 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 51
75652 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 52

75653 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 53
75654 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 54
75655 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 55
75656 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 56
75657 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 57
75658 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 58
75659 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 59
75660 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 60
75661 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 61
75662 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 62
75663 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 63
75664 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 64
75665 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 65
75666 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 66
75667 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 67
75668 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 68
75669 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 69
75670 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 70
75671 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 71
75672 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 72
75673 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 73
75674 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 74
75675 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 75
75676 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 76
75677 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 77
75678 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 78
75679 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 79
75680 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 80
75681 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 81
75682 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 82
75683 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 83
75684 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 84
75685 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 85
75686 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 86
75687 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 87
75688 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 88
75689 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 89
75690 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 90
75691 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 91
75692 := 7! × 5!/F(6) + 92

$$\begin{aligned} 75693 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 93 \\ 75694 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 94 \\ 75695 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 95 \\ 75696 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 96 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75697 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 97 \\ 75698 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 98 \\ 75699 &:= 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 99 \end{aligned}$$

3.3 Symmetric Representations in Reverse Order of Digits

Below are examples of numbers written in reverse order of digits:

3.3.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned} 17640 &:= 0 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17641 &:= 1 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17642 &:= 2 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17643 &:= 3 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17644 &:= 4 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17645 &:= 5 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17646 &:= 6 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17647 &:= 7 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17648 &:= 8 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \\ 17649 &:= 9 + F(F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) - 71 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20970 &:= 0 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20971 &:= 1 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20972 &:= 2 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20973 &:= 3 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20974 &:= 4 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20975 &:= 5 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20976 &:= 6 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20977 &:= 7 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20978 &:= 8 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \\ 20979 &:= 9 + F(F(7)) \times 90 \times F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22180 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22181 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22182 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22183 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22184 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22185 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22186 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22187 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22188 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \\ 22189 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) + F(12)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39270 &:= 0 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39271 &:= 1 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39272 &:= 2 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39273 &:= 3 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39274 &:= 4 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39275 &:= 5 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39276 &:= 6 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39277 &:= 7 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39278 &:= 8 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39279 &:= 9 - F(7 + 2) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39770 &:= 0 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39771 &:= 1 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39772 &:= 2 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39773 &:= 3 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39774 &:= 4 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39775 &:= 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39776 &:= 6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39777 &:= 7 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39778 &:= 8 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39779 &:= 9 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46690 &:= 0 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\ 46691 &:= 1 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$46692 := 2 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46693 := 3 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46694 := 4 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46695 := 5 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46696 := 6 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46697 := 7 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46698 := 8 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46699 := 9 + F(9) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$74290 := 0 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74291 := 1 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74292 := 2 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74293 := 3 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74294 := 4 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74295 := 5 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74296 := 6 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74297 := 7 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74298 := 8 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$74299 := 9 + F(9) \times (-2 + F(4)^7)$$

$$112640 := 0 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112641 := 1 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112642 := 2 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112643 := 3 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112644 := 4 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112645 := 5 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112646 := 6 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112647 := 7 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112648 := 8 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$112649 := 9 + F(4 + 6) \times 2^{11}$$

$$117670 := 0 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117671 := 1 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117672 := 2 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117673 := 3 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117674 := 4 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117675 := 5 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117676 := 6 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117677 := 7 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117678 := 8 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$117679 := 9 + 7^6 + F(7 + 1) \times 1$$

$$212280 := 0 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212281 := 1 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212282 := 2 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212283 := 3 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212284 := 4 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212285 := 5 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212286 := 6 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212287 := 7 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212288 := 8 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$212289 := 9 + (-F(8) + F(22)) \times 12$$

$$270400 := 00 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270401 := 10 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270402 := 20 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270403 := 30 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270404 := 40 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270405 := 50 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270406 := 60 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270407 := 70 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270408 := 80 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270409 := 90 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$274980 := 0 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274981 := 1 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274982 := 2 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274983 := 3 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274984 := 4 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274985 := 5 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274986 := 6 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274987 := 7 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274988 := 8 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$274989 := 9 + (-F(8) + F(9)^{F(4)}) \times 7 - F(2)$$

$$297440 := 0 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297441 := 1 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297442 := 2 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297443 := 3 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297444 := 4 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297445 := 5 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297446 := 6 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297447 := 7 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297448 := 8 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$297449 := 9 + 4 \times (F(4)^7 \times F(9) + 2)$$

$$317810 := 0 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317811 := 1 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317812 := 2 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317813 := 3 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317814 := 4 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317815 := 5 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317816 := 6 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317817 := 7 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317818 := 8 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$317819 := 9 - 1 + F(8 + 7 + 13)$$

$$332750 := 0 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332751 := 1 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332752 := 2 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332753 := 3 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332754 := 4 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332755 := 5 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332756 := 6 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332757 := 7 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332758 := 8 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$332759 := 9 + (57 - 2)^3 \times F(3)$$

$$372100 := 0 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372100 := 00 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372101 := 1 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372102 := 2 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372103 := 3 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372104 := 4 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372105 := 5 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372106 := 6 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372107 := 7 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372108 := 8 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372109 := 9 + F(01 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372111 := 11 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372122 := 22 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372133 := 33 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372144 := 44 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372155 := 55 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372166 := 66 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372177 := 77 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372188 := 88 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$372199 := 99 + F(1 + 2 \times 7)^{F(3)}$$

$$373490 := 0 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373491 := 1 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373492 := 2 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373493 := 3 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373494 := 4 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373495 := 5 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373496 := 6 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373497 := 7 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373498 := 8 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$373499 := 9 + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$374540 := 0 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374541 := 1 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374542 := 2 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374543 := 3 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374544 := 4 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374545 := 5 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374546 := 6 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374547 := 7 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374548 := 8 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$374549 := 9 - 4 + (5^4 - F(7))^{F(3)}$$

$$391850 := 0 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391851 := 1 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391852 := 2 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391853 := 3 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391854 := 4 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391855 := 5 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391856 := 6 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391857 := 7 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391858 := 8 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$391859 := 9 + 5^8 + (1 + F(9))^{F(3)}$$

$$393010 := 0 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393011 := 1 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393012 := 2 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393013 := 3 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393014 := 4 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393015 := 5 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393016 := 6 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393017 := 7 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393018 := 8 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$393019 := 9 + 10 \times (-3 + F(9))^3$$

$$423740 := 0 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423741 := 1 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423742 := 2 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423743 := 3 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423744 := 4 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423745 := 5 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423746 := 6 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423747 := 7 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423748 := 8 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$423749 := 9 + (F(4 \times 7)/3 - 2) \times 4$$

$$438980 := 0 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438981 := 1 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438982 := 2 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438983 := 3 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438984 := 4 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438985 := 5 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438986 := 6 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438987 := 7 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438988 := 8 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$438989 := 9 + (F(8) + F(9) + F(8))^3 + 4$$

$$458710 := 0 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458711 := 1 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458712 := 2 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458713 := 3 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458714 := 4 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458715 := 5 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458716 := 6 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458717 := 7 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458718 := 8 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$458719 := 9 + (1 + F(7)) \times (8^5 - F(4))$$

$$465650 := 0 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465651 := 1 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465652 := 2 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465653 := 3 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465654 := 4 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465655 := 5 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465656 := 6 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465657 := 7 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465658 := 8 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$465659 := 9 + 5^{F(6)} + F(5^{6-4})$$

$$477360 := 0 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7))^{F(4)}$$

$$477361 := 1 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7))^{F(4)}$$

$$477362 := 2 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477363 := 3 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477364 := 4 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477365 := 5 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477366 := 6 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477367 := 7 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477368 := 8 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$477369 := 9 + 6^3 \times (F(7) + F(7)^{F(4)})$$

$$498920 := 0 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498921 := 1 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498922 := 2 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498923 := 3 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498924 := 4 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498925 := 5 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498926 := 6 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498927 := 7 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498928 := 8 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$498929 := 9 + F(29) - F(8) \times 9^{F(4)}$$

$$537790 := 0 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537791 := 1 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537792 := 2 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537793 := 3 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537794 := 4 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537795 := 5 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537796 := 6 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537797 := 7 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537798 := 8 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537799 := 9 - F(9) + (-7 + 7 \times 3)^5$$

$$537850 := 0 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537851 := 1 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537852 := 2 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537853 := 3 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537854 := 4 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537855 := 5 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537856 := 6 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537857 := 7 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537858 := 8 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$537859 := 9 + 5 + F(8) + (7 \times F(3))^5$$

$$589840 := 0 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589841 := 1 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589842 := 2 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589843 := 3 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589844 := 4 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589845 := 5 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589846 := 6 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589847 := 7 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589848 := 8 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$589849 := 9 + 4^8 \times 9 + F(8) - 5$$

$$624030 := 0 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624031 := 1 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624032 := 2 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624033 := 3 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624034 := 4 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624035 := 5 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624036 := 6 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624037 := 7 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624038 := 8 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$624039 := 9 + F(30) \times F(4) / (-2 + 6)$$

$$742570 := 0 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742571 := 1 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742572 := 2 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742573 := 3 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742574 := 4 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742575 := 5 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742576 := 6 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742577 := 7 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742578 := 8 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$742579 := 9 + 2 \times F(7)^5 - F(4) - F(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 832030 &:= 0 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832031 &:= 1 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832032 &:= 2 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832033 &:= 3 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832034 &:= 4 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832035 &:= 5 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832036 &:= 6 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832037 &:= 7 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832038 &:= 8 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \\ 832039 &:= 9 + F(30) - 2 \times (-3 + 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 832650 &:= 0 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832651 &:= 1 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832652 &:= 2 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832653 &:= 3 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832654 &:= 4 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832655 &:= 5 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832656 &:= 6 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832657 &:= 7 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832658 &:= 8 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \\ 832659 &:= 9 + F(5 \times 6) + F(23 - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 839760 &:= 0 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839761 &:= 1 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839762 &:= 2 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839763 &:= 3 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839764 &:= 4 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839765 &:= 5 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839766 &:= 6 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839767 &:= 7 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839768 &:= 8 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \\ 839769 &:= 9 + (6^7 - 9) \times 3 - F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 974780 &:= 0 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974781 &:= 1 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974782 &:= 2 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974783 &:= 3 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974784 &:= 4 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974785 &:= 5 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974786 &:= 6 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974787 &:= 7 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974788 &:= 8 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \\ 974789 &:= 9 + F(8 + 7) \times 47 \times F(9) \end{aligned}$$

3.3.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned} 360 &:= 0 + 6!/F(3) \\ 361 &:= 1 + 6!/F(3) \\ 362 &:= 2 + 6!/F(3) \\ 363 &:= 3 + 6!/F(3) \\ 364 &:= 4 + 6!/F(3) \\ 365 &:= 5 + 6!/F(3) \\ 366 &:= 6 + 6!/F(3) \\ 367 &:= 7 + 6!/F(3) \\ 368 &:= 8 + 6!/F(3) \\ 369 &:= 9 + 6!/F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15490 &:= 0 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15491 &:= 1 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15492 &:= 2 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15493 &:= 3 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15494 &:= 4 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15495 &:= 5 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15496 &:= 6 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15497 &:= 7 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15498 &:= 8 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \\ 15499 &:= 9 + F(9) + F(4!)/F(5 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18480 &:= 0 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18481 &:= 1 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18482 &:= 2 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18483 &:= 3 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18484 &:= 4 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18485 &:= 5 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18486 &:= 6 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \\ 18487 &:= 7 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)! \end{aligned}$$

$$18488 := 8 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)!$$

$$18489 := 9 + 8!/F(4) + (8 - 1)!$$

$$20730 := 0 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20731 := 1 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20732 := 2 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20733 := 3 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20734 := 4 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20735 := 5 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20736 := 6 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20737 := 7 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20738 := 8 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20739 := 9 - 3! + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20740 := 0 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20741 := 1 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20742 := 2 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20743 := 3 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20744 := 4 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20745 := 5 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20746 := 6 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20747 := 7 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20748 := 8 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$20749 := 9 + 4 + F(F(7) - 0!)^2$$

$$23180 := 0 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23181 := 1 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23182 := 2 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23183 := 3 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23184 := 4 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23185 := 5 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23186 := 6 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23187 := 7 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23188 := 8 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$23189 := 9 + (-8 + F((1 + 3)!))/2$$

$$31250 := 0 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31251 := 1 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31252 := 2 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31253 := 3 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31254 := 4 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31255 := 5 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31256 := 6 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31257 := 7 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31258 := 8 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$31259 := 9 + 5^{(2+1)!} \times F(3)$$

$$33480 := 0 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33481 := 1 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33482 := 2 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33483 := 3 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33484 := 4 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33485 := 5 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33486 := 6 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33487 := 7 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33488 := 8 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33489 := 9 - (8! + F(4)!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33580 := 0 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33581 := 1 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33582 := 2 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33583 := 3 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33584 := 4 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33585 := 5 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33586 := 6 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33587 := 7 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33588 := 8 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33589 := 9 - (8! + 5!)/3! + F(3)!$$

$$34390 := 0 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34391 := 1 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34392 := 2 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34393 := 3 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34394 := 4 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34395 := 5 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34396 := 6 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34397 := 7 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34398 := 8 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34399 := 9 + 9!/F(3!) - 4! - F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$34490 := 0 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34491 := 1 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34492 := 2 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34493 := 3 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34494 := 4 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34495 := 5 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34496 := 6 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34497 := 7 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34498 := 8 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$34499 := 9 - F(9) - F(4!)/F(F(4)!) + F(3)!$$

$$35640 := 0 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35641 := 1 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35642 := 2 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35643 := 3 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35644 := 4 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35645 := 5 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35646 := 6 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35647 := 7 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35648 := 8 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35649 := 9 - F(4)!! \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)/F(3)$$

$$35960 := 0 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35961 := 1 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35962 := 2 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35963 := 3 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35964 := 4 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35965 := 5 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35966 := 6 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35967 := 7 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35968 := 8 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$35969 := 9 - F(6)!/9 + 5! + F(3)!$$

$$36050 := 0 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36051 := 1 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36052 := 2 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36053 := 3 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36054 := 4 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36055 := 5 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36056 := 6 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36057 := 7 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36058 := 8 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36059 := 9 + 50 \times (6! + F(F(3)))$$

$$36430 := 0 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36431 := 1 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36432 := 2 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36433 := 3 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36434 := 4 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36435 := 5 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36436 := 6 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36437 := 7 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36438 := 8 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36439 := 9 + 3!^{F(4)!} - F(F(F(6))) + 3!!$$

$$36440 := 0 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36441 := 1 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36442 := 2 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36443 := 3 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36444 := 4 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36445 := 5 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36446 := 6 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36447 := 7 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36448 := 8 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36449 := 9 + F(4) \times 4!!/F(F(6)!) + F(3)!$$

$$36960 := 0 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36961 := 1 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36962 := 2 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36963 := 3 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36964 := 4 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36965 := 5 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36966 := 6 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36967 := 7 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36968 := 8 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$36969 := 9 + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + F(3)!$$

$$37800 := 0 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37801 := 1 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37802 := 2 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37803 := 3 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37804 := 4 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37805 := 5 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37806 := 6 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37807 := 7 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37808 := 8 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37809 := 9 + 08! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$38400 := 0 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38401 := 1 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38402 := 2 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38403 := 3 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38404 := 4 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38405 := 5 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38406 := 6 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38407 := 7 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38408 := 8 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38409 := 9 + (F(F(04)!))! - 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$38640 := 0 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38641 := 1 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38642 := 2 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38643 := 3 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38644 := 4 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38645 := 5 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38646 := 6 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38647 := 7 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38648 := 8 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$38649 := 9 + F(4!)/6 \times (8 - 3)$$

$$39280 := 0 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39281 := 1 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39282 := 2 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39283 := 3 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39284 := 4 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39285 := 5 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39286 := 6 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39287 := 7 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39288 := 8 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39289 := 9 - (8/2)! + F(9)^3$$

$$39310 := 0 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39311 := 1 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39312 := 2 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39313 := 3 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39314 := 4 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39315 := 5 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39316 := 6 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39317 := 7 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39318 := 8 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39319 := 9 + 1 \times 3! + F(9)^3$$

$$39320 := 0 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39321 := 1 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39322 := 2 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39323 := 3 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39324 := 4 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39325 := 5 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39326 := 6 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39327 := 7 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39328 := 8 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$39329 := 9 + 2 \times F(3!) + F(9)^3$$

$$40230 := 0 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40231 := 1 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40232 := 2 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40233 := 3 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40234 := 4 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40235 := 5 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40236 := 6 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40237 := 7 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40238 := 8 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$40239 := 9 + F(3)! - (2 + 0)!/F(F(4)!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40260 &:= 0 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40261 &:= 1 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40262 &:= 2 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40263 &:= 3 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40264 &:= 4 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40265 &:= 5 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40266 &:= 6 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40267 &:= 7 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40268 &:= 8 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \\ 40269 &:= 9 + F(6)! - 20 \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40380 &:= 0 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40381 &:= 1 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40382 &:= 2 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40383 &:= 3 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40384 &:= 4 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40385 &:= 5 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40386 &:= 6 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40387 &:= 7 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40388 &:= 8 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \\ 40389 &:= 9 + 8! + 30 \times F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40740 &:= 0 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40741 &:= 1 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40742 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40743 &:= 3 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40744 &:= 4 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40745 &:= 5 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40746 &:= 6 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40747 &:= 7 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40748 &:= 8 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \\ 40749 &:= 9 + F(F(4)!)! + 70 \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41040 &:= 0 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41041 &:= 1 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41042 &:= 2 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41043 &:= 3 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41044 &:= 4 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41045 &:= 5 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41046 &:= 6 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41047 &:= 7 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41048 &:= 8 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \\ 41049 &:= 9 + F(4)!! + ((0! + 1)^{F(4)})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42240 &:= 0 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42241 &:= 1 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42242 &:= 2 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42243 &:= 3 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42244 &:= 4 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42245 &:= 5 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42246 &:= 6 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42247 &:= 7 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42248 &:= 8 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \\ 42249 &:= 9 + (F(F(4)!)! / F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)!)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42840 &:= 0 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42841 &:= 1 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42842 &:= 2 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42843 &:= 3 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42844 &:= 4 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42845 &:= 5 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42846 &:= 6 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42847 &:= 7 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42848 &:= 8 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \\ 42849 &:= 9 - F(F(4)!) \times F(8)^2 + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43440 &:= 0 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43441 &:= 1 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43442 &:= 2 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43443 &:= 3 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43444 &:= 4 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43445 &:= 5 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43446 &:= 6 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43447 &:= 7 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43448 &:= 8 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\ 43449 &:= 9 + F(4!) - F(4!) / F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$43740 := 0 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43741 &:= 1 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43742 &:= 2 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43743 &:= 3 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43744 &:= 4 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43745 &:= 5 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43746 &:= 6 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43747 &:= 7 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43748 &:= 8 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 43749 &:= 9 + F(4)^7 \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44160 &:= 0 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44161 &:= 1 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44162 &:= 2 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44163 &:= 3 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44164 &:= 4 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44165 &:= 5 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44166 &:= 6 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44167 &:= 7 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44168 &:= 8 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 44169 &:= 9 + F(6)! \times (-1 + 4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44320 &:= 0 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44321 &:= 1 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44322 &:= 2 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44323 &:= 3 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44324 &:= 4 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44325 &:= 5 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44326 &:= 6 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44327 &:= 7 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44328 &:= 8 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \\ 44329 &:= 9 - 2^{F(3!)+F(4)} + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44640 &:= 0 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44641 &:= 1 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44642 &:= 2 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44643 &:= 3 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44644 &:= 4 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44645 &:= 5 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44646 &:= 6 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44647 &:= 7 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44648 &:= 8 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 44649 &:= 9 + F(4!) - (F(6) + 4)^{F(4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44760 &:= 0 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44761 &:= 1 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44762 &:= 2 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44763 &:= 3 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44764 &:= 4 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44765 &:= 5 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44766 &:= 6 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44767 &:= 7 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44768 &:= 8 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \\ 44769 &:= 9 - 67 \times 4! + F(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45390 &:= 0 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45391 &:= 1 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45392 &:= 2 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45393 &:= 3 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45394 &:= 4 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45395 &:= 5 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45396 &:= 6 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45397 &:= 7 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45398 &:= 8 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \\ 45399 &:= 9 + (9! / F(3) + 5!) / 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46080 &:= 0 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46081 &:= 1 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46082 &:= 2 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46083 &:= 3 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46084 &:= 4 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46085 &:= 5 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46086 &:= 6 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46087 &:= 7 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46088 &:= 8 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \\ 46089 &:= 9 + 8! / F(F(06)) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$46240 := 0 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46241 := 1 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46242 := 2 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46243 := 3 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46244 := 4 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46245 := 5 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46246 := 6 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46247 := 7 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46248 := 8 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46249 := 9 + F(4!) - 2 \times 64$$

$$46280 := 0 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46281 := 1 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46282 := 2 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46283 := 3 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46284 := 4 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46285 := 5 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46286 := 6 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46287 := 7 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46288 := 8 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46289 := 9 - 82 - 6 + F(4!)$$

$$46530 := 0 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46531 := 1 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46532 := 2 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46533 := 3 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46534 := 4 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46535 := 5 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46536 := 6 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46537 := 7 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46538 := 8 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46539 := 9 + (3!^5 - F(F(6))) \times F(4)!$$

$$46760 := 0 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46761 := 1 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46762 := 2 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46763 := 3 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46764 := 4 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46765 := 5 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46766 := 6 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46767 := 7 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46768 := 8 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$46769 := 9 + F(6)! \times 7/6! + F(4!)$$

$$47040 := 0 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47041 := 1 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47042 := 2 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47043 := 3 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47044 := 4 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47045 := 5 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47046 := 6 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47047 := 7 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47048 := 8 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47049 := 9 + F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 7)!/F(4)!$$

$$47210 := 0 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47211 := 1 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47212 := 2 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47213 := 3 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47214 := 4 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47215 := 5 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47216 := 6 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47217 := 7 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47218 := 8 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47219 := 9 + F(F(F((1 + 2)!)))/F(7) + F(4!)$$

$$47670 := 0 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47671 := 1 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47672 := 2 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47673 := 3 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47674 := 4 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47675 := 5 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47676 := 6 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47677 := 7 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47678 := 8 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47679 := 9 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7!/4!$$

$$47880 := 0 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)!$$

$$47881 := 1 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)!$$

$$47882 := 2 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}47883 &:= 3 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47884 &:= 4 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47885 &:= 5 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47886 &:= 6 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47887 &:= 7 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47888 &:= 8 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)! \\47889 &:= 9 + 8! + (8! + 7!)/F(4)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49440 &:= 0 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49441 &:= 1 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49442 &:= 2 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49443 &:= 3 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49444 &:= 4 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49445 &:= 5 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49446 &:= 6 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49447 &:= 7 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49448 &:= 8 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! \\49449 &:= 9 + F(4!) + F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49770 &:= 0 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49771 &:= 1 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49772 &:= 2 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49773 &:= 3 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49774 &:= 4 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49775 &:= 5 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49776 &:= 6 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49777 &:= 7 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49778 &:= 8 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \\49779 &:= 9 + 7! \times 79/F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52440 &:= 0 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52441 &:= 1 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52442 &:= 2 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52443 &:= 3 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52444 &:= 4 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52445 &:= 5 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52446 &:= 6 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52447 &:= 7 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52448 &:= 8 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5! \\52449 &:= 9 - (4 - F(F(F(4)!))^2) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52800 &:= 0 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52801 &:= 1 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52802 &:= 2 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52803 &:= 3 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52804 &:= 4 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52805 &:= 5 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52806 &:= 6 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52807 &:= 7 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52808 &:= 8 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5! \\52809 &:= 9 + (-0! + F(8)^2) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52920 &:= 0 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52921 &:= 1 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52922 &:= 2 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52923 &:= 3 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52924 &:= 4 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52925 &:= 5 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52926 &:= 6 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52927 &:= 7 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52928 &:= 8 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5! \\52929 &:= 9 + F(-F(2) + 9)^2 \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53280 &:= 0 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53281 &:= 1 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53282 &:= 2 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53283 &:= 3 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53284 &:= 4 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53285 &:= 5 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53286 &:= 6 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53287 &:= 7 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53288 &:= 8 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5! \\53289 &:= 9 + (F(8)^2 + 3) \times 5!\end{aligned}$$

$$53470 := 0 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53471 &:= 1 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53472 &:= 2 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53473 &:= 3 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53474 &:= 4 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53475 &:= 5 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53476 &:= 6 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53477 &:= 7 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53478 &:= 8 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \\ 53479 &:= 9 - 7!/4 + F(F(F(3!))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53640 &:= 0 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53641 &:= 1 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53642 &:= 2 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53643 &:= 3 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53644 &:= 4 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53645 &:= 5 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53646 &:= 6 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53647 &:= 7 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53648 &:= 8 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \\ 53649 &:= 9 + 4 \times F(6)!/3 - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54270 &:= 0 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54271 &:= 1 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54272 &:= 2 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54273 &:= 3 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54274 &:= 4 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54275 &:= 5 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54276 &:= 6 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54277 &:= 7 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54278 &:= 8 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 54279 &:= 9 + F(F(7))^2 - 4! + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54530 &:= 0 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54531 &:= 1 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54532 &:= 2 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54533 &:= 3 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54534 &:= 4 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54535 &:= 5 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54536 &:= 6 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54537 &:= 7 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54538 &:= 8 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \\ 54539 &:= 9 + (F(F(F(3!))) - 5!/F(4)) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54580 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54581 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54582 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54583 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54584 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54585 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54586 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54587 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54588 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \\ 54589 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) - 5!/4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58920 &:= 0 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58921 &:= 1 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58922 &:= 2 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58923 &:= 3 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58924 &:= 4 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58925 &:= 5 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58926 &:= 6 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58927 &:= 7 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58928 &:= 8 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \\ 58929 &:= 9 + (2^9 - F(8)) \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59070 &:= 0 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59071 &:= 1 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59072 &:= 2 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59073 &:= 3 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59074 &:= 4 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59075 &:= 5 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59076 &:= 6 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59077 &:= 7 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59078 &:= 8 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \\ 59079 &:= 9 + F(7 + 0!) + 9^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$60360 := 0 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6$$

$$\begin{aligned}60361 &:= 1 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60362 &:= 2 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60363 &:= 3 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60364 &:= 4 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60365 &:= 5 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60366 &:= 6 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60367 &:= 7 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60368 &:= 8 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6 \\60369 &:= 9 + (-6! + (F(3!) + 0!)!)/6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}61440 &:= 0 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61441 &:= 1 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61442 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61443 &:= 3 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61444 &:= 4 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61445 &:= 5 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61446 &:= 6 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61447 &:= 7 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61448 &:= 8 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)! \\61449 &:= 9 + F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} \times (-1 + 6)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}63840 &:= 0 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63841 &:= 1 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63842 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63843 &:= 3 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63844 &:= 4 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63845 &:= 5 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63846 &:= 6 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63847 &:= 7 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63848 &:= 8 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)! \\63849 &:= 9 + F(F(4)!) \times F(8)!/(3 \times 6)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64350 &:= 0 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64351 &:= 1 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64352 &:= 2 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64353 &:= 3 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64354 &:= 4 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64355 &:= 5 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64356 &:= 6 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64357 &:= 7 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64358 &:= 8 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64359 &:= 9 + (-5 + 3!!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64380 &:= 0 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64381 &:= 1 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64382 &:= 2 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64383 &:= 3 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64384 &:= 4 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64385 &:= 5 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64386 &:= 6 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64387 &:= 7 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64388 &:= 8 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6 \\64389 &:= 9 + (F(F(8)) - 3!^{F(4)}) \times 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64440 &:= 0 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64441 &:= 1 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64442 &:= 2 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64443 &:= 3 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64444 &:= 4 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64445 &:= 5 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64446 &:= 6 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64447 &:= 7 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64448 &:= 8 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)! \\64449 &:= 9 + F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) \times (-4 + 6)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64560 &:= 0 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64561 &:= 1 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64562 &:= 2 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64563 &:= 3 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64564 &:= 4 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64565 &:= 5 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64566 &:= 6 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64567 &:= 7 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64568 &:= 8 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6) \\64569 &:= 9 + (F(6)!/5 + F(4)!) \times F(6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64620 &:= 0 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6) \\64621 &:= 1 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)\end{aligned}$$

$$64622 := 2 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64623 := 3 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64624 := 4 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64625 := 5 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64626 := 6 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64627 := 7 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64628 := 8 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$64629 := 9 + (-2 + 6!) \times F(4)!!/F(6)$$

$$65340 := 0 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65341 := 1 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65342 := 2 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65343 := 3 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65344 := 4 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65345 := 5 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65346 := 6 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65347 := 7 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65348 := 8 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$65349 := 9 + F(4)! \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 56)$$

$$66240 := 0 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66241 := 1 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66242 := 2 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66243 := 3 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66244 := 4 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66245 := 5 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66246 := 6 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66247 := 7 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66248 := 8 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$66249 := 9 + F(4)!^2 \times 6! + F(6)!$$

$$74160 := 0 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74161 := 1 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74162 := 2 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74163 := 3 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74164 := 4 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74165 := 5 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74166 := 6 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74167 := 7 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74168 := 8 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74169 := 9 + (6! + 1) \times F(4)!!/7$$

$$74560 := 0 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74561 := 1 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74562 := 2 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74563 := 3 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74564 := 4 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74565 := 5 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74566 := 6 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74567 := 7 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74568 := 8 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74569 := 9 + F(6) \times 5!/F(4) \times F(F(7))$$

$$74830 := 0 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74831 := 1 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74832 := 2 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74833 := 3 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74834 := 4 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74835 := 5 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74836 := 6 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74837 := 7 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74838 := 8 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74839 := 9 + (-F(3)^8 + F(F(F(F(4!)))) \times 7$$

$$74880 := 0 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74881 := 1 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74882 := 2 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74883 := 3 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74884 := 4 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74885 := 5 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74886 := 6 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74887 := 7 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74888 := 8 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$74889 := 9 + 8!/F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7)$$

$$80540 := 0 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!)$$

$$80541 := 1 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!)$$

$$80542 := 2 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80543 &:= 3 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80544 &:= 4 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80545 &:= 5 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80546 &:= 6 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80547 &:= 7 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80548 &:= 8 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \\ 80549 &:= 9 + F(F(4)) \times (-50 + 8!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84480 &:= 0 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84481 &:= 1 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84482 &:= 2 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84483 &:= 3 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84484 &:= 4 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84485 &:= 5 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84486 &:= 6 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84487 &:= 7 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84488 &:= 8 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \\ 84489 &:= 9 + 8! \times 44/F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84930 &:= 0 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84931 &:= 1 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84932 &:= 2 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84933 &:= 3 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84934 &:= 4 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84935 &:= 5 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84936 &:= 6 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84937 &:= 7 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84938 &:= 8 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \\ 84939 &:= 9 + (F(3!) \times F(9))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88830 &:= 0 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88831 &:= 1 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88832 &:= 2 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88833 &:= 3 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88834 &:= 4 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88835 &:= 5 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88836 &:= 6 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88837 &:= 7 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88838 &:= 8 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \\ 88839 &:= 9 + 3!/8 \times F(8 + 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94080 &:= 0 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94081 &:= 1 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94082 &:= 2 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94083 &:= 3 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94084 &:= 4 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94085 &:= 5 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94086 &:= 6 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94087 &:= 7 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94088 &:= 8 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \\ 94089 &:= 9 + 8! \times F(F(F(04!)))/9 \end{aligned}$$

3.4 Symmetric Nonconsecutive Representations in Reverse Order of Digits

The above subsections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 are with **symmetric** and **consecutive** representations. Below are some results, where we have **symmetry**, but the numbers are **non consecutive**.

$$\begin{aligned} 14400 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 00 = 00 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14411 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 11 = 11 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14422 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 22 = 22 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14433 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 33 = 33 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14444 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 44 = 44 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14455 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 55 = 55 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14466 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 66 = 66 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14477 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 77 = 77 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \\ 14488 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(4!))) \times F(4)!! + 88 = 88 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4!))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$14499 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(4)!! + 99 = 99 + F(4)!! \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 1)$$

$$33600 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 00 = 00 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33611 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 11 = 11 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33622 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 22 = 22 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33633 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 33 = 33 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33644 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 44 = 44 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33655 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 55 = 55 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33666 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 66 = 66 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33677 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 77 = 77 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33688 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 88 = 88 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$33699 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 99 = 99 - F(6)!/3! + F(3)!$$

$$46400 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 00 = 00 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46411 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 11 = 11 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46422 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 22 = 22 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46433 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 33 = 33 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46444 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 44 = 44 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46455 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 55 = 55 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46466 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 66 = 66 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46477 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 77 = 77 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46488 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 88 = 88 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$46499 := F(4!) + F(6) + 4! + 99 = 99 + F(4!) + F(6) + 4!$$

$$54900 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 00 = 00 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54911 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 11 = 11 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54922 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 22 = 22 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54933 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 33 = 33 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54944 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 44 = 44 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54955 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 55 = 55 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54966 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 66 = 66 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54977 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 77 = 77 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54988 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 88 = 88 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$54999 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 99 = 99 + (F(9) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times 5$$

$$37800 := 00 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37811 := 11 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37822 := 22 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37833 := 33 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37844 := 44 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37855 := 55 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37866 := 66 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37877 := 77 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37888 := 88 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$37899 := 99 + 8! - 7!/F(3)$$

$$22610 := 01 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22621 := 12 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22632 := 23 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22643 := 34 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22654 := 45 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22665 := 56 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22676 := 67 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22687 := 78 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$22698 := 89 + F(6)! - F(22)$$

$$44440 := 04 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44451 := 15 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44462 := 26 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44473 := 37 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44484 := 48 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44495 := 59 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$44406 := 60 - F(4!)/4! + F(4!)$$

$$47305 := -50 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47314 := -41 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47323 := -32 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47332 := -23 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47341 := -14 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47350 := -05 + F(3 + F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47503 := -30 + 5 \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47512 := -21 + 5 \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47521 := -12 + 5 \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$47530 := -03 + 5 \times F(F(7)) + F(4!)$$

$$270400 := 00 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270411 := 11 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270422 := 22 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270433 := 33 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270444 := 44 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270455 := 55 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270466 := 66 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270477 := 77 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270488 := 88 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

$$270499 := 99 + (40 \times F(7))^2$$

4 Symmetric Representations in terms of F(2), F(3) and F(4)

In the previous section, we gave symmetric numbers as blocks of 10. Since, F(2)=1, F(3)=2 and F(4)=3, still we can have symmetric numbers as blocks of 3. Similar to previous section, here also we have symmetric numbers in order of digits and its reverse. There are numbers those can be written in both the ways. The work is limited upto 6 digits. These are given in subsections below.

4.1 Symmetric Representations in Both Ways

Below are symmetric numbers in F(2), F(3) and F(4) in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse.

$$4182 := F(-F(4) + 1 + F(8)) + F(2) = F(2) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4))$$

$$4183 := F(-F(4) + 1 + F(8)) + F(3) = F(3) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4))$$

$$4184 := F(-F(4) + 1 + F(8)) + F(4) = F(4) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4))$$

$$6562 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(2) = F(2) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$$

$$6563 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(3) = F(3) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$$

$$6564 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(4) = F(4) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)}$$

$$10952 := F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(2) = F(2) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$$

$$10953 := F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(3) = F(3) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$$

$$10954 := F(F(10) - F(9)) + 5 + F(4) = F(4) + 5 + F(F(9 - 01))$$

$$10982 := 1 + F(09) + F(F(8)) + F(2) = F(2) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$$

$$10983 := 1 + F(09) + F(F(8)) + F(3) = F(3) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$$

$$10984 := 1 + F(09) + F(F(8)) + F(4) = F(4) + F(F(8)) + F(9) + 01$$

$$28762 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(7) \times F(6) + F(2) = F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28763 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(7) \times F(6) + F(3) = F(3) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$28764 := F(2 + F(8)) + F(7) \times F(6) + F(4) = F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(F(8) + 2)$$

$$32872 := 3 \times (-2 + F(F(8)) + F(7)) + F(2) = F(2) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$$

$$32873 := 3 \times (-2 + F(F(8)) + F(7)) + F(3) = F(3) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$$

$$32874 := 3 \times (-2 + F(F(8)) + F(7)) + F(4) = F(4) + (F(7) + F(F(8)) - 2) \times 3$$

$$43772 := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(2) = F(2) - F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4$$

$$43773 := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(3) = F(3) - F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4$$

$$43774 := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) + F(4) = F(4) - F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4$$

$$65592 := F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(2) = F(2) - F(9) + 5^5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$65593 := F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(3) = F(3) - F(9) + 5^5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$65594 := F(F(6)) \times 5^5 - F(9) + F(4) = F(4) - F(9) + 5^5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$65652 := F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5) + F(2) = F(2) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$65653 := F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5) + F(3) = F(3) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$65654 := F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5) + F(4) = F(4) + (-5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$65672 := -F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7 + F(2) = F(2) + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 5 - F(F(F(6)))$$

$$65673 := -F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7 + F(3) = F(3) + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 5 - F(F(F(6)))$$

$$65674 := -F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7 + F(4) = F(4) + 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 5 - F(F(F(6)))$$

$$73792 := (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(2) = F(2) + 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)})$$

$$73793 := (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(3) = F(3) + 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)})$$

$$73794 := (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 9 + F(4) = F(4) + 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)})$$

$$74992 := F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(2) = F(2) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4) + F(7))$$

$$74993 := F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(3) = F(3) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4) + F(7))$$

$$74994 := F(F(7) + F(4) + 9) - F(9) + F(4) = F(4) - F(9) + F(9 + F(4) + F(7))$$

$$75272 := F(7) + F(5^2) + F(F(7)) + F(2) = F(2) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$75273 := F(7) + F(5^2) + F(F(7)) + F(3) = F(3) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$75274 := F(7) + F(5^2) + F(F(7)) + F(4) = F(4) + F(F(7)) + F(25) + F(7)$$

$$76392 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3)) - F(9)) + F(2) = F(2) + (-F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76393 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3)) - F(9)) + F(3) = F(3) + (-F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76394 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3)) - F(9)) + F(4) = F(4) + (-F(9) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76462 := 7 \times (-F(F(6)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(2) = F(2) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$76463 := 7 \times (-F(F(6)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(3) = F(3) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$76464 := 7 \times (-F(F(6)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4) = F(4) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$76532 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + F(3))) + F(2) = F(2) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76533 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + F(3))) + F(3) = F(3) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76534 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(5 + F(3))) + F(4) = F(4) + (-F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76672 := (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(2) = F(2) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7))$$

$$76673 := (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(3) = F(3) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7))$$

$$76674 := (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7)) + F(4) = F(4) + (7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6 + F(7))$$

$$76742 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(7) + 4) + F(2) = F(2) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76743 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(7) + 4) + F(3) = F(3) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76744 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(7) + 4) + F(4) = F(4) + (4 + F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$86582 := F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(2) = F(2) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8))$$

$$86583 := F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(3) = F(3) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8))$$

$$86584 := F(F(8)) \times F(6) - F(-5 + F(8)) + F(4) = F(4) - F(F(8) - 5) + F(6) \times F(F(8))$$

$$98282 := 9 \times F(F(8)) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(2) = F(2) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9$$

$$98283 := 9 \times F(F(8)) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(3) = F(3) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9$$

$$98284 := 9 \times F(F(8)) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(4) = F(4) - F(F(8 - F(2))) + F(F(8)) \times 9$$

$$98452 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)) - 5) + F(2) = F(2) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98453 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)) - 5) + F(3) = F(3) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98454 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)) - 5) + F(4) = F(4) + (-5 - F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98542 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(4))) + F(2) = F(2) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98543 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(4))) + F(3) = F(3) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98544 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(4))) + F(4) = F(4) + (-F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98632 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(2) = F(2) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98633 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(3) = F(3) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 98634 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6) - F(F(3)))) + F(4) = F(4) + (F(F(F(3)) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147493 &:= ((1 \times 4)^7 + 4) \times 9 \times F(3) = F(3) + 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\ 147494 &:= ((1 \times 4)^7 + 4) \times 9 \times F(4) = F(4) + 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 229972 &:= F(2 + 2 + 9) \times F(9 + 7) + F(2) = F(2) + F(7 + 9) \times F(9 + 2 + 2) \\ 229973 &:= F(2 + 2 + 9) \times F(9 + 7) + F(3) = F(3) + F(7 + 9) \times F(9 + 2 + 2) \\ 229974 &:= F(2 + 2 + 9) \times F(9 + 7) + F(4) = F(4) + F(7 + 9) \times F(9 + 2 + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 297382 &:= (2 + 9 \times F(7))^{F(3)} \times F(8) + F(2) = F(2) + F(8) \times (F(3)^7 - 9)^2 \\ 297383 &:= (2 + 9 \times F(7))^{F(3)} \times F(8) + F(3) = F(3) + F(8) \times (F(3)^7 - 9)^2 \\ 297384 &:= (2 + 9 \times F(7))^{F(3)} \times F(8) + F(4) = F(4) + F(8) \times (F(3)^7 - 9)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 531442 &:= (5 - F(3))^{(-1+4) \times 4} + F(2) = F(2) + F(4)^{4 \times 1 + 3 + 5} \\ 531443 &:= (5 - F(3))^{(-1+4) \times 4} + F(3) = F(3) + F(4)^{4 \times 1 + 3 + 5} \\ 531444 &:= (5 - F(3))^{(-1+4) \times 4} + F(4) = F(4) + F(4)^{4 \times 1 + 3 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 832062 &:= F(8) + F((3 + 2) \times 06) + F(2) = F(2) + F(6 \times (02 + 3)) + F(8) \\ 832063 &:= F(8) + F((3 + 2) \times 06) + F(3) = F(3) + F(6 \times (02 + 3)) + F(8) \\ 832064 &:= F(8) + F((3 + 2) \times 06) + F(4) = F(4) + F(6 \times (02 + 3)) + F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 953332 &:= (-F(9) + F(-5 + 33)) \times 3 + F(2) = F(2) + 3 \times (F(33 - 5) - F(9)) \\ 953333 &:= (-F(9) + F(-5 + 33)) \times 3 + F(3) = F(3) + 3 \times (F(33 - 5) - F(9)) \\ 953334 &:= (-F(9) + F(-5 + 33)) \times 3 + F(4) = F(4) + 3 \times (F(33 - 5) - F(9)) \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Symmetric Representations in Digit's Order

Below are symmetric numbers in F(2), F(3) and F(4) in digit's order.

$$\begin{aligned} 52442 &:= (F(F(5 + 2)) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(2) & 98572 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(2) \\ 52443 &:= (F(F(5 + 2)) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(3) & 98573 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(3) \\ 52444 &:= (F(F(5 + 2)) - 4)^{F(F(4))} + F(4) & 98574 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 57 + F(4) \\ \\ 76692 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(2) & 117682 &:= 11 + 7^6 + F(8) + F(2) \\ 76693 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(3) & 117683 &:= 11 + 7^6 + F(8) + F(3) \\ 76694 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69 + F(4) & 117684 &:= 11 + 7^6 + F(8) + F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$142642 := F(14)^2 + F(6)^{F(4)} + F(2)$$

$$142643 := F(14)^2 + F(6)^{F(4)} + F(3)$$

$$142644 := F(14)^2 + F(6)^{F(4)} + F(4)$$

$$143642 := (F(14) + F(3))^{6-4} + F(2)$$

$$143643 := (F(14) + F(3))^{6-4} + F(3)$$

$$143644 := (F(14) + F(3))^{6-4} + F(4)$$

$$144392 := (F(14) + F(4))^{F(3)} - 9 + F(2)$$

$$144393 := (F(14) + F(4))^{F(3)} - 9 + F(3)$$

$$144394 := (F(14) + F(4))^{F(3)} - 9 + F(4)$$

$$161052 := (1^6 + 10)^5 + F(2)$$

$$161053 := (1^6 + 10)^5 + F(3)$$

$$161054 := (1^6 + 10)^5 + F(4)$$

$$162362 := (F(16)^2 - 3)/6 + F(2)$$

$$162363 := (F(16)^2 - 3)/6 + F(3)$$

$$162364 := (F(16)^2 - 3)/6 + F(4)$$

$$261122 := (2^{F(6)+1} - 1)^2 + F(2)$$

$$261123 := (2^{F(6)+1} - 1)^2 + F(3)$$

$$261124 := (2^{F(6)+1} - 1)^2 + F(4)$$

$$317852 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 8 \times 5 + F(2)$$

$$317853 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 8 \times 5 + F(3)$$

$$317854 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 8 \times 5 + F(4)$$

$$317902 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 90 + F(2)$$

$$317903 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 90 + F(3)$$

$$317904 := F((3 + 1) \times 7) + 90 + F(4)$$

$$371932 := 3 \times 7 \times F(19 + 3) + F(2)$$

$$371933 := 3 \times 7 \times F(19 + 3) + F(3)$$

$$371934 := 3 \times 7 \times F(19 + 3) + F(4)$$

$$670562 := 6^7 + 05^{F(6)} + F(2)$$

$$670563 := 6^7 + 05^{F(6)} + F(3)$$

$$670564 := 6^7 + 05^{F(6)} + F(4)$$

$$741322 := (7 \times 41 \times 3)^2 + F(2)$$

$$741323 := (7 \times 41 \times 3)^2 + F(3)$$

$$741324 := (7 \times 41 \times 3)^2 + F(4)$$

$$786392 := -7 + 8^6 \times 3 - F(9) + F(2)$$

$$786393 := -7 + 8^6 \times 3 - F(9) + F(3)$$

$$786394 := -7 + 8^6 \times 3 - F(9) + F(4)$$

$$786442 := (7 + 8^6 - 4) \times F(4) + F(2)$$

$$786443 := (7 + 8^6 - 4) \times F(4) + F(3)$$

$$786444 := (7 + 8^6 - 4) \times F(4) + F(4)$$

$$786462 := (7 + 8^6) * F(4) + F(6) + F(2)$$

$$786463 := (7 + 8^6) * F(4) + F(6) + F(3)$$

$$786464 := (7 + 8^6) * F(4) + F(6) + F(4)$$

$$786472 := (F(7) + 8^6) \times (-4 + 7) + F(2)$$

$$786473 := (F(7) + 8^6) \times (-4 + 7) + F(3)$$

$$786474 := (F(7) + 8^6) \times (-4 + 7) + F(4)$$

$$832482 := F(8)^{F(3)} + F(-2 + 4 * 8) + F(2)$$

$$832483 := F(8)^{F(3)} + F(-2 + 4 * 8) + F(3)$$

$$832484 := F(8)^{F(3)} + F(-2 + 4 * 8) + F(4)$$

$$849752 := F(8)/F(4) \times F(-9 + 7 \times 5) + F(2)$$

$$849753 := F(8)/F(4) \times F(-9 + 7 \times 5) + F(3)$$

$$849754 := F(8)/F(4) \times F(-9 + 7 \times 5) + F(4)$$

$$923522 := (F(9) - F(2) - F(3))^{5-F(2)} + F(2)$$

$$923523 := (F(9) - F(2) - F(3))^{5-F(2)} + F(3)$$

$$923524 := (F(9) - F(2) - F(3))^{5-F(2)} + F(4)$$

$$974162 := F(9 + 7)^{F(4-1)} - F(6) + F(2)$$

$$974163 := F(9 + 7)^{F(4-1)} - F(6) + F(3)$$

$$974164 := F(9 + 7)^{F(4-1)} - F(6) + F(4)$$

$$975254 := -9 + F(7) * (-5 + F(25)) + F(4)$$

$$975252 := -9 + F(7) * (-5 + F(25)) + F(2)$$

$$975253 := -9 + F(7) * (-5 + F(25)) + F(3)$$

4.3 Symmetric Representations in Reverse Order of Digits

Below are symmetric numbers in F(2), F(3) and F(4) in reverse order of digits.

$$15592 := F(2) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$$

$$15593 := F(3) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$$

$$15594 := F(4) - F(9) + 5^{5+1}$$

$$28562 := F(2) + (F(6) + 5)^{8/2}$$

$$28563 := F(3) + (F(6) + 5)^{8/2}$$

$$28564 := F(4) + (F(6) + 5)^{8/2}$$

$$39072 := F(2) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$$

$$39073 := F(3) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$$

$$39074 := F(4) - F(F(7)) + F(09)^3$$

$$39292 := F(2) - F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39293 := F(3) - F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39294 := F(4) - F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39682 := F(2) + F(8 + 6) + F(9)^3$$

$$39683 := F(3) + F(8 + 6) + F(9)^3$$

$$39684 := F(4) + F(8 + 6) + F(9)^3$$

$$46372 := F(2) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46373 := F(3) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46374 := F(4) + F(7 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$58912 := F(2) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5$$

$$58913 := F(3) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5$$

$$58914 := F(4) + F(19) + F(F(8)) \times 5$$

$$65642 := F(2) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$65643 := F(3) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$65644 := F(4) + 4^{F(6)} + 5 \times F(F(6))$$

$$67362 := F(2) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$67363 := F(3) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$67364 := F(4) - F(F(6))^3 + 7 \times F(F(F(6)))$$

$$170472 := F(2) + 7^4 \times 071$$

$$170473 := F(3) + 7^4 \times 071$$

$$170474 := F(4) + 7^4 \times 071$$

$$194482 := F(2) + F(8)^{F(4) \times 4 - 9 + 1}$$

$$194483 := F(3) + F(8)^{F(4) \times 4 - 9 + 1}$$

$$194484 := F(4) + F(8)^{F(4) \times 4 - 9 + 1}$$

$$226982 := F(2) + (F(8) + F(9) + 6)^{F(2+2)}$$

$$226983 := F(3) + (F(8) + F(9) + 6)^{F(2+2)}$$

$$226984 := F(4) + (F(8) + F(9) + 6)^{F(2+2)}$$

$$276342 := F(2) + (4 + 3^6) \times F(7 \times 2)$$

$$276343 := F(3) + (4 + 3^6) \times F(7 \times 2)$$

$$276344 := F(4) + (4 + 3^6) \times F(7 \times 2)$$

$$292682 := F(2) + (F(8) + F(6) + 2^9)^2$$

$$292683 := F(3) + (F(8) + F(6) + 2^9)^2$$

$$292684 := F(4) + (F(8) + F(6) + 2^9)^2$$

$$337562 := F(2) + (F(6) + 573)^{F(3)}$$

$$337563 := F(3) + (F(6) + 573)^{F(3)}$$

$$337564 := F(4) + (F(6) + 573)^{F(3)}$$

$$357912 := F(2) + (-1 + 9 \times (F(7) - 5))^3$$

$$357913 := F(3) + (-1 + 9 \times (F(7) - 5))^3$$

$$357914 := F(4) + (-1 + 9 \times (F(7) - 5))^3$$

$$390592 := F(2) - F(9) + 5^{F(9-3)}$$

$$390593 := F(3) - F(9) + 5^{F(9-3)}$$

$$390594 := F(4) - F(9) + 5^{F(9-3)}$$

$$514232 := F(2) + F(3) + F(24 + 5)$$

$$514233 := F(3) + F(3) + F(24 + 5)$$

$$514234 := F(4) + F(3) + F(24 + 5)$$

$$599782 := F(2) + F(8) \times F(7)^{-9/9+5}$$

$$599783 := F(3) + F(8) \times F(7)^{-9/9+5}$$

$$599784 := F(4) + F(8) \times F(7)^{-9/9+5}$$

$$688562 := F(2) + (F(6)^5 + F(8)) \times F(8) - F(6)$$

$$688563 := F(3) + (F(6)^5 + F(8)) \times F(8) - F(6)$$

$$688564 := F(4) + (F(6)^5 + F(8)) \times F(8) - F(6)$$

$$734812 := F(2) + (18^4 - 3) \times 7$$

$$734813 := F(3) + (18^4 - 3) \times 7$$

$$734814 := F(4) + (18^4 - 3) \times 7$$

$$803472 := F(2) - F(7)^4 + F(30) - 8$$

$$803473 := F(3) - F(7)^4 + F(30) - 8$$

$$803474 := F(4) - F(7)^4 + F(30) - 8$$

$$823572 := F(2) + 7^{5+F(3)} + 28$$

$$823573 := F(3) + 7^{5+F(3)} + 28$$

$$823574 := F(4) + 7^{5+F(3)} + 28$$

$$944812 := F(2) + (18^4 + F(4)) \times 9$$

$$944813 := F(3) + (18^4 + F(4)) \times 9$$

$$944814 := F(4) + (18^4 + F(4)) \times 9$$

4.4 Symmetric Representations in F(F(3)) and F(F(4))

In the previous section, we gave symmetric numbers in terms of $F(2)$, $F(3)$ and $F(4)$. Since $F(F(3)) = 1$ and $F(F(4)) = 2$, here also we have symmetric numbers in order of digits and its reverse. There are numbers those can be written in both the ways. The work is limited up to 5 digits. These are given in subsections below.

4.4.1 Symmetric Representations in Both Ways

Below are symmetric numbers in $F(F(3))$ and $F(F(4))$ in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse.

$$7923 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times F(2) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + F(2) \times F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7924 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times F(2) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + F(2) \times F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$8363 := F(F(8)) - F(3 \times 6) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$8364 := F(F(8)) - F(3 \times 6) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$10943 := F(F(-1 + 09)) - 4 + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) - 4 + F(F(9 - 01))$$

$$10944 := F(F(-1 + 09)) - 4 + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) - 4 + F(F(9 - 01))$$

$$21963 := 2 \times (1 + F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9) + 1) \times 2$$

$$21964 := 2 \times (1 + F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9) + 1) \times 2$$

$$32863 := 3 \times F(2) \times (F(F(8)) + F(6)) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(6) + F(F(8))) \times F(2) \times 3$$

$$32864 := 3 \times F(2) \times (F(F(8)) + F(6)) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(6) + F(F(8))) \times F(2) \times 3$$

$$35423 := F(3) \times F(5 \times 4 + 2) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3)$$

$$35424 := F(3) \times F(5 \times 4 + 2) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3)$$

$$43793 := 4 \times (F(3) + F(-F(7) + F(9))) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(F(9) - F(7)) + F(3)) \times 4$$

$$43794 := 4 \times (F(3) + F(-F(7) + F(9))) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(F(9) - F(7)) + F(3)) \times 4$$

$$66493 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 4 \times F(9) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(9) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6$$

$$66494 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 4 \times F(9) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(9) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6$$

$$68473 := 6 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$68474 := 6 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$74793 := -F(F(7)) + F(4 - F(7) + F(9)) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + F(F(9) - F(7) + 4) - F(F(7))$$

$$74794 := -F(F(7)) + F(4 - F(7) + F(9)) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + F(F(9) - F(7) + 4) - F(F(7))$$

$$75293 := F(F(7)) + F(5^2) + F(9) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + F(9) + F(25) + F(F(7))$$

$$75294 := F(F(7)) + F(5^2) + F(9) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + F(9) + F(25) + F(F(7))$$

$$76553 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 5) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (-5 - 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76554 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 5) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (-5 - 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$76623 := F(F(7) + F(6)) \times (6 + F(2)) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(2) + 6) \times F(F(6) + F(7))$$

$$76624 := F(F(7) + F(6)) \times (6 + F(2)) + F(F(4)) = F(F(3)) + (F(2) + 6) \times F(F(6) + F(7))$$

$$76653 := 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times 5 + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + 5 \times 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$76654 := 7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times 5 + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + 5 \times 6 + F(F(F(6))) \times 7$$

$$87513 := (F(F(8)) - 7) \times F(5 + 1) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + F(1 + 5) \times (-7 + F(F(8)))$$

$$87514 := (F(F(8)) - 7) \times F(5 + 1) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + F(1 + 5) \times (-7 + F(F(8)))$$

$$87673 := 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) \times 8$$

$$87674 := 8 \times (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(7) + F(F(6) + F(7))) \times 8$$

$$98623 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 6 \times 2) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (2 \times 6 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98624 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 6 \times 2) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (2 \times 6 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98683 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - F(8) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) - F(8) + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98684 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - F(8) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) - F(8) + (F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98753 := 9 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + 5 + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) \times 9$$

$$98754 := 9 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + 5 + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + 5 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) \times 9$$

$$98893 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 8 + F(9)) + F(F(3)) = F(F(3)) + (F(9) + 8 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

$$98894 := 9 \times (F(F(8)) + 8 + F(9)) + F(F(4)) = F(F(4)) + (F(9) + 8 + F(F(8))) \times 9$$

4.4.2 Symmetric Representations Reverse order of Digits

Below are symmetric numbers in $F(F(3))$ and $F(F(4))$ in reverse order of digits:

$$20973 := F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times 90 + 2$$

$$20974 := F(F(4)) + F(F(7)) \times 90 + 2$$

$$74393 := F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + F(4)^7)$$

$$74394 := F(F(4)) + F(9) \times (F(F(3)) + F(4)^7)$$

$$28673 := F(F(3)) + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2}$$

$$28674 := F(F(4)) + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2}$$

$$74763 := F(F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(7))$$

$$74764 := F(F(4)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(7))$$

$$39253 := F(F(3)) - 52 + F(9)^3$$

$$39254 := F(F(4)) - 52 + F(9)^3$$

$$75033 := F(F(3)) + F(30 - 5) + 7$$

$$75034 := F(F(4)) + F(30 - 5) + 7$$

$$39383 := F(F(3)) + (8 + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$39384 := F(F(4)) + (8 + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$86793 := F(F(3)) + (-97 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8$$

$$86794 := F(F(4)) + (-97 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8$$

$$59283 := F(F(3)) + F(F(8 - F(2))) + 9^5$$

$$59284 := F(F(4)) + F(F(8 - F(2))) + 9^5$$

$$97363 := F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(3)^7) \times 9$$

$$97364 := F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(3)^7) \times 9$$

$$69633 := F(F(3)) + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6)$$

$$69634 := F(F(4)) + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6)$$

$$98263 := F(F(3)) + (F(F(F(6))) - 28) \times 9$$

$$98264 := F(F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) - 28) \times 9$$

5 More Selfie Numbers

This section deals with the numbers not appearing above. Here also we have three subsections, where first one give the representations in both ways, second subsection give numbers in order of digits and the final subsection give the numbers in reverse order of digits. This section we have limited only up to 5 digits. In a similar way, we can work with number of higher width.

5.1 Both Ways Representations

5.1.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned}
 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) & &:= F(3) \times F(7 + 9) - 1 \\
 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 144 &:= F((-1 + 4) \times 4) & &2529 := F(2 \times 5) + F(2 \times 9) \\
 &:= F(4 \times (4 - 1)) & &:= F(9 \times 2) - F(5 \times 2) \\
 168 &:= 1 \times F(6) \times F(8) & &2576 := F(25 - 7) - F(6) \\
 &:= F(8) \times F(6) \times 1 & &:= -F(6) + F(-7 + 5^2) \\
 377 &:= F(3 \times 7 - 7) & &2577 := F(25 - 7) - 7 \\
 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) & &:= -7 + F(-7 + 5^2) \\
 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) & &2582 := F(2 \times 5 + 8) - 2 \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) & &:= -2 + F(8 + 5 \times 2) \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & &2584 := F(2 \times (5 + 8 - 4)) \\
 &:= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) & &:= F((-4 + 8) \times 5 - 2) \\
 1292 &:= 1 \times F(2 \times 9)/2 & &2585 := F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) \\
 &:= F(2 \times 9)/2 \times 1 & &:= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 1536 &:= (1 + 5) \times F(3)^{F(6)} & &2586 := 2 + F((-5 + 8) \times 6) \\
 &:= F(6)^3 \times F(5 - 1) & &:= F(6 \times (8 - 5)) + 2 \\
 1589 &:= -F(1 + 5) + F(8 + 9) & &3373 := (F(3) + F(7))^3 - F(3) \\
 &:= F(9 + 8) - F(5 + 1) & &:= -F(3) + (F(3) + F(7))^3 \\
 1618 &:= F(16 + 1) + F(8) & &4791 := F(4) \times F(7 + 9 + 1) \\
 &:= F(8) + F(16 + 1) & &:= F(1 + 9 + 7) \times F(4) \\
 1848 &:= (1 + F(8)) \times 4 \times F(8) & &4876 := -4 + F(8 + 7) \times F(6) \\
 &:= 84 \times (F(8) + 1) & &:= F(6) \times F(7 + 8) - 4 \\
 1856 &:= -1 + F(8 + 5) \times F(6) & &4893 := F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - 3 \\
 &:= F(6) \times (F(5 + 8) - 1) & &:= -3 + F(9) \times F(8 + 4) \\
 1925 &:= (1 + F(9)) \times F(2 \times 5) & &4913 := -4 + F(9 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= F(5 \times 2) \times (F(9) + 1) & &:= (-F(3) + 19)^{F(4)} \\
 1973 &:= -1 + F(9 + 7) \times F(3) & &6936 := 6 \times F(9) \times F(3 + 6) \\
 & & &:= F(6 + 3) \times F(9) \times 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10336 &:= (1 + 03) \times F(3 \times 6) \\ &:= F(6 \times 3) \times (3 + 01) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10937 &:= -1 \times 09 + F(3 \times 7) \\ &:= F(7 \times 3) - 9 \times 01 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11392 &:= F(11) \times F(3)^{9-2} \\ &:= 2^{9-F(3)} \times F(11) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12776 &:= F(1 + 2 + 7 + 7) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times F(7 + 7 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12788 &:= -1 + (-F(2) + F(7 + 8)) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times (F(8 + 7) - F(2)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12797 &:= (-1 + F(2 \times 7)) \times F(9) + F(7) \\ &:= F(7) + F(9) \times (F(7 \times 2) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12798 &:= 1 + F(2 \times 7) \times F(9) - F(8) \\ &:= -F(8) + F(9) \times F(7 \times 2) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12817 &:= -1 + (F(2 \times 8) - 1) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (-1 + F(8 \times 2)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12818 &:= (-1 + F(2 \times 8)) \times F(-1 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 - 1) \times (F(8 \times 2) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) \\ &:= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12959 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times 5 + F(9) \\ &:= F(9) + 5 \times (F(9 \times 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13525 &:= F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 2 - 5 \\ &:= -5 + 2 \times F(5 \times (3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13546 &:= F(1 \times 3) \times (F(5 \times 4) + F(6)) \\ &:= (F(6) + F(4 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13549 &:= 1 + F(3) \times (F(5 \times 4) + 9) \\ &:= (9 + F(4 \times 5)) \times F(3) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13572 &:= (1 + 35) \times F(7 \times 2) \\ &:= F(2 \times 7) \times (5 + 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13837 &:= (1 \times 3 \times 8)^3 + F(7) \\ &:= F(7) + (3 \times 8)^3 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14336 &:= 14 \times F(3)^{F(3)+F(6)} \\ &:= F(6)^3 \times (3^{F(4)} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14678 &:= -1 + F(4) \times F(6 + 7) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times F(7 + 6) \times F(4) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14976 &:= F(-1 + 4 + 9) \times F(7) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times F(7) \times F(9 + 4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14987 &:= (-1 + F(4) \times F(9) \times F(8)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times (F(8) \times F(9) \times F(4) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15464 &:= F(1 + 5) + F(4 \times 6)/F(4) \\ &:= F(4 \times 6)/F(4) + F(5 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15665 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + F(6) \times 5 \\ &:= 5^6 + F(6) \times 5 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16376 &:= (1^6 + 3)^7 - F(6) \\ &:= -F(6) + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16383 &:= -1 + F(6)^{-3+8}/F(3) \\ &:= F(3)^{8+3} \times F(6) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17496 &:= (-1 + F(7)^{F(4)} - 9) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (9/F(4))^7 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17711 &:= F((1 + 1) \times 7 + 7 + 1) \\ &:= F(17 + 7 - 1 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17997 &:= (-1 \times F(7) + F(9 + 9)) \times 7 \\ &:= (-F(7) + F(9 + 9)) \times 7 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18756 &:= (1 + (-8 + F(7))^5) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times (5^{F(7)-8} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19447 &:= -1 + F(9) \times 44 \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times 44 \times F(9) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19449 &:= -1 - F(9 + 4) + F(4)^9 \\ &:= -F(9 + 4) + F(4)^9 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19649 &:= (1 + F(9) - F(6))^{F(4)} - F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) + (-F(4) + 6)^9 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19682 &:= -1 + (9 - 6)^{8+F(2)} \\ &:= F(2 + 8 - 6)^9 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19684 &:= 1 + (9 - 6)^8 \times F(4) \\ &:= F(4)^8 \times (-6 + 9) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19697 &:= 1 + (9 - 6)^9 + F(7) \\ &:= F(7) + (9 - 6)^9 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19747 &:= (7 + F(4)^7) \times 9 + 1 \\ &:= 1 + 9 \times (7 + F(4)^7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19965 &:= (-1 + F(9)) \times (F(9 + 6) - 5) \\ &:= (-5 + F(6 + 9)) \times (F(9) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20274 &:= (F(20) \times F(2) - 7) \times F(4) \\ &:= F(4) \times (-7 + F(20)) \times F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21168 &:= (21 + F(16)) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times (6 + 1) \times F(12) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21894 &:= 2 \times (1 + F(8 + 9 + 4)) \\ &:= (F(4 + 9 + 8) + 1) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23182 &:= -2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8) / 2 \\ &:= -2 + F(8 \times 1 \times 3) / 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23183 &:= (-2 + F(3 \times 1 \times 8)) / F(3) \\ &:= F(3 \times 8) / F(1 \times 3) - F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23184 &:= F(23 + 1) / (8/4) \\ &:= F(4 \times (8 + 1 - 3)) / 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23688 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 + 8) \times 6 \times F(3) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24334 &:= 2 \times (-4 + 3^3)^{F(4)} \\ &:= (-4 + 3^3)^{F(4)} \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24447 &:= F(2 \times 4 \times 4 - 4) / F(7) \\ &:= F(7 \times 4) / (F(4) \times 4 + F(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24649 &:= -F(2) + (F(4)^6 - 4) \times F(9) \\ &:= (F(9) \times F(4) + F(6 + 4))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25368 &:= 2 \times (F(5 \times 3) - 6) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times (-6 + F(3 \times 5)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27648 &:= 2^7 \times 6^{F(-4+8)} \\ &:= 8^{F(4)} \times 6 \times (7 + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27783 &:= (2 + 7/7) \times F(8)^3 \\ &:= 3 \times F(8)^{7/7+2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28547 &:= -F(2) + (8 + 5)^4 - F(7) \\ &:= F(7)^4 + 5 - F(8) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28623 &:= F(2 \times 8) \times (6 + 23) \\ &:= (3 + 26) \times F(8 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28624 &:= F(2) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times F(2^4) &:= (-F(6) + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times (2 + F(3)) \\ &:= F(4^2) \times (F(6) + F(8)) + F(2) \\ 28635 &:= -F(2) - F(8) + F(6 \times 3 + 5) \\ &:= F(5 + 3 \times 6) - F(8) - F(2) \\ 28641 &:= -2 \times 8 + F(6 \times 4 - 1) \\ &:= F(-1 + 4 \times 6) - 8 \times 2 \\ 28644 &:= (-F(2) + 8) \times (F(6)^4 - 4) \\ &:= (-4 + 4^6) \times (8 - F(2)) \\ 28654 &:= F(2 \times (8 + 6) - 5) - F(4) \\ &:= -F(4) + F(-5 + (6 + 8) \times 2) \\ 28655 &:= -2 + F(8 \times 6 - 5 \times 5) \\ &:= F(5 \times 5 + 6 - 8) - 2 \\ 28657 &:= F(2 + (-8 + 6 + 5) \times 7) \\ &:= F(7 \times 5 - 6 - 8 + 2) \\ 28659 &:= 2 + F((8 - 6)^5 - 9) \\ &:= F(-9 \times 5 + 68) + 2 \\ 28678 &:= F(2 + 8 + 6 + 7) + F(8) \\ &:= F(8) + F(7 + 6 + 8 + 2) \\ 29267 &:= (-2 + 9) \times F(2 \times 6 + 7) \\ &:= 7 \times F(6 + 2 + 9 + 2) \\ 29988 &:= (F(2) \times F(9) + F(9)) \times F(8) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times (8 + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(2) \\ 32496 &:= (F(3 \times 2)^4 - F(9)) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (-F(9) + 4^{2 \times 3}) \\ 32696 &:= (F(3)^{2 \times 6} - 9) \times F(6) \\ &:= -F(6) \times 9 + F(6)^{2+3} \\ 32736 &:= (-F(3) + F((2 + 7) \times 3)) / 6 \end{aligned}$$
$$\begin{aligned} 32739 &:= 3 \times (F(2) + F(7 \times 3) - F(9)) \\ &:= (-F(9) + F(3 \times 7) + F(2)) \times 3 \\ 32748 &:= (-3 + 2^{F(7)}) \times 4 - 8 \\ &:= (-8 + 4^7 - 2) \times F(3) \\ 32758 &:= -F(3) + (F(2) + 7)^5 - 8 \\ &:= 8^5 + F(7) - 23 \\ 32772 &:= (2^{7+7} + 2) \times F(3) \\ &:= F(3) \times (2^{7+7} + 2) \\ 32838 &:= 3 \times F(2 \times 8 - 3 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 + 3 + 8) + F(23) \\ 32856 &:= 3 \times (F(2 \times 8 + 5) + 6) \\ &:= (6 + F(5 + 8 \times 2)) \times 3 \\ 32937 &:= 3 \times (-F(2) + F(9) + F(3 \times 7)) \\ &:= (F(7 \times 3) + F(9) - F(2)) \times 3 \\ 33286 &:= F(3 \times 3) \times (F(2 \times 8) - F(6)) \\ &:= (-F(6) + F(8 \times 2)) \times F(3 \times 3) \\ 33446 &:= -F(3) + F(3 + 4 \times 4) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times F(4 \times 4 + 3) - F(3) \\ 33552 &:= F(2 \times 5) \times F(5 \times 3) + F(3) \\ &:= F(3) + F(3 \times 5) \times F(5 \times 2) \\ 33592 &:= (F(3 + 3) + 5) \times F(9 \times 2) \\ &:= F(2 \times 9) \times (5 + F(3 + 3)) \\ 33618 &:= (F(3) + F(3 \times 6)) \times F(-1 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 - 1) \times (F(6 \times 3) + F(3)) \\ 33647 &:= 3 + (F(3 \times 6) + 4) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (4 + F(6 \times 3)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33667 &:= -3 + (F(3 \times 6) + 6) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (6 + F(6 \times 3)) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34992 &:= 3 \times ((F(4) + 9) \times 9)^2 \\ &:= F(2) \times (9 + 9)^4 / 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35421 &:= F(3) \times F(5 \times 4 + 2) - 1 \\ &:= -1 + F(2 + 4 \times 5) \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35422 &:= F(3) \times (5 - 4) \times F(22) \\ &:= 2 \times F(24 - 5 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35937 &:= (-F(-3 + 5) + F(9))^{F(-3+7)} \\ &:= ((F(7) - F(3)) \times F(9 - 5))^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36173 &:= F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + F(7)) - 3 \\ &:= -3 + (F(7) + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36176 &:= F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + 7 + 6) \\ &:= (6 + 7 + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36288 &:= 36 \times (F(2 \times 8) + F(8)) \\ &:= F(8) \times (8 - 2 + 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38448 &:= F(3 + 8) \times F(4) \times F(4 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 + 4) \times F(4) \times F(8 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38763 &:= 3 + (8 + 7) \times F(6 \times 3) \\ &:= (F((3 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39239 &:= 3 + (F(9)^2 - F(3)) \times F(9) \\ &:= (F(9)^{F(3)} - 2) \times F(9) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39284 &:= (F(3 \times 9) + 2) / (8 - F(4)) \\ &:= -4 - 8 \times 2 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39296 &:= -F(3) + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - 6 \\ &:= -6 + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39298 &:= F(3) + F(9)^2 \times F(9) - 8 \\ &:= -8 + F(9)^2 \times F(9) + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39302 &:= -3 + F(9)^3 + F(02) \\ &:= -2 + F(0 \times 3 + 9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39303 &:= F(3) + F(9)^3 - 03 \\ &:= -3/03 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39306 &:= F(3) + F(9)^{3+0 \times 6} \\ &:= -60 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39307 &:= 3 + F(9)^{3+0 \times 7} \\ &:= 7 \times 0 + 3 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39315 &:= 3 + F(9)^3 + F(1 + 5) \\ &:= -51 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39316 &:= 3 + F(9)^3 + 1 + F(6) \\ &:= 6 \times (-1 + 3) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39323 &:= -F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(2^3) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(2^3) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39327 &:= -3 + F(9)^3 + 2 \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times 2 - 3 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39328 &:= F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(2) + F(8) \\ &:= F(8 - 2) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39332 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - F(3^2) \\ &:= F(2) + 3^3 + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39333 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 33 \\ &:= -33 + 3^9 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$39334 := 3 + F(9)^3 + 3^{F(4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -4 + F(3 \times 3) + F(9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39336} & := -F(3) + F(9)^3 + F(3 + 6) \\
 & := F(6 + 3)^3 + F(9) - F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39348} & := 3^9 \times F(3) + F(4) - F(8) \\
 & := -F(8) + F(4) + 3^9 \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39374} & := F(3) \times (9 \times 3^7 + 4) \\
 & := (4 + F(7 - 3)^9) \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39377} & := F(39/3) \times F(7) \times F(7) \\
 & := F(7) \times F(7) \times F(39/3) \\
 \mathbf{39384} & := 3^9 \times F(3) + F(8) - F(4) \\
 & := (F(4)^8 + 3) \times (9 - 3) \\
 \mathbf{39387} & := 3^9 \times F(3) + 8 + F(7) \\
 & := F(7) + 8 + 3^9 \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39394} & := -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} \\
 & := (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39395} & := 3^9 \times F(3) + F(9) - 5 \\
 & := -5 + F(9) + 3^9 \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39396} & := F(3) \times (9 + 3^9 + 6) \\
 & := (6 + 9 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39397} & := F(3) \times (9 + 3^9) + F(7) \\
 & := F(7) + (9 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39398} & := (3 + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times F(9) - 8 \\
 & := -8 + F(9) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39434} & := F(3) \times (F(9) + F(4)^{3 \times F(4)}) \\
 & := (F(4)^{3 \times F(4)} + F(9)) \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{39474} & := F(3) \times 9 \times (-4 + F(7)^{F(4)}) \\
 & := (-4 + F(7)^{F(4)}) \times 9 \times F(3) \\
 \mathbf{42441} & := (-1 + 44) \times F(2^4) \\
 & := F(4^2) \times (44 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{42699} & := (F(4^2) + 6) \times (9 + F(9)) \\
 & := (9 + F(9)) \times (6 + F(2^4)) \\
 \mathbf{43736} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - F(3) \times 6) \\
 & := (-6 \times F(3) + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43756} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - F(6) \\
 & := -F(6) + (-5 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43757} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - 7 \\
 & := -7 + (-5 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43758} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) - 5) - F(8) \\
 & := -F(8) - 5 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43771} & := -1 \times F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 & := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{43784} & := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) \times F(8/4) \\
 & := 4 \times F((87 - 3)/4) \\
 \mathbf{43786} & := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + 8 - 6 \\
 & := -6 + 8 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43788} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) + 8/8) \\
 & := (8/8 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43792} & := 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + 9 - F(2) \\
 & := (2 + F(9 \times 7/3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43796} & := 4 \times (3 + F(7 \times (9 - 6))) \\
 & := (-6 + 9 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{43816} & := 4 \times (F(3 \times (8 - 1)) + F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (F(6) + F(18 + 3)) \times 4$$

$$\mathbf{43923} := F(4) \times (F(3) + 9)^{2 \times F(3)}$$

$$:= 3 \times (F(2) \times 9 + F(3))^4$$

$$\mathbf{44898} := (-4 + F(4) \times F(8) \times F(9)) \times F(8)$$

$$:= F(8) \times (F(9) \times F(8) \times F(4) - 4)$$

$$\mathbf{44924} := 44 \times (F(9) + F(2^4))$$

$$:= (F(4^2) + F(9)) \times 44$$

$$\mathbf{46096} := F(4 \times 6) - F(09) \times F(6)$$

$$:= -F(6) \times F(9) + F(06 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46179} := F(4 \times 6) - F(1 + 7) \times 9$$

$$:= -9 \times F(7 + 1) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46208} := F(4 \times 6) - 20 \times 8$$

$$:= -80 \times 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46224} := F(4 \times 6) - F(2 \times (2 + 4))$$

$$:= -F((4 + 2) \times 2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46226} := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - F(2 \times 6)$$

$$:= -F(6 \times 2) + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46277} := F(4 \times 6) - F(2) \times F(7) \times 7$$

$$:= -7 \times F(7) \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46283} := -3 - 82 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 - 83$$

$$\mathbf{46284} := F(4 \times 6) \times F(2) - 84$$

$$:= -4 \times F(8) \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46285} := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 85$$

$$:= 5 \times (F(8)^{F(-2+6)} - 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46288} := F(4 \times 6) - (2 + 8) \times 8$$

$$:= -8 \times (8 + 2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46294} := F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times (F(9) + F(4))$$

$$:= -(F(4) + F(9)) \times 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46295} := F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times F(9) - 5$$

$$:= -5 - F(9) \times 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46296} := F(4 \times 6) - F(2) \times 9 \times F(6)$$

$$:= -F(6) \times 9 \times F(2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46298} := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 9 \times 8$$

$$:= -8 \times 9 + 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46299} := F(4 \times 6) - F(2) - F(9) - F(9)$$

$$:= -F(9) - F(9) - F(2) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46313} := F(4 \times 6) - F(-3 + 13)$$

$$:= -F(-3 + 13) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46324} := -46 + F(3) + F(24)$$

$$:= -42 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46326} := F(4 \times 6) - F(3^2) - F(6)$$

$$:= -F(6 + 2) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46328} := F(4 \times 6) - 32 - 8$$

$$:= -8 \times (2 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46329} := F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 2 - F(9)$$

$$:= -F(9 - 2) \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46332} := F(4 \times 6) - (3 + 3)^2$$

$$:= -2 - F(3 \times 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46333} := F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 33$$

$$:= -33 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{46334} := F(4 \times 6) - F(-3 + 3 \times 4)$$

$$:= -F(4 \times 3 - 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46336 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - F(3 + 6) & &:= -5 - 5 - 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -F(6) \times F(3) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46338 &:= -(4 + 6) \times 3 + F(3 \times 8) & &:= 6 \times (-5 + 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= F(8 \times 3) - 3 \times (6 + 4) \\
 46339 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) - 3 \times 9 & &:= -F(7) + 5 - 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -9 \times 3 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46341 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3^{4-1} & &:= -8 - 5 + 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -1 \times F(4)^3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46342 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3 + 4) \times 2 & &:= -9 \times F(5 - 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= F(24) - F(3) - 6 \times 4 \\
 46343 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (F(3) + F(4))^{F(3)} & &:= F(4) + F(6 \times 3 + 7 - 1) \\
 &:= F(3) - F(4)^3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46344 &:= F((4 + 4) \times 3) - 6 \times 4 & &:= -6 + 7 \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times (4 + 4) \\
 46345 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 4 \times 5 & &:= F(7) - 7 + 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -5 \times 4 - 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46346 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - 4 \times 6 & &:= (-8 + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= F(6 \times 4) - 3 \times 6 - 4 \\
 46347 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 34 + F(7) & &:= F(-1 + 9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -F(7 + 4 - 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46348 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times 4 - 8 & &:= 2 \times (9 + 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -8 - 4 \times 3 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46352 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (3 + 5) \times 2 & &:= 3 \times 9 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -2 \times (5 + 3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46354 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) \times 5 - 4 & &:= (4 + 9) \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 &:= -4 - 5 \times F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46355 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - 5 - 5 & &:= -5 + F(9) - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 & & &:= -5 + F(9) - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46356 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (3 - 5) \times 6 & & \\
 & & & \\
 46357 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 + 5 - F(7) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46358 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 - 5 - 8 & & \\
 & & & \\
 46359 &:= -F(4) - 6 + F(3 \times 5 + 9) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46371 &:= 1^7 \times 3 + F(6 \times 4) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46376 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 + F(7) - F(6) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46377 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 - 7 + F(7) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46378 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - F(7) + F(8) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46391 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9 - 1) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46392 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F((3 + 9) \times 2) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46393 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) + 9 \times 3 & & \\
 & & & \\
 46394 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) \times (9 + 4) & & \\
 & & & \\
 46395 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3) + F(9) - 5 & & \\
 & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46396 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9) - F(6) \\ &:= -F(6) + F(9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46397 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(9) - 7 \\ &:= -7 + F(9) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46399 &:= -F(4) + F(6^3/9) + F(9) \\ &:= F(9) - 9/3 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46404 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 40 - 4 \\ &:= 40 - 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46407 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times F(07) \\ &:= F(7) \times F(04) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46419 &:= -4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(1 + 9) \\ &:= F(9 + 1) - 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46423 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4 + 2 \times 3) \\ &:= F(3 \times 2 + 4) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46428 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(4) \times (F(2) - F(8)) \\ &:= 8^2 - 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46432 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + 4^3) \times F(2) \\ &:= (F(2) + 3)^{F(4)} + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46436 &:= 4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(3)^6 \\ &:= F(6)^{F(3)} + 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46439 &:= F(4) + F(6 \times 4) + F(3) \times F(9) \\ &:= F(9) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46448 &:= -4 + F(6 \times 4) + 4 \times F(8) \\ &:= 84 - 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46449 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times F(4) \times 9 \\ &:= (9/F(4))^4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46472 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(7) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times F(7) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46476 &:= 4 + F(6 \times 4) + F(7) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times F(7) + 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46478 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4 + 7) + F(8) \\ &:= F(8) + F(7 + 4) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46487 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + F(8)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times (F(8) - 4) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46488 &:= ((F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times (-F(8) + (F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46496 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(9) - F(6) \\ &:= -F(6) + F(9) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46497 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4 \times F(9) - 7 \\ &:= -7 + F(9) \times 4 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46512 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F((5 + 1) \times 2) \\ &:= F(2 \times (1 + 5)) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46533 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 5 \times 33 \\ &:= 33 \times 5 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46536 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(5 + 3) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times F(3 + 5) + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46566 &:= -F(4) \times 6 \times 5 + 6^6 \\ &:= 6^6 - 5 \times 6 \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46618 &:= -4 + 6^6 - F(1 + 8) \\ &:= -F(8 + 1) + 6^6 - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46619 &:= -4 + 6^6 + 1 - F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) \times 1 + 6^6 - F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46624 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (6 - 2)^4 & &:= F(8 - 5) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} \\
 &:= 4 \times 2^6 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46627 &:= -F(4) + 6^6 - 2 \times F(7) & &:= F(4) + 6^{F(6) \times 5 - F(9)} \\
 &:= -F(7) \times 2 + 6^6 - F(4) & &:= (9 + 5 - F(6))^6 + F(4) \\
 46636 &:= 4 + 6^6 - 3 \times F(6) & &:= F(4) + 6^6 + F(7) - 1 \\
 &:= -F(6) \times 3 + 6^6 + 4 & &:= -1 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46637 &:= -4 + 6^6 - F(3) - F(7) & &:= (F(4) + 6^6 + F(7)) \times F(2) \\
 &:= F(7) + F(3)^{F(6)} + F(6 \times 4) & &:= F(2) \times F(7) + 6^6 + F(4) \\
 46638 &:= F(4) + (6 \times 6)^3 - F(8) & &:= -F(4) + 6^6 + 7 \times F(4) \\
 &:= (8 - F(3))^6 - 6 \times F(4) & &:= F(4) \times 7 + 6^6 - F(4) \\
 46643 &:= F(4) + 6^6 - 4^{F(3)} & &:= -4 + 6^6 - 7 + F(9) \\
 &:= -3 \times F(4) + 6^6 - 4 & &:= F(9) - 7 + 6^6 - 4 \\
 46645 &:= 4 + 6^6 - F(4) \times 5 & &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(7 + 7) + F(9) \\
 &:= -5 \times F(4) + 6^6 + 4 & &:= F(9) + F(7 + 7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46646 &:= -4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} - 6 & &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(7) \times 8 \times 4 \\
 &:= -6 - 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} & &:= 4 \times 8 \times F(7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46647 &:= 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(7) & &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(7) \times F(9) - F(7) \\
 &:= -F(7) + 4 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)} & &:= F(7) \times F(9) - F(7) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46653 &:= -4 + 6^6 + F(5 - 3) & &:= (4 + 6) \times F(8) + 6^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 + F(6))^6 - F(4) & &:= 6^6 + F(8) \times (6 + 4) \\
 46654 &:= -4 + 6^6 + 5 - F(4) & &:= F(4 \times 6) + 9 \times 4^{F(4)} \\
 &:= -4 + 5 + 6^6 - F(4) & &:= 4^{F(4)} \times 9 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46657 &:= F(4) + 6^6 + 5 - 7 & &:= F(4 \times 6) - 9 + F(6 + 9) \\
 &:= -7 + 5 + 6^6 + F(4) & &:= -9 + F(6 + 9) + F(6 \times 4) \\
 46658 &:= 4 + 6^6 - F(-5 + 8) & &:= F(4 \times 6) + 9 + F(8 + 7) \\
 & & &:= F(7 + 8) + 9 + F(6 \times 4) \\
 47345 &:= 4 + 7 \times (-F(3) + F(4 \times 5)) & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (F(5 \times 4) - F(3)) \times 7 + 4$$

$$:= (4 + F(2^4)) \times F(3)^6$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{49152} &:= F(4) \times (9 - 1)^5 / 2 \\ &:= 2^{5 \times 1 + 9} \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{64847} &:= -F(6) + (4 + F(8)^{F(4)}) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times (4 + F(8)^{F(4)}) - F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{49164} &:= (F(4) + 9) \times (1 + F(6)^4) \\ &:= (4^6 + 1) \times (9 + F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{65447} &:= -F(6 + 5) + 4 \times 4^7 \\ &:= (F(7) + F(4))^4 - F(5 + 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54136} &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times F(3)) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (F(3) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{65533} &:= F(6)^5 \times (5 - 3) - 3 \\ &:= -3 + F(3)^{5+5+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54298} &:= (F(5 + 4) \times F(2)) \times F(9 + 8) \\ &:= F(8 + 9) \times F(2) \times F(4 + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{65673} &:= -F(6) + 5 + 6 \times F(7 \times 3) \\ &:= F(3 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 - F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54336} &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 3^3) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (3^3 + F(4 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{68796} &:= (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) \times F(8) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times F(8) \times F(7) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54696} &:= (F(5 \times 4) + F(6) \times 9) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (9 \times F(6) + F(4 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69626} &:= -6 + F(9) \times F(6) \times 2^{F(6)} \\ &:= -6 + 2^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54737} &:= 5 \times (4 + F(7 \times 3)) - F(7) \\ &:= -F(7) + (F(3 \times 7) + 4) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69638} &:= 6 + F(9) \times F(6) \times F(3)^8 \\ &:= 8 \times F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54936} &:= (F(5 \times 4) + F(9) \times 3) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (3 \times F(9) + F(4 \times 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69972} &:= (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times 7^2 \\ &:= (F(2 \times 7) - F(9)) \times F(9) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55924} &:= -5^5 + 9^{F(2)+4} \\ &:= F(4)^{F(2)+9} - 5^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69984} &:= 6 \times 9 \times 9 \times F(8 + 4) \\ &:= F(4 + 8) \times 9 \times 9 \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{59057} &:= -5 + 9^{05} + F(7) \\ &:= F(7) - 5 + 09^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{73739} &:= -7 + (F(3)^{F(7)} + F(3)) \times 9 \\ &:= 9 \times F(3)^{F(7)} - F(3) + F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{62896} &:= (F(6) \times F(2 \times 8) - F(9)) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (-F(9) + F(8 \times 2) \times F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74415} &:= (7 + 4) \times F(4 \times 1 \times 5) \\ &:= F(5 \times 1 \times 4) \times (4 + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{63376} &:= F(6) \times F(3 \times 3) \times F(7 + 6) \\ &:= F(6 + 7) \times F(3 \times 3) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74752} &:= -F(7) \times F(4) \times 7 + F(5^2) \\ &:= F(25) - F(7) \times F(4) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{63424} := F(6)^{F(3)} \times (4 + F(2^4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74795 &:= (F(7) + F(4)^7) \times F(9) - 5 & &:= (F(8 + 7 + 6) + F(6)) \times 7 \\ &:= -5 + F(9) \times (F(7) + F(4)^7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74878 &:= F(-7 + 4 \times 8) - 7 \times F(8) & &76853 := -7 + 6 \times F(8) \times F(5 \times 3) \\ &:= -F(8) \times 7 + F(8 \times 4 - 7) & &:= F(3 \times 5) \times F(8) \times 6 - (7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74936 &:= (-7 + 4 \times 9) \times F(3 \times 6) & &76978 := F(7) \times 6 \times F(9 + 7) - 8 \\ &:= F(6 \times 3) \times (9 \times 4 - 7) & &:= -8 + F(7 + 9) \times 6 \times F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74952 &:= -F(7) \times F(4) - F(9) + F(5^2) & &78735 := (F(7) - 8)^7 + F(3 \times 5) \\ &:= F(25) - F(9) - F(4) \times F(7) & &:= F(5 \times 3) + (F(7) - 8)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) & &79947 := F(7 + 9) \times (F(9) + 47) \\ &:= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 & &:= (F(7) - 4) \times 9 \times F(9 + 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75012 &:= -F(7) + F((5 \times 01)^2) & &79968 := (F(7) \times F(9) + F(9)) \times F(6) \times F(8) \\ &:= F(2 \times 10 + 5) - F(7) & &:= 8 \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75025 &:= F(7 \times 5 \times 0 + 25) & &82936 := (8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(3)} - F(6) \\ &:= F(5^{2 \times 0 - 5 + 7}) & &:= (F(6) \times (F(3) + F(9)))^2 - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75026 &:= -7 + F(5^{02}) + F(6) & &83349 := F(8)^3 \times 3^4 / 9 \\ &:= -6 + F(20 + 5) + 7 & &:= (9 \times (4 + 3))^{F(3)} \times F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75029 &:= F(7) + F(5^{02}) - 9 & &85764 := F(8) \times (-5 - 7 + F(6)^4) \\ &:= -9 + F(20 + 5) + F(7) & &:= (4^6 - 7 - 5) \times F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75032 &:= 7 + F(5^{0 \times 3 + 2}) & &86919 := (-F(9) + F(19) - F(6)) \times F(8) \\ &:= F((2 + 3) \times 05) + 7 & &:= F(8) \times (-F(6) - F(9) + F(19)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75038 &:= F(7) + F(5 \times (-03 + 8)) & &87387 := (-F(8) + F(7 \times 3)) \times 8 - F(7) \\ &:= F((8 - 3) \times 05) + F(7) & &:= -F(7) + (-F(8) + F(3 \times 7)) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76398 &:= (F(7) \times F(6) + 3) \times F(9) \times F(8) & &87639 := F(8) + (-7 + F(6 \times 3)) \times F(9) \\ &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times (3 + F(6) \times F(7)) & &:= F(9) \times (F(3 \times 6) - 7) + F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76622 &:= 7 \times F((6 + 6^2) / 2) & &87672 := 8 \times (F(7) + F(6 \times 7 / 2)) \\ &:= F(22 - 6 / 6) \times 7 & &:= (F(27 - 6) + F(7)) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$76678 := 7 \times (F(6) + F(6 + 7 + 8)) \quad 87736 := 8 + F(7) + F(7 \times 3) \times F(6)$$

$$:= (F(6) + F(3 \times 7) + F(7)) \times 8$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{87856} &:= (F(8) + F(7)) \times F((8 - 5) \times 6) \\ &:= F(6 \times (-5 + 8)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{87937} &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) \\ &:= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{87945} &:= (-8 - F(7) + F(9)) \times F(4 \times 5) \\ &:= F(5 \times 4) \times (F(9) - F(7) - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88595} &:= (8 + F(8 + 5 + 9)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (F(9 + 5 + 8) + 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{89964} &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(4) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{91982} &:= F(9 + 1 + 9) \times (F(8) + F(2)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(9 + 1 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{93346} &:= F(9) + F(3) \times (F(3) + 4)^6 \\ &:= 6^{4+3} / 3 + F(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98325} &:= 9 \times (-F(8) + F(3 \times (2 + 5))) \\ &:= (F((5 + 2) \times 3) - F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98469} &:= (9 + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times F(8) \times 9 \\ &:= F(9) + (8 - F(4)) \times F(4)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98577} &:= 9 \times (F((8 - 5) \times 7) + 7) \\ &:= (7 + F(7 \times (-5 + 8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98586} &:= 9 \times (F(8 + 5 + 8) + F(6)) \\ &:= (F(6) + F(8 + 5 + 8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98703} &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) \\ &:= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

5.1.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13} &:= F(1 + 3!) \\ &:= F(3! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{21} &:= F(F((1 + 2)!)) \\ &:= F(F((2 + 1)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{23} &:= 2 + F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24} &:= F(2) \times 4! \\ &:= 4! \times F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{42} &:= 2 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{48} &:= F(4)! \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{147} &:= 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times F(F((4 - 1)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{227} &:= -(F(2 + 2))! + F(F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7)) - (F(2 + 2))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{247} &:= (-2 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{254} &:= F(F(2 + 5)) + F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(5 + 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{257} &:= (-F(2) + 5)! + F(F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7)) + (5 - F(2))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{273} &:= F(2) \times F(7) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(7) \times F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 274 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7) + F(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 336 &:= F(3) \times F(3!) \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= F(6)! / (F(3) + 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 347 &:= 3!! / F(F(4)) - F(7) \\ &:= -F(7) + F(4)! / F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354 &:= (-F(3) + 5!) \times F(4) \\ &:= F(4) \times (5!) - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 371 &:= -3! + F(F(7) + 1) \\ &:= F(1 + F(7)) - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 384 &:= F(3) \times 8 \times 4! \\ &:= 4! \times 8 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 432 &:= F(4) \times F(3! \times 2) \\ &:= 2 \times 3!^{F(4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 433 &:= -F(F(4)!) + F(F(3!))^{F(3)} \\ &:= F(F(3!))^{F(3)} - F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 441 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(4-1)} \\ &:= F(F((F(1 \times 4)!))^{F(F(4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 442 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(2) \\ &:= F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 443 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(3) \\ &:= F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 445 &:= F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 447 &:= F(4)!! - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7) \\ &:= -F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 448 &:= F(F(4)!)/!(F(4)!/8) \\ &:= 8! / (F(4)!/!) \times F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 462 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(2)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(8)) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times (F(8) + F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 487 &:= (4!/8)!! - F(F(7)) \\ &:= -F(F(7)) + (F(8 - 4))!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 496 &:= -F(F(4)!) + 9!/6! \\ &:= -F(6) + 9! / F(4)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 504 &:= F(F(5 + 0!)) \times 4! \\ &:= 4! \times F(F(0! + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 534 &:= F(5 + 3!) \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4)! \times F(3! + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 546 &:= (5 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 564 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times (F(F(6)) + 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 576 &:= -F(5 + 7) + 6! \\ &:= 6! - F(7 + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 594 &:= -5! + F(9) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 634 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 3!) + 4! \\ &:= 4! + F(-3! + F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 664 &:= -F(6)!/6! + F(4)!! \\ &:= F(4)!! - F(6)!/6! \end{aligned}$$

$$679 := 6! - 7 - F(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -F(9) - 7 + 6! \\
 \mathbf{694} & := 6! - F(9) + F(F(4)!) \\
 & := F(4)!! - F(9) + F(6) \\
 \mathbf{706} & := -F(7) - 0! + 6! \\
 & := 6! - 0! - F(7) \\
 \mathbf{714} & := (7 - 1)! - F(4)! \\
 & := -F(4)! + (-1 + 7)! \\
 \mathbf{732} & := F(7) + 3!! - F(2) \\
 & := -F(2) + 3!! + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{733} & := F(7) + (3 + 3)! \\
 & := (3 + 3)! + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{734} & := 7 \times F(3) + F(4)!! \\
 & := F(F(F(4))) + 3!! + F(7) \\
 \mathbf{735} & := 7 \times F(F(3!)) \times 5 \\
 & := 5 \times F(F(3!)) \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{746} & := F(7) \times F(F(4)) + 6! \\
 & := 6! + F(F(4)) \times F(7) \\
 \mathbf{748} & := 7 + F(4)!! + F(8) \\
 & := F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 \\
 \mathbf{754} & := -F(F(7)) + F(-5 + F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 & := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 5) - F(F(7)) \\
 \mathbf{846} & := F(8) \times F(4)! + 6! \\
 & := 6! + F(4)! \times F(8) \\
 \mathbf{945} & := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\
 & := 5 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{947} & := F(9) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(7)) \\
 & := F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{953} & := -F(9) + F(-5 + F(F(3!))) \\
 & := F(F(F(3!)) - 5) - F(9) \\
 \mathbf{1323} & := (-1 + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 & := F(F(3!)) \times (2^{3!} - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1324} & := 1 + F(F(3!))^2 \times F(4) \\
 & := F(F(F(4)!))^2 \times 3 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1336} & := (-1 + F(3!) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(6) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(3!) \times F(F(3!)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1343} & := -1 + (F(3!))! / (4! + 3!) \\
 & := (F(3!))! / (4! + 3!) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1344} & := (1 + F(3! + 4)) \times 4! \\
 & := 4! \times (F(4 + 3!) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1359} & := -1 + F(3!) \times 5 \times F(9) \\
 & := F(9) \times 5! / 3 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1374} & := (-1 - 3 + F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\
 & := (-4 + F(F(7))) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1376} & := -1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6)) \\
 & := -F(F(6)) + F(F(7)) \times 3! - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1378} & := 1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(8) \\
 & := -F(8) + F(F(7)) \times 3! + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1398} & := 1 \times 3! \times F(F(9) - F(8)) \\
 & := F(-F(8) + F(9)) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1404} & := (1 + F(F(F(4)! + 0!)) \times F(4)! \\
 & := F(4)! \times (0! + F(F(F(4)! + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1427} & := 1 \times F(4)!! \times 2 - F(7) \\
 & := -F(7) + 2 \times (4 - 1)!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1428 &:= F(1 + F(F(4)!)) \times 2 \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times 2 \times F(F(F(4)! + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1433 &:= -1 - F(4)! + 3!! + 3!! \\ &:= (3!! - 3) \times F(F(4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1434 &:= (1 - 4 + 3!!) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= (-F(4) + 3!!) \times F(4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1436 &:= (1 - F(4)) \times (F(3) - 6!) \\ &:= 6! \times F(3) - 4 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1438 &:= (1 - F(4)!!) \times (3! - 8) \\ &:= (8 - 3!) \times (F(4)!! - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1439 &:= -1 + F(F(4)) \times (-3 + 9)! \\ &:= (9 - 3)! \times F(F(4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1452 &:= (1 + F(4)!! + 5) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (5 + F(4)!! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1456 &:= F(1 + F(4)!) \times (5! - F(6)) \\ &:= (-F(6) + 5!) \times F(F(4)! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1457 &:= 1 + (-F(F(4)!) + 5!) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (5! - F(F(4)!)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1462 &:= 1 + F(F(F(4)!)) + 6! \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times 6! + F(F(F(4)!)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1463 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! \times F(3) \\ &:= F(3) \times 6! + 4! - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1464 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 6! + 4! \\ &:= 4! + 6! \times F(4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1467 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (6! + F(7)) \\ &:= (F(7) + 6!) \times F(F(4)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$1476 := (F(1 + F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$:= -6! + F(7)^{F(4)} - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1482 &:= (1 \times F(4)!! + F(8)) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (F(8) + (4 - 1)!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1483 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + 3!!) \\ &:= (3!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1484 &:= (1 + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(4)!! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1547 &:= (-1 + 5 \times 4!) \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times (4! \times 5 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1557 &:= -F(-1 + 5) + 5! \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times 5! - F(5 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1561 &:= 1 + 5! \times F(6 + 1) \\ &:= F(1 + 6) \times 5! + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1572 &:= (1 + 5!) \times F(7) - F(2) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(7) \times (5! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1574 &:= (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + F(F(F(4))) \\ &:= F(F(F(4))) + F(7) \times (5! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1637 &:= -1 + F(F(6)) \times 3! \times F(7) \\ &:= F(7) \times 3! \times F(F(6)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1638 &:= F(1 + 6) \times 3! \times F(8) \\ &:= F(8) \times 3! \times F(6 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1674 &:= -1 \times 6 + 7!/F(4) \\ &:= F(4)!! + F(F(7)) + 6! + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1724 &:= -1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \\ &:= F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) - 7! - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1726 &:= 1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) \\ &:= F(F(F(6)) - F(2)) - 7! + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1745 &:= 1 + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - 5! \\
 &:= -5! + F(F(4)!) \times F(F(7)) + 1 \\
 1793 &:= 1 + (F(F(7)) - 9) \times F(3!) \\
 &:= F(3!) \times (-9 + F(F(7))) + 1 \\
 1833 &:= (1 + F(F(8) - 3!)) \times 3 \\
 &:= (3! + (F(3!)!)) / (F(8) + 1) \\
 1843 &:= F(18) - F(4)!! - F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= -F(F(3!)) + F(F(4)!) \times F(F(8 - 1)) \\
 1873 &:= 1 + 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(3!) \\
 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + 8 + 1 \\
 1886 &:= -F(1 + 8) + 8! / F(F(6)) \\
 &:= F(6)! / F(8) - F(8 + 1) \\
 1943 &:= (-1 + (9 \times (F(4)!^3))) \\
 &:= 3!^{F(4)} \times 9 - 1 \\
 1944 &:= (((1 \times 9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 4!) \\
 &:= F(4)!^{F(4)} \times 9 \times 1 \\
 2016 &:= (F((2 + 0)!))! / (-1 + F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(6)! / (10 \times 2) \\
 2136 &:= (2 + 1) \times (3!! - F(6)) \\
 &:= (6! - F(3!)) \times (1 + 2) \\
 2145 &:= (2 + 1) \times (F(4)!! - 5) \\
 &:= (-5 + F(4)!!) \times (1 + 2) \\
 2147 &:= (2 + 1)!! \times F(4) - F(7) \\
 &:= -F(7) + F(4) \times (1 + 2)!! \\
 2154 &:= (-2 + (1 + 5)!) \times F(4) \\
 &:= F(4) \times ((5 + 1)! - 2) \\
 2184 &:= ((2 + 1)!! + 8) \times F(4) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (8 + (1 + 2)!!) \\
 2274 &:= (2 + F(2 \times 7)) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= F(4)! \times (F(7 \times 2) + 2) \\
 2304 &:= (2 \times (3 + 0)!)^{F(F(4))} \\
 &:= (4! \times F(03))^2 \\
 2312 &:= 2 \times (F(F(3!) + 1))^2 \\
 &:= 2 \times F(1 + F(3!))^2 \\
 2353 &:= F(2) + F(F(3!)) \times (5! - F(3!)) \\
 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (5! - F(3!)) + F(2) \\
 2354 &:= 2 - F(F(3!)) \times (-5! + F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= (-F(F(4)!) + 5!) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 2372 &:= 2 \times (3!! + F(F(7)) \times 2) \\
 &:= (2 \times F(F(7)) + 3!!) \times 2 \\
 2373 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + (3 + 2)!) \\
 2375 &:= 2 + F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + 5!) \\
 &:= (5! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) + 2. \\
 2376 &:= (2^{3!} + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(7)) + F(3!)^2) \\
 2435 &:= (-F(F(F(2) + F(4)!)) + 3!!) \times 5 \\
 &:= -5 \times (-3!! + F(F(F(4)! + F(2)))) \\
 2438 &:= -2 + 4 \times F(-3! + F(8)) \\
 &:= F(F(8) - 3!) \times 4 - 2 \\
 2439 &:= -F(2) + 4 \times F(3! + 9) \\
 &:= F(9 + 3!) \times 4 - F(2) \\
 2444 &:= (F(2) + F((F(F(F(4)!)) - F(4)!))) \times 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 4 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - F(4)!) + F(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2448} := F(2 \times F(4)!) \times (-4 + F(8))$$

$$:= (F(8) - 4) \times F(4!/2)$$

$$\mathbf{2449} := (F(2) + ((4! \times F(4)) \times F(9)))$$

$$:= F(9) \times 4! \times F(4) + F(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2456} := -F(2) + (-F(4) + 5!) \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= F(F(6)) \times (5! - F(4)) - F(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2458} := F(2) - (F(4) - 5!) \times F(8)$$

$$:= F(8) \times (5! - F(4)) + F(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2464} := -(F(2) + 4)! + F(-6 + 4!)$$

$$:= F(4! - 6) - (F(4) + 2)!$$

$$\mathbf{2465} := F(2) + F(4! - 6) - 5!$$

$$:= -5! + F(-6 + 4!) + F(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2474} := 2 \times F(4! - 7) - F(4)!!$$

$$:= -F(4)!! + F(-7 + 4!) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2478} := (-2 + (-F(F(4)) + 7)!) \times F(8)$$

$$:= (-F(8) + 7!/4) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2518} := -2 + 5! \times 1 \times F(8)$$

$$:= F(8) \times 1 \times 5! - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2519} := -F(2) + 5! \times F(-1 + 9)$$

$$:= F(9 - 1) \times 5! - F(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2533} := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(3!)) - F(3!)$$

$$:= -F(3!) + F(F(3!)) \times (5! + F(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2541} := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F((4 - 1)!))$$

$$:= 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2542} := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(2)$$

$$:= F(2) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2543} := F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(F(4))) + 5!) + 2$$

$$:= 2 + (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$\mathbf{2544} := (2 + 5)! / F(F(4)) + 4!$$

$$:= 4! + (F(F(4)) + 5)! / 2$$

$$\mathbf{2545} := 25 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5!$$

$$:= 5! \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 5^2$$

$$\mathbf{2561} := (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) - 1$$

$$:= -1 + F(F(6)) \times (5! + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2562} := (2 + 5!) \times F(6 + 2)$$

$$:= F(2 + 6) \times (5! + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2564} := (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) + F(F(4))$$

$$:= F(F(4)) + F(F(6)) \times (5! + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2574} := -2 + F(5 + F(7)) - F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= F(4!) / (F(7) + 5) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2634} := 2 \times (F(F(6)) + 3!^4)$$

$$:= F(4)! \times (-F(3) + F(F(6)))^2$$

$$\mathbf{2637} := -2 + F(F(6) + 3!) \times 7$$

$$:= 7 \times F(3! + F(6)) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2638} := -2 + 6! + (F(3!))! / F(8)$$

$$:= -8 + 3! \times F(F(6))^2$$

$$\mathbf{2644} := -2 + (F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times F(4)!$$

$$:= -F(F(4)) + F(4)! \times F(F(6))^2$$

$$\mathbf{2646} := F(2 + 6) \times F(4)! \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= F(-6 + 4!) + 62$$

$$\mathbf{2647} := F(2) \times 6! \times 4 - F(F(7))$$

$$:= (-F(F(7)) + 4 \times 6!) \times F(2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2686 &:= -2 + F(6)!/(F(8) - 6) & &:= F(F(7)) \times F(3! + 0!) + F(3!) \\
 &:= F(6)!/(F(8) - 6) - 2 \\
 2733 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(3!)) & &:= F(F(3!)) \times (0! + 4! + 5!) \\
 &:= (F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) - 7)/2 & &:= (5! + 4! + 0!) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 2747 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 7 & &:= (3! - 1)^5 + F(9) \\
 &:= F(F(7)) - F(4)! + 7!/2 & &:= F(9) + 5^{-1+3!} \\
 2753 &:= F(F(2) \times F(7)) + 5! \times F(F(3!)) & &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 1) - 6! \times 5 \\
 &:= F(F(F(3) + 5)) + 7!/2 & &:= -5 \times 6! + F(-1 + F(F(3!))) \\
 2844 &:= (-F(2) - 8 + F(4)!!) \times 4 & &:= (3! + 1)! - F(F(7)) \times F(6) \\
 &:= 4 \times (F(4)!! - 8 - F(2)) & &:= -F(6) \times F(F(7)) + (1 + 3!)! \\
 2846 &:= -F(F(2) + 8) + 4 \times 6! & &:= (3!! + 2)/F(F(4)) \times 9 \\
 &:= 6! \times 4 - F(8 + F(2)) & &:= (F(9) + 4! - F(2))^{F(3)} \\
 2856 &:= (2^8 - 5!) \times F(F(6)) & &:= F(3! \times 2) - F(6)) \times 4! \\
 &:= F(F(6)) \times (5! + 8 \times 2) & &:= 4! \times (-F(6) + F(2 \times 3!)) \\
 2878 &:= -2 + 8!/(-7 + F(8)) & &:= 3! \times 2 \times F(7) \times F(F(6)) \\
 &:= 8!/(-7 + F(8)) - 2 & &:= F(F(6)) \times F(7) \times 2 \times 3! \\
 2944 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(4)!!/F(F(4)) & &:= 3!! + F(2 \times 9) - F(6) \\
 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 4 \times 92 & &:= -F(6) + F(9 \times 2) + 3!! \\
 2964 &:= (F(-F(2) + 9) + 6!) \times 4 & &:= 3!! + F(2 \times 9) - 7 \\
 &:= 4 \times (6! + F(9 - F(2))) & &:= -7 + F(9 \times 2) + 3!! \\
 3016 &:= F(3!) \times F(0! + F(1 + 6)) & &:= F(3 \times 3!) - 0! + 3!! \\
 &:= F(F(6 + 1) + 0!) \times F(3!) & &:= 3!! - 0! + F(3 \times 3!) \\
 3024 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F((0! + 2) \times 4) & &:= 3!! + F(3! \times F(04)) \\
 &:= (F(4)^2)!/(-0! + 3!)! & &:= F(4! - 03!) + 3!! \\
 3029 &:= F(3! + 0!) \times F(F(-2 + 9)) & &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5 \\
 &:= F(F(9 - 2)) \times F(0! + 3!) & &:= 5 \times (-F(2 + F(3!)) + 3!!) \\
 3037 &:= F(3!) + F(0! + 3!) \times F(F(7)) & &:= F(F(F(3)) + 3!) \times 2^8 \\
 & & &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3344 &:= F(3) \times ((F(3!))!/4! - F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= (F(F(4)!)/4! - F(3!)) \times F(3) \\
 3347 &:= -F(7) + F(F(4)!)/(F(3) \times 3!) \\
 &:= (F(3!))/(3 \times 4) - F(7) \\
 3357 &:= -F(F(7)) + 5 \times (-F(3) + 3!!) \\
 &:= (3!! - F(3)) \times 5 - F(F(7)) \\
 3359 &:= -F(F(3)) - 3!! + 5! \times F(9) \\
 &:= F(9) \times 5! - 3!! - F(F(3)) \\
 3376 &:= F(3!)^{-3+7} - 6! \\
 &:= (F(6) + 7!/3) \times F(3) \\
 3383 &:= F(3!) + (F(8) - 3!)^3 \\
 &:= F(3!) - (3! - F(8))^3 \\
 3384 &:= F(3!) - 3!! + 8^4 \\
 &:= 4! + 8!/(F(3) \times 3!) \\
 3386 &:= -3!!/F(3) \times F(8) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(6))) - F(8) \times 3!!/F(3) \\
 3392 &:= F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 - F(2) \\
 &:= -F(2) + 9 \times F(3! + F(3!)) \\
 3393 &:= F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 \times F(F(3)) \\
 &:= F(F(3)) \times 9 \times F(3! + F(3!)) \\
 3394 &:= F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 + F(F(F(4))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 9 \times F(3! + F(3!)) \\
 3396 &:= 3! \times (3!! - F(9)) - 6! \\
 &:= F(F(6)) + (9 + 3!)^3 \\
 3427 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 4) \times 2 + F(F(7)) \\
 &:= F(F(7)) + 2 \times F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 3437 &:= F(F(7) + 3!) - 4! - 3!! \\
 &:= -3!! - 4! + F(3! + F(7)) \\
 3444 &:= (-F(3) + 4! \times 4!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= F(4)! \times (4! \times 4! - F(3)) \\
 3447 &:= -F(F(F(3!)) - 4) + 4 + 7! \\
 &:= 7! + 4 - F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 3448 &:= F(3 \times 4) \times 4! - 8 \\
 &:= -8 + 4! \times F(4 \times 3) \\
 3451 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(F(4)!)) \times (5! - 1) \\
 3452 &:= -F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(4)) + 5!^2 \\
 &:= -2 + 5!^{F(F(4))} - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 3454 &:= -F(3) + (4! + 5!) \times 4! \\
 &:= (4! + 5!) \times 4! - F(3) \\
 3456 &:= 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times F(6) \\
 &:= 6! \times 5 - F(4 \times 3) \\
 3457 &:= F(F(3)) + 4! \times F(5 + 7) \\
 &:= F(7 + 5) \times 4! + F(F(3)) \\
 3461 &:= -3!! + F(4! - 6 + 1) \\
 &:= F(16 + F(4)) - 3!! \\
 3462 &:= 3! + 4! \times F(6 \times 2) \\
 &:= F(2 \times 6) \times 4! + 3! \\
 3463 &:= -3!! + F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(3)) \\
 &:= F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) + F(F(4)) - 3!! \\
 3464 &:= F(3!) + 4! \times 6 \times 4! \\
 &:= F(4!) - F(6)! - F(4! - 3!) \\
 3466 &:= F(3) + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(6)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -F(6)! + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + F(3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3467 &:= -3!! + F(4)! + F(6 + F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7) + 6) + F(4)! - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3474 &:= -3!! + F(4) \times F(F(7)) \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4) \times F(F(7)) \times F(4)! - 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3482 &:= F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! + F(F(8) - 2) \\ &:= F(-2 + F(8)) - F(4)!! + F(F(3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3483 &:= 3 \times (F(4)!! + F(8)^{F(3)}) \\ &:= 3 \times (F(8)^{F(F(4))} + 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3485 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (-F(8) - F(F(4)) + 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3486 &:= F(3!)^4 - F(F(8) - 6) \\ &:= -F(-6 + F(8)) + 4^{3!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3487 &:= -F(3!) + (-F(4)! + F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7)) \times (F(8) - F(4)!) - F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3497 &:= F(3) + (4! - 9) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7)) \times (-9 + 4!) + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3498 &:= F(F(F(3!))) \times 4 + F(9) - 8! \\ &:= -8! + F(9) + 4 \times F(F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3511 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(11) \\ &:= -F(11) + 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3525 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25 \\ &:= 5^2 \times (5! + F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3534 &:= (F(3 \times 5) - F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4)! \times (F(3 \times 5) - F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3535 &:= (3!! - F(5 + F(3))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (-F(F(3) + 5) + 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3536 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(3)^6 \\ &:= -F(6)^{F(3)} + 5 \times 3!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3537 &:= F(3) + 5 \times (3!! - F(7)) \\ &:= (-F(7) + 3!!) \times 5 + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3538 &:= (F(3) + 5!) \times (F(3!) + F(8)) \\ &:= (F(8) + F(3!)) \times (5! + F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3544 &:= F(3!) \times 5! + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \\ &:= F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 5! \times F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3545 &:= (3!! + 5 - F(4)!) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (-F(4)! - 5 + 3!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3549 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (5! + 49) \\ &:= (-9 + F(4)!!) \times 5 - 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3554 &:= -F(F(3!)) + 5 \times (-5 + F(4)!!) \\ &:= (F(4)!! - 5) \times 5 - F(F(3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3563 &:= 3 - 5 \times (-6! + F(3!)) \\ &:= (3!! - F(6)) \times 5 + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3564 &:= F(4)! \times (6! - 5! - 3!) \\ &:= (-3! - 5! + 6!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3565 &:= (-F(3) - 5 + 6!) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (6! - 5 - F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3566 &:= 3! + 5 \times (6! - F(6)) \\ &:= (-F(6) + 6!) \times 5 + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3567 &:= F(3) + 5 \times (6! - 7) \\ &:= (-7 + 6!) \times 5 + F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3568 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (6! - 8) \\ &:= (F(8) \times F(F(6)) + 5) \times F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3569 &:= 3 + 5 \times 6! - F(9) & &:= -8 + (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 &:= -F(9) + 6! \times 5 + 3 \\
 3573 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (-7 + 3!!) & &3643 := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - 3 \\
 &:= (3!! - 7) \times 5 + F(3!) & &:= (-F(F(3!)) + 4 + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 3574 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(7) \times F(F(4)) & &3644 := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - F(F(4)) \\
 &:= -F(F(4)) \times F(7) + 5 \times 3!! & &:= (-F(4!) - F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 3579 &:= 3!! \times 5 + F(7) - F(9) & &3646 := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/(4!/F(6)) \\
 &:= -F(9) + F(7) + 5 \times 3!! & &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)!))/(6 - 3) \\
 3592 &:= 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(2) & &3656 := (F(3!))!/6! + 5 \times 6! \\
 &:= F(2) - 9 + 5 \times 3!! & &:= 6! \times 5 + F(6)!/3!! \\
 3593 &:= 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(3) & &3672 := 3! \times (F(F(6) + 7) + 2) \\
 &:= F(3) - 9 + 5 \times 3!! & &:= (2 + F(7 + F(6))) \times 3! \\
 3594 &:= -3! + 5! \times (F(9) - 4) & &3673 := 3!! + (F(F(F(6))) - 7!)/F(3) \\
 &:= (-4 + F(9)) \times 5! - 3! & &:= 3!! + (-7! + F(F(F(6))))/F(3) \\
 3595 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-5 + 9)))) \times 5 & &3674 := F(F(3!)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(7))/F(4) \\
 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(9 - 5))) + 3!!) & &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(7) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 3597 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(-9 + F(7)) & &3675 := (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 5 \\
 &:= -F(F(7) - 9) + 5 \times 3!! & &:= 5 \times (F(7) + 6! + F(3)) \\
 3598 &:= -F(3) + 5! \times (9 + F(8)) & &3684 := 3!! + (6! + F(8)) \times 4 \\
 &:= (F(8) + 9) \times 5! - F(3) & &:= (4 + F(F(8) - 6)) \times 3! \\
 3605 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5 & &3696 := (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 6 \\
 &:= 5 \times (-0! + 6! + F(3)) & &:= (6 + F(9 + 6)) \times 3! \\
 3624 &:= 3!! \times (6 - F(2)) + 4! & &3699 := (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 9 \\
 &:= 4! + (-F(2) + 6) \times 3!! & &:= 9 \times (F(9) + F(F(6) + 3!)) \\
 3627 &:= (3!! - (F(F(6)))^2) \times F(7) & &3705 := (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5 \\
 &:= F(7)^3 + 6! \times F(3) & &:= 5 \times (F(0! + 7) + 3!!) \\
 3638 &:= (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/3 - 8 & &3712 := F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) - 1) \times 2 \\
 & & &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(7))) \times F(3!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3724 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= -4 + 2 \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\
 3732 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \\
 3733 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) \times 3 - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 3 \times F(F(7)) - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 3734 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + 3) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= 4^{F(3)} \times F(F(7)) + 3! \\
 3738 &:= 3! \times 7 \times F(3 + 8) \\
 &:= F(8 + 3) \times 7 \times 3! \\
 3743 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - 7^4 \times 3 \\
 &:= -3!^4 + 7! - F(F(3)) \\
 3744 &:= 3 \times F(7) \times 4 \times 4! \\
 &:= (4! + 4!) \times F(7) \times 3! \\
 3746 &:= -3!! \times (7 + F(4)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= -6^4 + 7! + F(3) \\
 3749 &:= 3!! + F(7) \times F(4 + 9) \\
 &:= F(9 + 4) \times F(7) + 3!! \\
 3767 &:= 3! \times 7!/F(6) - F(7) \\
 &:= -F(7) + 6 \times 7!/F(3!) \\
 3776 &:= (3! + F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\
 &:= (6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times F(3!) \\
 3827 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times 2 - F(7) \\
 &:= -F(7) + 2 \times 8!/F(F(3!)) \\
 3832 &:= -F(3!) + 8!/F(F(3!)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times F(3!)/F(8) - F(3!) \\
 3834 &:= ((F(3!))!/F(8) - 3) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= F(F(4)) \times F(3!)/F(8) - 3! \\
 3835 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(3) - 5 \\
 &:= -5 + F(3!)/F(8) \times F(3) \\
 3838 &:= -F(3) + 8! \times F(3)/F(8) \\
 &:= 8! \times F(3)/F(8) - F(3) \\
 3857 &:= (F(3!) + F(8)) \times (5! + F(7)) \\
 &:= (F(7) + 5!) \times (F(8) + F(3!)) \\
 3875 &:= (F(3!))!/8 - F(F(7)) \times 5 \\
 &:= -5 \times F(F(7)) + (F(8)/3)! \\
 3882 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times 8!/F(8) + F(F(3!)) \\
 3896 &:= -F(-3 + F(8)) + 9 \times 6! \\
 &:= 6! \times 9 - F(F(8) - 3) \\
 3945 &:= F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-4 + 5!) \\
 &:= (5! - 4) \times F(9) + F(F(3)) \\
 3954 &:= 3! \times (F(9) + 5^4) \\
 &:= -F(4)! + 5! \times (F(9) - F(F(3))) \\
 3955 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times 5! - 5 \\
 &:= -5 + 5! \times (F(9) - F(F(3))) \\
 3963 &:= -3! + 9 \times (F(F(6)))^{F(3)} \\
 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - 3! \\
 3967 &:= 3! + (9 + F(6)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + 9) + 3! \\
 3976 &:= F(3!) \times (9! - 7!)/6! \\
 &:= F(6) \times (-7! + 9!)/3!! \\
 4032 &:= F(F(4)!)/(0! + 3^2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 2 \times F(3!)! / (-0! + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4048} := 4!! / (F(04) \times F(8)!) \\ := 8 \times (4! - 0!)! / (F(F(F(4)!)))!$$

$$\mathbf{4053} := (F(4)! + 0!)! - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) \\ := -F(F(F(3!)) - 5) + (0! + F(4)!)$$

$$\mathbf{4059} := -F(F(F(4)!)) \times 0! + 5! \times F(9) \\ := F(9) \times 5! - F(F(F(04)!))$$

$$\mathbf{4087} := -F(4)!! + (-0! + 8)! - F(F(7)) \\ := -F(F(7)) + (8 - 0!)! - F(4)!!$$

$$\mathbf{4094} := -F(F(4)) + (0! - 9)^4 \\ := -F(F(4)) + (9 - 0!)^4$$

$$\mathbf{4157} := -4! + F(1 + 5 + F(7)) \\ := F(F(7) + 5 + 1) - 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4173} := F((4 - 1)! + F(7)) - F(3!) \\ := -F(3!) + F(F(7) + F(1 \times 4)!)$$

$$\mathbf{4174} := -F(4)! - 1 + F(F(7) + F(4)!) \\ := F(F(4)! + F(7)) - 1 - F(4)!$$

$$\mathbf{4175} := -F(4)! + F(1 + F(7) + 5) \\ := F(5 + F(7) + 1) - F(4)!$$

$$\mathbf{4179} := F(F((4 - 1)!)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \\ := (-F(9) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(1 \times 4)!))$$

$$\mathbf{4194} := (F(4)!! - F(-1 + 9)) \times F(4)! \\ := (F(4)!! - F(9 - 1)) \times F(4)!$$

$$\mathbf{4202} := F(F(F(4)!)) + F(20 - F(2)) \\ := F(20 - F(2)) + F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$\mathbf{4203} := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + 0! + F(F(3!)) \\ := F(F(3!)) + 0! + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4204} := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) - 0! + 4! \\ := 4! - 0! + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4205} := 4! + F(-2 + F(F(0! + 5))) \\ := F(F(F(5 + 0!)) - 2) + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4223} := 42 + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) \\ := F(F(F(3!)) - 2) + 2 \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$\mathbf{4226} := -F(F(4)!)! / (F(2 + 2))! + F(F(F(6))) \\ := F(F(F(6))) - F(F(2 + 2)!)! / F(4)!$$

$$\mathbf{4232} := F(F(4)!) \times 23^2 \\ := 23^2 \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$\mathbf{4236} := F(F(F(4)!) + 2) + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \\ := (F(F(F(6)) - F(3)) + F(2 + F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4237} := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + F(3!) \times 7 \\ := 7 \times F(3!) + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4239} := 4! + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) + F(9) \\ := F(9) + F(F(F(3!)) - 2) + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4244} := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + F(4) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ := F(4) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4245} := (F(F(4)!))^2 + F(4! - 5) \\ := F(-5 + 4!) + 2^{F(4)!}$$

$$\mathbf{4247} := (F(F(4)!))! / (F(2) + F(F(4)!)) - F(F(7)) \\ := -F(F(7)) + F(F(4)!)! / (F(2) + F(F(4)!))$$

$$\mathbf{4249} := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + F(F(4)) \times F(9) \\ := F(9) \times F(F(4)) + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$\mathbf{4266} := -(F(4))^2 + 6! \times 6 \\ := (6! - F(6) - F(2)) \times F(4)!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4272 &:= 4! \times 2 \times F(F(7) - 2) \\ &:= F(-2 + F(7)) \times 2 \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4284 &:= F(F(4)^2) \times F(8) \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4)! \times ((8 - 2)! - F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4293 &:= (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3 \\ &:= 3 \times (-9 + 2 \times F(4)!!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4302 &:= (-F(4) + 3!!) \times (0! + 2)! \\ &:= (-2 - 0! + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4306 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! - 0!) - F(6) \\ &:= -F(6) + (-0! + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4307 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - F(07) \\ &:= -F(7) + 03!! \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4312 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - (F(1 + 2))! \\ &:= -2 + (-1 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4313 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 - 3! \\ &:= -3! - 1 + 3!! \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4314 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4)! \times 1 \times 3!! - F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4315 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 \times 5 \\ &:= -5 + 1 \times 3!! \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4318 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 1) - 8 \\ &:= (8 - 1)! - 3!! - F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4331 &:= (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! - 1 \\ &:= (-1 + F(3) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4332 &:= F(4)! \times (F(3) + (3 \times 2)!) \\ &:= (2 + 3!!) \times (3 + F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$4333 := (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(3))$$

$$:= 3! \times 3!! + F(3 + 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4335 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 3 \times 5 \\ &:= (5 + 3!! + 3!!) \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4336 &:= 4^{F(3)} + 3! \times 6! \\ &:= (6! + F(3)) \times 3! + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4337 &:= 4^{3!} + F(3!) + F(F(7)) \\ &:= F(7) + 3!! \times 3! + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4338 &:= (F(4) + 3!!) \times (-F(3) + 8) \\ &:= (F(8/F(3)) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4341 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(F((4 - 1)!)) \\ &:= (1 + F(4)!)! + F(F(3!)) - (F(4)!)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4342 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 4! - 2 \\ &:= -2 + (4 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4343 &:= 3!! \times F(4)! - F(F(3)) + 4! \\ &:= (4 + 3!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4346 &:= F(F(4)) + 3! \times (4 + 6!) \\ &:= 6! \times F(4)! + F(3) + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4347 &:= F(4) \times 3!! + F(4)^7 \\ &:= 7! + F(4) - 3!! + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4348 &:= (F(4)! + 3!!) \times F(4)! - 8 \\ &:= -8 + (F(4)! + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4362 &:= F(4)! \times (3^6 - 2) \\ &:= (F(2) + 6! + 3!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4364 &:= -4 + (F(3!) + 6!) \times F(4)! \\ &:= -4 + (6! + F(3!)) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4366 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - F(6) \\ &:= (F(6) + 6!) \times 3! - F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4367 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - 7 \\ &:= -7 + 6 \times 3^{F(4)!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4368 &:= (8 + 6!) \times F(3) \times F(4) \\ &:= (4! + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4373 &:= 4! \times F(3!) + F(F(7)) + 3! \\ &:= F(3! + F(7)) + F(3!) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4374 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times (7 - 4)! \\ &:= F(4)^7 \times 3! / F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4376 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 7 \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times 7 + 3!! \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4379 &:= -4 + (3!! - F(F(7))) \times 9 \\ &:= -9 \times (F(F(7)) - 3!!) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4383 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(8) \times 3 \\ &:= (3!! + F(8) + 3!!) \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4384 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 8^{F(F(4))} \\ &:= F(F(4)!) \times 8 + 3!! \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4385 &:= -F(4)^{F(3!)} + F(F(F((8 - 5)!))) \\ &:= F(F(F((-5 + 8)!))) - 3^{F(F(4)!)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4386 &:= F(4)! \times (3 + 8 + 6!) \\ &:= (6! + 8 + 3) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4398 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + F(9) - F(8)) \\ &:= (-F(8) + F(9) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4414 &:= (F(4)! / F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + F(4)! / F(F(F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4416 &:= 4! \times (4! - 1) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (-1 + 4!) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4424 &:= F(4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \times 2 + F(F(4)!) \\ &:= F(4!) \times 2 / F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4432 &:= (F(F(4)!) + F(4)! / F(F(3!))) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (F(3!) + F(4)! / F(F(F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4434 &:= (F(4)!! - F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! \\ &:= (-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4437 &:= 4^4 + F(3! + F(7)) \\ &:= F(F(7) + 3!) + 4^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4438 &:= F(4)! \times (F(4)!! + F(F(3!))) - 8 \\ &:= (F(8) + 3!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4439 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (F(4) + 3!!) \times 9 \\ &:= -9 \times (3!! + F(4)) + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4443 &:= (4! + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(3!)) \\ &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4446 &:= F(4)! \times (F(4 + 4) + 6!) \\ &:= (6! + F(4 + 4)) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4447 &:= -F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(4)!! + F(7)) \\ &:= (F(7) + F(4)!!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F(F(F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4448 &:= F(F(4)) + F(4)! \times (F(4)!! + F(8)) \\ &:= (F(8) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! + F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4462 &:= F(4)! \times (4! + 6!) - 2 \\ &:= -2 + (6! + 4!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4463 &:= F(4)! \times (4! + 6!) - F(F(3)) \\ &:= -F(F(3)) + (6! + 4!) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4466 &:= F(F(4)) + (4! + 6!) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times (6! + 4!) + F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4467 &:= F(4)! \times F(4)!! + F(F(6)) \times 7 \\ &:= -F(7) + F(6)! / (F(4) \times F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4469 &:= -F(4) - F(F(4)!) + F(6)! / 9 \\ &:= -9 \times 6! + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4473 &:= 4^{F(4)!} + F(7 \times F(3)) \\ &:= F(F(3) \times 7) + 4^{F(4)!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4474 &:= F(F(4)!) / (-4 + F(7)) - F(4)! \\ &:= F(F(4)!) / (F(7) - 4) - F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4476 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(4)) \times F(7) + 6!) \\ &:= F(6)! / (F(7) - 4) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4477 &:= -4! \times 4! + F(7) + 7! \\ &:= 7! + F(7) - 4! \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4493 &:= (-F(4)!! + F(4)) \times 9 + F(F(F(3)!)) \\ &:= F(3)! / 9 + F(F(4) + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4494 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (4! \times 9 - F(F(4))) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (9 \times 4! - F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4496 &:= F(F(4)!) + (F(F(4)!))! / 9 + F(6) \\ &:= F(6)! / 9 + 4 \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4498 &:= -F(4) + (F(F(4)!))! / 9 + F(8) \\ &:= 8! / 9 - F(4)! + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4536 &:= F(4)! \times (5! + 3!) \times 6 \\ &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(3) \times 5! - 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4567 &:= F(F(4)!) \times (-5! + 6!) - F(F(7)) \\ &:= -F(F(7)) + (6! - 5!) \times F(F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4574 &:= (F(F(4)) + 5)! - F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= -F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)) + (5 + F(F(4)))! \end{aligned}$$

$$4596 := (-F(4)! + 5!) \times F(9) + 6!$$

$$:= F(6)! / 9 + 5! - 4$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4599 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + 99) \\ &:= (99 + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4634 &:= (F(-4 + F(F(6)))) + 3!! \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= F(F(4)) \times (3!! + F(F(F(6)) - 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4644 &:= (F(4)!! + (F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4656 &:= F(4)! \times (6! + 56) \\ &:= (6! + 56) \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4663 &:= -F(F(4)! + F(6)) + F(6)! / F(3!) \\ &:= -F(3! + F(6)) + (F(F(6)) / F(4)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4667 &:= 4 - F(F(6) + 6) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(F(6) + 6) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4674 &:= -F(4)! + 6! \times F(7) / F(F(4)) \\ &:= -F(4)! + F(7) \times 6! / F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4687 &:= 4! - F(6 + 8) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(8 + 6) + 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4688 &:= -4! + F(-6 + F(8)) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times (F(F(8) - 6) - 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4689 &:= F(4)!! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 9 \\ &:= 9 \times F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4697 &:= -F(F(4)! + F(6)) + F(9) + 7! \\ &:= 7! + (F(9) - 6!) / F(F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4704 &:= 4! \times (F(7) + 0!)^{F(F(4))} \\ &:= 4! \times (0! + F(7))^{F(F(4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4725 &:= F(F((5 - 2)!!)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= (-F(F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(2) + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4727 &:= -4! \times F(7) - F(2) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(2) - F(7) \times 4! \\ 4728 &:= -4! \times F(7) + (-F(2) + 8)! \\ &:= (8 - F(2))! - F(7) \times 4! \\ 4733 &:= F(F(4)!) + (F(F(7)) - F(3!)) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) + F(F(4)!) \\ 4735 &:= (-F(4)! + F(F(7)) + 3!!) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (3!! + F(F(7)) - F(4)!) \\ 4743 &:= (-4! + F(F(7)) - F(4)!) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7))) - 4! \\ 4744 &:= (F(4)!!/F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)!) \\ &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4 \\ 4745 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7)) + F(4)!!) \\ 4749 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(F(7)) - F(F(4) + 9) \\ &:= 9! - F(F(4)!)! - F(7 \times 4) \\ 4753 &:= -F(4)!! + F(F(F(7) - 5))/F(3) \\ &:= -3!! + F(F(-5 + F(7)))/F(F(4)) \\ 4763 &:= -4 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-6 + F(F(7))) - 4 \\ 4764 &:= (-F(4)! + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)) - F(4) \\ &:= F(4)! \times (6! + 74) \\ 4767 &:= (-F(4) \times F(7) + 6!) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times (6! - F(7) \times F(4)) \\ 4769 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 7! - F(6) \times F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) \times F(6) + 7! + F(F(F(4))) \\ 4773 &:= -F((F(4) + F(7))) + 7! + 3!! \\ &:= 3!! + 7! - F(F(7) + F(4)) \\ 4776 &:= 4! \times F(7) \times F(7) + 6! \\ &:= 6! + F(7) \times F(7) \times 4! \\ 4778 &:= -F(F(4)!) - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(8) \\ &:= -F(8) - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(F(4)!) \\ 4779 &:= F(4)! - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) - F(F(7)) + 7! + F(4)! \\ 4783 &:= -4! - F(F(7)) + (F(8)/3)! \\ &:= F(3)!/8 - F(F(7)) - 4! \\ 4784 &:= F(4!) \times F(7)/(F(8) \times F(4)!) \\ &:= F(4)!/F(8) \times F(7)/F(4)! \\ 4786 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! - F(F(8) - F(6)) \\ &:= F(6)!/8 - F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 4787 &:= F(F(F(4))) - F(F(7)) - F(8) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(8) - F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4))) \\ 4789 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! - 8 \times F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) \times 8 + 7! + F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 4796 &:= -F(4)! + 7 \times (-F(9) + 6!) \\ &:= (6! - F(9)) \times 7 - F(4)! \\ 4797 &:= -F(4)^7/9 + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(9) - F(F(7)) + 4! \\ 4807 &:= -F(4 + 8 + 0!) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(0! + 8 + 4) \\ 4827 &:= -4! + F(8) \times (-2 + F(F(7))) \\ &:= (F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(8) - 4! \\ 4837 &:= (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 7 \times (3!! - F(8) - F(F(4)!))$$

$$4845 := -(F(F(4)!))!/F(8) + F(4 \times 5)$$

$$:= F(5 \times 4) - 8!/F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$4848 := F(4)!! + (8! + F(4!))/F(8)$$

$$:= -8 \times 4! + (F(8)/F(4))!$$

$$4856 := -4! + 8 \times F(5!/F(6))$$

$$:= F(6) \times F(5!/8) - 4!$$

$$4857 := -F(4) \times F(8) - 5! + 7!$$

$$:= 7! - 5! - F(8) \times F(4)$$

$$4859 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(8 + 5) - F(9)$$

$$:= -F(9) + F(5 + 8) \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$4863 := -F(-F(4)! + F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))/F(3)$$

$$:= -F(-3! + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))/F(F(4))$$

$$4867 := F(F(4)!) \times F(F(8) - 6) - F(7)$$

$$:= -F(7) + F(6) \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$4869 := -4! + F(8) \times F(-(F(F(6)) - F(9)))$$

$$:= F(F(9) - F(F(6))) \times F(8) - 4!$$

$$4875 := -4! - F(8) + 7! - 5!$$

$$:= -5! + 7! - F(8) - 4!$$

$$4877 := -4! + F(F(8) - 7) \times F(7)$$

$$:= F(7) \times F(-7 + F(8)) - 4!$$

$$4878 := F(4)! + F(8) \times F(F(7)) - F(8)$$

$$:= F(8) \times F(F(7)) - F(8) + F(4)!$$

$$4897 := F(F(F(4))) - F(F(8) - 9) + 7!$$

$$:= 7! - F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$4904 := -4 \times F(9) + (0! + F(4)!)$$

$$:= (F(4)! + 0!)! - F(9) \times 4$$

$$4914 := (F(4 + 9) + 1) \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (1 + F(9 + 4))$$

$$4917 := 4! + F(9 - 1) \times F(F(7))$$

$$:= F(F(7)) \times F(-1 + 9) + 4!$$

$$4927 := -4! - F(9 + 2) + 7!$$

$$:= 7! - F(2 + 9) - 4!$$

$$4934 := F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(9)/F(3))^{F(4)}$$

$$:= F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(3!) + 9)^{F(4)}$$

$$4937 := -F(4) \times F(9) - F(F(3)) + 7!$$

$$:= 7! - F(F(3)) - F(9) \times F(4)$$

$$4938 := (-4! \times F(9) + (F(3!)!)/8$$

$$:= (F(8)/3)! - F(9) \times F(4)$$

$$4944 := 4! \times (F(4)! \times F(9) + F(F(4)))$$

$$:= (F(4)! \times F(9) + F(F(4))) \times 4!$$

$$4947 := (F(4) - F(9)) \times F(4) + 7!$$

$$:= 7! + (F(4) - F(9)) \times F(4)$$

$$4957 := F(4) + F(9) - 5! + 7!$$

$$:= 7! - 5! + F(9) + F(4)$$

$$4968 := -F(F(4)!) \times 9 + F(6)!/8$$

$$:= 8 \times (6! - 9) - F(4)!!$$

$$4971 := -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! - 1$$

$$:= -1 + 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4))$$

$$4972 := F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + 7!/2)$$

$$:= F(2) \times 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4))$$

$$4973 := -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! + F(F(3))$$

$$:= F(F(3)) + 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4974 &:= (4! \times F(9) + F(7)) \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4)! \times (F(7) + F(9) \times 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4975 &:= F(-4! + F(9)) + 7! - 5! \\ &:= -5! + 7! + F(F(9) - 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4976 &:= -4! - F(9) + 7! - 6 \\ &:= -6 + 7! - F(9) - 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4977 &:= -F(4) \times (F(9) - F(7)) + 7! \\ &:= 7! + (F(7) - F(9)) \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4978 &:= -F(4)! \times 9 + 7! - 8 \\ &:= -8 + 7! - 9 \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4979 &:= -F(4) \times 9 + 7! - F(9) \\ &:= -F(9) + 7! - 9 \times F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4982 &:= -4! - F(9) + (8 - F(2))! \\ &:= (-F(2) + 8)! - F(9) - 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4984 &:= F(F(F(4)) + 9) \times 8! / F(4)!! \\ &:= (F(4)!! - 8) \times (9 - F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4986 &:= -F(4)! \times 9 + 8! / F(6) \\ &:= F(6)! / 8 - 9 \times F(4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4995 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9)! - 9 \times 5 \\ &:= -5 \times 9 + (9 - F(F(4)))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4997 &:= F(F(F(4))) \times (-9 - F(9) + 7!) \\ &:= (7! - F(9) - 9) \times F(F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5027 &:= (5 + 02)! - F(7) \\ &:= 7! - F(2 + 05) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5032 &:= -F(5 + 0!) + (3! + F(2))! \\ &:= (F(2) + 3!)! - F(0! + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$5033 := -5 + (0! + 3!)! - F(3)$$

$$:= -F(3) + (3! + 0!)! - 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5035 &:= -5 + (F(03) + 5)! \\ &:= -5 + (F(3) - 0 + 5)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5036 &:= -5 + 0! + (F(F(3)) + 6)! \\ &:= F(6)! / F(3!) + 0! - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5038 &:= -F(F(5 - 0!)) + (F(3!))! / 8 \\ &:= (F(8) / 3)! - F(F(-0! + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5039 &:= -(5 \times 0)! + (-F(3) + 9)! \\ &:= (9 - F(3))! - (0 \times 5)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5061 &:= F(F(5 + 0!)) + (6 + 1)! \\ &:= (1 + 6)! + F(F(0! + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5066 &:= F(F(6)) + (F(6) - 0!)! + 5 \\ &:= 5 + (0! + 6)! + F(F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5067 &:= 7! + F(F(6)) + 0! + 5 \\ &:= 5 + 0! + F(F(6)) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5069 &:= -5 + (0! + 6)! + F(9) \\ &:= F(9) + (F(6) - 0!)! - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5077 &:= 50 - F(7) + 7! \\ &:= 7! + F(7) + (-0! + 5)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5079 &:= 5 + 07! + F(9) \\ &:= F(9) + 7! + 05 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5082 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times F(8) \times (0! + 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5147 &:= 5! - F(1 + F(4)!) + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(F(4)!) + 1 + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5157 &:= -F(5 - 1) + 5! + 7! \\ &:= 7! - F(5 - 1) + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5186 &:= F(F(F(5+1))) - 8 \times 6! \\
 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8 \times (1+5)! \\
 5187 &:= ((5+1)! + F(8)) \times 7 \\
 &:= 7 \times (F(8) + (1+5)!) \\
 5233 &:= -5! \times 2 + F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) - 2 \times 5! \\
 5267 &:= F(F(5+2)) - 6 + 7! \\
 &:= F(F(7)) - 6 + (2+5)! \\
 5272 &:= F(F(5+2)) + 7! - F(2) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(F(7)) + (2+5)! \\
 5273 &:= (5+2)! + F(7+3!) \\
 &:= F(3!+7) + (2+5)! \\
 5274 &:= 5! \times 2 + 7! - F(4)! \\
 &:= -F(4)! + 7! + 2 \times 5! \\
 5277 &:= 5 - F(2) + F(F(7)) + 7! \\
 &:= F(F(7)) + 7! - F(2) + 5 \\
 5334 &:= (F(F(5+F(3))) + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(3)+5))) \\
 5337 &:= (5! - F(F(3!))) \times 3 + 7! \\
 &:= 7! - 3 \times F(F(3!)) - 5! \\
 5353 &:= (5! + F(F(3+5)))/F(3) \\
 &:= F(F(3+5))/F(3) - 5! \\
 5367 &:= F(5!/3!) - 6 \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= -3 + 7! + F(3!)/5! \\
 5394 &:= (-5! + 3!) \times 9 - F(4)! \\
 &:= -F(4)! + 9 \times (3! - 5!) \\
 5409 &:= (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 9 \\
 &:= 9 \times (0! + F(4)!! - 5!) \\
 5433 &:= -5!/F(4) + F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) - F(F(4)!) \times 5 \\
 5443 &:= (-5!/F(F(4)) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(3) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(F(4)) - F(4)! \times 5 \\
 5444 &:= -5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(F(4)) - 4! \\
 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(F(4)) - 4! - 5 \\
 5448 &:= 5! - F(4)!! + F(4!) - 8! \\
 &:= -8! - F(4)!! + F(4!) + 5! \\
 5464 &:= 5! \times 4! + F(-6+4!) \\
 &:= F(4! - 6) + 4! \times 5! \\
 5471 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7)) - 1 \\
 &:= -1 + F(F(7)) \times 4! + 5! \\
 5472 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7) \times F(2)) \\
 &:= F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times 4! - 5! \\
 5474 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(F(4)) \\
 &:= 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(F(4)) - 5! \\
 5484 &:= 5 + F(4)! + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) \\
 &:= F(4)! + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) + 5 \\
 5487 &:= (-5 + F(4)!!) \times 8 - F(F(7)) \\
 &:= -F(F(7)) + 8 \times (F(4)!! - 5) \\
 5535 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\
 &:= (5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 5)) \times 5 \\
 5544 &:= (5! + 5! + 4!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (4! + 5! + 5!) \\
 5589 &:= (5! \times 5 + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 9 \times (F(8) + 5! \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5592} := 5!/5 \times F(F(9 - 2))$$

$$:= F(F(-2 + 9)) \times 5!/5$$

$$\mathbf{5593} := (5! + F(F(F((F(-5 + 9))!)))/F(3))$$

$$:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(F(9 - 5)) + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5597} := 5 + (-5 + 9)! \times F(F(7))$$

$$:= F(F(7)) \times (9 - 5)! + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5624} := -5! + (6! - 2) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= F(F(4)!) \times (-2 + 6!) - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5632} := -5! + F(6) \times (3!! - F(2))$$

$$:= (-F(2) + 3!!) \times F(6) - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5634} := -5! + (F(6) \times 3!! - F(4)!)$$

$$:= -F(4)! + F(3!) \times 6! - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5635} := -5! + F(6) \times 3!! - 5$$

$$:= -5! + F(3!) \times 6! + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5664} := -5! + F(6) \times 6! + 4!$$

$$:= (F(4) + 6!) \times F(6) - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5673} := -F(5 + F(6)) - 7! + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$:= F(F(F(3!))) - 7! - F(F(6) + 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5693} := (5 + 6! - 9) \times F(3!)$$

$$:= F(3!) \times (-9 + 6!) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5697} := 5 \times 6! + 9 \times F(F(7))$$

$$:= F(F(7)) \times 9 + 6! \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{5733} := 5! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!)) + 3!!$$

$$:= 3!! + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5734} := -5 + 7! - F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!$$

$$:= F(4)!! - F(F(3!)) + 7! - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5736} := (-5 + F(7)) \times (-3 + 6!)$$

$$:= (6! - 3) \times (F(7) - 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5744} := (5 - 7 + F(4)!!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= (F(4)!! - F(F(4))) \times (F(7) - 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5747} := (-5 + F(7)) \times F(4)!! - F(7)$$

$$:= -F(7) + F(4)!! \times (F(7) - 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5748} := -5 - 7 + F(4)!! \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times F(4)!! - 7 - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5749} := -5 + 7! + F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9)$$

$$:= F(9) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5773} := -5! - F(7) - 7! + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$:= F(F(F(3!))) - 7! - F(7) - 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5783} := -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - 3$$

$$:= -3 + F(F(8)) - 7! + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5784} := -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))$$

$$:= F(4!)/8 - 7 - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5786} := 5 + 7! + F(8) + 6!$$

$$:= 6! + F(8) + 7! + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5833} := ((-5 + 8)!! + F(F(F(3!))))/F(3)$$

$$:= (3!! + F(F(F(3!))))/F(8 - 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5864} := 5! + 8 \times (6! - F(F(4)))$$

$$:= (-F(F(4)) + 6!) \times 8 + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5867} := 5! + 8 \times 6! - F(7)$$

$$:= -F(7) + 6! \times 8 + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5886} := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 6$$

$$:= 6 \times (F(8) + 8 \times 5!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5894 &:= -5! - 8! - F(9) + F(4!) \\ &:= F(4!) - F(9) - 8! - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5897 &:= F(F(F((-5 + 8)!))) - 9 - 7! \\ &:= -7! - 9 + F(F(F((8 - 5)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5906 &:= -((F(-5 + 9))! + 0!)! + F(F(F(6))) \\ &:= F(F(F(6))) - ((0! + F(9))/5)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5907 &:= F(F(F((F(-5 + 9)!))) + 0! - 7! \\ &:= -7! + 0! + F(F(F(F(9 - 5)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5973 &:= 5! \times 9 + F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) + 9 \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5994 &:= (5! - 9) \times 9 \times F(4!) \\ &:= F(4!) \times 9 \times (-9 + 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6027 &:= F(F(6) \times 02) + 7! \\ &:= 7! + F(2 \times F(06)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6039 &:= -F(6)! + F((0! + 3)!) - 9 \\ &:= -9 + F((3 + 0!)!) - F(6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6043 &:= -F(6)! + 0! + F(4!) - 3! \\ &:= -3! + F(4!) + 0! - F(6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6044 &:= -6! - 0! + F(4! - 4) \\ &:= F(4! - 4) - 0! - 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6045 &:= -6! + F(04 \times 5) \\ &:= F(5 \times 4) - 06! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6046 &:= F(F(F(6) - 0!) + F(F(F(4)))) - 6! \\ &:= -6! + F(F(F(4))) + F(-0! + F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6047 &:= F((7 - F(4))!) - 0! - F(6)! \\ &:= -F(6)! - 0! + F((-F(4) + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$6054 := -F(6)! + 0! + 5 + F(4!)$$

$$:= F(4!) + 5 + 0! - F(6)!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6056 &:= F(6) + F((-0! + 5)!) - F(6)! \\ &:= F(6) + F((5 - 0!)!) - F(6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6058 &:= F(F(F(6) - 0!)) \times (5 + F(8)) \\ &:= (F(8) + 5) \times F(F(0! + 6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6066 &:= F(F(F(6) - 0!) - 6! + F(F(6))) \\ &:= -6! + F(F(6)) + F(-0! + F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6074 &:= F(F(F(6))) + (0! - F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(7)) - 0!) + F(F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6165 &:= F(F(F(6) - 1) - 6! + 5! \\ &:= 5! - 6! + F(-1 + F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6174 &:= F(F(6)) \times (1 + F(7)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(7) + 1) \times F(F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6237 &:= F(F(6)) \times (2^{3!} + F(F(7))) \\ &:= (F(F(7)) + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6247 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(4)!! - F(F(7)) \\ &:= -F(F(7)) + F(4)^2 \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6264 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times (6! - 4!) \\ &:= (-4! + 6!) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6324 &:= -F(F(6))^{F(3)} + F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \\ &:= -F(F(F(4)!))^2 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6333 &:= -F(6)! - 3 + 3!^{3!} \\ &:= 3!^{3!} - 3 - F(6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6334 &:= -F(6)! + 3!^{3!} - F(F(4)) \\ &:= F(4)!^{3!} - F(3) - F(6)! \end{aligned}$$

$$6338 := 6^{3!} + F(3) - 8!$$

$$:= -8! + F(3) + 3!^6$$

$$\mathbf{6343} := F(6)!/3! - F(F(4)! + F(3!))$$

$$:= F(3)!/F(4)! - F(3! + F(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6344} := -F(6)! + F(3!) + F(4)!^{F(4)!}$$

$$:= F(4)!^{F(4)!} + F(3!) - F(6)!$$

$$\mathbf{6347} := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))} - 7!$$

$$:= F(7) + 4! \times 3!! - F(F(F(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{6367} := (F(6)! - 3!!)/6 - F(F(7))$$

$$:= -F(F(7)) + (F(6)! - 3!!)/6$$

$$\mathbf{6376} := 6! + F(3!) \times (-F(7) + 6!)$$

$$:= (6! - F(7)) \times F(3!) + 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6384} := F(F(6)) \times 38 \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= 4!!/F(8)! - F(3!) \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6426} := (6! - F(4!)) \times (F(2) + F(6))$$

$$:= ((F(6) - F(2))! + F(4!))/F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6435} := F(6 + 4) \times (-3 + 5!)$$

$$:= (5! - 3) \times F(4 + 6)$$

$$\mathbf{6444} := (6! - 4) \times F(4) \times F(4)$$

$$:= F(4) \times F(4) \times (-4 + 6!)$$

$$\mathbf{6447} := F(6)!/F(4)! - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7)$$

$$:= (7! + F(4!))/F(F(4)!) + F(F(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6448} := 6! + (F(4)!! - 4) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (F(4)!! - 4) + 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6454} := (F(4)!! + 5) \times 4! - F(F(F(6)))$$

$$:= -F(F(F(6))) + (F(4)!! + 5) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{6459} := -F(F(6)) + F(4)! \times 5! \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times 5! \times F(4)! - F(F(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6462} := (6 + F(4)) \times (6! - 2)$$

$$:= (-2 + 6!) \times (F(4) + 6)$$

$$\mathbf{6464} := F(4)!! + (6! - F(F(4))) \times F(6)$$

$$:= (6! - F(F(4))) \times F(6) + F(4)!!$$

$$\mathbf{6466} := F(F(F(6))) - F(6)!/(F(4) + 6)$$

$$:= -F(6)!/(F(4) + 6) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{6467} := (6 + F(4)) \times 6! - F(7)$$

$$:= -F(7) + (6 + F(4)) \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6469} := -F(6) - F(4) + 6! \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times 6! - F(4) - F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6473} := F(6) \times F(4)!! - 7 + 3!!$$

$$:= 3!! - 7 + F(4)!! \times F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6474} := 6! \times (-4 + F(7)) - F(4)!$$

$$:= -F(4)! + (F(7) - 4) \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6475} := 6! \times (-4 + F(7)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + (F(7) - 4) \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6494} := (6! + F(F(4))) \times 9 - 4$$

$$:= -4 + 9 \times (F(F(4)) + 6!)$$

$$\mathbf{6496} := -F(6) + 4! + 9 \times 6!$$

$$:= 6! \times 9 + 4! - F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6497} := (6! - 4!) \times 9 + F(F(7))$$

$$:= F(F(7)) + 9 \times (-4! + 6!)$$

$$\mathbf{6516} := 6! + F((5 - 1)!)/F(6)$$

$$:= 6! + F((-1 + 5)!)/F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6532} := -F(F(6) + 5) + F(F(F(3!))) - F(2)$$

$$:= -F(F(F(2) + 3!)) + F(5!/6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6569 &:= 9 \times 6! + F(5 + 6) & := F(4)! \times (F(4) - 6!) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(6 + 5) + 6! \times 9 \\
 6578 &:= -F(6)!/5! \times F(7) + F(F(8)) & 6645 &:= -6!/6 + F(4 \times 5) \\
 &:= -8! \times F(7)/5! + F(F(F(6))) & &:= F(5 \times 4) + 6!/6 \\
 6592 &:= -F(6) + 5! \times F(9 + F(2)) & 6647 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(6)) + F(4)!! - 7! \\
 &:= F(F(2) + 9) \times 5! - F(6) & &:= -7! + F(4)!! + F(F(F(6))) + F(F(6)) \\
 6594 &:= -6 + 5! \times F(F(9) - 4!) & 6648 &:= 6! + (F(F(6)) + F(4)!!) \times 8 \\
 &:= F(4)!! \times 9 + 5! - 6 & &:= (F(8) + F(4)!!) \times F(6) + 6! \\
 6624 &:= -6! \times 6 - 2 + F(F(F(F(4)!))) & 6656 &:= (6! - F(6) + 5!) \times F(6) \\
 &:= F(4!)/(F(2)^{F(6)} + 6) & &:= (6! + 5! - F(6)) \times F(6) \\
 6626 &:= -6! \times 6 + F(F(2 + 6)) & 6664 &:= -F(6)!/6! + F(6)!/F(4)! \\
 &:= F(F(6 + 2)) - 6! \times 6 & &:= F(F(4)!)!/6 - F(6)!/6! \\
 6627 &:= (F(F(6)) + F((6 - 2)!))/7 & 6677 &:= 6 + (6! + F(F(7))) \times 7 \\
 &:= -7! + F(2) + 6! + F(F(F(6))) & &:= 7 \times (F(F(7)) + 6!) + 6 \\
 6628 &:= -6! \times 6 + 2 + F(F(8)) & 6679 &:= F(6)!/6 - 7 - F(9) \\
 &:= F(F(8)) + 2 - 6! \times 6 & &:= -F(9) - 7 + F(6)!/6 \\
 6632 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times (-3!! + F(2)) & 6693 &:= F(6)!/6 - 9 \times 3 \\
 &:= (F(2) - 3!!) \times 6 + F(F(F(6))) & &:= -3 \times 9 + F(6)!/6 \\
 6634 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(6) - 3!! \times F(4)! & 6694 &:= F(6)!/6 - F(9) + F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= -F(4)! \times 3!! + F(F(F(6))) + F(6) & &:= F(F(4)!) - F(9) + F(6)!/6 \\
 6637 &:= (F((F(6) + (6 + 3))) + (7!)) & 6696 &:= (F(6)! - F(F(F(6)) - 9))/6 \\
 &:= ((7)! + F((3 + 6) + F(6))) & &:= (F(6)! - F(-9 + F(F(6))))/6 \\
 6638 &:= 6 \times (-6! + F(3)) + F(F(8)) & 6707 &:= F(6)!/(7 - 0!) - F(7) \\
 &:= F(F(8)) + (F(3) - 6!) \times 6 & &:= -F(7) + (0! + 7)!/6 \\
 6642 &:= 6! + 6 \times F(4^2) & 6714 &:= F(6)!/(7 - 1) - F(4)! \\
 &:= F(2^4) \times 6 + 6! & &:= -F(4)! + (1 + 7)!/6 \\
 6644 &:= F(F(F(6))) + (-6! + F(4)) \times F(4)! & 6731 &:= -F(F(6)) - F(7) + F(F(F(3!))) - 1 \\
 & & &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - F(7) - F(F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6733 &:= (F(6)! + F(7) \times 3!)/3! \\
 &:= F(3)!/3! + 7 + 6 \\
 6734 &:= F(F(F(6)))/F(7) \times F(3!) - F(F(4)) \\
 &:= (F(F(4)!)/3! - 7 + F(F(6))) \\
 6736 &:= -F(F(6)) + F(F(7)) \times (F(3!) + F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (F(3) + 7!/6) \\
 6744 &:= (6 + 7!/F(4)) \times 4 \\
 &:= F(4! - 4) - F(7) - F(6) \\
 6747 &:= 6! + 7! + F(F(4) + F(7)) \\
 &:= F(F(7) + F(4)) + 7! + 6! \\
 6763 &:= 6 + F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(3!)) \\
 &:= (F(3!) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) + 6 \\
 6773 &:= F(6) + F(7 + 7 + 3!) \\
 &:= F(3!) + F(7 + 7 + 6) \\
 6783 &:= F(6)! - (F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 3 \\
 &:= (3!!/8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 6813 &:= 6 \times 8 + F(-1 + F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 1) + 8 \times 6 \\
 6834 &:= (6! + 8!)/3! - F(4)! \\
 &:= -F(4)! + (3!! + 8!)/6 \\
 6885 &:= F(-F(6)/8 + F(8)) + 5! \\
 &:= 5! + F(F(8) - F(8 - 6)) \\
 6914 &:= -F(6)!/(9 + 1) + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 &:= -F(F(4)!)/(1 + 9) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 6967 &:= 6! \times 9 + 6! - F(F(7)) \\
 &:= -F(F(7)) + 6! \times 9 + 6! \\
 6984 &:= 6! \times 9 + F(8) \times 4! \\
 &:= 4! \times F(8) + 9 \times 6! \\
 7137 &:= 7! + (1 + F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= 7! + (F(3!) + 1) \times F(F(7)) \\
 7142 &:= F(F(7) + 1) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \\
 &:= F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) + F(1 + F(7)) \\
 7231 &:= F(F(7)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!)) - 1) \\
 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 2 \times F(F(7)) \\
 7237 &:= (F(7) \times F(2))^3 + 7! \\
 &:= F(7)^3 \times F(2) + 7! \\
 7265 &:= (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (6! \times 2 + F(7)) \\
 7327 &:= 7! \times 3/2 - F(F(7)) \\
 &:= 7!/2 \times 3 - F(F(7)) \\
 7344 &:= 7! + (F(3) \times 4!)^{F(F(4))} \\
 &:= (4! + 4!)^{F(3)} + 7! \\
 7346 &:= -7! + 3!! \times F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4)) \times 3!! - 7! \\
 7347 &:= (7! + F(F(3!)) + F(4!))/7 \\
 &:= (7! + F(4!) + F(F(3!)))/7 \\
 7353 &:= 7 + F(F(F(3!))) - 5 \times 3!! \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - 5 \times 3!! + 7 \\
 7366 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(3!))) \times (F(6) + F(F(6))) \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(F(6))) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 7413 &:= (F(F(7)) + (4 + 1)!) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= F(F(3!)) \times ((1 + 4)! + F(F(7))) \\
 7433 &:= F(F(7)) + (4 + 3!) \times 3!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 3!! \times (3! + 4) + F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7441} := 7^4 + (F(4)! + 1)! \\ := (1 + F(4)!)^4 + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7443} := (-F(7) - F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times F(4) + (F(3))! \\ := F(3)! - F(4) \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7444} := (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 4 \\ := 4 \times (-F(4) + F(F(4)!) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7446} := F(F(7)) \times F(4)! + F(4)! - F(6)! \\ := -F(6)! + F(4)! + F(4)! \times F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7455} := 7! + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! - 5) \\ := (5! - 5) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7456} := F(F(7)) \times (-4! + 56) \\ := (F(6) + 5!) / 4 \times F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7464} := F(F(7)) \times (4! + F(6)) + F(F(4)!) \\ := F(F(4)!) + (F(6) + 4!) \times F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7475} := 7! + (F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5 \\ := 5 \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!!) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7491} := (F(F(7)) - F(4)!) \times (F(9) - 1) \\ := (-1 + F(9)) \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7495} := -F(F(7)) + F(4)! / (F(9 - 5))! \\ := F((-5 + 9)! / F(4)! - F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7497} := F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 7! \\ := F(7) \times 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7547} := 7! + 5! \times F(F(F(4)!)) - F(7) \\ := 7! + F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5! - F(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7584} := 7! + 5! \times F(8) + 4! \\ := 4! + F(8) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7616} := (F(F(7)) + 6! - 1) \times F(6) \\ := F(6) \times (-1 + 6! + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7624} := 7! + F(-6 + 24) \\ := F(F(4)) \times F(2) \times 6 + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7637} := F(7) + F(6 \times 3) + 7! \\ := F(7) + F(3 \times 6) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7638} := (7! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3 - 8! \\ := -8! + 3 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7644} := F(7) \times F(F(6)) \times (4! + 4) \\ := (4! + 4) \times F(F(6)) \times F(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7684} := -F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) \times F(8 + F(4)!) \\ := F(F(4)!) + 8 \times F(F(6)) - F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7686} := 7! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 \\ := F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7688} := (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 8 \\ := 8 \times (8 + 6! + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7694} := (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(9) - 4! \\ := -4! + F(9) \times (-6 + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7696} := (F(F(7)) + 6! + 9) \times F(6) \\ := F(6) \times ((9 + 6!) + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7795} := -7 + F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 5! \\ := -5! + F(9) \times F(F(7)) - 7$$

$$\mathbf{7854} := (F(F(7)) + F(8) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(8) + F(F(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7874} := (F(F(7)) + F(8)) \times (7 + 4!) \\ := (4! + 7) \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7904 &:= (F(7+9) + 0!) \times F(F(4)!) \\ &:= F(F(4)!) \times (0! + F(9+7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7913 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 1 - F(3!) \\ &:= -F(3!) - 1 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7914 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - F((F(1 \times 4))!) \\ &:= -F((4-1)!) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7942 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7943 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! - 3 \\ &:= (F(F(3)) + F(4! - 9)) \times F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7944 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! - F(F(4)) \\ &:= 4! - F(F(4)) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7954 &:= 7! + F(9) + 5! \times 4! \\ &:= 4! \times 5! + F(9) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7994 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 9 \times F(F(4)!) \\ &:= F(F(4)!) \times 9 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8043 &:= 8! / (0! + 4) - F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(3)! / (4 + 0!) - F(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8056 &:= 8! / 05 - F(6) \\ &:= F(6)! / 5 - 08 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8344 &:= 8 \times 3!! + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \\ &:= F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 3!! \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8354 &:= F(F(8)) - 3!^5 / F(4) \\ &:= F(4! - 5) \times F(3) - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8373 &:= -F(8 \times F(3)) + F(7) \times 3!! \\ &:= 3!! \times F(7) - F(F(3) \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$8426 := F(F(8)) - (F(4) + 2)! \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= -F(6)! / 2^4 + F(F(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8494 &:= -F(F(8)) + F(4)!! \times 9 \times F(4) \\ &:= F(4)!! \times 9 \times F(4) - F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8535 &:= (F(F(8) - 5) + 3!!) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (3!! + F(-5 + F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8546 &:= F(F(8)) - 5!^{F(F(4))} / 6 \\ &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5! + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8573 &:= F(F(8)) - (5! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) \\ &:= F(F(3!)) \times (7 - 5!) + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8684 &:= F(F(8)) - F(6+8) \times F(4)! \\ &:= -F(4)! \times F(8+6) + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8694 &:= F(8) \times 69 \times F(4)! \\ &:= F(4!) \times 9 / (6 \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8776 &:= 8 \times (F(7+7) + 6!) \\ &:= 6! + F(7+7) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8784 &:= 8! / (F(7) - 8) + F(4)!! \\ &:= F(4)!! + 8! / (F(7) - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8786 &:= F(F(8)) - (7! + 8!) / F(F(6)) \\ &:= -6! \times F(8) / 7 + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8856 &:= (F(8+8) + 5!) \times F(6) \\ &:= F(6) \times (5! + F(8+8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8932 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (-3!! \times 9 + F(F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8944 &:= (8! / 9 - F(F(4)!)) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= F(F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) / 9 - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9243 &:= F(F(3!))^{F(4)} - 2 \times 9 \\ &:= -9 \times 2 + F(F(F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9284 &:= -9! + F(F(2) + 8) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(8 + F(2)) - 9! \\
 9326 &:= -F(9) + F(3! + F(2)) \times 6! \\
 &:= 6! \times F(F(2) + 3!) - F(9) \\
 9333 &:= 9 \times F(3!) + F(F(3!))^3 \\
 &:= F(F(3!))^3 + F(3!) \times 9 \\
 9334 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times (3!! - F(F(4))) \\
 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times F(-F(3) + 9) \\
 9343 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) - F(4)! + F(F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - F(4)! - F(F(3!) + 9) \\
 9345 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(F(3) + 9) \\
 9346 &:= -(F(9) + 3!)^{F(F(4))} + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(6))) - F(4) - F(F(3!) + 9) \\
 9347 &:= (-9 + 3!! + F(F(4)!)) \times F(7) \\
 &:= F(7) \times F(4)!! - F(-F(3) + 9) \\
 9349 &:= F(F(F(9 - 3))) - F(F(F(4)!)) + 9 \\
 &:= F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4))) - F(F(3!) + 9) \\
 9354 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) + 5 + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5 - F(F(3!) + 9) \\
 9373 &:= F(9 - F(3)) + F(7) \times 3!! \\
 &:= 3!! \times F(7) + F(-F(3) + 9) \\
 9394 &:= (F(9) + (3!! \times (9 + 4))) \\
 &:= (4 + 9) \times 3!! + F(9) \\
 9407 &:= F(9) + (F(4)!! + 0!) \times F(7) \\
 &:= F(7) \times (0! + F(4)!!) + F(9) \\
 9434 &:= (-F(9 \times F(F(4))) + F(3!)!)/4 \\
 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(F(3!)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 9 \\
 9438 &:= (-F(9) - F(4)!!) \times F(3) + F(F(8)) \\
 &:= F(F(8)) - F(3) \times (F(4)!! + F(9)) \\
 9447 &:= 9 + (F(4)! + F(4)!!) \times F(7) \\
 &:= F(7) \times (F(4)! + F(4)!!) + 9 \\
 9454 &:= -F(F(F(F(4)!))) + (-5! + F(4)!!) \times F(9) \\
 &:= F(9) \times (F(4)!! - 5!) - F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 9464 &:= (9 + 4) \times (F(6) + F(4)!!) \\
 &:= (F(4)!! + F(6)) \times (4 + 9) \\
 9486 &:= F(9) \times (F(4)!! - F(8) \times F(F(6))) \\
 &:= (6! - F(8)^{F(F(4))}) \times F(9) \\
 9566 &:= -F(9) + 5 \times F(6)!/F(F(6)) \\
 &:= F(6)!/F(F(6)) \times 5 - F(9) \\
 9576 &:= 9 \times (5! + F(7)) \times F(6) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (F(7) + 5!) \times 9 \\
 9633 &:= (F(9) - F(F(6))) \times (3!! + F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= (3!! + F(F(3!))) \times (-F(F(6)) + F(9)) \\
 9645 &:= (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!)/F(F(6)) + 9) \\
 9657 &:= 9 \times (6! + 5! + F(F(7))) \\
 &:= (F(F(7)) + 5! + 6!) \times 9 \\
 9667 &:= F(9) + (6! + F(F(6))) \times F(7) \\
 &:= F(7) \times (6! + F(F(6))) + F(9) \\
 9672 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times (7! - 6 \times F(9)) \\
 9724 &:= F(9) \times F(7) \times (-2 + 4!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (4! - 2) \times F(7) \times F(9)$$

$$:= 7! \times F(F(4)) - F(-F(8) + F(9))$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9784} &:= -F(9) \times F(7) + F(F(8)) - F(4)!! \\ &:= -F(4)!! + F(F(8)) - F(7) \times F(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9864} &:= (F(9) + F(8 + 6)) \times 4! \\ &:= 4! \times (F(6 + 8) + F(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9793} &:= -9 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 3!!) \\ &:= (3!! + F(9)) \times F(7) - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9873} &:= 9 \times (F(F(8) - 7) + 3!!) \\ &:= (3!! + F(-7 + F(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{9847} := -F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(4)) \times 7!$$

5.2 Digit's Order

5.2.1 Basic Operations

$$\mathbf{34} := F(3 \times F(4))$$

$$\mathbf{63} := F(F(6)) \times 3$$

$$\mathbf{64} := F(6)^{F(4)}$$

$$\mathbf{84} := F(8) \times 4$$

$$\mathbf{143} := -1 + F(4 \times 3)$$

$$\mathbf{144} := F((-1 + 4) \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{168} := 1 \times F(6) \times F(8)$$

$$\mathbf{189} := 1 \times F(8) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{233} := F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3))$$

$$\mathbf{234} := F(2) + F(F(3 + 4))$$

$$\mathbf{235} := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5))$$

$$\mathbf{237} := F(2) + 3 + F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{245} := 2 + F(4)^5$$

$$\mathbf{245} := 2 + F(4)^5$$

$$\mathbf{256} := 2^5 \times F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{256} := 2^5 \times F(6)$$

$$\mathbf{267} := F(F(2) + F(6)) + F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{374} := F(F(3) \times 7) - F(4)$$

$$\mathbf{376} := -F(F(3)) + F(-7 + F(F(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{377} := F(3 \times 7 - 7)$$

$$\mathbf{378} := F(F(3)) + F(-7 + F(8))$$

$$\mathbf{466} := F(F(4)) \times F(-F(6) + F(F(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{472} := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{630} := F(F(6)) \times 30$$

$$\mathbf{693} := F(F(6)) \times (F(9) - F(F(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{784} := (7 + F(8))^{F(4)}$$

$$\mathbf{840} := F(8) \times 40$$

$$\mathbf{882} := F(8) \times F(8) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{986} := F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6))$$

$$\mathbf{1042} := F(10) + F(4^2)$$

$$\mathbf{1042} := F(10) + F(4^2)$$

$$\mathbf{1165} := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{1175} := (1 + 1 + F(F(7))) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{1178} := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$$

$$\mathbf{1292} := F(1 \times 2 \times 9) / 2$$

$$\mathbf{1293} := F(12) \times 9 - 3$$

$$\mathbf{1293} := F(12) \times 9 - 3$$

$$\mathbf{1294} := F(12) \times 9 - F(F(4))$$

$$\mathbf{1364} := -F(13) + F(F(F(6))) - 4$$

$$\mathbf{1365} := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{1368} := (1 - 3 + F(F(F(6)))) / 8$$

$$\mathbf{1397} := -1 + (-3 + 9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{1429} := 1 + 42 \times F(9)$$

$$\mathbf{1429} := 1 + 42 \times F(9)$$

$$\mathbf{1487} := -F(14) + 8 \times F(F(7))$$

$$\mathbf{1525} := F(15) / 2 \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{1536} := (1 + 5) \times F(3)^{F(6)}$$

$$\mathbf{1575} := F(F(1 + 5)) \times 75$$

$$\mathbf{1576} := F(-1 + 5 + F(7)) - F(F(6))$$

$$\mathbf{1589} := -F(1 + 5) + F(8 + 9)$$

$$\mathbf{1592} := -1 \times 5 + F(F(9)) / 2$$

$$\mathbf{1593} := 1 - 5 + F(F(9)) / F(3)$$

$$\mathbf{1594} := F(F(1 + 5) + 9) - F(4)$$

$$\mathbf{1596} := -1^5 + F(9 + F(6))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1597 &:= F(1^5 + 9 + 7) & 2048 &:= 2^{F(04)+8} \\ 1597 &:= F(1^5 + 9 + 7) & 2048 &:= 2^{F(04)+8} \\ 1598 &:= 1^5 + F(9 + 8) & 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 \\ 1598 &:= 1^5 + F(9 + 8) & 2097 &:= (2 \times 0 + 9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 1617 &:= -1 + F(F(6)) + F(17) & 2185 &:= (F(21) - F(8))/5 \\ 1618 &:= F(16 + 1) + F(8) & 2185 &:= (F(21) - F(8))/5 \\ 1645 &:= F(16)/F(4) \times 5 & 2529 &:= -F(2 \times 5) + F(2 \times 9) \\ 1680 &:= 1 \times F(F(6)) \times 80 & 2563 &:= F(F(2 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 3) \\ 1684 &:= -1 + F(F(F(6))) - F(8)^{F(4)} & 2576 &:= F(25 - 7) - F(6) \\ 1687 &:= (F(F(1 + 6)) + 8) \times 7 & 2577 &:= F(25 - 7) - 7 \\ 1736 &:= (-1 + F(7))^3 + F(6) & 2578 &:= 2 + F(5 + F(7)) - 8 \\ 1736 &:= (-1 + F(7))^3 + F(6) & 2582 &:= F(2 \times 5 + 8) - 2 \\ 1763 &:= -1 + (7 \times 6)^{F(3)} & 2583 &:= -F(2) + F(-5 + F(8) + F(3)) \\ 1763 &:= -1 + (7 \times 6)^{F(3)} & 2584 &:= F(2 \times (5 + 8 - 4)) \\ 1764 &:= 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{F(F(4))} & 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) \\ 1778 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(8)) & 2586 &:= 2 + F((-5 + 8) \times 6) \\ 1785 &:= F(1 + 7) \times 85 & 2594 &:= 2 \times 5 + F(9 \times F(F(4))) \\ 1824 &:= (-1 + F(F(8))/2)/F(4) & 2597 &:= F(F(-2 + 5) \times 9) + F(7) \\ 1847 &:= -1 - 8 \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) & 2618 &:= F(F(2) + F(6)) + F(18) \\ 1848 &:= (1 + F(8)) \times 4 \times F(8) & 2639 &:= F(2 + F(6)) + F(F(3) \times 9) \\ 1856 &:= (-1 + F(8 + 5)) \times F(6) & 2645 &:= (2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times 5 \\ 1862 &:= F(F(-1 + 8)) \times F(6) - 2 & 2646 &:= 2 \times F(F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(F(6)) \\ 1863 &:= F(F(-1 + 8)) \times F(6) - F(F(3)) & 2648 &:= 2^6 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \\ 1864 &:= F(F(-1 + 8)) \times (6 + F(F(4))) & 2688 &:= 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 8 \\ 1865 &:= 1 + 8 \times F(F(6) + 5) & 2736 &:= (2 \times 7)^3 - F(6) \\ 1871 &:= -1 + 8 \times (F(F(7)) + 1) & 2736 &:= (2 \times 7)^3 - F(6) \\ 1872 &:= F(-1 + 8) \times F(F(7) - F(2)) & 2742 &:= (2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - 2 \\ 1873 &:= 1 + 8 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) & 2742 &:= (2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - 2 \\ 1877 &:= 1 \times 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(7) & 2743 &:= (2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - F(F(3)) \\ 1885 &:= F(1 + F(8) - 8) \times 5 & 2744 &:= (-2 + F(7) + F(4))^{F(4)} \\ 1890 &:= 1 \times F(8) \times 90 & 2744 &:= (-2 + F(7) + F(4))^{F(4)} \\ 1897 &:= (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 7 & 2746 &:= (2 + 7^{F(4)}) \times F(6) \\ 1925 &:= (1 + F(9)) \times F(2 \times 5) & 2746 &:= 2 + 7^{F(4)} \times F(6) \\ 1972 &:= (-1 + F(9 + 7)) \times 2 & 2754 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(5 + F(4))) \\ 1973 &:= -1 + F(9 + 7) \times F(3) & 2767 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F(6))) + F(7) \\ 1974 &:= F(1 \times 9 + 7) \times F(F(4)) & 2784 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 + 4) \\ 1976 &:= 19 \times F(7) \times F(6) & 2794 &:= -2 + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(4)) \\ 1976 &:= 19 \times F(7) \times F(6) & 2796 &:= F(2) \times F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(F(6))) \\ 1995 &:= F(-1 + 9) \times 95 & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2798 &:= 2 + F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(8)) & 3773 &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 \\
 2817 &:= F(2 \times (8 + 1)) + F(F(7)) & 3784 &:= 3^7 + F(F(8) - 4) \\
 2937 &:= (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(-F(3) + F(7)) & 3786 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 6 \\
 3178 &:= F(3) \times (F(17) - 8) & 3844 &:= (-F(3) + 8^{F(F(4))})^{F(F(4))} \\
 3178 &:= F(3) \times (F(17) - 8) & 3948 &:= F(3) \times 94 \times F(8) \\
 3192 &:= F(3) \times (-1 + F(F(9)/2)) & 3948 &:= F(3) \times 94 \times F(8) \\
 3194 &:= F(3) \times F(19 - F(F(4))) & 3966 &:= -3 + 9 \times F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 3196 &:= F(3) \times (1 + F(9 + F(6))) & 3968 &:= (-F(F(3)) + 9 \times F(F(6))) \times F(8) \\
 3364 &:= (3 + F(F(3) + F(6)))^{F(F(4))} & 3969 &:= F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 \\
 3367 &:= (3 + F(3)^{F(6)}) \times F(7) & 3979 &:= F(F(3)) + 9 \times F(7) \times F(9) \\
 3367 &:= 3 + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(7) & 4176 &:= -4 - 1 + F(F(7) + 6) \\
 3373 &:= -F(3) + (F(3) + F(7))^3 & 4177 &:= -4 + F(-1 + 7 + F(7)) \\
 3374 &:= -F(F(3)) + (F(3) + F(7))^{F(4)} & 4181 &:= F(-4 + 1 + F(8)) + 1 \\
 3382 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)))/2 & 4182 &:= F(F(4 - 1)) + F(F(8) - 2) \\
 3383 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)))/F(3) & 4183 &:= F(F(4)) + 1 \times F(F(8) - F(3)) \\
 3384 &:= (3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)))/F(F(4)) & 4184 &:= F(4) + F(1 + F(8) - F(4)) \\
 3495 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5 & 4197 &:= F(4) + F(19) + F(7) \\
 3528 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8 & 4197 &:= F(4) + F(19) + F(7) \\
 3569 &:= -F(F(3)) + 5 \times F(F(6)) \times F(9) & 4198 &:= -4 + F(19) + F(8) \\
 3575 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5 & 4198 &:= -4 + F(19) + F(8) \\
 3584 &:= (F(3) + 5) \times 8^{F(4)} & 4277 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7 \\
 3584 &:= (F(3) + 5) \times 8^{F(4)} & 4372 &:= F(F(4)) \times (3^7 - F(2)) \\
 3602 &:= F(3) + 60^2 & 4373 &:= F(F(4)) \times 3^7 - F(F(3)) \\
 3602 &:= F(3) + 60^2 & 4374 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(3)))^7 \times F(F(4)) \\
 3603 &:= 3 + 60^{F(3)} & 4386 &:= F(F(F(4))) - 3^8 + F(F(F(6))) \\
 3603 &:= 3 + 60^{F(3)} & 4388 &:= F(4) - 3^8 + F(F(8)) \\
 3635 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5 & 4394 &:= F(F(4)) \times (F(-F(3) + 9))^{F(4)} \\
 3639 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/3 - 9 & 4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) \\
 3644 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - 4 & 4455 &:= F(4)^4 \times 55 \\
 3645 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 5 & 4536 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + 5)^3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 3648 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/F(-4 + 8) & 4576 &:= 4 \times (5 \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \\
 3649 &:= (3 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(4))/9 & 4578 &:= (-F(4) \times 5 + F(F(7))) \times F(8) \\
 3666 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + F(F(6)))) \times 6 & 4624 &:= (4 + F(6)^2)^{F(F(4))} \\
 3726 &:= -F(3) + F(F(7)) \times 2 \times F(6) & 4632 &:= (F(4) + F(F(6))^3)/2 \\
 3728 &:= F(3) \times F(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 8 & 4647 &:= F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 3736 &:= (F(3) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) \times F(6) & 4720 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 20 \\
 3738 &:= F(3) \times F(F(7) - F(3)) \times F(8) & 4746 &:= (-4 + F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 3744 &:= F(3) \times F(7) \times F(F(4) \times 4) & 4765 &:= (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 5 \\
 & & 4766 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4767 &:= F(4) \times (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7 \\ 4768 &:= F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(8) \\ 4776 &:= (F(F(F(4)) + F(7)) - F(7)) \times F(6) \\ 4788 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7)) - 8) \times F(8) \\ 4791 &:= F(4) \times F(7 + 9 + 1) \\ 4794 &:= 47 \times F(9) \times F(4) \\ 4794 &:= 47 \times F(9) \times F(4) \\ 4847 &:= -4 - F(8) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \\ 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \\ 4871 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - 1) \\ 4872 &:= F(F(F(4))) \times F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \\ 4873 &:= F(F(F(4))) + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \\ 4874 &:= F(F(4)) + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\ 4876 &:= -4 + F(8 + 7) \times F(6) \\ 4877 &:= -F(4) + F(8) \times F(F(7)) - F(7) \\ 4878 &:= -F(F(4)) + 8 \times F(7 + 8) \\ 4887 &:= F(F(4)) - 8 + F(8) \times F(F(7)) \\ 4889 &:= -4 + F(8) \times F(-F(8) + F(9)) \\ 4892 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + F(8) \times F(F(9 - 2)) \\ 4893 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - 3 \\ 4894 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - F(F(4)) \\ 4896 &:= F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 6 \\ 4899 &:= F(4) + F(F(8) - 9) \times F(9) \\ 4913 &:= (-4 + F(9 - 1))^3 \\ 4935 &:= F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 5 \\ 4998 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9) \times F(9) \times F(8) \\ 5184 &:= (51 + F(8))^{F(F(4))} \\ 5439 &:= F(F(5 + F(4)))/F(3) - F(9) \\ 5463 &:= (-5 \times 4 + F(F(F(6))))/F(3) \\ 5464 &:= (-5) - 4 + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4)) \\ 5468 &:= -5 + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) \times (1/8) \\ 5473 &:= F(F(5 - 4 + 7))/F(3) \\ 5482 &:= 5 + 4 + (1/2) \times F(F(8)) \\ 5483 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)))/F(3) \\ 5675 &:= -5 \times (5 \times (6 - F(F(7)))) \\ 5785 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 5 \\ 5825 &:= 25 \times F(5 + 8) \\ 6300 &:= 300 \times F(F(6)) \\ 6548 &:= -F(6) - 5 + F(4)^8 \\ 6548 &:= -F(6) - 5 + F(4)^8 \\ 6561 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6562 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(2) \\ 6563 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(3) \\ 6564 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} + F(4) \\ 6615 &:= 15 \times (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \\ 6676 &:= -F(-6 + F(F(6))) \times 7 + F(F(F(6))) \\ 6728 &:= (F(F(F(6)))/F(7) - F(2)) \times 8 \\ 6736 &:= F(F(F(6)))/F(7) \times (F(3) + 6) \\ 6744 &:= -F(F(6)) + F(F(7) + F(4) + 4) \\ 6746 &:= -6 - F(7) + F(-F(F(F(4)))) + F(F(6)) \\ 6757 &:= (-6 + 7 \times 5) \times F(F(7)) \\ 6762 &:= -F(F(6))/7 + F(F(F(6))) - F(2) \\ 6763 &:= F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7) + 6) - F(3) \\ 6764 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 7 + 6) - F(F(F(4))) \\ 6765 &:= F(6 + F(7) + 6 - 5) \\ 6771 &:= 6 + F(F(7) + 7 \times 1) \\ 6772 &:= 6 + F(F(7) + 7) + F(2) \\ 6773 &:= 6 + F(F(7) + 7) + F(3) \\ 6774 &:= 6 + F(F(7) + 7) + F(4) \\ 6778 &:= -F(6) + F(F(7) + 7) + F(8) \\ 6784 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times 8 \times 4 \\ 6786 &:= F(F(6)) + F(-7 + F(8) + 6) \\ 6794 &:= F(6 + 7) + 9^4 \\ 6794 &:= F(6 + 7) + 9^4 \\ 6799 &:= F(F(F(6)) - F(-7 + 9)) + F(9) \\ 6845 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8^4 - 5 \\ 6867 &:= (-6 + F(8 + F(6))) \times 7 \\ 6924 &:= 6 \times (F(9)^2 - F(F(4))) \\ 6928 &:= 6 \times F(9)^2 - 8 \\ 6928 &:= 6 \times F(9)^2 - 8 \\ 6933 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - 3 \\ 6933 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - 3 \\ 6934 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - F(F(4)) \\ 6936 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times F(3 + 6) \\ 6942 &:= 6 \times (F(9)^{F(F(4))} + F(2)) \\ 6954 &:= F(F(6)) \times 9 + F(5 \times 4) \\ 6977 &:= (F(F(6)) + 9) \times F(F(7)) - F(7) \\ 6993 &:= F(F(6)) \times 9 \times (F(9) + 3) \\ 7163 &:= F(F(7) + 1) \times (F(F(6)) - F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7392 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times (F(9) - 2) \\7448 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8 \\7453 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))^5 - 3 \\7454 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))^5 - F(F(4)) \\7456 &:= F(F(7)) \times (F(F(4)) + 5 \times 6) \\7464 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(4) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\7476 &:= (7^{F(4)} + F(7)) \times F(F(6)) \\7645 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 5 \\7648 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6) \times 4 \times 8 \\7663 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(6) \times F(F(6) \times F(3)) \\7689 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-F(6)/8 + F(9)) \\7697 &:= F(7) \times F(6 + 9) - F(F(7)) \\7744 &:= (F(7) \times 7 - F(4))^{F(F(4))} \\7759 &:= 7 + (F(F(7)) - 5) \times F(9) \\7776 &:= (-7 + F(7))^{F(7)-F(6)} \\7776 &:= (-7 + F(7))^{F(7)-F(6)} \\7865 &:= F(7) \times (F(F(8)) - 6) - 5 \\7875 &:= (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \times 5 \\7883 &:= -F(7) + 8 \times F(8 \times F(3)) \\7911 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 11 \\7916 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 1 \times 6 \\7917 &:= (-F(7) + F(9)) \times F(1 + F(7)) \\7934 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 3 \times 4 \\7935 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F(3) + 5) \\7937 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(3) + F(7) \\7938 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(3) \times 8 \\7943 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(4 \times F(3)) \\7946 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4 \times 6 \\7949 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(4) \times 9 \\7957 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 5 \times 7 \\7964 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F(6)) \times F(F(4)) \\7974 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(7) \times 4 \\7978 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 7 \times 8 \\7985 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 5 \\7986 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 8 \times F(6) \\8213 &:= F(8) + 2^{13} \\8213 &:= F(8) + 2^{13} \\8247 &:= F(8 + 2) + F(F(4))^{F(7)} \\8294 &:= (F(F(8)) - 2) - F(9)) \times F(F(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8352 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(3)) - 5) \times 2 \\8361 &:= F(F(8)) - F(3 \times 6) - 1 \\8362 &:= F(F(8)) - F((3 + 6) \times 2) \\8363 &:= F(F(8)) + F(F(3)) - F(6 \times 3) \\8364 &:= F(F(8)) + F(3) - F(6 \times F(4)) \\8367 &:= -F(8) + 36 \times F(F(7)) \\8368 &:= -F(F(8) - 3) + 6 + F(F(8)) \\8383 &:= F(8) + F(3) \times F(F(8) - F(3)) \\8396 &:= -F(F(8) - 3) + F(9) + F(F(F(6))) \\8400 &:= 400 \times F(8) \\8464 &:= (84 + F(6))^{F(F(4))} \\8820 &:= 20 \times (F(8) \times F(8)) \\8849 &:= F(F(8)) - F(F(F(8)/F(4))) \times 9 \\8883 &:= F(8 + 8) \times (8 + F(F(3))) \\8972 &:= F(F(8)) - F(9 + 7) \times 2 \\9248 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8 \\9346 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) - F(4) + F(F(F(6))) \\9348 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) - F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) \\9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) + F(F(F(-F(4) + 9))) \\9363 &:= F(9) \times 3 + F(F(6))^3 \\9474 &:= 9^{F(4)} \times F(7) - F(4) \\9474 &:= 9^{F(4)} \times F(7) - F(4) \\9477 &:= 9^{-4+7} \times F(7) \\9477 &:= 9^{-4+7} \times F(7) \\9586 &:= -F(9) \times 5 \times 8 + F(F(F(6))) \\9756 &:= -F(9) \times 7 \times 5 + F(F(F(6))) \\9792 &:= F(9) \times (F(F(7)) + F(9 + F(2))) \\9837 &:= 98^{F(3)} + F(F(7)) \\10936 &:= -10 + F(9 \times 3 - 6) \\10946 &:= F(10 + 9 - 4 + 6) \\11177 &:= -1 - 1 + F(17) \times 7 \\11489 &:= (1 + (1 + 4)^8) / F(9) \\12348 &:= (F(12) + 3) \times 4 \times F(8) \\12384 &:= F(12) \times (F(3) + 84) \\12672 &:= F(12) \times F(6) \times (F(7) - 2) \\12816 &:= F(12) \times (81 + F(6)) \\13247 &:= -1 + F(3) \times F(24) / 7 \\13520 &:= F(1 \times 3) \times (-5 + F(20)) \\13530 &:= F((1 + 3) \times 5) \times F(3) + 0\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13543 &:= 13 + F(5 \times 4) \times F(3) \\ 13747 &:= F(13) \times (F(7) \times 4 + 7) \\ 13776 &:= (F(13) + F(7)) \times 7 \times F(6) \\ 13823 &:= -1 + (3 \times F(8 - 2))^3 \\ 13824 &:= ((1 + 3 + 8) \times 2)^{F(4)} \\ 14179 &:= 1 + 417 \times F(9) \\ 14326 &:= F(14) \times (32 + 6) \\ 14373 &:= F(14 + 3) \times (7 + F(3)) \\ 14739 &:= (-1 + 4 \times F(7))^3 / 9 \\ 15448 &:= F((1 + 5) \times 4) / F(4) - 8 \\ 15456 &:= F((1 + 5) \times 4) / (-5 + F(6)) \\ 15616 &:= -1 + 5^6 - 1 \times F(6) \\ 15625 &:= 1 \times 5^{F(6)} / 25 \\ 15627 &:= 1 + 5^6 + F(2)^{F(7)} \\ 15634 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + 3 \times F(4) \\ 15635 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + F(3) \times 5 \\ 15636 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + 3 + F(6) \\ 15637 &:= 1 + 5^6 - F(3) + F(7) \\ 15647 &:= 1 + 5^6 + F(4) \times 7 \\ 15648 &:= -1 + 5^6 + F(4) + F(8) \\ 15673 &:= -1 + 5^6 + 7^{F(3)} \\ 15692 &:= -1 + 5^6 + F(9) \times 2 \\ 15693 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + F(9) \times F(3) \\ 15696 &:= -1 + 5^6 + 9 \times F(6) \\ 15855 &:= F(15) \times (F(8) + 5) - 5 \\ 16347 &:= -1 - 6^{F(3)} + 4^7 \\ 16368 &:= -16 + F(3)^{6+8} \\ 16371 &:= -F(1 + 6) + F(3)^{F(7)+1} \\ 16372 &:= -1 \times 6 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times 2 \\ 16373 &:= 1 - 6 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times F(3) \\ 16378 &:= -1 \times 6 + F(3)^{-7+F(8)} \\ 16779 &:= F(16) \times ((F(7) + F(7)) - 9) \\ 16794 &:= -F(1 + 6) + 7^{9-4} \\ 16807 &:= (1 + 6)^{-8+F(07)} \\ 16815 &:= F(1 \times 6) + (8 - 1)^5 \\ 16847 &:= -1 + 6^{8-4} \times F(7) \\ 16863 &:= F(16) + (F(8) \times 6)^{F(3)} \\ 17239 &:= 1 + F(7)^2 \times 3 \times F(9) \\ 17399 &:= (1 + 7)^3 \times F(9) - 9 \\ 17564 &:= F(17) \times (5 + 6) - F(4) \\ 17568 &:= (-1 + F(7)^{-5+F(6)}) \times 8 \\ 17583 &:= 1 \times 7 + (5 + F(8))^3 \\ 17584 &:= 1 + 7 + (5 + F(8))^{F(4)} \\ 17622 &:= -F(17 - 6) + F(22) \\ 17697 &:= -1 - F(7) + F(6 + 9 + 7) \\ 17728 &:= 17 + F(7 \times 2 + 8) \\ 17849 &:= -1 + (F(7) + 8^{F(4)}) \times F(9) \\ 17947 &:= F(17) - F(9) + 4^7 \\ 18079 &:= F(18) \times 07 - 9 \\ 18177 &:= -F(18) + F(17) \times F(7) \\ 18473 &:= F((18 - 4)) \times (7^{F(3)}) \\ 18496 &:= (F(1 + 8) \times 4)^{F(9-6)} \\ 18523 &:= 1 + F(8)^{5-2} \times F(3) \\ 18970 &:= (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 70 \\ 19278 &:= 1 \times F(9) \times 27 \times F(8) \\ 19279 &:= 1 + 9^2 \times 7 \times F(9) \\ 19652 &:= 1 \times F(9)^{F(6)-5} / 2 \\ 19653 &:= 1 + F(9)^{F(6)-5} / F(3) \\ 19772 &:= -1 + 9 \times F(7) \times F(7)^2 \\ 19773 &:= 1 \times 9 \times F(7)^{F(7-3)} \\ 19774 &:= 1 + 9 \times F(7)^{7-4} \\ 20295 &:= F(20) \times F(2) \times F(9 - 5) \\ 20304 &:= (F(20) + 3) \times F(04) \\ 20329 &:= F(20) \times 3 \times F(2) + F(9) \\ 20347 &:= F(20) \times 3 + 4 \times F(7) \\ 20439 &:= F(20) \times F(4) + F(3 + 9) \\ 20484 &:= (F(20) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(4) \\ 20692 &:= 20 + F(6) \times F(9 \times 2) \\ 20736 &:= (-F(2) + F(07))^{-F(3)+6} \\ 21762 &:= F(21) + (F(7) \times F(6))^2 \\ 21837 &:= (F(21) - F(8)) \times F(3) - F(7) \\ 21953 &:= F(2) + (-1 + F(9) - 5)^3 \\ 21954 &:= 2 + (-1 + F(9) - 5)^{F(4)} \\ 22135 &:= 2 \times F(21) + 3^5 \\ 22528 &:= (2 + 2)^5 \times (F(2) + F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23744 &:= F(23) - (F(7) + 4)^{F(4)} \\ 24574 &:= -2 - (F(4) - 5)^{F(7)} \times F(4) \\ 24577 &:= F(2) + F(4) \times (-5 + 7)^{F(7)} \\ 26236 &:= (-2 + 6) \times (-2 + 3^{F(6)}) \\ 26246 &:= 2 + 6^2 \times F(4)^6 \\ 26248 &:= (-2 + 6) \times (F(2) + F(4))^8 \\ 26984 &:= -2 \times F(6) + (9 + F(8))^{F(4)} \\ 27634 &:= 2 \times (-7 + (F(6) \times 3)^{F(4)}) \\ 27644 &:= 2^7 \times 6^{F(4)} - 4 \\ 27945 &:= (-2 + F(7) \times 9) \times F(4)^5 \\ 28226 &:= 2 + F(8)^2 \times 2^6 \\ 28562 &:= F(2) + (8 + 5)^{6-2} \\ 28563 &:= 2 + (8 + 5)^{F(6)/F(3)} \\ 28574 &:= F(2) \times (8 + 5) + F(7)^4 \\ 28584 &:= 2 + F(8) + (5 + 8)^4 \\ 28629 &:= -28 + F(-6 + 29) \\ 28728 &:= (-2 + F(8)) \times 72 \times F(8) \\ 28823 &:= -2 + 8 \times F(8) + F(23) \\ 28928 &:= 2^8 \times (92 + F(8)) \\ 29184 &:= (2 + F(9 + 1)) \times 8^{F(4)} \\ 29466 &:= (-2 + F(9)^{F(4)} / F(6)) \times 6 \\ 29522 &:= (-F(2) + 9^5) / 2 - 2 \\ 29523 &:= (F(2) + 9^5) / 2 - F(3) \\ 29525 &:= (F(2) + 9^5) / F(-2 + 5) \\ 29537 &:= (-F(2) + 9^5) / F(3) + F(7) \\ 29584 &:= (2 + F(9) \times 5)^{8/4} \\ 29644 &:= F(29 - 6) + F(4 \times 4) \\ 29793 &:= 2 + (9 + F(7) + 9)^3 \\ 31248 &:= 31 \times (F(2^4) + F(8)) \\ 31256 &:= F(3) \times (1 + 2 + 5^6) \\ 31757 &:= -F(31 - 7) + 5^7 \\ 31944 &:= (3 + 19)^{F(4)} \times F(4) \\ 32734 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - 34 \\ 32757 &:= F(3) + (F(2) + 7)^5 - F(7) \\ 32773 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + 7 - F(3) \\ 32774 &:= F(3) \times (2^{7+7} + F(4)) \\ 32776 &:= F(3) \times 2^{7+7} + F(6) \\ 32781 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(8 - 1) \\ 32796 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(9) - 6 \\ 32798 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + 9 + F(8) \\ 32844 &:= 3 \times (2 + F(84/4)) \\ 32877 &:= 3 \times (F(28 - 7) + F(7)) \\ 33792 &:= F(3)^{3+7} \times (F(9) - F(2)) \\ 33825 &:= (F(3) + 3) \times F(8/2 \times 5) \\ 34742 &:= F(3) \times (4^7 + F(4^2)) \\ 34974 &:= 3 \times (-4 + F(9) \times 7^{F(4)}) \\ 34989 &:= 3 + 49 \times F(8) \times F(9) \\ 35934 &:= (-F(-3 + 5) + F(9))^3 - F(4) \\ 35987 &:= -3 + 59 \times F(8 + 7) \\ 36193 &:= F(3)^{F(6)} + (-1 + F(9))^3 \\ 36864 &:= F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(8 \times 6/4) \\ 37196 &:= (3^7 + 1) \times (9 + F(6)) \\ 37347 &:= -F(3) + F(7)^3 \times (4 + F(7)) \\ 37439 &:= F(3) \times F(7)^4 - 3^9 \\ 37522 &:= 3 + (F(7) + F(5^2)) / 2 \\ 37523 &:= (3 \times 7 + F(5^2)) / F(3) \\ 37632 &:= 3 \times (7 \times F(6) \times F(3))^2 \\ 38328 &:= 3 \times 8 \times F(3^2 + 8) \\ 38374 &:= -F(3) \times F(8) + (F(3) \times 7)^4 \\ 38845 &:= (-F(3)^8 + F(8)^4) / 5 \\ 39194 &:= -F(3) \times F(9 + 1) + F(9)^{F(4)} \\ 39236 &:= (-F(3) + F(9)^2) \times F(3 + 6) \\ 39273 &:= 3 - F(9) + F(2 + 7)^3 \\ 39285 &:= (F(3 \times 9) - F(2) + 8) / 5 \\ 39293 &:= F(3) - F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39294 &:= -3 - 9 + 2 + F(9)^{F(4)} \\ 39304 &:= F(3 \times 9/3)^{F(04)} \\ 39339 &:= 3^9 \times F(3) - 3 \times 9 \\ 43173 &:= F(4)^3 \times (F(17) + F(3)) \\ 43742 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - 42 \\ 43782 &:= (-4 + F(3 \times 7) \times 8) / 2 \\ 43787 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + F(8) / 7 \\ 45344 &:= -4^5 + F(3 \times (4 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45346 &:= -4^5 + F(3) + F(4 \times 6) & 54795 &:= 5 \times F(4 \times 7) / (F(9) - 5) \\ 45783 &:= -45 \times F(7) + F(8 \times 3) & 55339 &:= F(5 \times 5) - 3 - 3^9 \\ 46124 &:= -4 \times 61 + F(24) & 55342 &:= F(5 \times 5) - 3^{F(4)^2} \\ 46125 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (1 + 2)^5 & 56448 &:= 56 \times (F(4 \times 4) + F(8)) \\ 46133 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(13) - F(3) & 57349 &:= 5 + 7 \times F(3)^{4+9} \\ 46172 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (1 + F(7))^2 & 57645 &:= 5^7 - F(6)^4 \times 5 \\ 46184 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 184 & 58957 &:= -5 \times F(8) + 9^5 + F(7) \\ 46243 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (F(2) + 4)^3 & 59049 &:= F(-5 + 9) \times F(04)^9 \\ 46256 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 2 \times 56 & 59314 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 1 - 4 \\ 46310 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 - F(10) & 59315 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 1 - 5 \\ 46317 &:= F(4 \times 6) - 3 \times 17 & 59318 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 1^8 \\ 46327 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3^2) - 7 & 59319 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 \times 1^9 \\ 46335 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) - 35 & 59338 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - F(3) + F(8) \\ 46370 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3 + 7 \times 0) & 59347 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 4 \times 7 \\ 46372 &:= 4 + F(6^3 / (7 + 2)) & 59349 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - 4 + F(9) \\ 46373 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + F(7 - 3) & 59383 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + 8^{F(3)} \\ 46374 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 + 7 - 4 & 59392 &:= (-5 + F(9)) \times F(3)^{9+2} \\ 46416 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(4) \times 16 & 59426 &:= F(5 + 9) + F(4)^{2+F(6)} \\ 46431 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 4^3 - 1 & 60945 &:= 60 + 9 \times F(4 \times 5) \\ 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 61488 &:= 61 \times 48 \times F(8) \\ 46524 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 52 \times F(4) & 61848 &:= F(6) \times (F(18) \times F(4) - F(8)) \\ 46692 &:= 4 + 6^6 + F(9) - 2 & 62016 &:= F(6) \times (F(20) + F(16)) \\ 46698 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 6 \times (F(9) + F(8)) & 62564 &:= F(6)^2 + 5^6 \times 4 \\ 46993 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (F(9) - 9)^{F(3)} & 62946 &:= -6 - F(2 \times 9) + 4^{F(6)} \\ 48382 &:= 48^{F(3)} \times F(8) - 2 & 63164 &:= F(6)^{F(3)} \times F(16) - 4 \\ 48672 &:= 48 \times 6 \times F(7)^2 & 63175 &:= F(6 \times (3 + 1)) + 7^5 \\ 48828 &:= ((-F(4) + 8)^8 - F(2)) / 8 & 63964 &:= -6^{F(3)} + (F(9) + 6)^{F(4)} \\ 49278 &:= (-F(4) + 9) \times (2^{F(7)} + F(8)) & 63994 &:= -6 + (-3 + 9 + F(9))^{F(4)} \\ 49464 &:= (-4 + F(9 + 4)) \times 6^{F(4)} & 64837 &:= 6 + 4 + F(8)^3 \times 7 \\ 50653 &:= (50 - F(6) - 5)^3 & 64872 &:= 6 \times (-4 + (8 \times F(7))^2) \\ 52486 &:= -F(5 - 2) + F(4)^8 \times F(6) & 65142 &:= (65 + 1) \times F(4^2) \\ 52733 &:= 5 + (2 \times F(7))^3 \times 3 & 65368 &:= F(6)^5 \times F(3) - F(6) \times F(8) \\ 52743 &:= -5 + (2 \times F(7))^{F(4)} \times 3 & 65446 &:= -6 \times 5 \times F(4) + 4^{F(6)} \\ 53680 &:= F(5 \times 3) \times (F(6) + 80) & 65468 &:= -F(6 + 5) + 4^{F(6)} + F(8) \\ 54120 &:= (5 + F(4)) \times 1 \times F(20) & 65488 &:= -F(6) \times 5 + 4^8 - 8 \\ 54176 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times 7) \times F(6) & 65489 &:= -F(6) - 5 + 4^8 - F(9) \\ 54348 &:= (F(54/3) + 4) \times F(8) \\ 54576 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 57) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65523 &:= (F(6)^5 - 5) \times 2 - 3 & 83232 &:= 8 \times (F(3^2) \times 3)^2 \\
 65528 &:= F(6)^5 \times F(5 - 2) - 8 & 83328 &:= ((F(8) \times 3)^{F(3)} - F(2)) \times F(8) \\
 65536 &:= F(6)^5 \times (5 + 3 - 6) & 85184 &:= (F(8) + 5 + 18)^{F(4)} \\
 65538 &:= (F(6)^5 + 5) \times F(3) - 8 & 85224 &:= 8 \times (5 + 22^{F(4)}) \\
 65546 &:= (F(6)^5 + 5) \times (-4 + 6) & 85742 &:= -8 + (5 \times 7)^{F(4)} \times 2 \\
 65694 &:= 6 \times (F(5 \times 6 - 9) + F(4)) & 85848 &:= F(8) \times ((-5 + F(8))^{F(4)} - 8) \\
 65746 &:= 6 \times 5 \times 7 + 4^{F(6)} & 86184 &:= F(8) \times (F(6) + 1 \times 8^4) \\
 65892 &:= (65 - 8) \times F(9)^2 & 86528 &:= (8 \times (F(6) + 5))^2 \times 8 \\
 67116 &:= (67 + 1) \times F(16) & 87568 &:= 8 \times F(7 \times 5 - 6 - 8) \\
 67184 &:= 6 \times F(7) \times F(18) / F(4) & 87820 &:= -F(8) + F(7) \times (-8 + F(20)) \\
 67712 &:= F(6) \times (F(7) \times 7 + 1)^2 & 89712 &:= 89 \times 7 \times F(12) \\
 68913 &:= -F(6) + (8 + F(9) - 1)^3 & 91125 &:= (F(9) + 11)^{-2+5} \\
 72893 &:= -7 + (-2 + 8 \times F(9))^{F(3)} & 91145 &:= 9 + F(11) \times 4^5 \\
 73769 &:= -F(7) + (F(3)^{F(7)} + 6) \times 9 & 93393 &:= (F(9)^{F(3)} - 3) \times 9^{F(3)} \\
 73963 &:= -7 \times 3 + (F(9) \times F(6))^{F(3)} & 93628 &:= (9 \times F(3 + 6))^2 - 8 \\
 74379 &:= 7 \times F(4) + 3^7 \times F(9) & 93633 &:= (9 \times F(3 + 6))^{F(3)} - 3 \\
 74694 &:= F(7)^{-F(4)+6} \times F(9) - 4 & 93636 &:= (9 \times F(3 + 6))^{F(-3+6)} \\
 74698 &:= F(7)^{F(4)} \times F(6) \times F(9) / 8 & 97333 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))^3 - 3 \\
 74872 &:= 7^{F(4)} + (F(8) \times F(7))^2 & 97336 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))^{-3+6} \\
 74938 &:= F(7)^4 + 9 + F(3 \times 8) & 97344 &:= 9 \times F(7)^{F(3)} \times 4^{F(4)} \\
 74996 &:= (F(7)^{F(4)} + 9) \times F(9) - F(6) & 97417 &:= (9 + F(7) \times 4) \times F(17) \\
 75169 &:= F(7 + 5) + F(16 + 9) & 97682 &:= (F(9) \times F(7))^{-6+8} / 2 \\
 75625 &:= 75 \times F(6) + F(25) & 98192 &:= F(9) \times 8 \times (19^2) \\
 75647 &:= 7 + F(5 \times 6) / (4 + 7) & 98376 &:= (-9 + F(8)) \times (F(3)^{F(7)} + 6) \\
 76464 &:= (7 \times F(6) + F(4)) \times 6^4 & 98514 &:= 9 \times F((85 - 1) / 4) \\
 76594 &:= 7 \times (F(6 \times 5 - 9) - 4) & 98784 &:= 98 \times 7 \times F(8 + 4) \\
 76832 &:= -7^6 + F(8)^{F(3) \times 2} & 98974 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) \times F(9) + F(7)^{F(4)}) \\
 78125 &:= (F(7) - 8)^{1 \times 2 + 5} & 99223 &:= (9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^2 - F(3) \\
 81796 &:= ((F(8) + 1) \times F(7))^{F(9-6)} & 99225 &:= (9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^{F(-2+5)} \\
 82937 &:= (8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{F(3)} - 7 & & \\
 82944 &:= (-8 - 2 + F(9))^4 / 4 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

5.2.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned}
 123 &:= F(12) - F(F(3!)) & 248 &:= 2^{F(F(4)!)} - 8 \\
 126 &:= (1 + 2)! \times F(F(6)) & 264 &:= 2^{F(6)} + F(F(4)!) \\
 231 &:= -2 + F(F(3! + 1)) & 315 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 15 \\
 233 &:= F(F(2) + 3! + 3!) & 335 &:= -F(F(3)) + (F(3!))! / 5!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 362 &:= F(3) + 6!/2 \\
 364 &:= (F(3!) + 6!)/F(F(4)) \\
 420 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 20 \\
 438 &:= -F(4) + F(F(3!)) \times F(8) \\
 440 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} - 0! \\
 480 &:= 4! \times (F(8) - 0!) \\
 775 &:= -F(F(7)) + 7!/5 \\
 842 &:= F(F(8))/F(F(4)! + F(2)) \\
 987 &:= F(9!)/8! + 7 \\
 1024 &:= (1 + 0!)^{2+F(F(4)!)} \\
 1035 &:= F(10) \times F(F(3!)) - 5! \\
 1045 &:= F(10) \times (4! - 5) \\
 1260 &:= F(F((1 + 2)!)) \times 60 \\
 1296 &:= F(12) \times 9!/F(6)! \\
 1345 &:= 1 + F(3)!/(F(4)! \times 5) \\
 1352 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/5 - F(2) \\
 1353 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/(5 \times F(F(3))) \\
 1354 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/5 + F(F(F(4))) \\
 1435 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 3!! - 5 \\
 1470 &:= 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 70 \\
 1477 &:= 1 + F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) + F(7)) \\
 1493 &:= (-1 + F(F(4)!)/9)/3 \\
 1560 &:= 1 \times 5! \times F(F(6) - 0!) \\
 1575 &:= 15 + F(7) \times 5! \\
 1603 &:= F(16 + 0!) + 3! \\
 1631 &:= F(F(1 + 6)) \times (3! + 1) \\
 1664 &:= -16 + F(6)!/4! \\
 1679 &:= -1 + F(6)!/(F(7) - 9)! \\
 1686 &:= F(16) - F(8) + 6! \\
 1734 &:= 17^{F(3)} \times F(4)! \\
 1823 &:= -1 + (F(F(8)) - 2)/3! \\
 1824 &:= (-1 + F(F(8)) - F(2))/F(4)! \\
 1862 &:= F(18) - 6! - 2 \\
 1863 &:= F(18) - 6! - F(F(3)) \\
 1864 &:= F(18) - (6 - F(4))!! \\
 1920 &:= (-1 + 9)!/F(F((2 + 0)!)) \\
 2208 &:= F((2 + 2)!)/F(08) \\
 2214 &:= (F(22) + 1)/F(F(4)!)) \\
 2310 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!)) \times F(10) \\
 2317 &:= (2 \times 3)! + F(17) \\
 2330 &:= (2 + F(3!)) \times F(F(3! + 0!)) \\
 2540 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - 0! \\
 2583 &:= -F(2) + F((-5 + 8) \times 3!) \\
 2640 &:= (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times (4 + 0)! \\
 2648 &:= 2 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times F(8) \\
 2687 &:= -F(2) + F(6)!/(8 + 7) \\
 2735 &:= -F(2) - 7! + 3!^5 \\
 2748 &:= -2^{F(7)} - F(4)! + F(F(8)) \\
 2795 &:= (-F(2) + 7!/9) \times 5 \\
 2796 &:= 2 \times F(F(7)) \times (9 - 6)! \\
 2835 &:= (F(2) + 8)!/(F(3!) + 5!) \\
 2946 &:= (2^9 - F(F(F(4)!))) \times 6 \\
 3087 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (0 + F(8)) \times 7 \\
 3127 &:= (F(3!))!/12 - F(F(7)) \\
 3150 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 150 \\
 3155 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 5 \\
 3173 &:= ((F(3) \times F(17)) - F(F(3!))) \\
 3240 &:= 3!!/2 \times (F(F(4)! + 0!) \\
 3257 &:= (3^2)!/5! + F(F(7)) \\
 3312 &:= (F(3) + F(F(3!))) \times F(12) \\
 3375 &:= 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 5 \\
 3429 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!/2) \times 9 \\
 3435 &:= -F(F(3!)) + 4! \times 3!!/5 \\
 3460 &:= -(F(3!))! + 4 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - 0! \\
 3492 &:= 3 \times (F(F(4)! + F(9)^2) \\
 3580 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(8) + 0! \\
 3640 &:= (F(3!) + 6!) \times (4 + 0!) \\
 3647 &:= 3! \times F((F(F(6)) - F(4)!)) - F(7) \\
 3648 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 8 \\
 3649 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/(-F(4)! + 9) \\
 3653 &:= 3^6 \times 5 + F(3!) \\
 3658 &:= -F(3) + 6 \times F(5!/8) \\
 3694 &:= -F(F(F(3!))) + F(6 + 9) \times 4! \\
 3720 &:= F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) \times 2 - 0!) \\
 3730 &:= F(3) \times (F(F(7)) \times F(3!) + 0!) \\
 3770 &:= (3 + 7) \times F(F(7) + 0!) \\
 3856 &:= F(3)^8 + 5 \times 6! \\
 3927 &:= (F(3!) + 9) \times (-2 + F(F(7))) \\
 3935 &:= (3^9 - F(3!))/5 \\
 3960 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times (6 - 0)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3961 &:= (F(3!) + 9) \times F(F(6 + 1)) & 4740 &:= (4 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \\
 3968 &:= F(3!) \times (9!/6! - 8) & 4780 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(7))) \times (F(8) - 0!) \\
 4080 &:= (4 + 0!)! \times F(8 + 0!) & 4800 &:= F(4)! \times 800 \\
 4128 &:= (F(4!) + (F((1 + 2)!)))/F(8) & 4870 &:= -4! + F(8) \times F(F(7)) + 0! \\
 4147 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) + 1 + F(F(4)! + F(7)) & 4871 &:= -F(F(4)!) \times F(8) + 7! - 1 \\
 4160 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) + F(-1 + F(F(6)) - 0!) & 4874 &:= -F(F(4)!) \times F(8) + 7! + F(F(4)) \\
 4180 &:= F(-F(4 - 1) + F(8)) - 0! & 4892 &:= F(4!) - 8! - F(9)^2 \\
 4181 &:= F((4 - 1)! + F(8 - 1)) & 4960 &:= -F(4)!!/9 + (F(6) - 0!) \\
 4190 &:= F(F(4)!) + F(19) + 0! & 4967 &:= -F(F(F(4))) - 9 \times F(6) + 7! \\
 4193 &:= F(4)! + F(19) + 3! & 4970 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9)! - 70 \\
 4196 &:= F(4)! + F(19) - F(F(6)) & 4987 &:= F(F(4)) - F(9) - F(8) + 7! \\
 4200 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 200 & 5149 &:= -F(5 - 1) + F(4!)/9 \\
 4310 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 10 & 5280 &:= 5! \times 2 \times (F(8) + 0!) \\
 4319 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1^9 & 5332 &:= -5! - F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(3!)))/2 \\
 4340 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + 3!! \times F(4)! - 0! & 5336 &:= (-53 + 3!!) \times F(6) \\
 4365 &:= F(4)!! + 3^6 \times 5 & 5346 &:= (-5 \times 3!! + F(4!))/F(6) \\
 4378 &:= -F(4)^{F(3!)} - 7 + F(F(8)) & 5376 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 6 \\
 4394 &:= (-F(4)!! + (F(3!))!)/9 - F(4)! & 5384 &:= -F(5 + 3!) + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) \\
 4395 &:= (-F(4)!! + (F(3!))!)/9 - 5 & 5413 &:= (-5! + F(F(F((4 - 1)!)))/F(3) \\
 4399 &:= (-F(4)!! + (F(3!))! - 9)/9 & 5417 &:= F(5 \times F(4) - 1) + 7! \\
 4410 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10 & 5434 &:= (-5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(3) + F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 4428 &:= (F(4!) - F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 2)/8 & 5438 &:= (5! + F(F(4)!))^{F(3)} - F(F(8)) \\
 4430 &:= -F((F(F(F(4)!)) - F(4)!)) + (3! + 0)! & 5462 &:= -5 - F(4)! + F(F(F(6)))/2 \\
 4440 &:= F(4)! \times F(4)!! + (4 + 0)! & 5488 &:= (5! + 4 \times F(F(8)))/8 \\
 4450 &:= F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 50 & 5533 &:= (5! + F(F(5 + 3)))/F(3) \\
 4452 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F(5 + 2))) & 5653 &:= 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!)/F(3) \\
 4459 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(4) + 5)!/9 & 5674 &:= F(5!)/F(6) + 7! + 4! \\
 4472 &:= -F(F(4)!) + (F(F(4)!))!/(7 + 2) & 5738 &:= 5 + F(7) \times F(F(3!)) \times F(8) \\
 4475 &:= F(F(4)!)/(-4 + F(7)) - 5 & 5796 &:= F((5 - F(-7 + 9))!)/F(6) \\
 4479 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + F(F(4)!) \times 7!/9 & 5874 &:= 5! + 8!/7 - F(4)! \\
 4497 &:= 4 + (F(F(4)!))!/9 + F(7) & 5877 &:= -5 + F(F(8))/F(7) + 7! \\
 4560 &:= -4 \times 5! + (F(6) - 0)! & 5949 &:= (-59 + F(4)!!) \times 9 \\
 4563 &:= F(4)^5 + 6! \times 3! & 6036 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 0!) - 3^6 \\
 4569 &:= F(F(4)! + 5) + F(6)!/9 & 6048 &:= F(6 \times 04) - 8! \\
 4636 &:= (F(4!) - F(6))/F(3) + F(6) & 6084 &:= (6 \times F(-0! + 8))^{F(F(4))} \\
 4637 &:= -F(F(4))^{F(6)} + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) & 6193 &:= 6! + F(F(-1 + 9))/F(3) \\
 4647 &:= (F(F(4)!) \times F(F(F(6)) - F(4)!)) - F(F(7)) & 6392 &:= -F(6) + (3!!/9)^2 \\
 4660 &:= -(F(F(F(4))) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(6) - 0!)) & 6394 &:= -6 + (3!!/9)^{F(F(4))} \\
 4672 &:= -F(F(4)!) + 6! \times F(7)/2 & 6408 &:= (6! - F(F(4)!)) \times (0! + 8) \\
 4736 &:= (-F(F(4))^{7} + 3!!) \times F(6) & 6432 &:= (6! + 4!!/(F(F(3!))!))/2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6433 := (F(6)!/F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(F(3!))))/F(3)$$

$$6436 := F(F(F(6))) - F(4!)/3 + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$6456 := 6^{F(4)!} + 5! - F(6)!$$

$$6472 := F(6) \times (F(4)!! + F(F(7) - 2))$$

$$6477 := (F(6)! - F(F(F(4)!)) + 7!)/7$$

$$6490 := (6! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 9 + 0!$$

$$6493 := F(F(F(6)))/F(4) + 9 \times 3!!$$

$$6498 := (6! + F(F(4))) \times 9!/8!$$

$$6560 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} - 0!$$

$$6660 := F(6)!/6 - 60$$

$$6684 := -6 \times 6 + 8!/F(4)!$$

$$6715 := F(6)!/(7 - 1) - 5$$

$$6760 := F(6) - F(7) + F(F(F(6))) - 0!$$

$$6770 := 6 + F(F(7) + 7) - 0!$$

$$6780 := F(6) + 7 + F(F(8) - 0!)$$

$$6833 := 68 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(3!)))$$

$$6850 := F(F(F(6))) - 8^{5-0!}$$

$$6930 := 6 \times (F(9)^{F(3)} - 0!)$$

$$6944 := F(6) + F(9)^{F(F(4))} \times F(4)!$$

$$7203 := 7^{2+0!} \times F(F(3!))$$

$$7246 := 7! - 2 + F(4!)/F(F(6))$$

$$7248 := 7! + F(24)/F(8)$$

$$7349 := F(7)^3 + F(4!)/9$$

$$7350 := 7 \times F(F(3!)) \times 50$$

$$7357 := F(7)^3 + 5! + 7!$$

$$7365 := -F(F(7)) \times 3 + F(6)!/5$$

$$7434 := (7!/4 - F(F(3!))) \times F(4)!$$

$$7488 := F(7)!/((-F(4)!! + 8!) \times F(8))$$

$$7618 := 7! - 6 + F(18)$$

$$7632 := (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times 3!^2$$

$$7633 := (7! + F(F(F(6))) - 3!)/F(3)$$

$$7784 := 7! + (-7 + F(8))^{F(4)}$$

$$7793 := F(F(7)) + 7! \times 9/3!$$

$$7831 := -F(F(7)) + 8!/(3! - 1)$$

$$7855 := -F(F(7)) + (8! + 5!)/5$$

$$8063 := 8!/(-0! + 6) - F(F(3))$$

$$8085 := F(8) + 08!/5$$

$$8092 := (8 - 0!) \times F(9)^2$$

$$8145 := 81 + (F(F(4)!))!/5$$

$$8317 := 8!/3! + F(17)$$

$$8364 := F(F(8)) + F(3) - F(-6 + 4!)$$

$$8445 := 8!/4! + F(4 \times 5)$$

$$8642 := F(F(8)) - (F(6) \times F(4)!)^2$$

$$8644 := (8 + 6! \times 4!)/F(F(4))$$

$$8738 := F(F(8)) - F((7 - 3)!)/F(8)$$

$$8743 := F(F(8)) - F(7)^{F(4)} + 3!$$

$$8749 := F(F(8)) - F(7)^{-F(4)!+9}$$

$$8833 := (F(F(8)) + 8!/3!)/F(3)$$

$$8947 := 8!/9 \times F(F(4)) - F(7)$$

$$8974 := (8!/9 + 7) \times F(F(4))$$

$$9239 := F(9)^2 \times F(3!) - 9$$

$$9244 := F(9)^2 \times F(F(4)!) - 4$$

$$9353 := (F(9 \times 3) - 5)/F(F(3!))$$

$$9370 := 9 + 3!! \times F(7) + 0!$$

$$9450 := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 50$$

$$9938 := -(9! + 9!)/3!! + F(F(8))$$

5.3 Reverse Order of Digits

5.3.1 Basic Operations

$$34 := F(F(4)^{F(3)})$$

$$36 := 6^{F(3)}$$

$$63 := 3 \times F(F(6))$$

$$64 := F(F(4))^6$$

$$84 := 4 \times F(8)$$

$$143 := F(3 \times 4) - 1$$

$$144 := F(4 \times (4 - 1))$$

$$168 := F(8) \times F(6) \times 1$$

$$189 := 9 \times F(8) \times 1$$

$$231 := F(13) - 2$$

$$233 := F(F(3 \times 3 - 2))$$

$$234 := F(F(4 + 3)) + F(2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 235 &:= F(F(5 + F(3))) + 2 \\ 237 &:= F(F(7)) + F(3) + 2 \\ 243 &:= 3^{F(4)+2} \\ 256 &:= (F(F(6)) - 5)^2 \\ 267 &:= F(F(7)) + F(F(6) + F(2)) \\ 374 &:= -F(4) + F(7 \times F(3)) \\ 376 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 7) - F(F(3)) \\ 377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\ 378 &:= F(F(8) - 7) + F(F(3)) \\ 438 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} - F(4) \\ 466 &:= F(-F(6) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(4)) \\ 472 &:= 2 \times (F(F(7)) + F(4)) \\ 693 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times F(F(6)))) \\ 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\ 986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\ 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\ 1175 &:= 5 \times (F(F(7)) + 1 + 1) \\ 1178 &:= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\ 1292 &:= F(2 \times 9)/2 \times 1 \\ 1293 &:= F(F(3) \times 9)/2 + 1 \\ 1367 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6 - 31 \\ 1397 &:= F(F(7)) \times (9 - 3) - 1 \\ 1536 &:= F(6)^3 \times F(5 - 1) \\ 1546 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 4) - 51 \\ 1576 &:= F(F(6)) \times 75 + 1 \\ 1589 &:= F(9 + 8) - F(5 + 1) \\ 1594 &:= -F(4) + F(9 + F(5 + 1)) \\ 1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\ 1597 &:= F(F(7) + 9 - 5 \times 1) \\ 1598 &:= F(F(8) - 9 + 5) + 1 \\ 1618 &:= F(8) + F(16 + 1) \\ 1631 &:= F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\ 1684 &:= F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))/F(6 + 1) \\ 1687 &:= (F(F(7)) + 8) \times (6 + 1) \\ 1764 &:= 4 \times F(F(6)) \times F(7 + 1) \\ 1778 &:= (F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 7 \times 1 \\ 1847 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times 8 - 1 \\ 1848 &:= 84 \times (F(8) + 1) \\ 1856 &:= F(6) \times (F(5 + 8) - 1) \\ 1862 &:= -2 + F(6) \times F(F(8 - 1)) \\ 1863 &:= (F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 81 \\ 1864 &:= (F(F(4)) + 6) \times F(F(8 - 1)) \\ 1865 &:= F(5 + F(6)) \times 8 + 1 \\ 1871 &:= (1 + F(F(7))) \times 8 - 1 \\ 1872 &:= (F(2) + F(F(7))) \times 8 \times 1 \\ 1873 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times 8 + 1 \\ 1877 &:= F(7) + F(F(7)) \times 8 \times 1 \\ 1885 &:= 5 \times F(F(8) - 8 + 1) \\ 1897 &:= 7 \times (F(9) \times 8 - 1) \\ 1925 &:= F(5 \times 2) \times (F(9) + 1) \\ 1972 &:= 2 \times (F(7 + 9) - 1) \\ 1972 &:= 2 \times (F(7 + 9) - 1) \\ 1973 &:= F(3) \times F(7 + 9) - 1 \\ 1974 &:= F(F(4)) \times F(7 + 9 \times 1) \\ 2079 &:= 9 \times (F(F(7)) - 02) \\ 2097 &:= F(F(7)) \times (9 + 0 \times 2) \\ 2176 &:= -F(F(6)) + F(7)^{1+2} \\ 2197 &:= F(7)^{9/(1+2)} \\ 2296 &:= (-F(6) + F(9)^2) \times 2 \\ 2478 &:= F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(4))/2 \\ 2529 &:= F(9 \times 2) - F(5 \times 2) \\ 2563 &:= (3 + F(6)) \times F(F(5 + 2)) \\ 2576 &:= -F(6) + F(-7 + 5^2) \\ 2577 &:= -7 + F(-7 + 5^2) \\ 2578 &:= -8 + F(F(7) + 5) + 2 \\ 2581 &:= (F(18) - 5 + 2) \\ 2581 &:= F(18) - 5 + 2 \\ 2582 &:= -2 + F(8 + 5 \times 2) \\ 2583 &:= F(-3 + F(8)) - F(F(5 - 2)) \\ 2584 &:= F((-4 + 8) \times 5 - 2) \\ 2585 &:= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\ 2586 &:= F(6 \times (8 - 5)) + 2 \\ 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\ 2594 &:= F(F(F(4)) \times 9) + 5 \times 2 \\ 2597 &:= F(7) + F(9 \times F(5 - 2)) \\ 2639 &:= F(9 \times F(3)) + F(F(6) + 2) \\ 2645 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))^2 \\ 2646 &:= F(6 \times F(4)) + 62 \\ 2648 &:= F(F(8) - F(4)) + F(6)^2 \\ 2667 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2688 &:= 8 \times F(8) \times F(6) \times 2 \\ 2688 &:= 8 \times F(8) \times F(6) \times 2 \\ 2704 &:= (4 \times F(07))^2 \\ 2704 &:= (4 \times F(07))^2 \\ 2736 &:= (F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times F(F(7) - F(2)) \\ 2784 &:= (4 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \\ 2794 &:= (F(4) + 9) \times F(F(7)) - 2 \\ 2796 &:= (F(F(6)) - 9) \times F(F(7) \times F(2)) \\ 2798 &:= (F(8) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 2 \\ 2817 &:= F(F(7)) + F((1 + 8) \times 2) \\ 2937 &:= (F(F(7) - F(3))) \times (F(9) - F(2)) \\ 3025 &:= F(5 \times 2)^{F(03)} \\ 3025 &:= F(5 \times 2)^{F(03)} \\ 3087 &:= 7 \times F(8)^{F(03)} \\ 3087 &:= 7 \times F(8)^{F(03)} \\ 3136 &:= (F(F(6) + F(3)) + 1)^{F(3)} \\ 3249 &:= (F(9 + F(F(4)))) + 2)^{F(3)} \\ 3364 &:= (F(4 + 6) + 3)^{F(3)} \\ 3364 &:= (F(4 + 6) + 3)^{F(3)} \\ 3372 &:= (2 + F(7))^3 - 3 \\ 3372 &:= (2 + F(7))^3 - 3 \\ 3373 &:= (F(3) + F(7))^3 - F(3) \\ 3374 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(7))^3 - F(F(3)) \\ 3376 &:= (F(6) + 7)^3 + F(F(3)) \\ 3381 &:= (F(-1 + F(8)) - 3)/F(3) \\ 3382 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) \\ 3383 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) \\ 3384 &:= (F(4) + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) \\ 3385 &:= (5 + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) \\ 3495 &:= 5 \times F(9 + 4) \times 3 \\ 3495 &:= 5 \times F(9 + 4) \times 3 \\ 3528 &:= F(8)^2 \times (5 + 3) \\ 3528 &:= F(8)^2 \times (5 + 3) \\ 3569 &:= F(9) \times F(F(6)) \times 5 - F(F(3)) \\ 3575 &:= 5 \times F(7) \times F(5 \times F(3)) \\ 3628 &:= -F(8) + (F(2) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3635 &:= 5 \times (3^6 - F(3)) \\ 3635 &:= 5 \times (3^6 - F(3)) \\ 3639 &:= -9 + (-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3644 &:= -4 + (-F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3645 &:= 5 \times (F(4) + 6)^3 \\ 3645 &:= 5 \times (F(4) + 6)^3 \\ 3646 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 6)/3 \\ 3647 &:= (-7 + F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3648 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)))/(6 - 3) \\ 3649 &:= (F(F(9/F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3652 &:= (2 \times 5 + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3653 &:= (F(F(3) + 5) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3664 &:= (46 + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3666 &:= 6 \times (F(-6 + F(F(6))) + F(F(3))) \\ 3694 &:= (4 \times F(9) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3718 &:= (F(8) + 1) \times F(7)^{F(3)} \\ 3718 &:= (F(8) + 1) \times F(7)^{F(3)} \\ 3726 &:= F(6) \times 2 \times F(F(7)) - F(3) \\ 3728 &:= 8 \times F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times F(3) \\ 3736 &:= F(6) \times (F(3) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) \\ 3738 &:= F(8) \times F(3) \times F(F(7) - F(3)) \\ 3744 &:= F(F(4) \times 4) \times F(7) \times F(3) \\ 3786 &:= 6 \times (F(8) + F(F(7) + F(3))) \\ 3789 &:= 9 \times F(F(8))/(F(7) \times F(3)) \\ 3796 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(9) \times F(7))/3 \\ 3844 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) + F(4) \times F(8))^{F(3)} \\ 3864 &:= -4 \times (F(F(6)) - F(8 \times F(3))) \\ 3927 &:= (F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(9)/F(3) \\ 3948 &:= F(F(8) - F(F(4))) - F(F(9 - F(3))) \\ 3961 &:= F(F(1 + 6)) \times F(9)/F(3) \\ 3966 &:= F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - 3 \\ 3968 &:= F(8) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - F(F(3)) \\ 3969 &:= (9 \times 6 + 9)^{F(3)} \\ 3969 &:= (9 \times 6 + 9)^{F(3)} \\ 3979 &:= F(9) \times F(7) \times 9 + F(F(3)) \\ 3999 &:= (9 + F(9)) \times 93 \\ 3999 &:= (9 + F(9)) \times 93 \\ 4096 &:= F(6)^{9 \times 0 + 4} \\ 4096 &:= F(6)^{9 \times 04} \\ 4147 &:= (7 + 4) \times F(14) \\ 4147 &:= (7 + 4) \times F(14) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4167 &:= F(F(7) + 6) - 14 \\4176 &:= F(6 + F(7)) - 1 - 4 \\4177 &:= F(F(7) + 7 - 1) - 4 \\4181 &:= F(18 + 1^4) \\4181 &:= F(18 + 1^4) \\4182 &:= F(2) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\4183 &:= F(3) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\4184 &:= F(4) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\4277 &:= 7 \times (F(F(7) + 2) + F(F(F(4)))) \\4356 &:= (65 + F(F(3)))^{F(F(4))} \\4373 &:= 3^7 \times F(3) - F(F(F(4))) \\4374 &:= F(4)^7 \times (-F(3) + 4) \\4374 &:= F(4)^7 \times (-F(3) + 4) \\4378 &:= (-8 + F(7)^3) \times F(F(4)) \\4394 &:= (4 + 9)^3 \times F(F(4)) \\4427 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-2 + F(4 + 4)) \\4428 &:= (F(F(8) + F(2)) + F(F(F(4))))/4 \\4455 &:= 55 \times F(4)^4 \\4455 &:= 55 \times F(4)^4 \\4536 &:= 6^3 \times F(5 + F(4)) \\4576 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(F(7)) \times 5) \times 4 \\4578 &:= F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - 5 \times F(4)) \\4624 &:= (4 + 2^6)^{F(F(4))} \\4647 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \\4693 &:= F(3)^9 + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \\4736 &:= F(6)^{F(3)} \times 74 \\4736 &:= F(6)^{F(3)} \times 74 \\4746 &:= F(F(6)) \times (-F(4) + F(F(7)) - 4) \\4765 &:= 5 \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(7)) \times 4) \\4766 &:= F(F(6)) \times (-6 + F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\4767 &:= (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 7 \times F(4) \\4768 &:= F(8) \times (-6 + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(4))) \\4776 &:= F(6) \times (-F(7) + F(F(7) + F(F(4)))) \\4781 &:= F(18) + F(7)^{F(4)} \\4781 &:= F(18) + F(7)^{F(4)} \\4788 &:= F(8) \times (-8 + F(F(7)) + F(4)) \\4791 &:= F(1 + 9 + 7) \times F(4) \\4847 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times F(8) - 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4864 &:= F(F(4))^{F(6)} \times (F(8) - F(F(4))) \\4871 &:= (-1 + F(F(7))) \times F(8) - F(F(F(4))) \\4872 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times F(8) \times F(F(F(4))) \\4873 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times F(8) + F(F(F(4))) \\4874 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times F(8) + F(F(4)) \\4876 &:= F(6) \times F(7 + 8) - 4 \\4877 &:= -F(7) + F(F(7)) \times F(8) - F(4) \\4878 &:= 8 \times F(7 + 8) - F(F(4)) \\4887 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(8) - 8 + F(F(4)) \\4889 &:= F(F(9) - F(8)) \times F(8) - 4 \\4892 &:= F(F(-2 + 9)) \times F(8) - F(F(F(4))) \\4893 &:= -3 + F(9) \times F(8 + 4) \\4894 &:= -F(F(4)) + F(9) \times F(8 + 4) \\4896 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times 8 \times F(4) \\4896 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times 8 \times F(4) \\4899 &:= F(9) \times F(-9 + F(8)) + F(4) \\4913 &:= (-F(3) + 19)^{F(4)} \\4935 &:= 5 \times F(3 + 9 + 4) \\4935 &:= 5 \times F(3 + 9 + 4) \\4956 &:= F(F(6)) \times 59 \times 4 \\4964 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} - F(F(9)/F(F(4))) \\4987 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(8) + 94 \\4998 &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times (9 - F(F(4))) \\5346 &:= (F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 3^5 \\5376 &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(7) + 3^5) \\5428 &:= F(F(8))/2 - 45 \\5464 &:= -4 + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4)) - 5 \\5468 &:= F(F(8))/(6 - 4) - 5 \\5469 &:= -9 + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4)) + 5 \\5473 &:= F(3 \times 7)/(-F(4) + 5) \\5473 &:= F(3 \times 7)/(-F(4) + 5) \\5478 &:= F(F(8))/F(7 - 4) + 5 \\5486 &:= F(6) + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) + 5 \\5528 &:= F(F(8))/2 + 55 \\5675 &:= 5 \times (F(F(7)) - 6) \times 5 \\5679 &:= -9 \times F(F(7)) + 6^5 \\5728 &:= F(8)^2 \times F(7) - 5 \\5728 &:= F(8)^2 \times F(7) - 5 \\5738 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5738 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 5 \\ 5785 &:= 5 \times (-8 + F(F(7))) \times 5 \\ 5825 &:= 5^2 \times F(8 + 5) \\ 5825 &:= 5^2 \times F(8 + 5) \\ 6327 &:= -F(F(7)) - F(2) + 3^{F(6)} \\ 6328 &:= -F(F(8 - F(2))) + 3^{F(6)} \\ 6394 &:= 4 \times F(F(9)/F(3)) + 6 \\ 6408 &:= 80^{F(F(4))} + F(6) \\ 6417 &:= -F(F(7) - 1) + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6456 &:= -F(F(6)) \times 5 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6472 &:= -F(-2 + F(7)) + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6489 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6489 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6493 &:= -F(3) \times F(9) + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6493 &:= -F(3) \times F(9) + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ 6561 &:= (F(1 \times 6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6561 &:= 1 \times (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6562 &:= F(2) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6563 &:= F(3) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6564 &:= F(4) + (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \\ 6676 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 7 \times F(-6 + F(F(6))) \\ 6736 &:= F(F(F(6)))/(F(F(3)) \times F(7)) \times F(6) \\ 6744 &:= F(F(4)^{F(4)} - 7) - F(F(6)) \\ 6757 &:= F(F(7)) \times (5 \times 7 - 6) \\ 6763 &:= -F(3) + F(F(F(6)) - 7 + 6) \\ 6764 &:= (F(F(4) + F(6))) \times 76 \\ 6765 &:= F(-56 + 76) \\ 6765 &:= F(-56 + 76) \\ 6771 &:= F(1 \times 7 + F(7)) + 6 \\ 6772 &:= -F(2) + F(F(7) + 7) + F(6) \\ 6773 &:= F(F(3)) \times F(F(7) + 7) + F(6) \\ 6774 &:= F(4) + F(F(7) + 7) + 6 \\ 6778 &:= F(F(8)) + F(7) - F(F(7) + 6) \\ 6784 &:= 4 \times (-F(8) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\ 6786 &:= F(F(6)) + F(F(8) - 7 + 6) \\ 6799 &:= F(9) + F(F(9) + 7 - F(F(6))) \\ 6867 &:= 7 \times (-6 + F(8 + F(6))) \\ 6936 &:= F(6 + 3) \times F(9) \times 6 \\ 6954 &:= F(4 \times 5) + 9 \times F(F(6)) \\ 6977 &:= -F(7) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6))) \\ 6993 &:= (3 + F(9)) \times 9 \times F(F(6)) \\ 7163 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times F(1 + F(7)) \\ 7223 &:= (32 - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7392 &:= (-2 + F(9)) \times (-F(3) + F(F(7))) \\ 7448 &:= 8 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + 4 \times F(F(7))) \\ 7456 &:= (F(F(6)) - 5) \times F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7458 &:= 85^{F(F(4))} + F(F(7)) \\ 7463 &:= -3^6 + F(F(4))^{F(7)} \\ 7464 &:= F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6))) + F(4) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7476 &:= F(F(6)) \times (7^{F(4)} + F(7)) \\ 7543 &:= (F(3) + 4)^5 - F(F(7)) \\ 7648 &:= 8 \times 4 \times (6 + F(F(7))) \\ 7663 &:= F(F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(6) - F(F(7)) \\ 7689 &:= (F(9) - F(8 - 6)) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7697 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 6) - F(F(7)) \\ 7756 &:= 6^5 - F(7) - 7 \\ 7756 &:= 6^5 - F(7) - 7 \\ 7759 &:= F(9) \times (-5 + F(F(7))) + 7 \\ 7776 &:= 6^{F(7) - F(-7 + F(7))} \\ 7865 &:= (-5 + F(-6 + F(8))) \times F(7) \\ 7875 &:= 5 \times (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \\ 7883 &:= F(F(3) \times 8) \times 8 - F(7) \\ 7896 &:= F(6) \times 987 \\ 7896 &:= F(6) \times 987 \\ 7902 &:= -20 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7911 &:= -11 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7916 &:= -6 + 1 \times F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7917 &:= F(F(7) + 1) \times (F(9) - F(7)) \\ 7934 &:= 4 \times 3 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7935 &:= F(5 + F(3)) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7937 &:= F(7) + F(3) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7938 &:= 8 \times F(3) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7939 &:= F(9)/F(3) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7943 &:= F(F(3)^{F(4)}) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7946 &:= 6 \times 4 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7949 &:= 9 \times F(4) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7954 &:= F(F(4))^5 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7957 &:= 7 \times 5 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7964 &:= F(F(4)) \times F(F(6)) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7974 &:= 4 \times F(7) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7978 &:= 8 \times 7 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 7985 &:= 5 \times F(F(8)) + 9 - F(7) \\ 7986 &:= F(6) \times 8 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 8172 &:= 2^{F(7)} + 1 - F(8) \\ 8172 &:= 2^{F(7)} + 1 - F(8) \\ 8174 &:= F(F(4))^{F(7)} - 18 \\ 8184 &:= F(F(4))^{F(8-1)} - 8 \\ 8294 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + F(-2 + F(8))) \\ 8352 &:= 2 \times (-5 + F(-F(3) + F(8))) \\ 8361 &:= -1 - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8)) \\ 8362 &:= 2 \times F(F(6) + 3 + 8) \\ 8363 &:= F(F(3)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8)) \\ 8364 &:= F(F(4)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8)) \\ 8367 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6^{F(3)} - F(8) \\ 8368 &:= F(F(8)) + 6 - F(-3 + F(8)) \\ 8383 &:= F(3) \times F(F(8) - F(3)) + F(8) \\ 8396 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(9) - F(-3 + F(8)) \\ 8738 &:= F(F(8)) - 3^7 - F(8) \\ 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) \\ 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) \\ 8883 &:= (F(F(3)) + 8) \times F(8 + 8) \\ 8906 &:= -60 \times F(9) + F(F(8)) \\ 8972 &:= -2 \times F(7 + 9) + F(F(8)) \\ 9248 &:= F(8)^{F(4)} - F(-2 + 9) \\ 9248 &:= F(8)^{F(4)} - F(-2 + 9) \\ 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) \\ 9586 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8 \times 5 \times F(9) \\ 9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9) \\ 9792 &:= (F(F(2) + 9) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \\ 10912 &:= F(21) - F(9 \times 01) \\ 11125 &:= 5^{2+1} \times F(11) \\ 11264 &:= (4 \times F(6))^2 \times 11 \\ 11664 &:= (F(4) \times 6 \times 6)^{1+1} \\ 11837 &:= 7 \times (-F(3) + F(8)) \times F(11) \\ 11844 &:= F(4) \times 4 \times F(8 \times (1 + 1)) \\ 12238 &:= F(8 \times 3)/2 - F(21) \\ 12537 &:= (-F(7) + F(3 \times 5)) \times 21 \\ 12543 &:= 3 \times F((4 + 5) \times 2 + 1) \\ 12768 &:= (F(8) \times 6 - F(7))^2 - 1 \\ 12769 &:= (9 + F(6) \times F(7))^2 \times 1 \\ 12815 &:= 5 \times (F(18) - 21) \\ 12831 &:= 13 \times F(8 \times 2 \times 1) \\ 12873 &:= 3 + F(7 + 8) \times 21 \\ 12915 &:= 5 \times (-1 + F(9 \times 2 \times 1)) \\ 12925 &:= 5 \times (F(2) + F(9 \times 2)) \times 1 \\ 12935 &:= 5 \times (3 + F(9 \times 2 \times 1)) \\ 12945 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(9 \times 2) + 1) \\ 12965 &:= 5 \times (F(6) + F(9 \times 2) + 1) \\ 13176 &:= 6 \times (F(7)^{1 \times 3})^{-1} \\ 13377 &:= F(7) \times 7^3 \times 3 \times 1 \\ 13689 &:= (9 \times (F(8) - F(6)))^{3-1} \\ 13715 &:= 5 \times ((1 + F(7))^3 - 1) \\ 13798 &:= F(8) \times 9 \times 73 + 1 \\ 14635 &:= -5 + (3 + F(6))^4 - 1 \\ 14636 &:= -6 + (3 + F(6))^4 + 1 \\ 14759 &:= (9^5 - F(7))/4 \times 1 \\ 15251 &:= F(15) \times 25 + 1 \\ 15366 &:= 6 \times (F(6)^3 \times 5 + 1) \\ 15488 &:= 8 \times 8 \times (F(4)^5 - 1) \\ 15498 &:= F(8) \times (9 + F(4)^{5+1}) \\ 15544 &:= -F(4)^4 + 5^{5+1} \\ 15563 &:= F(3) \times (6^5 + 5) + 1 \\ 15583 &:= -F(3) \times F(8) + 5^{5+1} \\ 15591 &:= -1 \times F(9) + 5^{5+1} \\ 15623 &:= -F(3) + (-F(2) + 6)^{5+1} \\ 15633 &:= (F(3) + 3)^6 + F(5 + 1) \\ 15676 &:= (-F(6) + F(7))^6 + 51 \\ 15771 &:= F(1 + 7) \times 751 \\ 15792 &:= 2 \times F(9 + 7) \times F(5 + 1) \\ 16382 &:= -2 + (8/F(3))^{6+1} \\ 16418 &:= F(8 + 1) + 4^{6+1} \\ 16419 &:= F(9) + 1 + 4^{6+1} \\ 16724 &:= 4 \times F(2 \times 7 + 6 - 1) \\ 16739 &:= -F(9) \times F(3) + 7^{6-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16752 &:= -F(2 \times 5) + 7^{6-1} & 23197 &:= F(7) + F((9-1) \times 3)/2 \\ 16758 &:= F(8) \times (5 + F(7) \times 61) & 23256 &:= F(6 \times (5-2)) \times 3^2 \\ 16828 &:= F(8) + (-F(2) + 8)^{6-1} & 23264 &:= (F(4)^6 - 2) \times 32 \\ 16926 &:= 62 \times (F(9) \times F(6) + 1) & 23329 &:= ((F(9) + 2)^3 + F(3))/2 \\ 17199 &:= 9 \times 91 \times F(7 + 1) & 23409 &:= (9 + F(04 \times 3))^2 \\ 17253 &:= 3^5 \times F(2) \times 71 & 23478 &:= F(8) \times F(7) \times 43 \times 2 \\ 17339 &:= F(9)^{F(3)} \times (F(3) + F(7)) - 1 & 23718 &:= ((F(8) + 1) \times 7)^{F(3)} + 2 \\ 17456 &:= F(6) \times (-5 + F(4)^7 \times 1) & 23826 &:= 6 \times (2 + (F(8) \times 3)^2) \\ 17484 &:= -4 + 8 \times (F(4)^7 - 1) & 23898 &:= F(8) \times F(9) + F(8 \times 3)/2 \\ 17488 &:= 8 \times (F(8-4)^7 - 1) & 23991 &:= (-1 + F(9)) \times (9^3 - 2) \\ 17576 &:= F(6) \times F(7)^{-5+7+1} & 24126 &:= F(6)^2 \times F(14) - 2 \\ 17647 &:= F(7)^{F(4)} \times F(6) + 71 & 24128 &:= 8^2 \times F(14) \times F(2) \\ 17664 &:= F(4 \times 6) \times F(6)/F(7 + 1) & 24255 &:= 55 \times F(2 \times 4)^2 \\ 17697 &:= F(7 + 9 + 6) - F(7) - 1 & 24326 &:= -F(6) + 23^{F(4)} \times 2 \\ 17712 &:= F(21 + 7/7) + 1 & 24327 &:= -7 + 23^{F(4)} \times 2 \\ 17725 &:= F(-5 + 27) + F(7) + 1 & 24328 &:= ((F(8) + 2)^3 - F(4)) \times 2 \\ 18482 &:= 2 \times (F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8) + 1) & 24337 &:= F(7)^{F(3)} \times F(3 \times 4) + F(2) \\ 18592 &:= (-2 + F(9)) \times 581 & 24339 &:= (F(9)^{F(3)} + 3) \times F(4 \times 2) \\ 18873 &:= F(3 \times 7 - 8) \times 81 & 24368 &:= (F(8) + F(6))^3 - F(4 \times 2) \\ 18954 &:= (F(4)^5 - 9) \times 81 & 24386 &:= (F(6) + F(8))^3 - 4 + F(2) \\ 19355 &:= 553 \times (F(9) + 1) & 24387 &:= (F(7) + 8 \times F(3))^{F(4)} - 2 \\ 19656 &:= 6^{-5+F(6)} \times 91 & 24388 &:= (8 + F(8))^3 - F(4 - 2) \\ 19745 &:= 5 \times (4 \times F(7 + 9) + 1) & 24389 &:= (F(9) - 8 + 3)^{F(4)} \times F(2) \\ 19873 &:= (3^7 + F(8)) \times 9 + 1 & 24392 &:= (29^3 + F(4)) \times F(2) \\ 19893 &:= 3^9 + F(8) \times (9 + 1) & 24395 &:= (-5 + F(9))^3 + 4 + 2 \\ 20193 &:= 3 \times (-F(9) + F(10 \times 2)) & 24546 &:= (F(6)^4 - 5) \times (4 + 2) \\ 20273 &:= 3 \times (-7 + F(20)) - F(2) & 24576 &:= 6 \times (F(7) - 5)^4 \times F(2) \\ 20295 &:= F(-5 + 9) \times F(20) \times F(2) & 24675 &:= 5 \times (F(7) - F(6)) \times F(4^2) \\ 20296 &:= (-6 + 9) \times F(20) + F(2) & 24964 &:= (F(4) \times 6 \times 9 - 4)^2 \\ 20485 &:= 5 \times (8^4 + F(02)) & 24997 &:= 7 \times (F(9 + 9) + F(4^2)) \\ 20886 &:= 6 \times (-F(8) + 80)^2 & 25376 &:= F(6) \times F(7) \times (3^5 + F(2)) \\ 20915 &:= 5 \times (F(19) + 02) & 25532 &:= (F(23) - 5^5) \times F(2) \\ 21892 &:= F(29 - 8) \times 1 \times 2 & 25662 &:= 26 \times F(6 + 5 \times 2) \\ 21912 &:= (F(21) + 9 + 1) \times 2 & 25921 &:= (1 + (-2 + F(9)) \times 5)^2 \\ 22799 &:= (F(9) + 9 \times F(7))^2 - 2 & 26376 &:= (6 + F(7))^3 \times 6 \times 2 \\ 23176 &:= -F(6) + F((7 + 1) \times 3)/2 & 26377 &:= F(7) + F(7)^3 \times 6 \times 2 \\ 23177 &:= -7 + F((7 + 1) \times 3)/2 & & \\ 23188 &:= (8 + F(8 \times 1 \times 3))/2 & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26573 &:= F(3 \times 7) + 5^6 + 2 \\ 26637 &:= F(7) \times (F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(6) + F(2)) \\ 26896 &:= (F(6) + (F(9) - 8) \times 6)^2 \\ 26928 &:= (F(8) + F(2)) \times F(9) \times 6^2 \\ 26987 &:= -F(7) + (F(8) + 9)^{6/2} \\ 26998 &:= (F(8) + 9)^{9-6} - 2 \\ 27024 &:= 4 \times (F(20) - 7 - 2) \\ 27147 &:= (F(7) + 4) \times F(17) - 2 \\ 27148 &:= (F(8) - 4) \times F(17) - F(2) \\ 27225 &:= F(5 \times 2)^2 \times (7 + 2) \\ 27345 &:= 5 \times (4 + F(3 \times 7))/2 \\ 27365 &:= 5 \times F((6 - 3) \times 7)/2 \\ 27385 &:= 5 \times (8 + F(3 \times 7))/2 \\ 27468 &:= F(8) \times (6^4 + F(7) - F(2)) \\ 27792 &:= (2 + F(9)) \times 772 \\ 27847 &:= F(7)^4 - F(8) \times F(7 + 2) \\ 27848 &:= 8 \times (F(4) + 8 \times 7)^2 \\ 28237 &:= F(7) + (F(3 \times 2) \times F(8))^2 \\ 28288 &:= (8 \times F(8))^2 + 8^2 \\ 28376 &:= F(6) \times (F(7)^{F(3)} \times F(8) - 2) \\ 28431 &:= 13 \times F(4)^{8-F(2)} \\ 28446 &:= (6^4 - F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(2)) \\ 28532 &:= F(23) - 5^{F(8/2)} \\ 28544 &:= 4^{F(4)} \times (5 + F(8)^2) \\ 28561 &:= 1 \times (F(6) + 5)^{8/2} \\ 28632 &:= F(23) - 6 - F(8) + 2 \\ 28671 &:= -1 + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\ 28672 &:= F(2) \times 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\ 28732 &:= F(23) - 7 + 82 \\ 28746 &:= 6 \times F(4) \times F(7 + 8 + 2) \\ 28794 &:= F(4 + 9) + F(7)^{8/2} \\ 29177 &:= 7 \times (-F(7) + F(19)) + F(2) \\ 29197 &:= 7 \times (-9 + F(19) - F(2)) \\ 29241 &:= (1 + (F(4) + 2) \times F(9))^2 \\ 29529 &:= ((9 \times F(2))^5 + 9)/2 \\ 29813 &:= F(31 - 8) + F(9)^2 \\ 29989 &:= 98 \times F(9) \times 9 + F(2) \\ 30976 &:= (F(6) \times (F(7) + 9))^{F(03)} \\ 31329 &:= (F(9 + 2) \times F(3) - 1)^{F(3)} \\ 32158 &:= 8^5 - F(12 + 3) \\ 32677 &:= -7 \times F(7) + F(6)^{2+3} \\ 32684 &:= -4 \times F(8) + F(6)^{2+3} \\ 32746 &:= F(6)^4 - 7 + F(23) \\ 32753 &:= F(3)^{5+7} + F(23) \\ 32756 &:= F(6)^5 - 7 - 2 - 3 \\ 32759 &:= -9 + (-5 + F(7))^{2+3} \\ 32762 &:= 2^{F(6)+7} - 2 \times 3 \\ 32763 &:= -3 + F(6)^{7-2} - F(3) \\ 32764 &:= ((-4 + F(6))^7 - 2) \times F(3) \\ 32765 &:= -5 + F(6)^{7-2} + F(3) \\ 32766 &:= F(6)^{-6+F(7)-2} - F(3) \\ 32839 &:= F(9) + 3^8 \times (2 + 3) \\ 32845 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^8 + 2^3) \\ 33282 &:= (2^8 + 2)^{F(3)} / F(3) \\ 33327 &:= 7 \times (23 \times 3)^{F(3)} \\ 33448 &:= 8 \times F(4 + 4 \times 3 + 3) \\ 33489 &:= (9 \times F(8) - 4 - F(3))^{F(3)} \\ 33578 &:= (-F(8) + 7^5 + 3) \times F(3) \\ 33617 &:= 7^{-1+6} \times F(3) + 3 \\ 33631 &:= 13 \times (F(6 \times 3) + 3) \\ 33696 &:= (-F(6) + F(9)) \times 6^{F(3) \times F(3)} \\ 33785 &:= 5 \times (-8 + F(-7 + 3^3)) \\ 33856 &:= (F(6) \times (5 + F(8) - 3))^{F(3)} \\ 34188 &:= F(8) \times 814 \times F(3) \\ 34285 &:= 5 \times ((F(8) - 2)^{F(4)} - F(3)) \\ 34475 &:= 5 \times 7 \times (F(4 \times 4) - F(3)) \\ 34545 &:= 5 \times (F(4 \times 5) + F(4 \times 3)) \\ 34596 &:= (6 + 9 \times 5 \times 4)^{F(3)} \\ 34848 &:= 8 \times (F(4) \times F(8) + F(4))^{F(3)} \\ 34968 &:= 8 \times (6 \times 9^{F(4)} - 3) \\ 36284 &:= -4 + F(8) \times (2 \times 6)^3 \\ 36481 &:= (-1 + 8 \times 4 \times 6)^{F(3)} \\ 36483 &:= ((F(3) + F(8))^{F(4)} - 6) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$36992 := (-2 + F(9)) \times F(9) \times F(6 + 3)$$

$$36994 := 4 \times F(9) \times F(9) \times F(6) + F(3)$$

$$37044 := 4 \times (F(4) \times 07)^3$$

$$37349 := (9 + 4 \times F(3)) \times F(7)^3$$

$$37368 := -8 + F(6)^3 \times 73$$

$$37376 := F(6)^{F(7-3)} \times 73$$

$$37516 := (F((6 - 1) \times 5) + 7) / F(3)$$

$$37629 := 9 \times F((2^6 - 7) / 3)$$

$$37835 := 5 \times (-F(3) + 87^{F(3)})$$

$$37885 := 5 \times (8 + 87^{F(3)})$$

$$37947 := F(7) \times F(4) \times 973$$

$$38413 := -3 + 14^{8/F(3)}$$

$$38416 := (6 + 1)^4 \times 8 \times F(3)$$

$$38493 := 39 \times F(48/3)$$

$$38565 := 5 \times (6^5 - F(8) \times 3)$$

$$38784 := (-4 + F(8 + 7)) \times 8^{F(3)}$$

$$38792 := -2^9 + (F(7) + F(8))^3$$

$$38808 := (80 + 8) \times F(8)^{F(3)}$$

$$38809 := (9 \times F(08) + 8)^{F(3)}$$

$$39064 := -4 \times 60 + F(9)^3$$

$$39139 := F(9)^3 - F(1 + 9) \times 3$$

$$39178 := -F(8) \times (7 - 1) + F(9)^3$$

$$39187 := -F(7) \times (8 + 1) + F(9)^3$$

$$39189 := -F(9) - 81 + F(9)^3$$

$$39223 := -3^{2 \times 2} + F(9)^3$$

$$39236 := -F(6 + 3) \times 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39238 := -8^{F(3)} - 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39249 := -F((9 - 4) \times 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39251 := -1 - 52 + F(9)^3$$

$$39252 := -F(2) \times 52 + F(9)^3$$

$$39256 := F(6) \times (-5 - F(2)) + F(9)^3$$

$$39258 := -F(8) - 5^2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39259 := -9 \times 5 + (F(2) \times F(9))^3$$

$$39262 := -2 \times F(6 + 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39264 := (F(4)^{F(6)} \times 2 - F(9)) \times 3$$

$$39265 := -5 \times F(6) + F(2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39266 := -6 \times 6 - 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39281 := -1 - F(8) - F(2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39282 := -2 - F(8) + F(2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39283 := -F(3) \times F(8) / 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39286 := -6 \times F(8/2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39287 := -7 - 8 - 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39288 := -8 - 8 + (F(2) \times F(9))^3$$

$$39289 := -9 - 8 + 2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39291 := -1 \times F(9 - 2) + F(9)^3$$

$$39295 := -F(-5 + 9)^2 + F(9)^3$$

$$39297 := -7 + (F(9) \times F(2))^{9/3}$$

$$39301 := 1 \times 0 - 3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39305 := F(5 - 03) + F(9)^3$$

$$39308 := 8 / F(03) + F(9)^3$$

$$39312 := (2 \times 1)^3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39313 := (3 \times 1) \times 3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39314 := (4 + 1) \times F(3) + F(9)^3$$

$$39317 := F(7) + F(1^3 \times 9)^3$$

$$39318 := (8 - 1) \times F(3) + F(9)^3$$

$$39322 := (-22 + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$39324 := -42 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$39325 := (5 + 2) \times 3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39329 := -F(9) + 2 \times 3^9 - 3$$

$$39331 := 1 \times 3^3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39337 := (F(7) - F(3)) \times 3 + F(9)^3$$

$$39338 := F(8 + 3/3) + F(9)^3$$

$$39339 := F(9)^3 - F(3) + F(9) + 3$$

$$39342 := -24 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$39343 := 3 \times F(4 + 3) + F(9)^3$$

$$39344 := -F(4) + 43 + F(9)^3$$

$$39346 := -6 - 4 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$39347 := -F(7) + (-F(4) + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$39349 := -9 + (-4 + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$39351 := -15 + 3^9 \times F(3)$$

$$39352 := (-2 - 5 + 3^9) \times F(3)$$

$$39353 := F(3) \times (-5 + 3^9) - 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39354 &:= -F(4) + 53 + F(9)^3 \\ 39358 &:= -8 + (5 - F(3))^9 \times F(3) \\ 39359 &:= F(9) + F(5 + 3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39372 &:= 2 \times (F(7 - 3))^9 + 3 \\ 39375 &:= -5 + (7 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\ 39376 &:= F(6) \times (7 + F(3)) + F(9)^3 \\ 39381 &:= -1 + (8 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\ 39388 &:= (F(8) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(9)^3 \\ 39392 &:= (F(-2 + 9) + 3^9) \times F(3) \\ 39408 &:= (F(8) + F(04)^9) \times F(3) \\ 39416 &:= F(6) \times 14 + F(9)^3 \\ 39432 &:= 2^{3+4} + F(9)^3 \\ 39439 &:= -9 + F(3 \times 4) + F(9)^3 \\ 39468 &:= F(8) \times F(6) - 4 + F(9)^3 \\ 39475 &:= 57 \times F(4) + F(9)^3 \\ 39477 &:= F(7) \times F(7) + 4 + F(9)^3 \\ 39478 &:= (8 \times 7 + F(4)^9) \times F(3) \\ 39489 &:= 9 \times F(8) - 4 + F(9)^3 \\ 39492 &:= 2 \times 94 + F(9)^3 \\ 39504 &:= 40 \times 5 + F(9)^3 \\ 39524 &:= 4 \times F(2 \times 5) + F(9)^3 \\ 39529 &:= 9 \times 25 + F(9)^3 \\ 39544 &:= -F(4) + F(4)^5 + F(9)^3 \\ 39547 &:= (7 - 4)^5 + F(9)^3 \\ 39564 &:= 4 \times 65 + F(9)^3 \\ 39598 &:= F(8) \times (9 + 5) + F(9)^3 \\ 39647 &:= 7^{-F(4)+6} + F(9)^3 \\ 39655 &:= 55 \times (-F(6) + 9^3) \\ 39681 &:= F(1 \times 8 + 6) + F(9)^3 \\ 39688 &:= 8 \times 8 \times 6 + F(9)^3 \\ 39733 &:= 33 \times F(7) + F(9)^3 \\ 39738 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} - 7 + F(9)^3 \\ 39749 &:= F(9)^{F(4)} + F(7) \times F(9) + 3 \\ 39766 &:= 66 \times 7 + F(9)^3 \\ 39914 &:= F(-4 + 19) + F(9)^3 \\ 39927 &:= 7 \times F(2 + 9) + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39936 &:= F(6)^3 \times (9 \times 9 - 3) \\ 39987 &:= -F(7) + (8 \times (F(9) - 9))^{F(3)} \\ 39997 &:= 7 \times 99 + F(9)^3 \\ 40698 &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times (60 - F(4)) \\ 42272 &:= -2^{F(7)} / 2 + F(24) \\ 42588 &:= F(8) \times (F(8) + 5)^2 \times F(4) \\ 42845 &:= F(5 \times 4) \times (F(8) - 2) / F(4) \\ 42873 &:= -F(3) + (F(7) + F(8) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\ 42875 &:= (5 \times 7)^{F(8 \times 2 / 4)} \\ 42909 &:= F(9) + (F(09) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\ 42938 &:= F(8) \times 3 + (F(9) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\ 43267 &:= (F(7) \times F(6) \times 2)^{F(3)} + F(4) \\ 43276 &:= ((F(6) \times F(7))^2 + 3) \times 4 \\ 43688 &:= (-8 + 8^6 / F(3)) / F(4) \\ 43752 &:= -2^5 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\ 43772 &:= (F(2 \times 7 + 7) - 3) \times 4 \\ 43797 &:= F(7) + F(9 \times 7 / 3) \times 4 \\ 43812 &:= (F(21) + F(8) / 3) \times 4 \\ 43912 &:= (F(21) + F(9) - F(3)) \times 4 \\ 44771 &:= -F(17) + F(7 \times 4 - 4) \\ 45738 &:= F(8) \times (3^7 - 5 - 4) \\ 45753 &:= F(3 \times 5) \times 75 + F(4) \\ 45873 &:= 3^7 \times F(8) - 54 \\ 45991 &:= F(19) \times (-9 + 5 \times 4) \\ 46048 &:= -8 \times 40 + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46137 &:= F(7)^3 \times (1 + 6) \times F(4) \\ 46152 &:= F(25 - 1) - 6^{F(4)} \\ 46216 &:= -F(6) - F(12) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46217 &:= -7 - F(12) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46245 &:= -5^{F(4)} + 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46247 &:= -(7 + 4)^2 + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46265 &:= 5 \times (-F(6) + F(2 + 6))^{F(4)} \\ 46274 &:= -47 \times 2 + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46304 &:= -4^{03} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46306 &:= -60 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46315 &:= -51 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46319 &:= 91 \times (-3 + F(6))^{F(4)} \\ 46322 &:= -2 \times 23 + F(6 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$46349 := -(F(9) + 4)/F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46351 := -15 - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46361 := -1 - F(6) + F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46362 := 2 \times (-6 + 3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46363 := -3 - 6/3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46364 := F(4 \times 6) - 3 + F(6 - 4)$$

$$46365 := (5 - 6) \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46366 := F(6 + 6 \times 3) - 6 + 4$$

$$46367 := -(7 - 6)^3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46368 := F(8 \times 6/3 \times 6/4)$$

$$46369 := (9 - 6)/3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46379 := (9 + F(7))/F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46415 := 51 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46417 := 7^{-1+F(4)} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46422 := -F(2) + F(24) + F(6 + 4)$$

$$46426 := 62 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46437 := 73 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46459 := 95 - 4 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46537 := F(7)^{-3+5} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46563 := 3 \times 65 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46601 := -F(10) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46614 := 41 \times 6 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46622 := -2 + 2^{F(6)} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46635 := -5^{F(3)} + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46639 := -F(9)/F(3) + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46649 := -9/F(4) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46652 := F(2)^5 \times (6^6 - 4)$$

$$46655 := -5/5 + (6 \times 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$46662 := 2 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46665 := 5 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46666 := F(6) + 6^6 + 6 - 4$$

$$46667 := F(7) + 6^6 - 6 + 4$$

$$46668 := 8 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46669 := 9 + F(6) + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46681 := F(1 \times 8) + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46682 := F(2) + F(8) + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46683 := F(3) + F(8) + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46685 := 5 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46686 := 6 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46687 := F(7) + F(8) + 6^6 - F(4)$$

$$46688 := F(8) + 8 + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46689 := 9 + F(8) + 6^6 + F(4)$$

$$46872 := (-F(2) + (F(7) - 8)^6) \times F(4)$$

$$46873 := -F(3) + (F(7) - 8)^6 \times F(4)$$

$$46875 := 5^{(-7+8) \times 6} \times F(4)$$

$$46926 := 62 \times 9 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46978 := F(8 + 7) + F(96/4)$$

$$47327 := 7 \times (F(2 \times (3 + 7))) - 4$$

$$47372 := (F(2 \times 7)^{F(3)} - F(7))/F(4)$$

$$47628 := F(8)^2 \times (F(6) \times F(7) + 4)$$

$$47664 := F(4 \times 6) + 6^{7-F(4)}$$

$$47736 := 6^3 \times F(7) \times (F(7) + 4)$$

$$47796 := 6 \times (-F(9) + (F(7) + 7)^{F(4)})$$

$$48384 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84$$

$$49254 := (4^{5+2} + F(9)) \times F(4)$$

$$51764 := F(4)^6 \times 71 + 5$$

$$52448 := 8 \times (F(4)^{4 \times 2} - 5)$$

$$52493 := (F(3) \times 9)^4/2 + 5$$

$$52496 := F(6) \times (9^4 + F(2)^5)$$

$$53133 := 3 \times F((3 \times 1)^3 - 5)$$

$$53227 := -F(7) + 22^3 \times 5$$

$$53482 := -F(28) + F(4 + 3)^5$$

$$53946 := 6 \times (F(4) + F(9)) \times 3^5$$

$$54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))$$

$$54168 := 8 \times (6 + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))$$

$$54176 := F(6) \times (7 + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))$$

$$54216 := F(6) \times (12 + F(4 \times 5))$$

$$54248 := 8 \times (4^2 + F(4 \times 5))$$

$$54288 := 8 \times (F(8) \times F(2) + F(4 \times 5))$$

$$54289 := F(9 + 8/2)^{-F(4)+5}$$

$$54294 := F(4 + 9)^{-2+4} + 5$$

$$54717 := -F(7) + F(17 + 4) \times 5$$

$$54735 := (5 + F(3 \times 7) - 4) \times 5$$

$$54849 := 9^{F(4)} + 8 \times F(4 \times 5)$$

$$54925 := (5 \times F(-2 + 9))^{F(4)}/5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57267 &:= 7 \times (-6 + 2^{F(7)} - 5) & 62976 &:= (F(6) + 7 \times F(9)) \times 2^{F(6)} \\ 57322 &:= 2 \times F(23) + F(7) - 5 & 63368 &:= (86 + 3)^{F(3)} \times F(6) \\ 57323 &:= F(3) \times (F(23) + 7) - 5 & 63392 &:= (F(2 + 9)^{F(3)} + 3) \times F(6) \\ 57326 &:= (6 + F(23)) \times (7 - 5) & 63498 &:= (F(8) \times (9 + F(4)))^{F(3)} - 6 \\ 57327 &:= F(7) + F(23) \times (7 - 5) & 63744 &:= (4^4 - 7) \times F(3)^{F(6)} \\ 57332 &:= F(23) \times F(3) + F(7) + 5 & 63888 &:= (F(8) + 8/8)^3 \times 6 \\ 57339 &:= (9 - F(3)) \times F(3)^{F(7)} - 5 & 64024 &:= (F(4) + 20^{F(4)}) \times F(6) \\ 58944 &:= F(4) \times (F(4)^9) - F(8) \times 5 & 64384 &:= 4^8 - F(3 \times 4) \times F(6) \\ 58964 &:= F(4)^{F(6)} \times 9 - 85 & 64488 &:= (F(8) \times 8^{F(4)} - 4) \times 6 \\ 59018 &:= -F(8) - 10 + 9^5 & 64539 &:= 9 \times (F(3 \times 5) + F(4)^{F(6)}) \\ 59028 &:= -F(8) + 2 \times 0 + 9^5 & 64544 &:= -F(4 \times 4) - 5 + 4^{F(6)} \\ 59034 &:= F(4) \times (3^{09} - 5) & 64812 &:= (F(21) - F(8 + 4)) \times 6 \\ 59043 &:= -3 - F(4) + 09^5 & 64824 &:= -F(4) + 2 \times F(8)^4/6 \\ 59044 &:= F(4) \times F(4)^{09} - 5 & 64826 &:= (-6 + 2 \times F(8)^4)/6 \\ 59046 &:= -6 + F(4) + 09^5 & 64827 &:= 7 \times (2 \times F(8))^{F(4)}/F(6) \\ 59047 &:= -F(7 - 4) + 09^5 & 64835 &:= (5 + F(3)) \times F(8)^{F(4)} + F(6) \\ 59048 &:= -F(8/4) + 09^5 & 64864 &:= 4^{F(6)} - 84 \times F(6) \\ 59138 &:= F(8 + 3) + 1 \times 9^5 & 64881 &:= (1 + 88) \times F(4)^6 \\ 59193 &:= F(3 + 9) + 1 \times 9^5 & 64935 &:= -F(5 \times 3) + 9 + 4^{F(6)} \\ 59218 &:= F(8 - 1)^2 + 9^5 & 64945 &:= -5^4 + F(9) + 4^{F(6)} \\ 59238 &:= F(8) \times 3^2 + 9^5 & 65159 &:= -F(9 + 5) + (-1 + 5)^{F(6)} \\ 59389 &:= F(9) \times (8 + F(3)) + 9^5 & 65464 &:= 4^{F(6)} - (4 + 5) \times F(6) \\ 59415 &:= 51 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5 & 65472 &:= (2^{F(7)} - F(4) - 5) \times F(6) \\ 59418 &:= -8 + F(14) + 9^5 & 65542 &:= 2 \times (F(4) + 5)^5 + 6 \\ 59426 &:= F(6 + 2 \times 4) + 9^5 & 65544 &:= 4^{F(-4+5+5)} + F(6) \\ 59432 &:= 23 \times F(4 + 9 + 5) & 65562 &:= 2 \times (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(6)) \\ 59617 &:= 71 \times F(6) + 9^5 & 65625 &:= (5 - F(2))^{F(6)} + F(5 + 6) \\ 59647 &:= F(7) \times 46 + 9^5 & 65628 &:= (-8 + F(26 - 5)) \times 6 \\ 59651 &:= F(15) - F(6) + 9^5 & 66912 &:= 2 \times (F(19) \times F(6) + F(6)) \\ 59653 &:= F(3 \times 5) - 6 + 9^5 & 67398 &:= (8 \times 9)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 6 \\ 59659 &:= 9^5 + F((-6 + 9) \times 5) & 68894 &:= (F(4)^9 \times F(8) + F(8))/6 \\ 59725 &:= 52 \times F(7) + 9^5 & 69631 &:= -1 + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\ 59764 &:= F(4 + 6) \times F(7) + 9^5 & 69632 &:= (F(2) \times F(3))^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\ 61029 &:= 9 \times (F(20) + 16) & 69956 &:= 6^5 \times 9 - F(9) + 6 \\ 62214 &:= F(4) \times F(12)^2 + 6 & 71564 &:= -F(4)^{F(6)} + (5 \times 1)^7 \\ 62426 &:= (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26 & 72384 &:= F(4) \times 8^{F(3)} \times F(2 \times 7) \\ 62584 &:= 4 \times (F(8) + (5 \times F(2))^6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 72893 &:= -F(3) + (F(9) \times 8)^2 + 7 \\
 72999 &:= 9 \times (-9 \times 9 + 2^{F(7)}) \\
 73539 &:= -9 \times (F(3+5) - F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73674 &:= (-4 + F(7)) \times (-6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73719 &:= 9 \times (-1^7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73724 &:= -4 + 2^{F(7)} \times (F(3) + 7) \\
 73728 &:= (8 \times 2 - 7) \times F(3)^{F(7)} \\
 73736 &:= F(6) + F(3)^{F(7)} \times (F(3) + 7) \\
 73791 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (7 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \\
 73971 &:= ((1 + 7) \times F(9))^{F(3)} - F(7) \\
 73984 &:= (-4 + F(8)) \times F(9) \times F(3)^7 \\
 73991 &:= ((-1 + 9) \times F(9))^{F(3)} + 7 \\
 73997 &:= (7 \times F(9) + F(9))^{F(3)} + F(7) \\
 74088 &:= (F(8) + F(8))^{-04+7} \\
 74358 &:= F((8 - 5) \times 3) \times F(4)^7 \\
 74366 &:= F(6) + F(6 + 3) \times F(4)^7 \\
 74492 &:= -2 + F(9) \times (4 + F(4)^7) \\
 74719 &:= F(9) \times (1 + F(7)^{F(4)}) - F(7) \\
 75023 &:= -F(3) + F(2^{05} - 7) \\
 75031 &:= -1 + F(30 - 5) + 7 \\
 75034 &:= -4 + F(30 - 5) + F(7) \\
 75059 &:= F(9) + F(5^{-05+7}) \\
 75258 &:= F(8 + 5) + F(2^5 - 7) \\
 75536 &:= -F(6 \times 3) - 5 + 5^7 \\
 75937 &:= -F(7)^3 + 9 + 5^7 \\
 75983 &:= -3 \times F(8) \times F(9) + 5^7 \\
 76648 &:= 8 \times (F(4)^6 + F(6)) \times F(7) \\
 77748 &:= (8 - F(4))^7 - F(7 + 7) \\
 77756 &:= F(6) + 5^7 - F(7 + 7) \\
 78123 &:= -F(3) + (-2 - 1 + 8)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78138 &:= (8 - 3)^{-1+8} + F(7) \\
 78159 &:= F(9) + 5^{1^8 \times 7} \\
 78358 &:= F(8 + 5) + (-3 + 8)^7 \\
 78399 &:= 9 \times (F(9) \times F(3)^8 + 7) \\
 79492 &:= 2 \times (F(9)^{F(4)} + F(9) \times F(7)) \\
 79929 &:= 9 \times (-2 + 9 \times F(9 + 7)) \\
 82824 &:= 4 \times (-F(2) + F(8 \times 2)) \times F(8) \\
 82923 &:= (32 \times 9)^2 - F(8) \\
 83478 &:= -8 + F(7)^{F(4)} \times 38 \\
 83486 &:= (-F(6) + F(8))^{F(4)} \times 38 \\
 83498 &:= (8 + 9)^4 - F(3) - F(8) \\
 85293 &:= 3^{9-F(2)} \times (5 + 8) \\
 86016 &:= (F(6)^{10-6}) \times F(8) \\
 86688 &:= F(8) \times 86 \times 6 \times 8 \\
 87455 &:= -5 \times (5 - F(4)^7) \times 8 \\
 88809 &:= 90 \times F(8 + 8) - F(8) \\
 89355 &:= (5 + 5^3 \times F(9)) \times F(8) \\
 89488 &:= F(8 + 8) / F(4) \times F(9) \times 8 \\
 91976 &:= -6 + (F(7) + 9) \times F(19) \\
 92991 &:= (-1 + 9 \times F(9))^2 - F(9) \\
 93296 &:= F(6) \times (9 - 2)^3 \times F(9) \\
 94928 &:= (82 \times F(9) + 4) \times F(9) \\
 97655 &:= (-5 + 5^{F(6)}) / (F(7) - 9) \\
 97824 &:= 4 \times (F(28) / F(7) + 9) \\
 98183 &:= 38 \times F(18) - 9 \\
 98239 &:= F(9 \times 3) / 2 + F(8) + 9 \\
 98245 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^{F(2)+8} - F(9)) \\
 98425 &:= 5 \times (2 + F(-4 + 8))^9 \\
 99688 &:= (8 + 86 \times F(9)) \times F(9) \\
 99945 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^9 + 9 \times F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

5.3.2 With Factorial

$$\begin{aligned}
 256 &:= (F(6) + 5!) \times 2 \\
 344 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 43 \\
 472 &:= 2 \times F(F(7)) + F(4)! \\
 497 &:= (-7! + 9!) / F(4)!! \\
 639 &:= -9^{F(3)} + 6! \\
 736 &:= 6! + 3 + F(7) \\
 1364 &:= (F(4!) + F(6)) / F(F(3)!) + 1 \\
 1365 &:= 5 \times F(F(6)) \times F(3! + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1368 &:= (F(F(8)) + 6)/F(3!) - 1 \\ 1429 &:= -9 + 2 \times (F(4)!! - 1) \\ 1432 &:= 2 \times 3!! - F((4 - 1)!) \\ 1542 &:= 2 \times (F(4)!! + 51) \\ 1593 &:= F(F(3!) + 9) - 5 + 1 \\ 1597 &:= F(-7 + (9 - 5)! \times 1) \\ 1646 &:= F(6)!/4! - F(F(6) + 1) \\ 1673 &:= (3! + F(F(7))) \times (6 + 1) \\ 2091 &:= (F(19) + 0!)/2 \\ 2205 &:= 5 \times F(F((0! + 2)!))^2 \\ 2287 &:= -F(F(7)) + (8 - F(2))!/2 \\ 2401 &:= (F(10) - F(4)!)^2 \\ 2447 &:= (7! + F(4!))/F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2) \\ 2457 &:= (7! - 5! - F(4)!)/2 \\ 2484 &:= F(4)!! + (F(8) \times F(F(4)))^2 \\ 2576 &:= (-F(6) + 7! + 5!)/2 \\ 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F((5 - 2)!) \\ 2597 &:= (7! + F(9) + 5!)/2 \\ 2643 &:= -3 + F(4)! \times F(F(6))^2 \\ 2645 &:= (5! + F(4)!) \times F(F(6)) - F(2) \\ 2664 &:= (F(4!) - 6! - F(6)!)/2 \\ 2743 &:= (F(F(F(3!)))/F(F(4)) + F(7))/2 \\ 2744 &:= 4 \times (F(4)!! - F(7 + 2)) \\ 2754 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5! + F(F(7)) + F(2) \\ 2774 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(7)) + 7!/2 \\ 2848 &:= (-8 + F(4)!!) \times 8/2 \\ 2867 &:= -F(7) + 6! \times 8/2 \\ 2884 &:= (F(4)!! \times 8 + 8)/2 \\ 2896 &:= 6! + F(9) \times 8^2 \\ 2905 &:= -5! + F(0! + 9)^2 \\ 2954 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-5! + F(F(9)/2)) \\ 2966 &:= F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(6))!)/(9 \times 2)! \\ 3136 &:= (F(6) \times (3! + 1))^{F(3)} \\ 3215 &:= (5! - 1)^2 - F(F(F(3!))) \\ 3239 &:= (9 \times 3!! - 2)/F(3) \\ 3327 &:= F(7) \times 2^{F(3!)} - F(F(3)) \\ 3345 &:= 5^{F(4)} \times F(F(3!)) + 3!! \\ 3348 &:= (8!/4! - 3!) \times F(3) \\ 3416 &:= 61 \times F(F(4)!)/3!! \\ 3459 &:= 9!/(5 \times F(F(F(4)!))) + 3 \\ 3478 &:= -F(F(8))/F(7) + F(4)! \times 3!! \\ 3493 &:= F(3)!/9 - F(4^{F(3)}) \\ 3584 &:= 4 \times (-8 + 5!) \times F(3!) \\ 3639 &:= F(9 + 3!) \times 6 - F(F(3!)) \\ 3641 &:= (1 - 4! + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3642 &:= (F(2) - F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\ 3645 &:= 5 \times F(4)^{(6-3)!} \\ 3728 &:= 8 \times 2 \times F(7 + 3!) \\ 3736 &:= -6! + F(3)^{F(7)}/F(3) \\ 3755 &:= 5^5 + 7!/F(3!) \\ 3757 &:= F(7) \times 5! + F(7)^3 \\ 3765 &:= (-5! + 6 \times 7!)/F(3!) \\ 3774 &:= F(4)! \times (-7 \times F(7) + 3!!) \\ 3784 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(8) + F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\ 3786 &:= (F(F(6)) + F(8 + 7)) \times 3! \\ 3794 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + 9 + F(7)^3 \\ 3864 &:= F(4)!/((-6 + 8) \times 3!) \\ 3886 &:= (6! - 8 + F(F(8)))/3 \\ 3928 &:= (-F(8) + 2^9) \times F(3!) \\ 3944 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 493 \\ 4072 &:= 2^{F(7)-0!} - 4! \\ 4134 &:= (F(4)!! - 31) \times F(4)! \\ 4224 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 22 \times 4! \\ 4248 &:= 8 \times F(F(F(4)!))^2 + F(4)!! \\ 4317 &:= (7 - 1)! \times 3! - F(4) \\ 4344 &:= (4 + (F(4) \times F(3)!)) \times F(4)! \\ 4345 &:= 5^{F(F(4))} + 3!! \times F(4)! \\ 4363 &:= -F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(6)) \times 3^{F(4)!} \\ 4396 &:= F(6)!/9 - F(F(3!)) \times 4 \\ 4433 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(-F(3) + 4!))/4 \\ 4445 &:= 5^{F(4)} + F(4)! \times F(4)!! \\ 4452 &:= (F(F(2 + 5)) - F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ 4456 &:= F(6)!/(5 + 4) - 4! \\ 4478 &:= 8!/(F(7) - 4) - F(F(4)) \\ 4594 &:= F(F(4)!)/9 + 5! - F(4)! \\ 4598 &:= 8!/9 + 5! - F(F(4)) \\ 4608 &:= (8 + 0!) \times F(6)^{F(4)} \\ 4657 &:= F(F(7)) \times 5!/6 - F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4658 &:= -F(F(8)) + 5^6 - F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 4675 &:= -5 + F(7) \times 6! / F(F(4)) \\
 4676 &:= (6! \times F(7) - F(6)) / F(F(4)) \\
 4696 &:= F(6)! / 9 + 6^{F(4)} \\
 4765 &:= 5! \times (6! + F(F(7))) / 4! \\
 4782 &:= -2^8 + 7! - F(F(4)) \\
 4794 &:= (F(4)!! - F(9)) \times 7 - F(F(4)!) \\
 4872 &:= (-F(2) + F(7 + 8)) \times F(F(4)!) \\
 4896 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times (8 - 4)! \\
 4901 &:= F(10 + 9) + F(4)!! \\
 4946 &:= (F(F(6)) / F(4))! - 94 \\
 5064 &:= 4! + (F(6) - (0 \times 5)!)! \\
 5374 &:= -F(F(4)) + 7! + F(3)! / 5! \\
 5395 &:= (5! \times 9 - F(F(3))) \times 5 \\
 5417 &:= 7! + F(-1 + F(4) \times 5) \\
 5439 &:= -F(9) + F(F(F(3)!)) / (-F(4) + 5) \\
 5546 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 45 \times 5! \\
 5672 &:= 2^{F(7)} - F(F(6)) \times 5! \\
 5684 &:= F(4)! / 8 + F(6) - 5! \\
 5774 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) / F(7) \times 7 - 5! \\
 5778 &:= 8! / 7 + F(7) + 5 \\
 5789 &:= F(9) + 8! / 7 - 5 \\
 5794 &:= -F(4)! / 9 + F(F(F(7) - 5)) \\
 5846 &:= -6! + F(4)^8 + 5 \\
 6024 &:= -F(4)!! + F(20) - F(F(6)) \\
 6069 &:= 9! / 60 + F(F(6)) \\
 6253 &:= (F(F(F(3)!)) + 5!) / 2 + 6! \\
 6399 &:= 9 \times (-9 \times F(F(3)) + 6!) \\
 6441 &:= -(1 + 4)! + F(4)^{F(6)} \\
 6445 &:= -5! + 4 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\
 6478 &:= 8! / 7 - F(F(4)) + 6! \\
 6479 &:= (9! / 7 - F(F(4)!)) / F(6) \\
 6525 &:= -5! \times 2 + F(5! / 6) \\
 6549 &:= -9 \times 4! + F(5! / 6) \\
 6595 &:= -5 \times F(9) + F(5! / 6) \\
 6639 &:= -9^{F(3)} + F(6)! / 6 \\
 6669 &:= 9! / F(6)! \times (6! + F(F(6))) \\
 6699 &:= 9! / (9 \times 6) - F(F(6)) \\
 6718 &:= (8! + 1 - F(7)) / 6 \\
 6758 &:= (8! - 5 + F(F(7))) / 6 \\
 6776 &:= F(6) \times (7 + 7! / 6) \\
 6839 &:= (F(9) \times F(F(3!)) + 8!) / 6 \\
 6867 &:= 7 \times F(F(6)) + 8! / 6 \\
 6888 &:= 8 \times F(8) + 8! / 6 \\
 7056 &:= F(6)! / 5! \times F(0! + 7) \\
 7245 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(4)!))^2 + 7! \\
 7324 &:= (F(F(4)!)! + 2 + F(F(F(3!)))) / 7 \\
 7389 &:= 9 \times (-F(8) + F(F(F(3!))) / F(7)) \\
 7448 &:= (-8 + F(F(4)!) \times 4 \times F(F(7))) \\
 7454 &:= F(F(4)!)! / 5 - F(F(F(4)) + F(7)) \\
 7466 &:= -6 - 6! + F(F(4))^{F(7)} \\
 7472 &:= 2^{F(7)} - (-4 + 7)!! \\
 7542 &:= -F(2) + F(4)!^5 - F(F(7)) \\
 7544 &:= F(F(F(4))) + F(4)!^5 - F(F(7)) \\
 7586 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8! / (5 + 7) \\
 7648 &:= 8 \times (F(4) + 6! + F(F(7))) \\
 7656 &:= 6^5 - (-F(6) + F(7))! \\
 7663 &:= F(3!) \times F(F(6) + F(6)) - F(F(7)) \\
 7728 &:= F(8) \times 2^7 + 7! \\
 7734 &:= F(4)! / 3! - 7 + F(7) \\
 7763 &:= 3!^{-F(6)+F(7)} - F(7) \\
 7783 &:= 3!^{-8+F(7)} + 7 \\
 7844 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (F(4)! + 8!) / F(7) \\
 7883 &:= F(3!) \times F(8 + 8) - F(7) \\
 7993 &:= F(F(3)!)! / (9 + 9)! + F(7) \\
 8064 &:= 4 \times F(6)! / (-0! + F(8)) \\
 8405 &:= -(5! + 0!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) \\
 8427 &:= (-7! + 2) / F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) \\
 8447 &:= -7! / F(F(4)) + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) \\
 8616 &:= 6! + F(16) \times 8 \\
 8629 &:= -F(F(9) / 2) - 6! + F(F(8)) \\
 8639 &:= (9! / F(3) - F(F(6))) / F(8) \\
 8849 &:= -9 \times F(-F(F(4)!) + F(8)) + F(F(8)) \\
 8968 &:= (8! + F(6)!) / 9 + 8 \\
 9344 &:= 4!^{F(4)} - F(3)! / 9 \\
 9384 &:= F(4)! / (F(8) \times F(3!)) \times F(9) \\
 9424 &:= F(4)!! + 2^{F(F(4)!) \times F(9)} \\
 9474 &:= -F(4) + F(7) \times (F(4)!! + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9477 := F(7) \times ((7 - 4)!! + 9)$$

$$9488 := 8 \times (8! + 4) / F(9)$$

$$9626 := F(F(F(6))) - (2 \times 6)! / 9!$$

$$9632 := (F((F(2) + 3)!) + F(6)!)/9$$

$$9664 := (F(4)!^6 + F(6)!)/9$$

$$9736 := F(6) \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 7) / 9$$

$$9744 := (F(4!) + F(4!) - 7!) / 9$$

6 Selfie Patterns with Fibonacci Sequence Values

There are numbers that can be extended just multiplying by 10 without loss of properties of numbers. This type we call as *number patterns*. This section deals with numbers patterns in selfie numbers having Fibonacci sequence values. This kind of numbers are only in terms of digit's order.

$$63 := F(F(6)) \times 3$$

$$630 := F(F(6)) \times 30$$

$$6300 := F(F(6)) \times 300$$

$$84 := F(8) \times 4$$

$$840 := F(8) \times 40$$

$$8400 := F(8) \times 400$$

$$168 := 1 \times F(F(6)) \times 8$$

$$1680 := 1 \times F(F(6)) \times 80$$

$$16800 := 1 \times F(F(6)) \times 800$$

$$189 := 1 \times F(8) \times 9$$

$$1890 := 1 \times F(8) \times 90$$

$$18900 := 1 \times F(8) \times 900$$

$$472 := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 2$$

$$4720 := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 20$$

$$47200 := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 200$$

$$882 := F(8) \times F(8) \times 2$$

$$8820 := F(8) \times F(8) \times 20$$

$$88200 := F(8) \times F(8) \times 200$$

$$1165 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 5$$

$$11650 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 50$$

$$116500 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 500$$

$$1175 := (1 + 1 + F(F(7))) \times 5$$

$$11750 := (1 + 1 + F(F(7))) \times 50$$

$$117500 := (1 + 1 + F(F(7))) \times 500$$

$$1365 := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 5$$

$$13650 := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 50$$

$$136500 := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 500$$

$$1525 := F(15) / 2 \times 5$$

$$15250 := F(15) / 2 \times 50$$

$$152500 := F(15) / 2 \times 500$$

$$1645 := F(16) / F(4) \times 5$$

$$16450 := F(16) / F(4) \times 50$$

$$164500 := F(16) / F(4) \times 500$$

$$1687 := (F(F(1 + 6)) + 8) \times 7$$

$$16870 := (F(F(1 + 6)) + 8) \times 70$$

$$168700 := (F(F(1 + 6)) + 8) \times 700$$

$$1785 := F(1 + 7) \times 85$$

$$17850 := F(1 + 7) \times 850$$

$$178500 := F(1 + 7) \times 8500$$

$$1848 := (F(F(-1 + 8)) - F(F(4))) \times 8$$

$$18480 := (F(F(-1 + 8)) - F(F(4))) \times 80$$

$$184800 := (F(F(-1 + 8)) - F(F(4))) \times 800$$

$$1885 := F(1 + F(8) - 8) \times 5$$

$$18850 := F(1 + F(8) - 8) \times 50$$

$$188500 := F(1 + F(8) - 8) \times 500$$

$$1897 := (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 7$$

$$18970 := (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 70$$

$$189700 := (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 700$$

$$1972 := (-1 + F(9 + 7)) \times 2$$

$$19720 := (-1 + F(9 + 7)) \times 20$$

$$197200 := (-1 + F(9 + 7)) \times 200$$

$$1995 := F(-1 + 9) \times 95$$

$$19950 := F(-1 + 9) \times 950$$

$$199500 := F(-1 + 9) \times 9500$$

$$2079 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9$$

$$20790 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 90$$

$$207900 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 900$$

$$2645 := (2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times 5$$

$$26450 := (2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times 50$$

$$264500 := (2 + F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times 500$$

$$2646 := F(2 + 6)^{F(F(4))} \times 6$$

$$26460 := F(2 + 6)^{F(F(4))} \times 60$$

$$264600 := F(2 + 6)^{F(F(4))} \times 600$$

$$2688 := 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 8$$

$$26880 := 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 80$$

$$268800 := 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 800$$

$$2744 := 2 \times 7^{F(4)} \times 4$$

$$27440 := 2 \times 7^{F(4)} \times 40$$

$$274400 := 2 \times 7^{F(4)} \times 400$$

$$3495 := 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5$$

$$34950 := 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 50$$

$$349500 := 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 500$$

$$3528 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8$$

$$35280 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 80$$

$$352800 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 800$$

$$3635 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5$$

$$36350 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 50$$

$$363500 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 500$$

$$3645 := (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 5$$

$$36450 := (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 50$$

$$364500 := (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 500$$

$$3666 := (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + F(F(6)))) \times 6$$

$$36660 := (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + F(F(6)))) \times 60$$

$$366600 := (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + F(F(6)))) \times 600$$

$$3864 := (F(F(3) \times 8) - F(F(6))) \times 4$$

$$38640 := (F(F(3) \times 8) - F(F(6))) \times 40$$

$$386400 := (F(F(3) \times 8) - F(F(6))) \times 400$$

$$4277 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7$$

$$42770 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 70$$

$$427700 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 700$$

$$4455 := F(4)^4 \times 55$$

$$44550 := F(4)^4 \times 550$$

$$445500 := F(4)^4 \times 5500$$

$$4765 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 5$$

$$47650 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 50$$

$$476500 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 500$$

$$4896 := F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 6$$

$$48960 := F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 60$$

$$489600 := F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 600$$

$$4935 := F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 5$$

$$49350 := F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 50$$

$$493500 := F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 500$$

$$5785 := (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 5$$

$$57850 := (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 50$$

$$578500 := (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 500$$

$$5825 := F(5 + 8) \times 25$$

$$58250 := F(5 + 8) \times 250$$

$$582500 := F(5 + 8) \times 2500$$

$$6561 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65610 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \times 10 \\
 656100 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} \times 100 \\
 6728 &:= (F(F(F(6)))/F(7) - F(2)) \times 8 \\
 67280 &:= (F(F(F(6)))/F(7) - F(2)) \times 80 \\
 672800 &:= (F(F(F(6)))/F(7) - F(2)) \times 800 \\
 7448 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8 \\
 74480 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 80 \\
 744800 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 800 \\
 7645 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 5 \\
 76450 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 50 \\
 764500 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 500 \\
 7985 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 5 \\
 79850 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 50 \\
 798500 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 500 \\
 8352 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 2 \\
 83520 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 20 \\
 835200 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 200 \\
 9248 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8 \\
 92480 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 80 \\
 924800 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 800 \\
 10443 &:= (F(10) + 4)^{F(F(4))} \times 3 \\
 104430 &:= (F(10) + 4)^{F(F(4))} \times 30 \\
 1044300 &:= (F(10) + 4)^{F(F(4))} \times 300 \\
 11125 &:= F(11) \times 125 \\
 111250 &:= F(11) \times 1250 \\
 1112500 &:= F(11) \times 12500 \\
 11264 &:= 11 \times 2^{F(6)} \times 4 \\
 112640 &:= 11 \times 2^{F(6)} \times 40 \\
 1126400 &:= 11 \times 2^{F(6)} \times 400 \\
 11466 &:= (F(11) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(6)) \times 6 \\
 114660 &:= (F(11) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(6)) \times 60 \\
 1146600 &:= (F(11) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(6)) \times 600 \\
 11837 &:= F(11) \times (F(8) - F(3)) \times 7 \\
 118370 &:= F(11) \times (F(8) - F(3)) \times 70 \\
 1183700 &:= F(11) \times (F(8) - F(3)) \times 700 \\
 11844 &:= F((1 + 1) \times 8) \times F(4) \times 4 \\
 118440 &:= F((1 + 1) \times 8) \times F(4) \times 40 \\
 1184400 &:= F((1 + 1) \times 8) \times F(4) \times 400 \\
 12264 &:= (F(12) + 2) \times F(F(6)) \times 4 \\
 122640 &:= (F(12) + 2) \times F(F(6)) \times 40 \\
 1226400 &:= (F(12) + 2) \times F(F(6)) \times 400 \\
 12543 &:= F((1 + 2) \times 5 + 4) \times 3 \\
 125430 &:= F((1 + 2) \times 5 + 4) \times 30 \\
 1254300 &:= F((1 + 2) \times 5 + 4) \times 300 \\
 12768 &:= (-1 + F(2 + 7 + F(6))) \times 8 \\
 127680 &:= (-1 + F(2 + 7 + F(6))) \times 80 \\
 1276800 &:= (-1 + F(2 + 7 + F(6))) \times 800 \\
 12915 &:= (-1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times 1 \times 5 \\
 129150 &:= (-1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times 1 \times 50 \\
 1291500 &:= (-1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times 1 \times 500 \\
 12925 &:= (1^2 + F(9 \times 2)) \times 5 \\
 129250 &:= (1^2 + F(9 \times 2)) \times 50 \\
 1292500 &:= (1^2 + F(9 \times 2)) \times 500 \\
 12935 &:= (F(1 \times 2 \times 9) + 3) \times 5 \\
 129350 &:= (F(1 \times 2 \times 9) + 3) \times 50 \\
 1293500 &:= (F(1 \times 2 \times 9) + 3) \times 500 \\
 12945 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + 4) \times 5 \\
 129450 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + 4) \times 50 \\
 1294500 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + 4) \times 500 \\
 12965 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + F(6)) \times 5 \\
 129650 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + F(6)) \times 50 \\
 1296500 &:= (1 + F(2 \times 9) + F(6)) \times 500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13765 &:= (-1 - F(3)^{F(7)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 & 1647900 &:= (-1 - F(6) \times (4 - F(F(7)))) \times 900 \\
 137650 &:= (-1 - F(3)^{F(7)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 50 & 16644 &:= (1 - F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times 4 \\
 1376500 &:= (-1 - F(3)^{F(7)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 500 & 166440 &:= (1 - F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times 40 \\
 13975 &:= (-1 + (3 + 9) \times F(F(7))) \times 5 & 1664400 &:= (1 - F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))) \times 400 \\
 139750 &:= (-1 + (3 + 9) \times F(F(7))) \times 50 & 16722 &:= (-1 + F(6 + F(7)) \times 2) \times 2 \\
 1397500 &:= (-1 + (3 + 9) \times F(F(7))) \times 500 & 167220 &:= (-1 + F(6 + F(7)) \times 2) \times 20 \\
 14637 &:= (1 + F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) / (F(3)) \times 7 & 1672200 &:= (-1 + F(6 + F(7)) \times 2) \times 200 \\
 146370 &:= (1 + F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) / (F(3)) \times 70 & 16724 &:= F(-1 + 6 + 7 \times 2) \times 4 \\
 1463700 &:= (1 + F(-F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))) / (F(3)) \times 700 & 167240 &:= F(-1 + 6 + 7 \times 2) \times 40 \\
 14703 &:= F(14) \times F(7) \times 03 & 1672400 &:= F(-1 + 6 + 7 \times 2) \times 400 \\
 147030 &:= F(14) \times F(7) \times 030 & 16728 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7))) / 2 \times 8 \\
 1470300 &:= F(14) \times F(7) \times 0300 & 167280 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7))) / 2 \times 80 \\
 15225 &:= (F(15) - F(2)) \times 25 & 1672800 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7))) / 2 \times 800 \\
 152250 &:= (F(15) - F(2)) \times 250 & 16744 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7)) + 4) \times 4 \\
 1522500 &:= (F(15) - F(2)) \times 2500 & 167440 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7)) + 4) \times 40 \\
 15325 &:= (F(15) + 3) \times 25 & 1674400 &:= (1 + F(6 + F(7)) + 4) \times 400 \\
 153250 &:= (F(15) + 3) \times 250 & 16749 &:= (F(1 \times 6) \times F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times 9 \\
 1532500 &:= (F(15) + 3) \times 2500 & 167490 &:= (F(1 \times 6) \times F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times 90 \\
 15792 &:= F(1 + 5) \times F(7 + 9) \times 2 & 1674900 &:= (F(1 \times 6) \times F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times 900 \\
 157920 &:= F(1 + 5) \times F(7 + 9) \times 20 & 16935 &:= (F(-1 + F(F(6))) + 9) / F(3) \times 5 \\
 1579200 &:= F(1 + 5) \times F(7 + 9) \times 200 & 169350 &:= (F(-1 + F(F(6))) + 9) / F(3) \times 50 \\
 16372 &:= (-1 \times 6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 2 & 1693500 &:= (F(-1 + F(F(6))) + 9) / F(3) \times 500 \\
 163720 &:= (-1 \times 6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 20 & 17475 &:= F(17 - 4) \times 75 \\
 1637200 &:= (-1 \times 6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times 200 & 174750 &:= F(17 - 4) \times 750 \\
 16413 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(6))) / F(F(4)) - 1) \times 3 & 1747500 &:= F(17 - 4) \times 7500 \\
 164130 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(6))) / F(F(4)) - 1) \times 30 & 17568 &:= (-1 + F(7)^{-5+F(6)}) \times 8 \\
 1641300 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(6))) / F(F(4)) - 1) \times 300 & 175680 &:= (-1 + F(7)^{-5+F(6)}) \times 80 \\
 16464 &:= (-1 + F(F(6)) + 4^6) \times 4 & 1756800 &:= (-1 + F(7)^{-5+F(6)}) \times 800 \\
 164640 &:= (-1 + F(F(6)) + 4^6) \times 40 & 18235 &:= (-1 + (F(F(8)) - 2) / 3) \times 5 \\
 1646400 &:= (-1 + F(F(6)) + 4^6) \times 400 & 182350 &:= (-1 + (F(F(8)) - 2) / 3) \times 50 \\
 16479 &:= (-1 - F(6) \times (4 - F(F(7)))) \times 9 & 1823500 &:= (-1 + (F(F(8)) - 2) / 3) \times 500 \\
 164790 &:= (-1 - F(6) \times (4 - F(F(7)))) \times 90 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18245 &:= (1 + F(F(8)))/(-F(2) + 4) \times 5 \\182450 &:= (1 + F(F(8)))/(-F(2) + 4) \times 50 \\1824500 &:= (1 + F(F(8)))/(-F(2) + 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18277 &:= (F(18) + 27) \times 7 \\182770 &:= (F(18) + 27) \times 70 \\1827700 &:= (F(18) + 27) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18482 &:= (1 + F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 2 \\184820 &:= (1 + F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 20 \\1848200 &:= (1 + F(8)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18522 &:= 1 \times F(8)^{5-2} \times 2 \\185220 &:= 1 \times F(8)^{5-2} \times 20 \\1852200 &:= 1 \times F(8)^{5-2} \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18756 &:= (1 + (-8 + F(7))^5) \times 6 \\187560 &:= (1 + (-8 + F(7))^5) \times 60 \\1875600 &:= (1 + (-8 + F(7))^5) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19552 &:= (-1 + F(9 + 5)) \times 52 \\195520 &:= (-1 + F(9 + 5)) \times 520 \\1955200 &:= (-1 + F(9 + 5)) \times 5200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19735 &:= (F(19) - F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 5 \\197350 &:= (F(19) - F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 50 \\1973500 &:= (F(19) - F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19745 &:= (1 + F(9 + 7) \times 4) \times 5 \\197450 &:= (1 + F(9 + 7) \times 4) \times 50 \\1974500 &:= (1 + F(9 + 7) \times 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19775 &:= (F(19) + 7 - F(F(7))) \times 5 \\197750 &:= (F(19) + 7 - F(F(7))) \times 50 \\1977500 &:= (F(19) + 7 - F(F(7))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19845 &:= F(-1 + 9) \times F(8) \times 45 \\198450 &:= F(-1 + 9) \times F(8) \times 450 \\1984500 &:= F(-1 + 9) \times F(8) \times 4500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19986 &:= (-1 + F(9) \times 98) \times 6 \\199860 &:= (-1 + F(9) \times 98) \times 60\end{aligned}$$

$$1998600 := (-1 + F(9) \times 98) \times 600$$

$$\begin{aligned}20193 &:= (F(20) \times 1 - F(9)) \times 3 \\201930 &:= (F(20) \times 1 - F(9)) \times 30 \\2019300 &:= (F(20) \times 1 - F(9)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20343 &:= (F(20) + F(3)^4) \times 3 \\203430 &:= (F(20) + F(3)^4) \times 30 \\2034300 &:= (F(20) + F(3)^4) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20373 &:= (F(20) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times 3 \\203730 &:= (F(20) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times 30 \\2037300 &:= (F(20) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20865 &:= (F(-2 + F(08)) - F(6)) \times 5 \\208650 &:= (F(-2 + F(08)) - F(6)) \times 50 \\2086500 &:= (F(-2 + F(08)) - F(6)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21782 &:= (-F(2 + 1 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 2 \\217820 &:= (-F(2 + 1 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 20 \\2178200 &:= (-F(2 + 1 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21842 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 2 \\21842 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 2 \\218420 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 20 \\218420 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 20 \\2184200 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$2184200 := (F(21) - F(8) - 4) \times 200$$

$$\begin{aligned}21862 &:= (F(21) - F(8) + 6) \times 2 \\218620 &:= (F(21) - F(8) + 6) \times 20 \\2186200 &:= (F(21) - F(8) + 6) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21872 &:= (-2 - 1 + F(F(8)) - 7) \times 2 \\218720 &:= (-2 - 1 + F(F(8)) - 7) \times 20 \\2187200 &:= (-2 - 1 + F(F(8)) - 7) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21892 &:= F(21) \times (-8 + 9) \times 2 \\218920 &:= F(21) \times (-8 + 9) \times 20 \\2189200 &:= F(21) \times (-8 + 9) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21912 &:= (F(21) + 9 + 1) \times 2 \\ 219120 &:= (F(21) + 9 + 1) \times 20 \\ 2191200 &:= (F(21) + 9 + 1) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22995 &:= (-F(2) + 2^9) \times 9 \times 5 \\ 229950 &:= (-F(2) + 2^9) \times 9 \times 50 \\ 2299500 &:= (-F(2) + 2^9) \times 9 \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23676 &:= (-2 + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 6 \\ 236760 &:= (-2 + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 60 \\ 2367600 &:= (-2 + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23826 &:= (2 + (3 \times F(8))^2) \times 6 \\ 238260 &:= (2 + (3 \times F(8))^2) \times 60 \\ 2382600 &:= (2 + (3 \times F(8))^2) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23945 &:= (-2 + 3 \times F(F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 239450 &:= (-2 + 3 \times F(F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times 50 \\ 2394500 &:= (-2 + 3 \times F(F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23965 &:= (2 + 3 \times F(9 + F(6))) \times 5 \\ 239650 &:= (2 + 3 \times F(9 + F(6))) \times 50 \\ 2396500 &:= (2 + 3 \times F(9 + F(6))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24255 &:= F(2 \times 4)^2 \times 55 \\ 242550 &:= F(2 \times 4)^2 \times 550 \\ 2425500 &:= F(2 \times 4)^2 \times 5500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24465 &:= F(2^4 - F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \times 5 \\ 244650 &:= F(2^4 - F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \times 50 \\ 2446500 &:= F(2^4 - F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24475 &:= (2 + F(4 + 4) \times F(F(7))) \times 5 \\ 244750 &:= (2 + F(4 + 4) \times F(F(7))) \times 50 \\ 2447500 &:= (2 + F(4 + 4) \times F(F(7))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24573 &:= (-F(2) + (-F(4) + 5)^{F(7)}) \times 3 \\ 245730 &:= (-F(2) + (-F(4) + 5)^{F(7)}) \times 30 \\ 2457300 &:= (-F(2) + (-F(4) + 5)^{F(7)}) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$24675 := F(2^4) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 246750 &:= F(2^4) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) \times 50 \\ 2467500 &:= F(2^4) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24785 &:= (F(2) + (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times F(8)) \times 5 \\ 247850 &:= (F(2) + (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times F(8)) \times 50 \\ 2478500 &:= (F(2) + (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times F(8)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24843 &:= (2 + F(F(4) + 8))^{F(F(4))} \times 3 \\ 248430 &:= (2 + F(F(4) + 8))^{F(F(4))} \times 30 \\ 2484300 &:= (2 + F(F(4) + 8))^{F(F(4))} \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24997 &:= (F(2^4) + F(9 + 9)) \times 7 \\ 249970 &:= (F(2^4) + F(9 + 9)) \times 70 \\ 2499700 &:= (F(2^4) + F(9 + 9)) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25775 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - F(7)) \times 5 \\ 257750 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - F(7)) \times 50 \\ 2577500 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - F(7)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25795 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - 9) \times 5 \\ 257950 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - 9) \times 50 \\ 2579500 &:= (2 \times F(5 + F(7)) - 9) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26047 &:= (F(2) + 60)^{F(F(4))} \times 7 \\ 260470 &:= (F(2) + 60)^{F(F(4))} \times 70 \\ 2604700 &:= (F(2) + 60)^{F(F(4))} \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26244 &:= (F(2) + 6 + 2)^4 \times 4 \\ 262440 &:= (F(2) + 6 + 2)^4 \times 40 \\ 2624400 &:= (F(2) + 6 + 2)^4 \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26411 &:= (F(2) + 6)^4 \times 11 \\ 264110 &:= (F(2) + 6)^4 \times 110 \\ 2641100 &:= (F(2) + 6)^4 \times 1100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26464 &:= (F(2 + F(6)) + F(4)^{F(6)}) \times 4 \\ 264640 &:= (F(2 + F(6)) + F(4)^{F(6)}) \times 40 \\ 2646400 &:= (F(2 + F(6)) + F(4)^{F(6)}) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$26484 := (F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(4 + 8)) \times 4$$

$$264840 := (F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(4 + 8)) \times 40$$

$$2648400 := (F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(4 + 8)) \times 400$$

$$26645 := (-F(2 \times 6) + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4))) \times 5$$

$$266450 := (-F(2 \times 6) + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4))) \times 50$$

$$2664500 := (-F(2 \times 6) + F(F(F(6)))/F(F(4))) \times 500$$

$$26675 := (F(2) + F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(7)))) \times 5$$

$$266750 := (F(2) + F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(7)))) \times 50$$

$$2667500 := (F(2) + F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(7)))) \times 500$$

$$26765 := ((2 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) - 6) \times 5$$

$$267650 := ((2 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) - 6) \times 50$$

$$2676500 := ((2 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) - 6) \times 500$$

$$26855 := (2^{F(6)} \times F(8) - 5) \times 5$$

$$268550 := (2^{F(6)} \times F(8) - 5) \times 50$$

$$2685500 := (2^{F(6)} \times F(8) - 5) \times 500$$

$$27164 := (2 \times F(7) + F(-1 + F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$271640 := (2 \times F(7) + F(-1 + F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$2716400 := (2 \times F(7) + F(-1 + F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$27279 := (2 + F(F(7)) \times F(2) \times F(7)) \times 9$$

$$272790 := (2 + F(F(7)) \times F(2) \times F(7)) \times 90$$

$$2727900 := (2 + F(F(7)) \times F(2) \times F(7)) \times 900$$

$$27345 := (F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(3) - 4) \times 5$$

$$273450 := (F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(3) - 4) \times 50$$

$$2734500 := (F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(3) - 4) \times 500$$

$$27365 := F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(-3 + 6) \times 5$$

$$273650 := F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(-3 + 6) \times 50$$

$$2736500 := F(F(F(2) + 7))/F(-3 + 6) \times 500$$

$$27675 := (F(2 \times 7) - F(6)) \times 75$$

$$276750 := (F(2 \times 7) - F(6)) \times 750$$

$$2767500 := (F(2 \times 7) - F(6)) \times 7500$$

$$27963 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 3$$

$$279630 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 30$$

$$2796300 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 300$$

$$27964 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$279640 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$2796400 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$27968 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + 6)) \times 8$$

$$279680 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + 6)) \times 80$$

$$2796800 := (F(2) + F(F(7)) \times (9 + 6)) \times 800$$

$$28275 := F(2 \times 8 - 2) \times 75$$

$$282750 := F(2 \times 8 - 2) \times 750$$

$$2827500 := F(2 \times 8 - 2) \times 7500$$

$$28288 := (F(2) + F(8)^2) \times 8 \times 8$$

$$282880 := (F(2) + F(8)^2) \times 8 \times 80$$

$$2828800 := (F(2) + F(8)^2) \times 8 \times 800$$

$$28672 := 2^8 \times F(6) \times 7 \times 2$$

$$286720 := 2^8 \times F(6) \times 7 \times 20$$

$$2867200 := 2^8 \times F(6) \times 7 \times 200$$

$$28746 := F(2 + 8 + 7) \times F(4) \times 6$$

$$287460 := F(2 + 8 + 7) \times F(4) \times 60$$

$$2874600 := F(2 + 8 + 7) \times F(4) \times 600$$

$$28824 := (F(-F(2) + F(8)) + F(8)^2) \times 4$$

$$288240 := (F(-F(2) + F(8)) + F(8)^2) \times 40$$

$$2882400 := (F(-F(2) + F(8)) + F(8)^2) \times 400$$

$$29197 := (-F(2) - 9 + F(19)) \times 7$$

$$291970 := (-F(2) - 9 + F(19)) \times 70$$

$$2919700 := (-F(2) - 9 + F(19)) \times 700$$

$$29466 := (-2 + F(9)^{F(4)})/F(6) \times 6$$

$$294660 := (-2 + F(9)^{F(4)})/F(6) \times 60$$

$$2946600 := (-2 + F(9)^{F(4)})/F(6) \times 600$$

$$29766 := (2 \times F(9) + F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times 6$$

$$297660 := (2 \times F(9) + F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times 60$$

$$2976600 := (2 \times F(9) + F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \times 600$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29989 &:= F(2) + F(9) \times 98 \times 9 \\ 299890 &:= F(2) + F(9) \times 98 \times 90 \\ 2998900 &:= F(2) + F(9) \times 98 \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31648 &:= (F(3) + F(16)) \times 4 \times 8 \\ 316480 &:= (F(3) + F(16)) \times 4 \times 80 \\ 3164800 &:= (F(3) + F(16)) \times 4 \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32463 &:= (- (3 + 2)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3 \\ 324630 &:= (- (3 + 2)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 30 \\ 3246300 &:= (- (3 + 2)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32675 &:= (3 + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 5 \\ 326750 &:= (3 + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 50 \\ 3267500 &:= (3 + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32684 &:= (F(3)^{F(F(2)+6)} - F(8)) \times 4 \\ 326840 &:= (F(3)^{F(F(2)+6)} - F(8)) \times 40 \\ 3268400 &:= (F(3)^{F(F(2)+6)} - F(8)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32744 &:= (-F(3) + 2^{F(7)} - 4) \times 4 \\ 327440 &:= (-F(3) + 2^{F(7)} - 4) \times 40 \\ 3274400 &:= (-F(3) + 2^{F(7)} - 4) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32747 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(4) \times 7 \\ 327470 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(4) \times 70 \\ 3274700 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - F(4) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32753 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - 5 \times 3 \\ 327530 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - 5 \times 30 \\ 3275300 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - 5 \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32805 &:= (F(3) + F(2))^8 \times 05 \\ 328050 &:= (F(3) + F(2))^8 \times 050 \\ 3280500 &:= (F(3) + F(2))^8 \times 0500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32883 &:= (-3 \times 2 + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 3 \\ 328830 &:= (-3 \times 2 + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 30 \\ 3288300 &:= (-3 \times 2 + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32943 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 3 \\ 329430 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 30 \\ 3294300 &:= (F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33448 &:= F(3^3 - 4 - 4) \times 8 \\ 334480 &:= F(3^3 - 4 - 4) \times 80 \\ 3344800 &:= F(3^3 - 4 - 4) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33488 &:= (3 + F(3) + F(-F(F(4)) + F(8))) \times 8 \\ 334880 &:= (3 + F(3) + F(-F(F(4)) + F(8))) \times 80 \\ 3348800 &:= (3 + F(3) + F(-F(F(4)) + F(8))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33785 &:= (F(3^3 - 7) - 8) \times 5 \\ 337850 &:= (F(3^3 - 7) - 8) \times 50 \\ 3378500 &:= (F(3^3 - 7) - 8) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33815 &:= (F(F(3)) - 3 + F(F(8) - 1)) \times 5 \\ 338150 &:= (F(F(3)) - 3 + F(F(8) - 1)) \times 50 \\ 3381500 &:= (F(F(3)) - 3 + F(F(8) - 1)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33835 &:= (F(3) + F((F(3) + 8) \times F(3))) \times 5 \\ 338350 &:= (F(3) + F((F(3) + 8) \times F(3))) \times 50 \\ 3383500 &:= (F(3) + F((F(3) + 8) \times F(3))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33845 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + 4) \times 5 \\ 338450 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + 4) \times 50 \\ 3384500 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + 4) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33855 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + 5) \times 5 \\ 338550 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + 5) \times 50 \\ 3385500 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + 5) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33865 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + F(6)) \times 5 \\ 338650 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + F(6)) \times 50 \\ 3386500 &:= (F(-3/3 + F(8)) + F(6)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33875 &:= (-3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + F(7)) \times 5 \\ 338750 &:= (-3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + F(7)) \times 50 \\ 3387500 &:= (-3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)) + F(7)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33995 &:= (F(F(3) + F(3) \times 9) + F(9)) \times 5 \\ 339950 &:= (F(F(3) + F(3) \times 9) + F(9)) \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

$$3399500 := (F(F(3) + F(3) \times 9) + F(9)) \times 500$$

$$34445 := (F(3) + F(4)^4)^{F(F(4))} \times 5$$

$$344450 := (F(3) + F(4)^4)^{F(F(4))} \times 50$$

$$3444500 := (F(3) + F(4)^4)^{F(F(4))} \times 500$$

$$34475 := (-F(3) + F(4 \times 4)) \times 7 \times 5$$

$$344750 := (-F(3) + F(4 \times 4)) \times 7 \times 50$$

$$3447500 := (-F(3) + F(4 \times 4)) \times 7 \times 500$$

$$34545 := (F(3 \times 4) + F(5 \times 4)) \times 5$$

$$345450 := (F(3 \times 4) + F(5 \times 4)) \times 50$$

$$3454500 := (F(3 \times 4) + F(5 \times 4)) \times 500$$

$$34848 := (3 + F(4) \times F(8))^{F(F(4))} \times 8$$

$$348480 := (3 + F(4) \times F(8))^{F(F(4))} \times 80$$

$$3484800 := (3 + F(4) \times F(8))^{F(F(4))} \times 800$$

$$36485 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) + F(F(8)) \times 5$$

$$364850 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) + F(F(8)) \times 50$$

$$3648500 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) + F(F(8)) \times 500$$

$$36875 := (F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F(8 + 7)) \times 5$$

$$368750 := (F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F(8 + 7)) \times 50$$

$$3687500 := (F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) + F(8 + 7)) \times 500$$

$$36992 := F(3) \times F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 2$$

$$369920 := F(3) \times F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 20$$

$$3699200 := F(3) \times F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 200$$

$$36994 := F(3) + F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 4$$

$$369940 := F(3) + F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 40$$

$$3699400 := F(3) + F(6) \times F(9) \times F(9) \times 400$$

$$37044 := (3 \times 7)^{F(04)} \times 4$$

$$370440 := (3 \times 7)^{F(04)} \times 40$$

$$3704400 := (3 \times 7)^{F(04)} \times 400$$

$$37288 := (F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8))) \times 8$$

$$372880 := (F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8))) \times 80$$

$$3728800 := (F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8))) \times 800$$

$$37295 := (-3 + F(F(7)) \times (-2 + F(9))) \times 5$$

$$372950 := (-3 + F(F(7)) \times (-2 + F(9))) \times 50$$

$$3729500 := (-3 + F(F(7)) \times (-2 + F(9))) \times 500$$

$$37392 := (-F(3 + F(7)) + 3^9) \times 2$$

$$373920 := (-F(3 + F(7)) + 3^9) \times 20$$

$$3739200 := (-F(3 + F(7)) + 3^9) \times 200$$

$$37623 := (3 \times F(F(7) + 6) - 2) \times 3$$

$$376230 := (3 \times F(F(7) + 6) - 2) \times 30$$

$$3762300 := (3 \times F(F(7) + 6) - 2) \times 300$$

$$37648 := (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(6)^4) \times 8$$

$$376480 := (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(6)^4) \times 80$$

$$3764800 := (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(6)^4) \times 800$$

$$38272 := (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2^{F(7)}) \times 2$$

$$382720 := (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2^{F(7)}) \times 20$$

$$3827200 := (-F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2^{F(7)}) \times 200$$

$$38367 := (F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))/F(3) + F(6)) \times 7$$

$$383670 := (F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))/F(3) + F(6)) \times 70$$

$$3836700 := (F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))/F(3) + F(6)) \times 700$$

$$38635 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 - F(F(3))) \times 5$$

$$386350 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 - F(F(3))) \times 50$$

$$3863500 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 - F(F(3))) \times 500$$

$$38645 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$386450 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 50$$

$$3864500 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 500$$

$$38675 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + 7) \times 5$$

$$386750 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + 7) \times 50$$

$$3867500 := (F(3 \times 8)/6 + 7) \times 500$$

$$39168 := F(3 + 9) \times F(1 + F(6)) \times 8$$

$$391680 := F(3 + 9) \times F(1 + F(6)) \times 80$$

$$3916800 := F(3 + 9) \times F(1 + F(6)) \times 800$$

$$39275 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-2 + F(F(7)))) \times 5$$

$$392750 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-2 + F(F(7)))) \times 50$$

$$3927500 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-2 + F(F(7)))) \times 500$$

$$39282 := (3^9 - 2 \times F(8)) \times 2$$

$$392820 := (3^9 - 2 \times F(8)) \times 20$$

$$3928200 := (3^9 - 2 \times F(8)) \times 200$$

$$39301 := -3 + F(9)^3 \times 01$$

$$393010 := -3 + F(9)^3 \times 010$$

$$3930100 := -3 + F(9)^3 \times 0100$$

$$39352 := (3^9 - F(3) - 5) \times 2$$

$$393520 := (3^9 - F(3) - 5) \times 20$$

$$3935200 := (3^9 - F(3) - 5) \times 200$$

$$39486 := (-F(F(3)) + 9^4 + F(8)) \times 6$$

$$394860 := (-F(F(3)) + 9^4 + F(8)) \times 60$$

$$3948600 := (-F(F(3)) + 9^4 + F(8)) \times 600$$

$$39615 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times F(F(6 + 1))) \times 5$$

$$396150 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times F(F(6 + 1))) \times 50$$

$$3961500 := (F(F(3)) + F(9) \times F(F(6 + 1))) \times 500$$

$$39625 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(F(6) - F(2)))) \times 5$$

$$396250 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(F(6) - F(2)))) \times 50$$

$$3962500 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(F(6) - F(2)))) \times 500$$

$$39795 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) + F(9)) \times 5$$

$$397950 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) + F(9)) \times 50$$

$$3979500 := (3 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) + F(9)) \times 500$$

$$39832 := (3^9 + F(F(F(8)/3))) \times 2$$

$$398320 := (3^9 + F(F(F(8)/3))) \times 20$$

$$3983200 := (3^9 + F(F(F(8)/3))) \times 200$$

$$39984 := 3 \times F(9) \times 98 \times 4$$

$$399840 := 3 \times F(9) \times 98 \times 40$$

$$3998400 := 3 \times F(9) \times 98 \times 400$$

$$42336 := (4 \times F(2^3))^{F(3)} \times 6$$

$$423360 := (4 \times F(2^3))^{F(3)} \times 60$$

$$4233600 := (4 \times F(2^3))^{F(3)} \times 600$$

$$42849 := (F(4) \times (2 + F(8)))^{F(F(4))} \times 9$$

$$428490 := (F(4) \times (2 + F(8)))^{F(F(4))} \times 90$$

$$4284900 := (F(4) \times (2 + F(8)))^{F(F(4))} \times 900$$

$$42864 := (F(4) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$428640 := (F(4) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$4286400 := (F(4) - F(F(-F(2) + 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$42872 := 4 \times (2 + F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \times 2$$

$$428720 := 4 \times (2 + F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \times 20$$

$$4287200 := 4 \times (2 + F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \times 200$$

$$43464 := (F(F(F(4))) - 3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$434640 := (F(F(F(4))) - 3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$4346400 := (F(F(F(4))) - 3^4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$43664 := (-F(4) \times 3 + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(6))) \times 4$$

$$436640 := (-F(4) \times 3 + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(6))) \times 40$$

$$4366400 := (-F(4) \times 3 + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(6))) \times 400$$

$$43684 := (-4 - F(F(3) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 4$$

$$436840 := (-4 - F(F(3) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 40$$

$$4368400 := (-4 - F(F(3) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 400$$

$$43685 := (F(4)^{3+6} - F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$436850 := (F(4)^{3+6} - F(F(8))) \times 50$$

$$4368500 := (F(4)^{3+6} - F(F(8))) \times 500$$

$$43735 := (4 \times 3^7 - F(F(3))) \times 5$$

$$437350 := (4 \times 3^7 - F(F(3))) \times 50$$

$$4373500 := (4 \times 3^7 - F(F(3))) \times 500$$

$$43745 := (F(F(F(4))) + 3^7 \times 4) \times 5$$

$$437450 := (F(F(F(4))) + 3^7 \times 4) \times 50$$

$$4374500 := (F(F(F(4))) + 3^7 \times 4) \times 500$$

$$43824 := (4 \times F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2) \times 4$$

$$438240 := (4 \times F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2) \times 40$$

$$4382400 := (4 \times F(3) + F(F(8)) + 2) \times 400$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &43844 := (4 \times 3 + F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times 4 \\
 &438440 := (4 \times 3 + F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times 40 \\
 &4384400 := (4 \times 3 + F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times 400 \\
 &43864 := (-4 + 3 + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 4 \\
 &438640 := (-4 + 3 + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 40 \\
 &4386400 := (-4 + 3 + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 400 \\
 &43884 := (F(F(4)) + F(3) + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 4 \\
 &438840 := (F(F(4)) + F(3) + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 40 \\
 &4388400 := (F(F(4)) + F(3) + F(8) + F(F(8))) \times 400 \\
 &43964 := ((F(4) + F(3)) \times 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 \\
 &439640 := ((F(4) + F(3)) \times 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40 \\
 &4396400 := ((F(4) + F(3)) \times 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400 \\
 &43984 := (4^{F(3)} + F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 4 \\
 &439840 := (4^{F(3)} + F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 40 \\
 &4398400 := (4^{F(3)} + F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 400 \\
 &44364 := (F(F(4) \times 4) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 \\
 &443640 := (F(F(4) \times 4) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40 \\
 &4436400 := (F(F(4) \times 4) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400 \\
 &44395 := (-4 + F(4^{F(3)}) \times 9) \times 5 \\
 &443950 := (-4 + F(4^{F(3)}) \times 9) \times 50 \\
 &4439500 := (-4 + F(4^{F(3)}) \times 9) \times 500 \\
 &44415 := F(4) \times F(4 \times 4) \times 15 \\
 &444150 := F(4) \times F(4 \times 4) \times 150 \\
 &4441500 := F(4) \times F(4 \times 4) \times 1500 \\
 &44664 := (4 \times F(4 + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 \\
 &446640 := (4 \times F(4 + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40 \\
 &4466400 := (4 \times F(4 + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400 \\
 &44684 := (F(F(F(4) + 4)) - F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 4 \\
 &446840 := (F(F(F(4) + 4)) - F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 40 \\
 &4468400 := (F(F(F(4) + 4)) - F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 400 \\
 &44724 := (F(F(4 + 4)) + F(F(7)) + 2) \times 4 \\
 &447240 := (F(F(4 + 4)) + F(F(7)) + 2) \times 400 \\
 &44733 := (4^{F(4)} \times F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 3 \\
 &447330 := (4^{F(4)} \times F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 30 \\
 &4473300 := (4^{F(4)} \times F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \times 300 \\
 &44737 := (4 \times F(4 + F(7)) + 3) \times 7 \\
 &447370 := (4 \times F(4 + F(7)) + 3) \times 70 \\
 &4473700 := (4 \times F(4 + F(7)) + 3) \times 700 \\
 &44764 := (F(4) \times 4 + F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 \\
 &447640 := (F(4) \times 4 + F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40 \\
 &4476400 := (F(4) \times 4 + F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400 \\
 &44768 := (4 + 4 \times F(F(7)) \times 6) \times 8 \\
 &447680 := (4 + 4 \times F(F(7)) \times 6) \times 80 \\
 &4476800 := (4 + 4 \times F(F(7)) \times 6) \times 800 \\
 &45384 := ((4 \times 5)^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) \times 4 \\
 &453840 := ((4 \times 5)^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) \times 40 \\
 &4538400 := ((4 \times 5)^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) \times 400 \\
 &45696 := 4 \times 56 \times F(9) \times 6 \\
 &456960 := 4 \times 56 \times F(9) \times 60 \\
 &4569600 := 4 \times 56 \times F(9) \times 600 \\
 &45717 := (F(4 \times 5) - F(F(7)) - 1) \times 7 \\
 &457170 := (F(4 \times 5) - F(F(7)) - 1) \times 70 \\
 &4571700 := (F(4 \times 5) - F(F(7)) - 1) \times 700 \\
 &45832 := (4^5 + F(F(8)) \times F(3)) \times 2 \\
 &458320 := (4^5 + F(F(8)) \times F(3)) \times 20 \\
 &4583200 := (4^5 + F(F(8)) \times F(3)) \times 200 \\
 &46137 := F(4) \times F(6 + 1)^3 \times 7 \\
 &461370 := F(4) \times F(6 + 1)^3 \times 70 \\
 &4613700 := F(4) \times F(6 + 1)^3 \times 700 \\
 &46353 := (F(4 \times 6) / 3 - 5) \times 3 \\
 &463530 := (F(4 \times 6) / 3 - 5) \times 30
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4635300 := (F(4 \times 6)/3 - 5) \times 300$$

$$46488 := ((F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 8$$

$$464880 := ((F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 80$$

$$4648800 := ((F(4) \times 6)^{F(4)} - F(8)) \times 800$$

$$46495 := (4 + F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(9)) \times 5$$

$$464950 := (4 + F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(9)) \times 50$$

$$4649500 := (4 + F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(9)) \times 500$$

$$46768 := ((4 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 8$$

$$467680 := ((4 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 80$$

$$4676800 := ((4 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 800$$

$$46865 := (F(4)^6 - 8) \times 65$$

$$468650 := (F(4)^6 - 8) \times 650$$

$$4686500 := (F(4)^6 - 8) \times 6500$$

$$47327 := (-4 + F((7 + 3) \times 2)) \times 7$$

$$473270 := (-4 + F((7 + 3) \times 2)) \times 70$$

$$4732700 := (-4 + F((7 + 3) \times 2)) \times 700$$

$$47365 := (-4 + F(7) \times 3^6) \times 5$$

$$473650 := (-4 + F(7) \times 3^6) \times 50$$

$$4736500 := (-4 + F(7) \times 3^6) \times 500$$

$$47368 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7) + 3) \times 6) \times 8$$

$$473680 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7) + 3) \times 6) \times 80$$

$$4736800 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7) + 3) \times 6) \times 800$$

$$47464 := ((-F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$474640 := ((-F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$4746400 := ((-F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 4 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$47467 := (F(4) + F(7) + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$474670 := (F(4) + F(7) + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6)))) \times 70$$

$$4746700 := (F(4) + F(7) + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(6)))) \times 700$$

$$47526 := F(4 + 7)^{F(5-2)} \times 6$$

$$475260 := F(4 + 7)^{F(5-2)} \times 60$$

$$4752600 := F(4 + 7)^{F(5-2)} \times 600$$

$$47736 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7)) - 3) \times 6$$

$$477360 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7)) - 3) \times 60$$

$$4773600 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} - F(F(7)) - 3) \times 600$$

$$47784 := (F(F(4) + F(7)) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 4$$

$$477840 := (F(F(4) + F(7)) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 40$$

$$4778400 := (F(F(4) + F(7)) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 400$$

$$47845 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} + F(F(8)))/F(F(4)) \times 5$$

$$478450 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} + F(F(8)))/F(F(4)) \times 50$$

$$4784500 := (F(F(4))^{F(7)} + F(F(8)))/F(F(4)) \times 500$$

$$47946 := ((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6$$

$$479460 := ((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 60$$

$$4794600 := ((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 600$$

$$48377 := (F(F(4)) + F(8 \times F(3)) \times 7) \times 7$$

$$483770 := (F(F(4)) + F(8 \times F(3)) \times 7) \times 70$$

$$4837700 := (F(F(4)) + F(8 \times F(3)) \times 7) \times 700$$

$$48384 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 84$$

$$483840 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 840$$

$$4838400 := (F(4) \times 8)^{F(3)} \times 8400$$

$$48664 := (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8) - 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$486640 := (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8) - 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$4866400 := (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8) - 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$48935 := (-F(4) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 5$$

$$489350 := (-F(4) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 50$$

$$4893500 := (-F(4) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 500$$

$$48945 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 5$$

$$489450 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 50$$

$$4894500 := (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) - F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 500$$

$$49239 := (-4 + F(F(9 - F(2))))/F(3) \times 9$$

$$492390 := (-4 + F(F(9 - F(2))))/F(3) \times 90$$

$$4923900 := (-4 + F(F(9 - F(2))))/F(3) \times 900$$

$$\begin{aligned}49285 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) - F(9))^2 + F(F(8)) \times 5 \\492850 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) - F(9))^2 + F(F(8)) \times 50 \\4928500 &:= (-F(F(F(4))) - F(9))^2 + F(F(8)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49368 &:= (-F(4) + 9^3) \times 68 \\493680 &:= (-F(4) + 9^3) \times 680 \\4936800 &:= (-F(4) + 9^3) \times 6800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49785 &:= (-F(F(4)) - F(9 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\497850 &:= (-F(F(4)) - F(9 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\4978500 &:= (-F(F(4)) - F(9 + 7) + F(F(8))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49795 &:= (F(F(F(-F(4) + 9))) - F(7 + 9)) \times 5 \\497950 &:= (F(F(F(-F(4) + 9))) - F(7 + 9)) \times 50 \\4979500 &:= (F(F(F(-F(4) + 9))) - F(7 + 9)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49923 &:= (F(4) \times (9 + F(9)))^2 \times 3 \\499230 &:= (F(4) \times (9 + F(9)))^2 \times 30 \\4992300 &:= (F(4) \times (9 + F(9)))^2 \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49928 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9 \times 9)^2 \times 8 \\499280 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9 \times 9)^2 \times 80 \\4992800 &:= (-F(F(4)) + 9 \times 9)^2 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52743 &:= (5 + (2 \times F(7))^{F(4)}) \times 3 \\527430 &:= (5 + (2 \times F(7))^{F(4)}) \times 30 \\5274300 &:= (5 + (2 \times F(7))^{F(4)}) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53133 &:= F(5^{3-1} - 3) \times 3 \\531330 &:= F(5^{3-1} - 3) \times 30 \\5313300 &:= F(5^{3-1} - 3) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53163 &:= (5 \times F(3) + F(1 + F(F(6)))) \times 3 \\531630 &:= (5 \times F(3) + F(1 + F(F(6)))) \times 30 \\5316300 &:= (5 \times F(3) + F(1 + F(F(6)))) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53488 &:= (5^3 + F(4)^8) \times 8 \\534880 &:= (5^3 + F(4)^8) \times 80 \\5348800 &:= (5^3 + F(4)^8) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$53565 := (F(F(5 + 3)) - F(5 + F(6))) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}535650 &:= (F(F(5 + 3)) - F(5 + F(6))) \times 50 \\5356500 &:= (F(F(5 + 3)) - F(5 + F(6))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53985 &:= (-5 - F(3 + 9) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\539850 &:= (-5 - F(3 + 9) + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\5398500 &:= (-5 - F(3 + 9) + F(F(8))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54128 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times 1 + F(2)) \times 8 \\541280 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times 1 + F(2)) \times 80 \\5412800 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times 1 + F(2)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54168 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times 6) \times 8 \\541680 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times 6) \times 80 \\5416800 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 1 \times 6) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54248 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 2^4) \times 8 \\542480 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 2^4) \times 80 \\5424800 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 2^4) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54281 &:= (F(F(5 + F(F(4))))^2 - 8) \times 1 \\542810 &:= (F(F(5 + F(F(4))))^2 - 8) \times 10 \\5428100 &:= (F(F(5 + F(F(4))))^2 - 8) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54288 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times 8 \\542880 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times 80 \\5428800 &:= (F(5 \times 4) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54385 &:= (-5 - 4^3 + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\543850 &:= (-5 - 4^3 + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\5438500 &:= (-5 - 4^3 + F(F(8))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54465 &:= (-54 + F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\544650 &:= (-54 + F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 50 \\5446500 &:= (-54 + F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54485 &:= (-5 - 44 + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\544850 &:= (-5 - 44 + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\5448500 &:= (-5 - 44 + F(F(8))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54568 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 56) \times 8 \\545680 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 56) \times 80 \\5456800 &:= (F(5 \times 4) + 56) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54585 &:= (5 - F(4 + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\
 545850 &:= (5 - F(4 + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\
 5458500 &:= (5 - F(4 + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 500 \\
 54625 &:= (-F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(6 + 2))) \times 5 \\
 546250 &:= (-F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(6 + 2))) \times 50 \\
 5462500 &:= (-F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(6 + 2))) \times 500 \\
 54645 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(F(6)) + 4) \times 5 \\
 546450 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(F(6)) + 4) \times 50 \\
 5464500 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(F(6)) + 4) \times 500 \\
 54655 &:= (-5 \times 4 + F(F(F(6))) + 5) \times 5 \\
 546550 &:= (-5 \times 4 + F(F(F(6))) + 5) \times 50 \\
 5465500 &:= (-5 \times 4 + F(F(F(6))) + 5) \times 500 \\
 54675 &:= 5 \times F(4)^{-6+F(7)} \times 5 \\
 546750 &:= 5 \times F(4)^{-6+F(7)} \times 50 \\
 5467500 &:= 5 \times F(4)^{-6+F(7)} \times 500 \\
 54685 &:= (-54/6 + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\
 546850 &:= (-54/6 + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\
 5468500 &:= (-54/6 + F(F(8))) \times 500 \\
 54695 &:= (5 - F(4) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) \times 5 \\
 546950 &:= (5 - F(4) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) \times 50 \\
 5469500 &:= (5 - F(4) + F(F(F(6))) - 9) \times 500 \\
 54725 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^7 + 2) \times 5 \\
 547250 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^7 + 2) \times 50 \\
 5472500 &:= 5 \times (F(4)^7 + 2) \times 500 \\
 54735 &:= (5 - 4 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 5 \\
 547350 &:= (5 - 4 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 50 \\
 5473500 &:= (5 - 4 + F(7 \times 3)) \times 500 \\
 54765 &:= (5 + F(F(4)) + F(F(7) + F(6))) \times 5 \\
 547650 &:= (5 + F(F(4)) + F(F(7) + F(6))) \times 50 \\
 5476500 &:= (5 + F(F(4)) + F(F(7) + F(6))) \times 500 \\
 54785 &:= (-5 + F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\
 547850 &:= (-5 + F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\
 5478500 &:= (-5 + F(4) + F(7) + F(F(8))) \times 500 \\
 54825 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 5 \\
 548250 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 50 \\
 5482500 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 500 \\
 54835 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 5 \\
 548350 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 50 \\
 5483500 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 500 \\
 54845 &:= (5^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\
 548450 &:= (5^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 50 \\
 5484500 &:= (5^{F(F(4))} + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) \times 500 \\
 54855 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + 5) \times 5 \\
 548550 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + 5) \times 50 \\
 5485500 &:= (5 \times 4 + F(F(8)) + 5) \times 500 \\
 54865 &:= (F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 6) \times 5 \\
 548650 &:= (F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 6) \times 50 \\
 5486500 &:= (F(5 + F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 6) \times 500 \\
 54885 &:= (5 \times F(F(4)) + (F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\
 548850 &:= (5 \times F(F(4)) + (F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 50 \\
 5488500 &:= (5 \times F(F(4)) + (F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 500 \\
 54895 &:= (-5 + 4 + F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times 5 \\
 548950 &:= (-5 + 4 + F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times 50 \\
 5489500 &:= (-5 + 4 + F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times 500 \\
 54955 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) + 9 \times 5) \times 5 \\
 549550 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) + 9 \times 5) \times 50 \\
 5495500 &:= (F(F(5 + F(4))) + 9 \times 5) \times 500 \\
 54965 &:= (F(5 + F(F(4))) + F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\
 549650 &:= (F(5 + F(F(4))) + F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 50 \\
 5496500 &:= (F(5 + F(F(4))) + F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 500 \\
 55125 &:= (5 \times F(F(5 + 1)))^2 \times 5 \\
 551250 &:= (5 \times F(F(5 + 1)))^2 \times 50 \\
 5512500 &:= (5 \times F(F(5 + 1)))^2 \times 500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55447 &:= F(5 + 5 + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))} \times 7 \\
 554470 &:= F(5 + 5 + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))} \times 70 \\
 5544700 &:= F(5 + 5 + F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))} \times 700 \\
 56284 &:= (5^{6-F(2)} + F(F(8))) \times 4 \\
 562840 &:= (5^{6-F(2)} + F(F(8))) \times 40 \\
 5628400 &:= (5^{6-F(2)} + F(F(8))) \times 400 \\
 57121 &:= (5 + F(F(7)) + 1)^2 \times 1 \\
 571210 &:= (5 + F(F(7)) + 1)^2 \times 10 \\
 5712100 &:= (5 + F(F(7)) + 1)^2 \times 100 \\
 57132 &:= (5 + F(7)^{1+3}) \times 2 \\
 571320 &:= (5 + F(7)^{1+3}) \times 20 \\
 5713200 &:= (5 + F(7)^{1+3}) \times 200 \\
 57312 &:= (F(F(-5 + F(7)) + F(3)) - 1) \times 2 \\
 573120 &:= (F(F(-5 + F(7)) + F(3)) - 1) \times 20 \\
 5731200 &:= (F(F(-5 + F(7)) + F(3)) - 1) \times 200 \\
 58686 &:= (-5 \times F(F(8) - F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 6 \\
 586860 &:= (-5 \times F(F(8) - F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 60 \\
 5868600 &:= (-5 \times F(F(8) - F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 600 \\
 58746 &:= (5 + F(8) \times F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 6 \\
 587460 &:= (5 + F(8) \times F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 60 \\
 5874600 &:= (5 + F(8) \times F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 600 \\
 59665 &:= (F(F(F(-5 + 9)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5 \\
 596650 &:= (F(F(F(-5 + 9)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 50 \\
 5966500 &:= (F(F(F(-5 + 9)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 500 \\
 61476 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 1 - F(4) \times F(F(7))) \times 6 \\
 614760 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 1 - F(4) \times F(F(7))) \times 60 \\
 6147600 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 1 - F(4) \times F(F(7))) \times 600 \\
 61824 &:= (-F(6) + F(18)) \times 24 \\
 618240 &:= (-F(6) + F(18)) \times 240 \\
 6182400 &:= (-F(6) + F(18)) \times 2400 \\
 62426 &:= (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 26 \\
 624260 &:= (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 260 \\
 6242600 &:= (F(6) - F(2))^4 \times 2600 \\
 62482 &:= (F(F(F(6)) - F(2)) \times F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 2 \\
 624820 &:= (F(F(F(6)) - F(2)) \times F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 20 \\
 6248200 &:= (F(F(F(6)) - F(2)) \times F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 200 \\
 62568 &:= ((-6 + F(2))^5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8 \\
 625680 &:= ((-6 + F(2))^5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 80 \\
 6256800 &:= ((-6 + F(2))^5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 800 \\
 62715 &:= F(6 \times 2 + 7) \times 15 \\
 627150 &:= F(6 \times 2 + 7) \times 150 \\
 6271500 &:= F(6 \times 2 + 7) \times 1500 \\
 63168 &:= (6 + F(3)) \times F(16) \times 8 \\
 631680 &:= (6 + F(3)) \times F(16) \times 80 \\
 6316800 &:= (6 + F(3)) \times F(16) \times 800 \\
 63368 &:= F(F(6) + 3)^{F(-3+6)} \times 8 \\
 633680 &:= F(F(6) + 3)^{F(-3+6)} \times 80 \\
 6336800 &:= F(F(6) + 3)^{F(-3+6)} \times 800 \\
 63786 &:= (-F(F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 6 \\
 637860 &:= (-F(F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 60 \\
 6378600 &:= (-F(F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 600 \\
 64075 &:= F(6 + 4) \times F(F(07)) \times 5 \\
 640750 &:= F(6 + 4) \times F(F(07)) \times 50 \\
 6407500 &:= F(6 + 4) \times F(F(07)) \times 500 \\
 64266 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(F(2) + 6))) \times 6 \\
 642660 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(F(2) + 6))) \times 60 \\
 6426600 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - F(F(F(2) + 6))) \times 600 \\
 64296 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(4) - F(F(-2 + 9))) \times 6 \\
 642960 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(4) - F(F(-2 + 9))) \times 60 \\
 6429600 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(4) - F(F(-2 + 9))) \times 600 \\
 64356 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times F(F(3) \times 5)) \times 6 \\
 643560 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times F(F(3) \times 5)) \times 60
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6435600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times F(F(3) \times 5)) \times 600$$

$$64488 := (6^4 + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) \times 8$$

$$644880 := (6^4 + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) \times 80$$

$$6448800 := (6^4 + F(-F(F(F(4))) + F(8))) \times 800$$

$$64596 := (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times 5 \times 9) \times 6$$

$$645960 := (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times 5 \times 9) \times 60$$

$$6459600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 4 \times 5 \times 9) \times 600$$

$$64656 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4) + 6) \times 5) \times 6$$

$$646560 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4) + 6) \times 5) \times 60$$

$$6465600 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4) + 6) \times 5) \times 600$$

$$64686 := (-F(F(6)) - F(4 + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$646860 := (-F(F(6)) - F(4 + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6468600 := (-F(F(6)) - F(4 + F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$64986 := (F(F(6)) - 4 \times F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$649860 := (F(F(6)) - 4 \times F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6498600 := (F(F(6)) - 4 \times F(9) + F(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$65376 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times (3 + 7)) \times 6$$

$$653760 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times (3 + 7)) \times 60$$

$$6537600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times (3 + 7)) \times 600$$

$$65406 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 40) \times 6$$

$$654060 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 40) \times 60$$

$$6540600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 40) \times 600$$

$$65436 := (-F(6) \times 5 + F(F(4 \times F(3)))) \times 6$$

$$654360 := (-F(6) \times 5 + F(F(4 \times F(3)))) \times 60$$

$$6543600 := (-F(6) \times 5 + F(F(4 \times F(3)))) \times 600$$

$$65463 := (F(6)^5 - F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 3$$

$$654630 := (F(6)^5 - F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 30$$

$$6546300 := (F(6)^5 - F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 300$$

$$65522 := (F(6)^5 - 5 - 2) \times 2$$

$$655220 := (F(6)^5 - 5 - 2) \times 20$$

$$6552200 := (F(6)^5 - 5 - 2) \times 200$$

$$65532 := (F(6)^5 - 5 + 3) \times 2$$

$$655320 := (F(6)^5 - 5 + 3) \times 20$$

$$6553200 := (F(6)^5 - 5 + 3) \times 200$$

$$65541 := F(F(6)) \times (5^5 - 4) \times 1$$

$$655410 := F(F(6)) \times (5^5 - 4) \times 10$$

$$6554100 := F(F(6)) \times (5^5 - 4) \times 100$$

$$65542 := (F(6)^5 + 5 - F(F(4))) \times 2$$

$$655420 := (F(6)^5 + 5 - F(F(4))) \times 20$$

$$6554200 := (F(6)^5 + 5 - F(F(4))) \times 200$$

$$65556 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 5 + 5) \times 6$$

$$655560 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 5 + 5) \times 60$$

$$6555600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 5 + 5) \times 600$$

$$65562 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(6)) \times 2$$

$$655620 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(6)) \times 20$$

$$6556200 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(6)) \times 200$$

$$65572 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(7)) \times 2$$

$$655720 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(7)) \times 20$$

$$6557200 := (F(6)^5 + 5 + F(7)) \times 200$$

$$65586 := ((-F(6) + 5) \times 5 + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$655860 := ((-F(6) + 5) \times 5 + F(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6558600 := ((-F(6) + 5) \times 5 + F(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$65616 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 6 + 1) \times 6$$

$$656160 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 6 + 1) \times 60$$

$$6561600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 - 6 + 1) \times 600$$

$$65651 := ((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 6 + 5) \times 1$$

$$656510 := ((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 6 + 5) \times 10$$

$$6565100 := ((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 6 + 5) \times 100$$

$$65736 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(7) + F(3)) \times 6$$

$$657360 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(7) + F(3)) \times 60$$

$$6573600 := (F(F(F(6))) - 5 + F(7) + F(3)) \times 600$$

$$65766 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(-5 + F(7)) - 6) \times 6$$

$$657660 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(-5 + F(7)) - 6) \times 60$$

$$6576600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(-5 + F(7)) - 6) \times 600$$

$$65796 := (F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(7) - 9)) \times 6$$

$$657960 := (F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(7) - 9)) \times 60$$

$$6579600 := (F(F(F(6))) + 5 \times (F(7) - 9)) \times 600$$

$$65826 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 6$$

$$658260 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 60$$

$$6582600 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8)) - F(2)) \times 600$$

$$65832 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 3 \times 2$$

$$658320 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 3 \times 20$$

$$6583200 := (F(F(6)) + 5 + F(F(8))) \times 3 \times 200$$

$$65916 := (F(6) \times 5 + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 6$$

$$659160 := (F(6) \times 5 + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 60$$

$$6591600 := (F(6) \times 5 + F(F(9 - 1))) \times 600$$

$$66336 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6) + F(3)) \times F(3))) \times 6$$

$$663360 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6) + F(3)) \times F(3))) \times 60$$

$$6633600 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6) + F(3)) \times F(3))) \times 600$$

$$66576 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(5 + 7)) \times 6$$

$$665760 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(5 + 7)) \times 60$$

$$6657600 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(5 + 7)) \times 600$$

$$66636 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 6$$

$$666360 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 60$$

$$6663600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \times 600$$

$$66666 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6 + 6) + F(F(6))) \times 6$$

$$666660 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6 + 6) + F(F(6))) \times 60$$

$$6666600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(6 + 6) + F(F(6))) \times 600$$

$$66726 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(7)^2) \times 6$$

$$667260 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(7)^2) \times 60$$

$$6672600 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 + F(7)^2) \times 600$$

$$66786 := (-F(6) \times 6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$667860 := (-F(6) \times 6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6678600 := (-F(6) \times 6 + F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$66936 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times (F(9) + F(F(3)))) \times 6$$

$$669360 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times (F(9) + F(F(3)))) \times 60$$

$$6693600 := (F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times (F(9) + F(F(3)))) \times 600$$

$$67144 := (-F(F(6)) + 7^{1+4}) \times 4$$

$$671440 := (-F(F(6)) + 7^{1+4}) \times 40$$

$$6714400 := (-F(F(6)) + 7^{1+4}) \times 400$$

$$67176 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + 17) \times 6$$

$$671760 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + 17) \times 60$$

$$6717600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)) + 17) \times 600$$

$$67335 := 67^{F(3)} \times 3 \times 5$$

$$673350 := 67^{F(3)} \times 3 \times 50$$

$$6733500 := 67^{F(3)} \times 3 \times 500$$

$$67986 := (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times (F(9) + F(8))) \times 6$$

$$679860 := (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times (F(9) + F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6798600 := (F(F(F(6))) + 7 \times (F(9) + F(8))) \times 600$$

$$68286 := (-6 + F(8)^2 + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$682860 := (-6 + F(8)^2 + F(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$6828600 := (-6 + F(8)^2 + F(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$68316 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} - 1) \times 6$$

$$683160 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} - 1) \times 60$$

$$6831600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} - 1) \times 600$$

$$68346 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 4) \times 6$$

$$683460 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 4) \times 60$$

$$6834600 := (F(F(F(6))) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 4) \times 600$$

$$68467 := (F(F(6)) \times F(8 \times F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 7$$

$$684670 := (F(F(6)) \times F(8 \times F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 70$$

$$6846700 := (F(F(6)) \times F(8 \times F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 700$$

$$68537 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(8) \times F(5 \times F(3))) \times 7$$

$$685370 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(8) \times F(5 \times F(3))) \times 70$$

$$6853700 := (F(F(F(6))) - F(8) \times F(5 \times F(3))) \times 700$$

$$\begin{aligned}68544 &:= 6 \times F(8) \times 544 \\685440 &:= 6 \times F(8) \times 5440 \\6854400 &:= 6 \times F(8) \times 54400 \\69336 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(9 + 3 + 3)) \times 6 \\693360 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(9 + 3 + 3)) \times 60 \\6933600 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + F(9 + 3 + 3)) \times 600 \\69579 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(9) \times (-5 + F(F(7)))) \times 9 \\695790 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(9) \times (-5 + F(F(7)))) \times 90 \\6957900 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(9) \times (-5 + F(F(7)))) \times 900 \\69632 &:= F(6) \times F(9) \times F(6) \times 32 \\696320 &:= F(6) \times F(9) \times F(6) \times 320 \\6963200 &:= F(6) \times F(9) \times F(6) \times 3200 \\69727 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(9 + 7) + 2) \times 7 \\697270 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(9 + 7) + 2) \times 70 \\6972700 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(9 + 7) + 2) \times 700 \\69875 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) - F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times 5 \\698750 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) - F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times 50 \\6987500 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) - F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times 500 \\70844 &:= (F(F(7 \times 0 + 8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \times 4 \\708440 &:= (F(F(7 \times 0 + 8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \times 40 \\7084400 &:= (F(F(7 \times 0 + 8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \times 400 \\72666 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \\726660 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 60 \\7266600 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + 6) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 600 \\73284 &:= (F(F(7) + F(3)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 4 \\732840 &:= (F(F(7) + F(3)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 40 \\7328400 &:= (F(F(7) + F(3)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 400 \\73367 &:= (-F(F(7)) \times F(3) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\733670 &:= (-F(F(7)) \times F(3) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 70 \\7336700 &:= (-F(F(7)) \times F(3) + F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 700 \\73395 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 3 \times F(F(-3 + 9))) \times 5 \\733950 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 3 \times F(F(-3 + 9))) \times 50 \\7339500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 3 \times F(F(-3 + 9))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73648 &:= (-F(7 + 3) + F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 8 \\736480 &:= (-F(7 + 3) + F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 80 \\7364800 &:= (-F(7 + 3) + F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 800 \\73719 &:= (F(F(7 - 3))^{F(7)} - 1) \times 9 \\737190 &:= (F(F(7 - 3))^{F(7)} - 1) \times 90 \\7371900 &:= (F(F(7 - 3))^{F(7)} - 1) \times 900 \\73791 &:= (7 + F(3))^{F(7)} \times 9 \times 1 \\737910 &:= (7 + F(3))^{F(7)} \times 9 \times 10 \\7379100 &:= (7 + F(3))^{F(7)} \times 9 \times 100 \\74487 &:= (-F(F(7) + F(F(4)))/F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 7 \\744870 &:= (-F(F(7) + F(F(4)))/F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 70 \\7448700 &:= (-F(F(7) + F(F(4)))/F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 700 \\74529 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(4)) + 5))^2 \times 9 \\745290 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(4)) + 5))^2 \times 90 \\7452900 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(4)) + 5))^2 \times 900 \\74665 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))^6 + F(F(6))) \times 5 \\746650 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))^6 + F(F(6))) \times 50 \\7466500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))^6 + F(F(6))) \times 500 \\74688 &:= (-F(7) - F(-4 + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\746880 &:= (-F(7) - F(-4 + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 80 \\7468800 &:= (-F(7) - F(-4 + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 800 \\74977 &:= (-F(F(7)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(9) - F(7))) \times 7 \\749770 &:= (-F(F(7)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(9) - F(7))) \times 70 \\7497700 &:= (-F(F(7)) - F(F(4)) + F(F(9) - F(7))) \times 700 \\75635 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times 5 \\756350 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times 50 \\7563500 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times 500 \\75645 &:= (F(7 + 5) - F(F(6)))^{F(4)} \times 5 \\756450 &:= (F(7 + 5) - F(F(6)))^{F(4)} \times 50 \\7564500 &:= (F(7 + 5) - F(F(6)))^{F(4)} \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75735 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(3)) \times 5 \\
 757350 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(3)) \times 50 \\
 7573500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(3)) \times 500 \\
 75745 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + 4) \times 5 \\
 757450 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + 4) \times 50 \\
 7574500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + 4) \times 500 \\
 75765 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(6)) \times 5 \\
 757650 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(6)) \times 50 \\
 7576500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 5 \times F(7) + F(6)) \times 500 \\
 75957 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) - 95) \times 7 \\
 759570 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) - 95) \times 70 \\
 7595700 &:= (F(F(F(7) - 5)) - 95) \times 700 \\
 76167 &:= (-F(7) \times (6 - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\
 761670 &:= (-F(7) \times (6 - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 70 \\
 7616700 &:= (-F(7) \times (6 - 1) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 700 \\
 76631 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 6 + 3) \times 1 \\
 766310 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 6 + 3) \times 10 \\
 7663100 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 6 + 3) \times 100 \\
 76657 &:= (F(F(7 + 6/6)) + 5) \times 7 \\
 766570 &:= (F(F(7 + 6/6)) + 5) \times 70 \\
 7665700 &:= (F(F(7 + 6/6)) + 5) \times 700 \\
 76691 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69) \times 1 \\
 766910 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69) \times 10 \\
 7669100 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6))) + 69) \times 100 \\
 76867 &:= (-7 + F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 7 \\
 768670 &:= (-7 + F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 70 \\
 7686700 &:= (-7 + F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 700 \\
 76937 &:= (F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(9) - F(3)) \times 7 \\
 769370 &:= (F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(9) - F(3)) \times 70 \\
 7693700 &:= (F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + F(9) - F(3)) \times 700 \\
 78142 &:= (-F(F(7)) + F(8 + 1)^{F(4)}) \times 2 \\
 781420 &:= (-F(F(7)) + F(8 + 1)^{F(4)}) \times 20 \\
 7814200 &:= (-F(F(7)) + F(8 + 1)^{F(4)}) \times 200 \\
 78197 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 1 - 9) \times 7 \\
 781970 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 1 - 9) \times 70 \\
 7819700 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 1 - 9) \times 700 \\
 78445 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8 \times F(4))/F(4)) \times 5 \\
 784450 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8 \times F(4))/F(4)) \times 50 \\
 7844500 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8 \times F(4))/F(4)) \times 500 \\
 78568 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + 8) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8 \\
 785680 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + 8) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 80 \\
 7856800 &:= ((-F(F(7)) + 8) \times 5 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 800 \\
 78827 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 82) \times 7 \\
 788270 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 82) \times 70 \\
 7882700 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)) + 82) \times 700 \\
 79215 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 - 1) \times 5 \\
 792150 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 - 1) \times 50 \\
 7921500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 - 1) \times 500 \\
 79225 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + F(2)) \times 5 \\
 792250 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + F(2)) \times 50 \\
 7922500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + F(2)) \times 500 \\
 79235 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + 3) \times 5 \\
 792350 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + 3) \times 50 \\
 7923500 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(9) \times 2 + 3) \times 500 \\
 79648 &:= (-F(7 + 9) + F(F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times 8 \\
 796480 &:= (-F(7 + 9) + F(F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times 80 \\
 7964800 &:= (-F(7 + 9) + F(F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times 800 \\
 79929 &:= (F(7 + 9) \times 9 - 2) \times 9 \\
 799290 &:= (F(7 + 9) \times 9 - 2) \times 90 \\
 7992900 &:= (F(7 + 9) \times 9 - 2) \times 900 \\
 81088 &:= (-810 + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\
 810880 &:= (-810 + F(F(8))) \times 80 \\
 8108800 &:= (-810 + F(F(8))) \times 800
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 81186 &:= (F(F(8)) + 1 + F(18)) \times 6 \\
 811860 &:= (F(F(8)) + 1 + F(18)) \times 60 \\
 8118600 &:= (F(F(8)) + 1 + F(18)) \times 600 \\
 \\
 82688 &:= (F(F(8)) \times F(2) - F(-6 + F(8))) \times 8 \\
 826880 &:= (F(F(8)) \times F(2) - F(-6 + F(8))) \times 80 \\
 8268800 &:= (F(F(8)) \times F(2) - F(-6 + F(8))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 82824 &:= F(8) \times (-F(2) + F(8 \times 2)) \times 4 \\
 828240 &:= F(8) \times (-F(2) + F(8 \times 2)) \times 40 \\
 8282400 &:= F(8) \times (-F(2) + F(8 \times 2)) \times 400 \\
 \\
 83169 &:= (F(8)^3 + 1 - F(F(6))) \times 9 \\
 831690 &:= (F(8)^3 + 1 - F(F(6))) \times 90 \\
 8316900 &:= (F(8)^3 + 1 - F(F(6))) \times 900 \\
 \\
 83259 &:= (F(8)^3 - 2 \times 5) \times 9 \\
 832590 &:= (F(8)^3 - 2 \times 5) \times 90 \\
 8325900 &:= (F(8)^3 - 2 \times 5) \times 900 \\
 \\
 83343 &:= (F(8)^3 \times 3 - F(F(4))) \times 3 \\
 833430 &:= (F(8)^3 \times 3 - F(F(4))) \times 30 \\
 8334300 &:= (F(8)^3 \times 3 - F(F(4))) \times 300 \\
 \\
 83488 &:= (-8^3 + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\
 834880 &:= (-8^3 + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 80 \\
 8348800 &:= (-8^3 + F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 83826 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(3) + 8)^2) \times 6 \\
 838260 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(3) + 8)^2) \times 60 \\
 8382600 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(3) + 8)^2) \times 600 \\
 \\
 83968 &:= (-F(8)^{F(3)} - 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8 \\
 839680 &:= (-F(8)^{F(3)} - 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 80 \\
 8396800 &:= (-F(8)^{F(3)} - 9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 84208 &:= (F(F(8)) - 420) \times 8 \\
 842080 &:= (F(F(8)) - 420) \times 80 \\
 8420800 &:= (F(F(8)) - 420) \times 800 \\
 \\
 84368 &:= (-F(8) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(3)} + F(F(F(6))) \times 8 \\
 843680 &:= (-F(8) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(3)} + F(F(F(6))) \times 80 \\
 8436800 &:= (-F(8) - F(F(F(4))))^{F(3)} + F(F(F(6))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 84755 &:= (F(8 + 4) + 7^5) \times 5 \\
 847550 &:= (F(8 + 4) + 7^5) \times 50 \\
 8475500 &:= (F(8 + 4) + 7^5) \times 500 \\
 \\
 84777 &:= (F(F(8)) + 4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times 7 \\
 847770 &:= (F(F(8)) + 4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times 70 \\
 8477700 &:= (F(F(8)) + 4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times 700 \\
 \\
 84985 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(9) \times F(8)) \times 5 \\
 849850 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(9) \times F(8)) \times 50 \\
 8498500 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(9) \times F(8)) \times 500 \\
 \\
 85728 &:= (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(7)) - 2) \times 8 \\
 857280 &:= (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(7)) - 2) \times 80 \\
 8572800 &:= (F(F(8)) + 5 - F(F(7)) - 2) \times 800 \\
 \\
 85888 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(8) + F(8))) \times 8 \\
 858880 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(8) + F(8))) \times 80 \\
 8588800 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(8) + F(8))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 85968 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 8 \\
 859680 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 80 \\
 8596800 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 \times (F(9) + 6)) \times 800 \\
 \\
 86288 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(6) \times (F(2) - F(8))) \times 8 \\
 862880 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(6) \times (F(2) - F(8))) \times 80 \\
 8628800 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(6) \times (F(2) - F(8))) \times 800 \\
 \\
 86368 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - F(F(3) \times 6)) \times 8 \\
 863680 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - F(F(3) \times 6)) \times 80 \\
 8636800 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - F(F(3) \times 6)) \times 800 \\
 \\
 86448 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(F(6) + 4) + 4) \times 8 \\
 864480 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(F(6) + 4) + 4) \times 80 \\
 8644800 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(F(6) + 4) + 4) \times 800 \\
 \\
 86688 &:= F(8) \times 6 \times 688 \\
 866880 &:= F(8) \times 6 \times 6880
 \end{aligned}$$

$$8668800 := F(8) \times 6 \times 68800$$

$$86728 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times F(7) - F(2)) \times 8$$

$$867280 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times F(7) - F(2)) \times 80$$

$$8672800 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times F(7) - F(2)) \times 800$$

$$86848 := (F(F(8)) - 6 - 84) \times 8$$

$$868480 := (F(F(8)) - 6 - 84) \times 80$$

$$8684800 := (F(F(8)) - 6 - 84) \times 800$$

$$86888 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times 8 - F(8)) \times 8$$

$$868880 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times 8 - F(8)) \times 80$$

$$8688800 := (F(F(8)) - F(6) \times 8 - F(8)) \times 800$$

$$86928 := (F(F(8)) - (6 + F(9)) \times 2) \times 8$$

$$869280 := (F(F(8)) - (6 + F(9)) \times 2) \times 80$$

$$8692800 := (F(F(8)) - (6 + F(9)) \times 2) \times 800$$

$$86968 := (F(F(8)) - 69 - 6) \times 8$$

$$869680 := (F(F(8)) - 69 - 6) \times 80$$

$$8696800 := (F(F(8)) - 69 - 6) \times 800$$

$$87128 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 + 1 + 2)) \times 8$$

$$871280 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 + 1 + 2)) \times 80$$

$$8712800 := (F(F(8)) - F(7 + 1 + 2)) \times 800$$

$$87168 := (F(F(8)) - 71 + F(F(6))) \times 8$$

$$871680 := (F(F(8)) - 71 + F(F(6))) \times 80$$

$$8716800 := (F(F(8)) - 71 + F(F(6))) \times 800$$

$$87285 := (-F(8) - F(F(7)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 5$$

$$872850 := (-F(8) - F(F(7)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 50$$

$$8728500 := (-F(8) - F(F(7)) + F(F(2) + F(8))) \times 500$$

$$87288 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 28) \times 8$$

$$872880 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 28) \times 80$$

$$8728800 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 28) \times 800$$

$$87328 := (F(F(8)) - (F(7) + F(3)) \times 2) \times 8$$

$$873280 := (F(F(8)) - (F(7) + F(3)) \times 2) \times 80$$

$$8732800 := (F(F(8)) - (F(7) + F(3)) \times 2) \times 800$$

$$87375 := (-8 + F(F(7)))/3 \times F(F(7)) \times 5$$

$$873750 := (-8 + F(F(7)))/3 \times F(F(7)) \times 50$$

$$8737500 := (-8 + F(F(7)))/3 \times F(F(7)) \times 500$$

$$87448 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4 - 4) \times 8$$

$$874480 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4 - 4) \times 80$$

$$8744800 := (F(F(8)) - 7 - 4 - 4) \times 800$$

$$87512 := (F(F(8)) - 7) \times (5 - 1) \times 2$$

$$875120 := (F(F(8)) - 7) \times (5 - 1) \times 20$$

$$8751200 := (F(F(8)) - 7) \times (5 - 1) \times 200$$

$$87764 := (F(F(8)) + 7 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$$

$$877640 := (F(F(8)) + 7 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 40$$

$$8776400 := (F(F(8)) + 7 \times 7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 400$$

$$87888 := (F(F(8)) + (F(7) - 8) \times 8) \times 8$$

$$878880 := (F(F(8)) + (F(7) - 8) \times 8) \times 80$$

$$8788800 := (F(F(8)) + (F(7) - 8) \times 8) \times 800$$

$$87928 := (F(F(8)) + F(7) + F(9) - 2) \times 8$$

$$879280 := (F(F(8)) + F(7) + F(9) - 2) \times 80$$

$$8792800 := (F(F(8)) + F(7) + F(9) - 2) \times 800$$

$$88168 := (F(F(8)) + 81 - 6) \times 8$$

$$881680 := (F(F(8)) + 81 - 6) \times 80$$

$$8816800 := (F(F(8)) + 81 - 6) \times 800$$

$$88248 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + F(4)) \times 8$$

$$882480 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + F(4)) \times 80$$

$$8824800 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + F(4)) \times 800$$

$$88288 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + 8) \times 8$$

$$882880 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + 8) \times 80$$

$$8828800 := (F(F(8)) + 82 + 8) \times 800$$

$$88435 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - 3) \times 5$$

$$884350 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - 3) \times 50$$

$$8843500 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - 3) \times 500$$

$$88445 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 5$$

$$884450 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 50$$

$$8844500 := (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 500$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88495 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) + 9) \times 5 \\ 884950 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) + 9) \times 50 \\ 8849500 &:= (-F(8) + F(F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) + 9) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88515 &:= (-8 + F(F(8) + F(F(F(5 - 1)))) \times 5 \\ 885150 &:= (-8 + F(F(8) + F(F(F(5 - 1)))) \times 50 \\ 8851500 &:= (-8 + F(F(8) + F(F(F(5 - 1)))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88545 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(8 - 5))) - F(F(4))) \times 5 \\ 885450 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(8 - 5))) - F(F(4))) \times 50 \\ 8854500 &:= (F(F(8) + F(F(8 - 5))) - F(F(4))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88555 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(8) - 5/5)) \times 5 \\ 885550 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(8) - 5/5)) \times 50 \\ 8855500 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(F(8) - 5/5)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88595 &:= (8 + F(8 + 5 + 9)) \times 5 \\ 885950 &:= (8 + F(8 + 5 + 9)) \times 50 \\ 8859500 &:= (8 + F(8 + 5 + 9)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88635 &:= (8 + 8 + F(F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \times 5 \\ 886350 &:= (8 + 8 + F(F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \times 50 \\ 8863500 &:= (8 + 8 + F(F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88728 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(8) \times 7 - 2) \times 8 \\ 887280 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(8) \times 7 - 2) \times 80 \\ 8872800 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(8) \times 7 - 2) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89448 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9 + 4) + F(F(4))) \times 8 \\ 894480 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9 + 4) + F(F(4))) \times 80 \\ 8944800 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9 + 4) + F(F(4))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89472 &:= (F(8) \times 9 + F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \times 2 \\ 894720 &:= (F(8) \times 9 + F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \times 20 \\ 8947200 &:= (F(8) \times 9 + F(4)) \times F(F(7)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89488 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F(9) - 4) \times 8) \times 8 \\ 894880 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F(9) - 4) \times 8) \times 80 \\ 8948800 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F(9) - 4) \times 8) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89768 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) + F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times 8 \\ 897680 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) + F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times 80 \\ 8976800 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) + F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89968 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) \times 9 - 6) \times 8 \\ 899680 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) \times 9 - 6) \times 80 \\ 8996800 &:= (F(F(8)) + F(9) \times 9 - 6) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92732 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) - F(3)) \times 2 \\ 927320 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) - F(3)) \times 20 \\ 9273200 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) - F(3)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92742 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) + F(4)) \times 2 \\ 927420 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) + F(4)) \times 20 \\ 9274200 &:= (F(9 + 2 + F(7)) + F(4)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93312 &:= (F(9) + F(3))^3 \times 1 \times 2 \\ 933120 &:= (F(9) + F(3))^3 \times 1 \times 20 \\ 9331200 &:= (F(9) + F(3))^3 \times 1 \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94365 &:= (9^{F(F(4))} \times F(F(F(F(3)) + 6))) \times 5 \\ 943650 &:= (9^{F(F(4))} \times F(F(F(F(3)) + 6))) \times 50 \\ 9436500 &:= (9^{F(F(4))} \times F(F(F(F(3)) + 6))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94566 &:= (F(9) \times 4 + 5^6) \times 6 \\ 945660 &:= (F(9) \times 4 + 5^6) \times 60 \\ 9456600 &:= (F(9) \times 4 + 5^6) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94647 &:= (-9 + F(F(4)) \times F(F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 7 \\ 946470 &:= (-9 + F(F(4)) \times F(F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 70 \\ 9464700 &:= (-9 + F(F(4)) \times F(F(F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96489 &:= (-9 - 6^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\ 964890 &:= (-9 - 6^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) \times 90 \\ 9648900 &:= (-9 - 6^{F(4)} + F(F(8))) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96849 &:= (-9 \times F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + 4) \times 9 \\ 968490 &:= (-9 \times F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + 4) \times 90 \\ 9684900 &:= (-9 \times F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + 4) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97569 &:= (F(F(9) - F(7)) - 5 \times F(F(6))) \times 9 \\ 975690 &:= (F(F(9) - F(7)) - 5 \times F(F(6))) \times 90 \\ 9756900 &:= (F(F(9) - F(7)) - 5 \times F(F(6))) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}97875 &:= (F(9 + F(7)) + 8 \times F(F(7))) \times 5 \\978750 &:= (F(9 + F(7)) + 8 \times F(F(7))) \times 50 \\9787500 &:= (F(9 + F(7)) + 8 \times F(F(7))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98289 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) + F(2) + 8) \times 9 \\982890 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) + F(2) + 8) \times 90 \\9828900 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) + F(2) + 8) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98373 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) \times 3 - F(7)) \times 3 \\983730 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) \times 3 - F(7)) \times 30 \\9837300 &:= (-F(9) + F(F(8)) \times 3 - F(7)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98471 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4) - 7) \times 1 \\984710 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4) - 7) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$9847100 := (9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4) - 7) \times 100$$

$$\begin{aligned}98521 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 5 + 2) \times 1 \\985210 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 5 + 2) \times 10 \\9852100 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 5 + 2) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98571 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 57) \times 1 \\985710 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 57) \times 10 \\9857100 &:= (9 \times F(F(8)) + 57) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}99144 &:= F(9) \times 9^{F(1 \times 4)} \times 4 \\991440 &:= F(9) \times 9^{F(1 \times 4)} \times 40 \\9914400 &:= F(9) \times 9^{F(1 \times 4)} \times 400\end{aligned}$$

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